

**GENDER EQUALITY AND AUTHENTICITY-
WOMEN LEADING INDIA'S AUTOMOBILE INDUSTRY**

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Dedication:

This thesis is dedicated first and foremost to my God and King, my Lord Jesus Christ, for His unwavering Grace and Mercy that has sustained me throughout this journey.

To my family, for their unconditional love and support, and for the many sacrifices each one of them had made: my Mum Cynthia; my Husband, Bharath; my son, Nathan; my daughter, Tabitha; and my aunt, Scarlet, who continually upheld me in her prayers. I also extend my gratitude to my wider family (Uncle Trevor) whose encouragement has carried me through.

My supervisors, Dr Pravin Balaraman and Dr Xiuli Guo, whose mentorship, guidance and support shaped not only this research but also my growth as a scholar and practitioner.

To the women leaders of India's automobile sector, who continue to lead with authenticity and courage in spaces where their voices are often underrepresented.

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And to my prayer warriors across the globe who faithfully upheld me and this thesis in their prayers.

Student Declaration

I declare that this thesis has not been submitted for another comparable academic award.

Signed: Pearlana Rebecca Bharath kumar **Date:** 19 Feb 2026

Abstract

This study explores the role of authentic leadership in enabling sponsorship for women leaders within India's passenger car original equipment manufacturing (OEM) sector, examining how authenticity, leadership, and gender intersect to shape professional advancement in a traditionally male-dominated industry. Adopting an interpretive phenomenological approach with thematic analysis, the research captures the lived experiences of 25 women leaders through in-depth interviews and complements these insights with five focus group discussions involving their direct reports, providing a multi-dimensional understanding of women's leadership journeys and the influence of authenticity on sponsorship. Findings reveal that authentic leadership helps women navigate internal and systemic challenges while remaining anchored in personal values, with traits such as ethical decision-making, transparent communication, emotional intelligence, and resilience contributing to credibility and trust, which in turn attracted informal sponsorship from senior leaders and peers.

Participants actively sought feedback for self-reflection and development, highlighting authenticity as a dynamic process that can challenge gendered norms and foster more inclusive sponsorship practices. The study offers actionable insights for HR professionals, organisational leaders, and engineering institutions, including early-career leadership development tailored for women, structured sponsorship pathways, and workplace cultures that value authenticity over conformity. By foregrounding the voices of women leaders and the impact of authenticity on career progression, this research addresses a critical gap in the Indian automotive sector and provides a novel framework for developing inclusive leadership cultures in traditionally masculinised industries, contributing to leadership theory from a Global South perspective.

Keywords: Authenticity, women leaders, gender, automobile, India

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List of Abbreviations:

AL-Authentic Leadership
ALI-Authentic leadership inventory
BANI-brittle, anxious, nonlinear and incomprehensible
CSP-Corporate sustainability practices
DEI-Diversity, equity and inclusion
FGD-Focus group discussion
GET-Graduate engineering trainees
HARP- Heightening your awareness of your research Philosophy
HR-Human Resources
PR-Public Relations
IPA-Interpretive Phenomenological Analysis
IDI-In depth Interview
KPI-Key performance Indicators
LAS-Lead authenticity scale
LR-Literature Review
NLE-Narrative literature review
OEM-Original equipment manufacturers
POSH-Prevention of sexual harassment
PRISMA-Preferred reporting items for systematic reviews and meta-analysis
SLR-Systematic Literature Review
SMART-Specific, measurable, assignable, realistic and time related
STEM-Science, technology, engineering and Mathematics
TPM-Three pillar model
VUCA-Volatile, Uncertain, complex and ambiguity
WIA-Women in Automotive

CHAPTER ONE: INTRODUCTION

There exist examples of organisations' contributions towards the rapid growth and increase in the women's workforce, which is evident in both Indian, Global South, and Western perspectives. Various media reports have provided empirical findings from the context of Indian demographics. According to media reports from *The Hindu* (2023), "findings from Tamil Nadu stated 43% of the women workforce within the manufacturing sector, predominantly in potential markets such as electric vehicle manufacturing units and within the automobile sector, which are employing more women than ever before." This is also similar in findings from the *Business Standard* (2023), which noted that "Chennai, along with southern cities, tops the list for female employment." These reports and findings from media outlets, from an Indian perspective, highlight that women are on the rise within the traditionally male-dominated automobile industry. However, the subtle emphasis on the term "hiring" in such headlines presents a paradox. Despite gains in education, employment, and equal pay, women remain underrepresented in leadership positions, a concern that is frequently overlooked by both the media and organisations.

In contrast, Western headlines tend to scrutinise and offer criticism regarding the gap in women's leadership. For example, a publication by *Europe Auto News* (2023) asked, "Why should men care about advancing women in automotive?" also, *Forbes* (2022) listed key factors explaining the underrepresentation of Women in Automotive Leadership. While India highlights a positive aspect and celebrates women entering the industry, the Western world questions what happens to them after they enter. The looming, bilateral question is: What happens to the women who enter the industry? Reasons for low participation in leadership roles.

Empirical research within the domain of women's leadership has expanded exponentially within the body of literature, becoming part of many management association discussions both in terms of theory and in practice. The disparity between celebration and critical analysis has driven research into barriers along the leadership pipeline (Mbatha and Ruiters, 2025). However, major studies within the body within the body of literature focus on external factors, adopt a general perspective, and largely examine Western settings (Owen, Pacheco and Yamanaka, 2024). Although women are not underrepresented numerically, issues such as workplace challenges, societal expectations, and parental duties are well-established in the literature.

According to Braun *et al.* (2017), women in leadership are often expected to display strong agentic characteristics while simultaneously avoiding violations of gender stereotypes, a delicate balance that demands androgynous skills. Roy (2015) posits that young women are preparing for careers by investing in education, while Fuller's (2013) study asserts that women's educational achievements have progressively equalled those of men, positioning them well for the professional domain. Providing equal access to education and opportunities has helped reduce some historical challenges to women's leadership progression. Education is widely considered a key milestone in empowering women, challenging traditional gender roles, and bringing transformative change to women's lives (Chakrabarti and Biswas, 2012). Evidently, statistical data reinforces this trend. Amongst the 1.5 million engineering students in India (Sharma, 2025). Women comprise of 40% of India's STEM graduates (Tiwari, 2025). However, this rise in education has not translated equally into leadership roles. According to Sarkar (*Economic Times of India*, 2024), only 12% of women in the manufacturing sector occupy senior leadership roles, and just 4% hold executive positions such as Managing Director (MD), Chief Executive Officer (CEO), Chief Financial Officer (CFO), or Director (Bhattacharyya, *Economic Times of India*, 2024). The percentage is even lower in the

automobile industry, with women holding below 1% of senior leadership roles. The exclusion of women from decision-making roles in India's energy and mobility transition carries significant costs; without women "in the driver's seat", the country risks replicating the inequalities of the fossil fuel era in the emerging clean energy and electric vehicle (EV) economy, undermining both fairness and effectiveness. However, placing women at the centre of policy and leadership could enable India to set a global benchmark for inclusion within the Global South and accelerate a more equitable green transition (Sakka, 2025).

Whilst there is some progression in terms of qualification attainment by women in the automotive workforce in relation to that of men, there exists an underrepresentation in leadership positions (Horowitz, 2018). The growing rate of education amongst women has positively impacted organisations in India to implement ambiguous gender diversity targets. These targets often result in the emergence of challenges and barriers that present themselves in nuanced forms, most notably in the limited career advancement of women, especially into leadership positions. As Walker (2021) and Schuh (2014) argue, gender development is a vital component of human development, and fostering the advancement of women is fundamental to the development of society. Although opportunities have expanded, women face distinct barriers in leadership contexts in comparison to the male perspective. According to Hoyt (2016), there exists a generalised consensus amongst scholars that leadership remains one of the most critical areas of academic and practical study. Gipson (2017) asserts that research into gender-focused leadership has been essential in highlighting the unique difficulties faced by women, including stereotypical biases and perceptions. Consequently, understanding how gender intersects with leadership and how selection processes differ is significant. Rudman (2001) and Garcia (2006) highlighted that earlier diversity research tended to focus primarily on observable challenges like bias and discrimination.

Although the value of leadership is widely recognised, Hanek (2022) contends that it is still viewed through a masculine lens, with women being less frequently preferred for leadership roles. While the number of women in the workforce has increased significantly over the years, their underrepresentation in key leadership positions remains a critical blind spot. As Madsen (2020) asserts, this oversight limits an organisation's capacity to adapt to an ever-evolving work environment. These contradictions between the growth in women's workforce participation and their underrepresentation in leadership highlight the need to explore how leadership itself may influence the breaking of the so-called glass ceiling (Bertrand *et al.*, 2019). Additionally, studies have been useful in understanding the external factors that affect women's leadership experiences (Vahidpour *et al.*, 2025; Xiao *et al.*, 2023; Harman and Sealy, 2017; Xiao *et al.*, 2023; Pillay-Naidoo and Vermeulen, 2023) and have offered key departure points for further research. However, a gap remains in examining traits that explore the intersubjectivity of gender and leadership (Dy and MacNeil, 2025; Lengermann and Niebrugge, 1995; Ford, 2006). From an organisational perspective, the role of sponsorship in building inclusive cultures remains underexplored (Pless and Maak, 2004; BNP Media, 2024; DeWitty and McCamey, 2022). At the individual level, there is limited investigation into how authenticity interacts with gendered leadership experiences (Sinclair, 2007).

1.1. Introduction to Authentic Leadership:

Authentic leadership has emerged as a prominent construct within contemporary leadership scholarship, particularly in response to growing concerns around ethical conduct, leader credibility, and value-driven leadership in complex organisational environments. While the concept has evolved over time, there is broad agreement that authentic leadership centres on self-awareness, moral integrity, relational transparency, and alignment between values and action. Authentic leadership did not emerge as a contemporary management trend in isolation;

rather, it evolved from deeper philosophical traditions concerned with the nature of the “true self.” Classical thinkers such as Socrates and Aristotle emphasised self-knowledge and moral virtue (Laceulle, 2018), while existential philosophers including Heidegger (1962) conceptualised authenticity as alignment between one’s inner values and outward actions. The construct entered leadership scholarship formally in the early 2000s through the work of Luthans and Avolio (2003), who positioned authentic leadership within the domain of positive organisational behaviour in response to growing concerns around ethical failures and declining trust in corporate leadership. A significant milestone in the development of authentic leadership was the contribution of Bill George (2003), whose book *Authentic Leadership: Rediscovering the Secrets to Creating Lasting Value* framed authenticity as the foundation of sustainable and ethical leadership. Drawing on interviews with senior executives, George argued that effective leaders are guided by purpose, values, relationships, self-discipline, and heart.

Unlike trait-based or charismatic models, his approach emphasised self-awareness, moral courage, and alignment between personal life stories and professional leadership practice. George’s work shifted the discourse from leadership style to leadership character, thereby influencing subsequent academic conceptualisations by Luthans and Avolio (2003) and later empirical operationalisation by Walumbwa et al. (2008). Subsequent theoretical refinement by Avolio and Gardner (2005) and operationalisation by Walumbwa et al. (2008) established authentic leadership as a measurable construct encompassing self-awareness, internalised moral perspective, balanced processing, and relational transparency. More recent scholarship has expanded the concept beyond an individual psychological trait to a relational and contextually enacted process, shaped by organisational culture, gendered expectations, and social validation. This evolutionary trajectory provides the theoretical foundation upon which this study situates authentic leadership within the Indian automobile sector.

Early conceptualisations of authenticity emphasised the individual's ownership of self and purpose. Gardner *et al.* (2011) describe authenticity as a state in which an individual becomes "the master of his or her own domain," highlighting autonomy and self-governance as foundational elements. Building on this perspective, Leroy *et al.* (2015) define authentic leadership as occurring when individuals enact their "true selves" within leadership roles, positioning authenticity as congruence between identity and behaviour.

Subsequent definitions expanded the construct to include reflective and relational dimensions. Gardner *et al.* (2021) emphasise leaders' ongoing reflection on core values, motives, strengths, and goals, arguing that authenticity is not static but enacted through relationships with others. Similarly, Lux and Lowe (2024) conceptualise authentic leadership as a value-based and congruent form of leadership characterised by self-awareness, an internalised moral perspective, balanced information processing, and relational transparency.

More recent scholarship has highlighted the emotional and relational outcomes of authentic leadership. Liu *et al.* (2025) argue that authentic leadership strengthens leader–follower bonds by fostering positive emotional states such as joy, creativity, and interest, thereby enhancing engagement and trust. Hargrove (2025) further extends the construct by emphasising emotional maturity, suggesting that authentic leaders regardless of gender or background connect emotionally with subordinates in ways that support credibility and influence.

Across these definitions, authentic leadership is consistently positioned as value-driven, relational, and contextually enacted, rather than as a fixed leadership style or a set of prescribed behaviours. Drawing on these interpretations, and informed by the foundational work of Luthans and Avolio (2003), this study adopts the following working definition of authentic leadership:

“Authentic leadership incorporates an internalisation of a leader’s personal credibility, enhanced through integrity, to foster social virtues through expressions of a distinctive vision, a sense of passion driven by purpose, and care for followers”.

This working definition reflects the study’s emphasis on authenticity as a lived and relational leadership practice, particularly within gendered and male-dominated organisational contexts.

1.2.Statement of the Problem

Scholarly works have asserted a disparity within the body of literature. Hobbins (2022) posits that the majority of studies on women in leadership have been extensively researched within a Western perspective. This research study aims to address the intrinsic barriers that contribute to the leadership gap, specifically within the context of the Indian automobile manufacturing industry. According to the Gender Diversity in the Boardroom Report (2017), while the number of women entering the automotive industry has been increasing, their representation in leadership roles remains significantly below average. This disparity emphasises the need to build a deeper understanding of women’s internal career growth processes. Furthermore, as demonstrated by Chowdhury (2020), the Indian automobile industry has unique operational dynamics and a deeply embedded organisational culture, which together manifest a complex working environment for women leaders.

Furthermore, Mies (2019) points out, much of the existing literature has focused on the demand side of gender diversity. This research, therefore, seeks to address the underrepresentation of women in leadership positions in India’s automotive sector by examining the intrinsic factors that may facilitate their career progression.

While there is growing literature acknowledging the importance of women in leadership, some scholars argue that gender has little influence on leadership ability (Powell, 1990). Nonetheless,

anecdotal evidence suggests that women are often legacy-minded and demonstrate exceptional leadership in times of crisis (Adams, 2023). Although leadership ideally should not be differentiated by gender, it is undeniable that men and women possess distinct capabilities, which influence their leadership styles in unique yet equally valuable ways.

For instance, women have been found to outperform men in networking skills (Inks *et al.*, 2020; Gunnarsdóttir *et al.*, 2025; Paustian-Underdahl *et al.*, 2024; Xu and Martin, 2011; Tonge and Broadbridge, 2008; López-Bonilla *et al.*, 2023). Moreover, women tend to adopt leadership styles that are more strongly associated with effectiveness than those of men (Eagly, 2007; Dias, Veloso and Treff, 2020; Burns and Martin, 2022; Cords, 2006). Despite being commended for their leadership abilities, women remain significantly underrepresented in leadership roles. This paradox indicates that while women bring essential advantages to leadership, their underrepresentation despite demonstrated competence warrants further examination. Specifically, this study explores the role of authenticity, a leadership trait that has received limited scholarly attention, especially within a contextualised Indian framework.

Despite extensive scholarship on women and leadership, dominant frameworks continue to privilege Western centric bias in leadership approach which may miss out on fully capturing how leadership is understood in non-western context, especially Kark, R. (2024) in his commentary examines leadership theories through a gendered lens and critiques how traditional framework largely developed within western context overlooking diversity in leadership experiences. Similarly, many authors, critic mainstream leadership approach such as (Avolio *et al.*, 2009) (Dickson *et al.*, 2003) (Ehrnrooth *et al.*, 2023) (Benson, 2025).

Leadership studies often focus on sectors where leadership is highly theorised such as service-sector, Hopkins, (2021) highlights how assessments of women's leadership remain skewed by dominant organisational biases, similar thoughts shared by various authors (Shek *et al.*, 2025)

(Pahi *et al.*, 2022) (Rabiul *et al.*, 2022). Much leadership research continues to focus on formal roles, rather than relational, emergent and non-hierarchical (Hurt, 2023) (Messalti, 2024). These approaches insufficiently account for how women in capital-intensive, masculinised manufacturing contexts construct leadership legitimacy through intrinsic traits such as authenticity and relational sponsorship. As a result, current literature lacks a contextualised, process-based understanding of how women leaders in India's automotive sector navigate leadership advancement.

1.3. Rationale of the Research Study

Research in leadership spans a wide range of topics, including theories (Winkler, 2010), styles (De Vries *et al.*, 2010), traits (Bagherian *et al.*, 2023), and the impacts and outcomes of leadership (Bush *et al.*, 2021). As organisations evolve, so too do the challenges and expectations placed on leaders, making continuous research in this area both relevant and necessary. As leadership studies advance in tandem with broader industrial transformations, gendered leadership has gained attention as a critical subfield. However, both leadership and gendered leadership have progressed along divergent trajectories (Lipton, 2015).

Leadership has historically been shaped by social, economic, and cultural influences, while gendered leadership has focused more on how traits, qualities, and perceptions are conditioned by gender norms (Yadav and Lata, 2018). Literature indicates that women were largely excluded from leadership roles historically, as the qualities traditionally associated with leadership were aligned with masculine characteristics (Blake *et al.*, 2020). The emergence of second-wave feminism, which advocated for gender equality in the workplace (Molony, 2017), provided a platform to reconceptualise leadership and recognise styles often attributed to women, such as inclusivity, empathy, and collaboration.

This shift led to the recognition of leadership traits emphasising empathy, charisma, and authenticity (Gartzia, 2012). As a result, existing studies have gradually moved away from male-centric leadership models, promoting more diverse and inclusive approaches. This evolution mirrors broader changes across industries, reflecting efforts by organisations to foster inclusive workplace cultures. Yet, despite the increasing entry of women into the workforce, barriers and underrepresentation persist in key leadership positions, particularly in male-dominated industries such as the automobile sector (Bryan, 2020).

Although the literature on women in leadership has expanded significantly, key gaps persist within the body of literature. Specifically, there is a lack of empirical research addressing gender diversity and leadership effectiveness within the Indian automobile industry. There is also a notable disparity in studies focusing on successful women leaders and the role of sponsorship in enabling their career growth. Despite its relevance, scholarly work on authentic leadership by women remains sparse, limited and case studies demonstrating how women lead authentically within the industry are underrepresented.

Moreover, while gender and leadership have been studied extensively, there is a limited intersectional analysis connecting leadership, gender, and authenticity. Most studies tend to examine gender in isolation, which may result in an oversimplified understanding of women's leadership experiences. As Binns and Kerfoot (2011) suggest, examining gender without an intersectional perspective risk overlooking the complex interactions between personal, organisational, and societal factors that influence leadership. This study seeks to bridge these gaps through a qualitative design incorporating in-depth interviews, focus group discussions, and case studies. In doing so, it offers a more comprehensive understanding of authentic leadership and intrinsic career development pathways, with particular emphasis on the role of sponsorship (Cho *et al.*, 2019).

This research is timely, given that the Indian automobile industry has witnessed a rapid increase in the female workforce. However, literature highlights a contradiction despite the growing candidate pool of qualified women; their progression into leadership roles remains limited (Stein, 2015). This discrepancy and gap necessitate an exploration of the underlying causes and the role of authentic leadership in enabling women's advancement. Studies by Mousavi *et al.* (2022) and Prakash and Nauriyal (2020) posit that although the participation of women in the industry is still relatively low, increasing female representation has the potential to significantly boost productivity, particularly in making India a global leader in shared mobility.

This study adopts the research onion framework, whereby each methodological layer is carefully examined and unpeeled to reveal the detailed processes involved (Saunders and Thornhill, 2009). It takes a virtuous approach, as described by Tranfield and Starkey (1998), where the research is both "theory-sensitive and practice-led". Furthermore, the study draws on Gibbons' Mode 2 of knowledge production, which promotes collaboration between the supply side of academic knowledge and the demand side of industry practice (Sexton and Lu, 2009). This dual focus allows the study to remain grounded in scholarly theory while simultaneously addressing real-world challenges in the Indian automobile segment.

1.4. Research Aim

This research aims to explore the lived experience of women leaders within the automobile industry and to examine the impact of authentic leadership towards creating sponsors for their growth.

1.5. Research Objectives and Questions

Women continue to have greater representation in service-oriented sectors such as education, healthcare, government, and hospitality (Bowles and McGinn, 2005; Torrejón Pérez *et al.*, 2025; Rambe *et al.*, 2018; Greenwald, 2004; Myers, 2001; Shah *et al.*, 2025). However, this

trend does not extend equally into traditional, male-dominated industries such as manufacturing. Oakley (2000) argues that women are less likely to be offered leadership roles in such sectors due to entrenched gender norms and structural barriers that hinder progression. This disparity reinforces the need for industry-specific research that investigates the nuanced dynamics of women's leadership in sectors where they are underrepresented, such as the automobile manufacturing industry in India. To accomplish the aim of this study, the following objectives guided the course of this research. These are:

Research objective 1: To explore how women leaders in the Indian automobile industry understand, construct, and enact authentic leadership in their professional roles.

Research objective 2: to examine the internal organisational challenges women encounter and how authentic leadership is used to navigate and mitigate these challenges.

Research objective 3: to obtain comparative insight into how authenticity, leadership and gender intersect in creating sponsorship.

To ensure the purpose and the objectives of this study were actualised, key questions were provided to guide the research study and to provide quality findings and answers to the problem definition. These research questions were formulated to strike a balance, avoiding extremes in breadth or narrowness, thereby facilitating insightful outcomes (Przybylski and Weinstein, 2017). This approach ensures that the study explores relevant complexities while maintaining clarity and feasibility. These questions are:

RQ 1: How do successful women leaders navigate and sustain leadership effectiveness within the Indian automobile Industry?

RQ 2: What were some of the challenges they had to overcome internally?

RQ 3: How do authenticity, leadership, and gender intersect in building a culture of sponsorships, advocating for women's career advancement?

1.6 Research Methodology:

This study adopts a qualitative research design grounded in an interpretive phenomenological approach (IPA) to explore the lived experiences of women leaders within India's automobile manufacturing industry. Given the study's focus on understanding how authentic leadership is experienced, constructed, and enacted within gendered organisational contexts, an interpretivist paradigm was considered most appropriate. This philosophical stance enables an in-depth exploration of meaning, subjectivity, and sense-making as articulated by participants, rather than seeking causal explanations or generalisable outcomes.

Primary data were collected through semi-structured, in-depth interviews with 25 women leaders occupying managerial and senior leadership roles across leading Indian and multinational automobile original equipment manufacturers (OEMs) within India. These interviews facilitated rich, reflective accounts of leadership journeys, identity construction, and experiences of authenticity within a traditionally male-dominated industry. To complement and triangulate these perspectives, the study also incorporated five focus group discussions (FGDs) with direct reports of selected women leaders. This dual-perspective design enabled a more holistic understanding of authentic leadership by examining both self-perceptions and follower interpretations.

Data were analysed using thematic analysis informed by interpretive phenomenological principles, allowing patterns of meaning to emerge inductively from the data. NVivo software was employed to support systematic coding and theme development. The analysis progressed from initial coding to the identification of higher-order themes and meta-categories, capturing the interplay between intrapersonal leadership formation, organisational realities, and relational mechanisms such as sponsorship.

Ethical considerations were rigorously addressed throughout the research process, including informed consent, confidentiality, and participant anonymity. By combining interpretive depth with methodological rigour, the chosen approach enabled the study to generate contextually grounded insights into how authenticity, gender, and leadership intersect to shape sponsorship and career advancement for women leaders in India's automobile sector

1.7 Contribution

Originality is widely recognised as a cornerstone of academic research. Şuteu (2022) states that originality forms the core ingredient in scholarly inquiry, emphasising that researchers seeking to present something new must first conduct a thorough evaluation of existing knowledge within their domain. Similarly, Guetzkow *et al.* (2004) argue that originality lies in the discovery or creation of new knowledge that adds value to the existing body of work. Both authors acknowledge that the nature and expression of originality may vary across academic disciplines.

Phillips and Pugh (2011, p. 70) provide a practical framework for demonstrating originality through nine key strategies. This study aligns with several of these strategies and makes an original contribution by being one of the first to explore authentic leadership within the context of the Indian automobile manufacturing industry, particularly through the lens of gender.

This research contributes to knowledge and shows originality by offering a unique synthesis through the integration of concepts of authentic leadership, gender, and intersectionality within a previously unexamined sector and geographical context. This intersectional lens, applied to leadership studies, contributes fresh perspectives to the fields of leadership and gender studies addressing a clear gap in the literature identified through a combination of narrative and systematic literature review.

One of the originality criteria outlined by Phillips and Pugh (2011) assert the application of an established theory or technique to a new context. This offers potential for novel insights into how authenticity is understood, enacted, and perceived by women in a male-dominated industry.

Furthermore, by employing a dual-method approach lead interviews with women leaders and focus group discussions with their teams capturing multiple perspectives on the same phenomenon. This methodological strategy enhances the originality of the research by providing a holistic understanding of women's authentic leadership within organisational structures.

This study explicitly addresses the lack of empirical research on authentic leadership in the Indian automotive sector and how it intersects with gendered leadership dynamics. By doing so, it opens a new line of inquiry within leadership studies and contributes to more inclusive understandings of leadership theory and practice. This study explores under-researched areas within the leadership discipline (Phillips and Pugh, 2011).

Finally, this study's originality lies in its unique combination of themes, context, and methodological approach. By investigating the convergence of authenticity, gender, leadership, and sponsorship within a specific industry and national setting, this research adds value in a

way that has not previously been done, fulfilling Phillips and Pugh's (2011) final criterion of contributing to knowledge in a genuinely original way.

1.7.1 Empirical Contribution

The empirical relevance of this study is grounded in its applicability to women aspiring to grow into leadership roles by embracing their authentic selves leading with purpose, passion, and in alignment with their values. This study resonates with the concept of authentic leadership as defined by George (2003, p. 200), where leaders are guided by self-discipline, build strong relationships, and lead with the heart. It provides a lens through which women can navigate leadership on their own terms, without conforming to traditional masculine norms of behaviour.

The study also holds significance for the automobile industry, particularly for organisations seeking to empower their women workforce and create inclusive, innovation-driven, and sustainable cultures.

Furthermore, this research unfolds within a context where interest in authentic leadership is increasing, particularly in relation to equitable policies that promote long-term change. Many diversity initiatives have lacked sustainability due to policies that fail to recognise the varied experiences of women. Often, women leaders are pressured to conform to rigid norms of leadership, where traits such as assertiveness may be misconstrued as aggression. A historical illustration is Mary Wollstonecraft, the philosopher and women's rights advocate, whose outspoken views were deemed notorious in her time, as they challenged prevailing gender norms (Fairclough and Packham, 2024).

This reflects a broader issue wherein women who deviate from the communal ideals of leadership by "thinking for themselves" as encouraged during the Enlightenment have historically been regarded with scorn or labelled as possessing masculine traits (Eagly, 2005).

Such historical patterns continue to influence organisational norms today, creating subtle barriers for women leaders who do not conform to conventional leadership prototypes.

In addition, much of the scholarly research on women in leadership has predominantly focused on women leaders in isolation, often neglecting the perceptions of their teams or subordinates. This unidirectional approach results in a fragmented understanding of leadership experiences and contributes to uneven expectations within workplace cultures. To counter this, leadership development and policy design must move beyond treating women as a homogeneous group and instead acknowledge intersectional identities encompassing different cultural backgrounds, industrial experiences, and personal trajectories. This necessitates a rethinking of how leadership is conceptualised and implemented across industries.

In this regard, the study advocates the application of Heidegger's (1962) model of 'authentic care', which supports enabling women leaders to develop their own styles of leadership rather than conforming to existing masculine templates. Authentic leadership, therefore, becomes the intersection between gender and leadership, offering a pathway for more inclusive and empowering leadership development frameworks.

The contribution of this study lies in its potential to offer a sustainable leadership model grounded in authenticity, a trait that allows women to integrate their personal values with organisational goals. This alignment can create a sense of belonging, purpose, and inclusive acceptance within organisational cultures.

While prior studies, such as Evans (2001), have emphasised the influence of copying leadership styles, particularly within educational settings, they failed to identify practical tools for women to implement lasting change. Similarly, Mashele and Alagidede (2022) observed that South African women leaders, when relying solely on transformational leadership during crises, faced sustainability challenges and were compelled to adopt transactional leadership approaches to

meet their goals. Such prescriptive models often overlook the complex behavioural realities of leadership, especially for women navigating traditionally male-dominated industries.

This study challenges such one-size-fits-all prescriptions by proposing authentic leadership as a viable alternative, a trait rather than a style, focused on internal values and self-awareness. In doing so, it contributes to addressing the current leadership crisis by encouraging values-based leadership, where women leaders can pursue their mission with authenticity and passion, while contributing to the collective mission of their organisations.

1.7.2. Theoretical Contribution

The primary theoretical contribution of this study lies in its advancement of women's leadership studies through the integration of authentic leadership theory with gender studies. Recent research by Amo (2023) has shown that women experience imposter syndrome at a higher rate than men, often doubting their own capabilities and internalising negative beliefs about their leadership performance. This study adds to the body of knowledge by theorising how authentic leadership can mitigate such internalisation through the development of a leadership style rooted in self-awareness and self-acceptance. In doing so, it contributes to the broader literature on gendered leadership by proposing intrinsic strategies that empower women to construct sustainable and meaningful career paths while also influencing the stereotypical attributes typically associated with women in leadership roles.

In addition, the study contributes to the growing stream of research on authentic leadership (AL) by exploring its implications in the context of sponsorship. While traditional leadership models often emphasise positional power or behavioural traits, this study identifies the role of authenticity in cultivating sponsor relationships, thereby opening new theoretical avenues in leadership scholarship. By connecting AL with sponsorship, the study challenges conventional

notions of leadership progression and proposes a more value-driven, relational approach to leadership development for women.

Another significant theoretical contribution concerns the role of context in shaping authentic leadership. While scholars such as Gardiner (2015) have asserted that contextual factors, particularly gender, can act as barriers to women's leadership development, most studies on AL overlook how these contextual realities shape the embodiment of authenticity. As Fusco (2018) has argued, AL is often reduced to a narrow set of competencies or leadership behaviours. This study resists such reductionism by positioning authentic leadership as a lived strategy, capable of enabling sponsorship and leadership growth. Importantly, the study expands the scope of AL by incorporating not only the perspectives of women leaders but also those of their team members, gathered through focus group discussions. This dual-perspective approach offers a more comprehensive understanding of authenticity as it is experienced and perceived within organisational systems.

Finally, this study contributes to theoretical literature by contextualising AL within a specific industry, the Indian automobile manufacturing sector, thereby highlighting how industry-specific dynamics influence the development and expression of authenticity. Much of the existing literature on AL has focused on its role in combating unethical behaviour, which, while important, tends to crystallise the concept into a fixed framework of ethical conduct (Nicholson and Carroll, 2013). In contrast, this study conceptualises authentic leadership as fluid, socially constructed, and contested, not as a static set of traits, but as a dynamic interplay between self, others, and organisational culture.

By intersecting authentic leadership with gender and leadership studies, this research positions authenticity not merely as an individual virtue but as a social virtue that takes shape in the interactions between leaders and their environments. Adopting the standpoint of Nicholson and

Carroll (2013), this study explores authenticity beyond the individual leader's self-concept to investigate how it is perceived, co-constructed, and validated by others, in this case, the teams that report into women leaders. In doing so, it contributes to the collectivist dimensions of leadership theory, supporting a view of leadership as a shared and relational endeavour, rather than one solely centred on the individual.

1.8 Research approach and research journey:

This research is informed by the researcher's insider position as an employee within the Indian automobile industry, a context that provided both the impetus and the lens through which the study was conceived. Prolonged professional engagement within this male-dominated sector enabled the researcher to observe, first-hand, the increasing participation of women in technical and managerial roles alongside their persistent underrepresentation in senior leadership and decision-making positions. These observations were not episodic but cumulative, emerging over years of professional practice and shaping critical questions about leadership, authenticity, and career progression for women in the industry.

The researcher's insider status played a formative role in the evolution of the research approach. Rather than positioning leadership as a set of measurable competencies or outcomes (Conger and Ready, 2004), lived organisational experience revealed leadership to be deeply relational (Zheng *et al.*, 2025), contextual, and negotiated particularly for women navigating gendered expectations and informal power structures (Gooty *et al.*, 2025). This recognition prompted a deliberate move away from positivist approaches towards an interpretivist research paradigm, which privileges meaning-making, subjectivity, and context in understanding social phenomena.

The research journey was therefore characterised by a reflexive engagement with both practice and theory. Exposure to dominant leadership models largely developed within Western

(Ghamrawi *et al.*, 2025), service-sector contexts highlighted their limited explanatory power in capturing the realities of women leaders operating within capital-intensive manufacturing environments (Mayimele, 2025). As an insider, the researcher was acutely aware of the informal networks, cultural norms, and unspoken rules that shape leadership advancement, including the pivotal role of sponsorship. These insights reinforced the need for a qualitative, phenomenological approach capable of capturing the depth and complexity of women's leadership experiences as they are lived and interpreted.

Adopting an interpretive phenomenological approach enabled the researcher to bracket personal assumptions while remaining attentive to participants' meaning-making processes. Reflexivity was maintained throughout the research journey through conscious self-examination, transparent documentation of analytic decisions, and the use of participant validation. The researcher's positionality was thus treated not as a source of bias to be eliminated, but as a resource to be critically managed enhancing access, trust, and contextual understanding while upholding analytical rigour.

Furthermore, the researcher's professional embeddedness strengthened the ethical commitment underpinning the study. Having experienced the organisational realities under investigation, the researcher approached participants' narratives with sensitivity, respect, and an awareness of the risks associated with visibility and disclosure in corporate environments. This informed the study's emphasis on confidentiality, anonymity, and voluntary participation.

Overall, the research approach reflects a practice-informed scholarly journey, where insider knowledge and academic inquiry intersect. By consciously integrating professional experience with interpretive methodology, the study offers a contextually grounded exploration of how women leaders in the automobile industry experience authentic leadership and cultivate sponsorship for career advancement. This reflexive positioning provides the foundation for the

methodological choices detailed in Chapter Three and reinforces the study's contribution to leadership research within male-dominated industrial contexts.

1.9. Structure of the Thesis

This thesis is comprising of six chapters. Each chapter follows a successful research structure building upon the last to construct a nuanced understanding of how authentic leadership, gender, and sponsorship intersect within the Indian automobile manufacturing sector a traditionally male-dominated space.

The first chapter is the introductory chapter. This section provides a detailed introduction to the research background, identifying the key rationale and scope for this study. This sets out by providing a clear aim to the research, identifies key objectives to actualise the research purpose and key research question to guide the inquiry. Importantly, it establishes the originality of the study by positioning it within wider debates on leadership and gender, while highlighting the need to explore authenticity as a leadership model in a sector where hierarchical and masculine norms have historically prevailed.

Chapter two provides a basics to provide clarification to the research questions. This chapter provides a detailed exploration of literature to identify the challenges facing women from a leadership perspective and how to mitigate these issues. This review chapter adopts a narrative overview and a systematic literature process to provide a thorough review of leadership within the body of literature. A comprehensive review process provides a detailed understanding of leadership theories identifying how many reinforce conformity and hierarchy rather than inclusivity. Furthermore, focus of this research explores gendered leadership, identifying the internalised barriers women face such as imposter syndrome and emotional labour which form the basis and formation of their leadership identity. This chapter also explores modern progressive paradigms of leadership namely charismatic and authentic leadership. Drawing

upon key scholarly studies such as from Walumbwa *et al.* (2008); Gardiner (2015); Owolabi (2020); Mayo (2018), findings from the process identifies significant gaps in both theory and practice: the intersection of authenticity, gender, and leadership remains insufficiently examined. This identified gap provides the conceptual bridge to the study's empirical design in the following chapter.

Chapter three presents the research methodology. This chapter provides a detailed discussion of methodological choices adopted during this study. Data analysis and other processes are presented along with the ethical considerations made. This research adopts a qualitative interpretive phenomenological approach to delve into women's lived experiences of leadership in the automotive sector. This approach, rooted in the work of Smith, Flowers and Larkin (2009), allows for a deep exploration of meaning capturing how women construct and interpret their leadership journeys in their own voices.

Chapter four provides the empirical findings from the field for this research study. These findings are derived through the qualitative method of research adopting semi-structured interviews and focus group data across five major Indian and multinational organisations. Empirical findings in this chapter provides a deeper insight on how women leaders negotiate their professional identities and leadership styles in environments with gendered based expectations. Findings were analysed methodologically and systematically utilizing NVivo software, with 46 codes and 11 overarching themes emerging from the process. These themes were further organised into four meta-categories: Intrapersonal Leadership Formation, External Barriers and Organisational Realities, Leadership Growth and Advancement, and Support Mechanisms and Relational Capital.

Chapter five provides a discussion of research findings with reference to existing literature. This chapter offers a critical analysis aligned with the study's research questions. Findings from

this research study asserts that women in India's automotive industry build their leadership journeys through a blend of inner authenticity and pragmatic adaptability. Traits such as emotional intelligence, integrity, and confidence rooted in personal and familial values emerge as crucial to their success. Furthermore, this study highlights the structural inequalities in leadership. Women often lack formal mentoring, face cultural resistance, and are left to seek informal pathways to leadership. Nevertheless, they demonstrate remarkable resilience, proactively seeking development opportunities and building peer networks. The discussion underlines that true leadership advancement for women lies in the alignment of personal values with organisational ethos, and in dismantling patriarchal structures that continue to shape workplace dynamics. Finally, this chapter presents the empirical focus on the intersection of authenticity, gender and leadership. These elements are not merely individual traits or attributes; they interact with, and are shaped by, wider organisational and societal contexts. As such, the study calls for a recalibration of leadership norms away from traditional, masculine-centric models and towards more inclusive, value-driven paradigms.

Chapter Six provides a thorough reflective summation of this research, which includes findings of the study, limitations and future research. This study reiterates the central argument: that women's leadership success in India's automotive sector is not simply a product of organisational systems, but is often self-propelled fostered through personal authenticity, intentional relationship-building, and alignment of individual and institutional values.

CHAPTER TWO: LITERATURE REVIEW

2.1. Narrative literature Review Introduction

This chapter provides a detailed examination and review of literature. The literature review adopts a balanced approach by combining both narrative and systematic literature review methods, leveraging the strengths of each to complement the overall study. The review begins with a narrative literature review (NLR), which provides a comprehensive understanding of the research landscape, particularly by examining the evolution of leadership and gendered leadership. This method allows for a broad exploration of the theories and concepts shaping these areas. In contrast, the systematic literature review (SLR) ensures that the conclusions drawn are based on high-quality evidence, minimising bias and enhancing the reliability of the findings.

Furthermore, this chapter inculcates both methods to provide a holistic view, providing a deeper understanding of authentic leadership from women's perspective within the context of the Indian Automobile industry. The narrative review explores the challenges and limitations of women leaders, identification of literature gaps concerning leadership, authentic leadership, and gender. These identified gaps proffer themes emerging throughout the literature review, guiding the study's framework. While these concepts are explored in a variety of contexts, this research will primarily focus on the application of authentic leadership to women leaders within the Indian automobile industry.

The review will also discuss the criteria used for literature selection, drawing on a wide range of sources, from seminal works to contemporary research. Classic authors such as Maxwell (2013); Goleman (2021); Bennis and Nanus (2003), as well as more recent scholars like Sinek (2009); Mayo (2018); Owolabi (2020) and Ferguson (2016), are included. Among the various theories and leadership traits explored, George's (2007) authentic leadership trait was selected

as a fitting framework for understanding the impact of women leaders in the Indian automobile sector.

Fig 1: Concepts of the study

2.2. Definition of Terms

Table 1: Definition of Terms

Term	Definition
<u>Authentic Leadership</u>	“a process that draws from both positive psychological capacities and a highly developed organisational context, which results in both greater self-awareness and self-regulated positive behaviours on the part of leaders and associates, fostering positive self-development” (Luthans and Avolio, 2003, p. 243)
<u>Automotive</u>	The automotive industry consists in the sector of design, development, production and commercialisations of cars and car parts” (European Commission, 2022)
<u>Automobile</u>	May be considered as autonomous vehicle, that is it must have: an energy supply; a motor; transmission; control systems and wheels (Gaevskiy and Odinkova, 2019)

<u>Gender</u>	Combination of the way a person feels/identifies and a social construction” (Hall <i>et al.</i> , 2021)
<u>Influence</u>	Influence is about affecting an outcome; it is about motivating a behavioural change or an action. It is about you and understanding the impact you have on other people and their perceptions of you. It’s about progressing things without forcing them or being pushy” (Cass, 2017, p. 28)
<u>Leadership</u>	Leaders are able to build teams, motivate people, manage conflict, negotiate resources and prioritize tasks” (Schwartz, 2018)
<u>Protocol</u>	A protocol is “defined as an explicit road map of planned methodological approach of the review” (Shamseer <i>et al.</i> , 2015)
<u>Sponsorship</u>	“Sponsorship is a professional relationship that focuses on career advancement and rests on power” (Levin <i>et al.</i> , 2021)
	Spending one’s social capital or using one’s influence to advocate for a protégé” (Chow, 2021)

Table 1 presents the key terms and working definitions adopted in this study. It provides conceptual clarity by outlining how core constructs such as authentic leadership, gender, sponsorship, and leadership are defined and interpreted within the context of this research. Establishing these definitions ensures consistency in meaning and supports a shared understanding of key concepts throughout the thesis.

2.3. Leadership

Leadership is a multifaceted phenomenon and remains a subject of great interest to scholars, researchers, and policymakers (Collinson and Tourish, 2015). The study of leadership spans a variety of disciplines, from biology to neuroscience, anthropology, and psychology (Spisak, 2020). The term "leadership" has intrigued professionals from various fields for centuries. Cerfolio (2020, p. 22) asserts that in the context of healthcare, *“to drive quality and excellence leaders had to take accountabilities for all variables and metrics, as great leaders inspire those around them.”* Over the course of the 21st century, leadership studies have evolved, drawing upon a range of theories, styles, and adaptations, all shaped by the cultural, situational, and behavioural contexts in which leadership occurs (SAGE Publications, 2025).

Adams and Knüpfner (2018) posits that the concept of leadership dates back to early writings by Plato around 380 BC, which suggested that leaders are born with certain dispositions. This school of thought is shared by Mertz (2015) who examines the debate over whether leadership is an inherent trait or a learned skill. The Great Man Theory, which argues that “great leaders are born and not created,” posits that figures like Emperor Suleiman the Magnificent exemplified such innate leadership qualities (Nilufer, 2019; Carlyle, 1841). However, this theory has faced significant criticism, as it was primarily applied to warriors and distinguished men, leading some scholars to characterise it as a cult (Mouton, 2019).

Until the 19th century, much of the leadership debate focused on its intrinsic nature, and leadership was generally regarded as an agentic trait. Notably, during this period, Queen Victoria was one of the most influential monarchs, demonstrating the presence of female leadership in an era dominated by male figures. Sullivan (2020) highlights that leadership can be both innate and developed, a view that has become more widely accepted in contemporary discourse.

In recent years, organisations have shifted from viewing leadership as an innate skill to recognising it as a developable quality. As Westfall (2019, p. 19) suggests, nearly 95% of learning organisations plan to increase their investment in leadership, which has contributed to the growth of the global leadership industry, now valued at an estimated \$366 billion. Day (2018) discusses different levels of understanding of leadership, noting that many key discoveries remain misunderstood or inconsistent with practical approaches. The quest for a deeper understanding of leadership has led to multiple definitions, with notable differences between traditional and contemporary perspectives, especially regarding inclusivity (Eddy, 2022).

Stogdill (1991) concludes that a singular definition of leadership remains elusive, as it is shaped by a range of variables, including social contexts, personal traits, attributes, and styles. (Anderson *et al.*, 2017) argue that the expectations of millennial workers have further complicated the study of leadership, leading to increased complexity in leadership theories. Fraser (2019) contends that leadership in the 21st century requires a new definition, one that is adaptable to the BANI world (brittle, anxious, nonlinear, and incomprehensible), where speed and flexibility are critical. This view aligns with Lewis (2019); and Schoemaker and Teece (2018) studies, who highlight the need to address the influx of change in a world where traditional rules no longer apply.

Throughout history, the understanding of leadership has evolved, resulting in the development of various theories that range from perceiving it as a collection of core skills to recognising it as a dynamic process. Weaver (2019, p. 45) asserts this perspective by asserting that “leadership is a revolutionary process and could not be built overnight, and exceptional leaders are never born ready.” Recent scholarly research has presented leadership as both an innate and inclusive construct, highlighting the importance of self-ownership within leadership roles

(Kuhl, 2019). Attributes such as authenticity and inherent qualities (Mayo, 2018) are increasingly valued within organisations. As stipulated by Hannah (2013), these modern ideas may, in fact, be perceived as rebranded versions of traditional concepts. While contemporary leadership theories recognise the significance of classical notions, they also expand upon them, emphasising the critical need for examining leadership as organisations work towards sustainability within the context of the BANI world. (Giessner and van Knippenberg, 2008) reinforce this perspective by emphasising that leadership is a dynamic activity wherein leaders engage and mobilise followers to execute it effectively.

2.3.1 Leadership Definitions:

Table 2: Leadership Definitions

Author	Definition	Themes
Stogdill (1950, p. 3)	Leadership is the practice of steering an organized group toward setting and accomplishing goals	Influence and goal
Prentice (1961, p. 143)	Leadership is the accomplishment of a goal through the marshalling of human assistants	Goal, Marshalling
Katz and Kahn (1978, p. 528)	The added sway that surpasses mere following of the organization's standard directives	influence
Ibacco (1989, p. 229)	"Leadership means setting an example. When you find yourself in a position of leadership, people follow your every move. And when leaders act people watch, so you have to be careful about everything you say and everything you do"	Authenticity

Fondas (1990)	Leadership will be restored in business, Zaleznik argues, by imagination, charisma, and talent; thus, he camps with the "leaders are born" (not made) school of philosophers.	Innate qualities
Bass (1997)	The leader shares a vision and sense of mission with the followers	Vision
Cohen (1999)	The ability to influence others to willingly follow direction	Influence
Kotter (1999, p. 25)	"Management controls people by pushing them in the right direction; leadership motivates them by satisfying basic human needs"	motivation
Lynham and Chermack (2006)	Leadership does not exist in isolation. Without followership, there is no leadership	followership
Northouse (2018)	Leadership is a relational process involving influence and goal achievement within a group	Process and influence
Brent <i>et al.</i> (2019)	Leadership involved motivating others toward the achievement of a specific goal and leading organisational change	Motivation & change
Reni (2019)	Leadership is not about a person, and it is different from management. Leadership is an influence relationship among leaders and followers who intend real changes that reflect their mutual purposes	Influence, followers

Benzel (2021)	“Leadership is the art of causing others to deliberately create a result that otherwise would not have happened.”	Result driven
Sellami <i>et al.</i> (2022)	Leadership involves the exercise of influence over others	Influence
Kouzes and Posner (2023, p. 3)	“Leadership is the art of mobilising others to want to struggle for shared aspirations, through practices that build trust, model the way, and inspire a shared vision”	Mobilisation and trust

Table 2 summarises influential leadership definitions presented across the literature. It highlights the evolution of leadership thinking over time and illustrates the diversity of perspectives regarding influence, vision, motivation, and leader–follower relationships. This comparison supports the study’s positioning of leadership as a multifaceted and relational construct, providing a foundation for examining leadership through the lens of authenticity and gender.

The definitions offered by various scholars provide a broad range of perspectives on leadership, encompassing influence, vision, and relational dynamics, reflecting the evolution of leadership ideas over time. Stogdill (1950) and Prentice (1961) discuss leadership, with a particular emphasis on the importance of goals. Both recognise the significance of human interaction, whether through influence or mobilisation. Ibbaco (1989) and Katz and Kahn (1978) present distinct yet complementary views on leadership. Katz and Kahn (1978) focus on the mechanisms of leadership, while Ibbaco (1989) emphasises leading by example. Both stress

influences are present, but Katz and Kahn (1978) concentrate on gradual influence, whereas Ibacco (1989) emphasises personal conduct and the ability to inspire followers.

Cohen (1999), Sellami *et al.* (2022), and Lynham and Chermack (2006) emphasise the relational nature of leadership, highlighting the active involvement of followers and the reciprocal dynamic between leaders and followers. These perspectives portray leadership as a shared endeavour, with both leaders and followers playing vital roles. Definitions by Bass (1997); Northouse (2018); Brent *et al.* (2019); and Kouzes and Posner (2023) emphasise the importance of vision and the realisation of goals, depicting leaders as visionaries who inspire and motivate their followers towards shared aims.

Kotter (1999) makes a notable distinction by comparing leadership with management, arguing that while leadership focuses on motivation, management is more about direction. Fondas (1990) views leadership mainly through the lens of traits, while Northouse (2018) and Brent *et al.* (2019) concentrate on leadership styles. More modern definitions, such as Benzel's (2021), introduce the idea that leadership involves deliberate action, implying that leaders create the conditions for success rather than simply influencing others.

Overall, these definitions demonstrate the multifaceted nature of leadership. Insights from these various perspectives suggest that to be a successful leader, it is essential to build trust, inspire teams, and create a compelling vision for the future.

2.3.2 Leadership Theories

According to Newstead *et al.* (2021), in their extensive review of research, most studies suggest that leadership has been viewed from a process-to-people perspective, with leaders often seen as role models. However, it is apparent that while leadership is fundamentally a study of process, the leader is defined as an individual, a concept that has, over time, been somewhat

neglected in the literature. (Lange and Rowold, 2019) demonstrate that mindfulness in leadership is a style that enables leaders to maintain a positive attitude, foster transparency in communication, and cultivate an open-minded approach. This style reflects the understanding that leadership exists because of the people being led, emphasising that the essence of leadership is in the relationships between leaders and their followers.

In leadership studies, the leader remains a crucial factor. Literature has highlighted the transition from managerial roles to more effective leadership (Malik, 2023; Chiu *et al.*, 2017). This shift has contributed to the development of theories centred on leadership traits. As the concept of leadership evolved into that of a role model, the study of leadership traits became increasingly significant. The table below presents various leadership theories that have been developed over the years, illustrating the evolution of thought on why certain individuals are recognised as leaders, compared to others. The selected theories range from classical to contemporary, offering a broad understanding of the concept of leadership across time.

Table 3: Leadership Theory Comparison

Leadership Theory	Theorist	Synopsis of the theory	Leader Quality	Reference
Great man theory	Thomas Carlyle	Great leaders are born not developed	Born to Lead	(Strauss, 2012) (Spector, 2016)
Trait Theory	Gordon Allport	Personal traits that differentiated a leader from followers	Traits to lead	(Luria <i>et al.</i> , 2019)

Behavioural theory	John B. Watson	How leaders behave can be taught.	Learn to Lead	(Derue <i>et al.</i> , 2011)
Contingency Theory	Fred Fiedler	Leader's action varies as per the situation faced by the leader	Flexible	(Tortorella and Fogliatto, 2017)
Ethical Leadership	Brown <i>et al</i>	Being honest and fair in leadership	Lead by stewardship	(Kaptein, 2019)
Servant Leadership	Robert K. Greenleaf	Leaders' role as a supporter of their team.	Lead by serving others	(Van, 2011)
Situational Theory	Dr. Paul Hersey and Dr. Ken Blanchard	No single theory of leadership is the best. A leader who adopts to any given situation in getting the job done is considered the most effective.	Lead by situation	(Henry, Samer and Seokhwa, 2009)
Transactional Theory	Max Weber	Leadership based on process and control	Lead by process	(L. Guarana and Avolio, 2022)
Transformational Theory	James MacGregor Burns	Inspiring others to follow	Lead by Influence	(Sobaih <i>et al.</i> , 2022)

Table 3 compares key leadership theories discussed in the literature.

It outlines the central assumptions, focus, and leader orientation of both classical and contemporary leadership theories. This comparison helps identify theoretical gaps, particularly

regarding gender sensitivity and contextual relevance, which informs the selection of authentic leadership as the primary theoretical lens for this study.

Existing studies reveal a clear lack of integration among leadership theories, with a strong focus on identifying the appropriate theoretical framework for leaders. As (Duan *et al.*, 2017) observe, since leaders are evaluated based on their behaviour and soft skills, leadership theories are often designed to capture these attitudes, behaviours, and beliefs. Additionally, the role of women in leadership remains insufficiently explored within this context. While leadership has traditionally been linked to masculine traits, there has been limited progress in adopting a more inclusive perspective that incorporates the female experience in leadership. The exclusion of women from leadership discourses underscores a significant gap, as women encounter unique challenges and barriers in leadership positions (Eagly and Carli, 2003).

A critical review of the literature reveals a lack of correlation between leadership theories, particularly when considered individually. For example, the Great Man theory, which emphasises innate traits, does not sufficiently explain how these traits relate to effective leadership. Likewise, the behavioural theory, suggesting that leadership skills can be learned and developed, conflicts with trait-based theories. This disconnects among theories presents a significant obstacle to developing a unified definition or framework for leadership. Consequently, this gap remains a key reason why new theories and models are continually proposed to fill the voids left by existing frameworks (Northouse, 2018). Furthermore, existing theories mainly concentrate on the individual leader, the leadership process, and the leadership position. However, they overlook the wider context in which leaders operate, such as the industries they are part of, the cultural environment, and organisational diversity, including gender, age, and technological progress. These aspects are vital for understanding how leadership can succeed in modern contexts.

The onset of the COVID-19 pandemic further revealed the shortcomings of traditional leadership theories, as leaders found it challenging to manage teams in remote or hybrid work environments. The move to digital communication and the need for crisis management skills showed that leadership is not solely about predefined traits or behaviours but about the ability to adapt swiftly to changing circumstances. As Roberts (2020) argues, none of the established leadership theories fully address the challenges presented by environmental crises, which have grown increasingly significant in today's world. Bert (2006) reviews John C. Maxwell's *The 360-Degree Leader*, which discusses leadership within a middle-management context and highlights top-down and bottom-up leadership approaches. Nevertheless, it fails to cover essential modern challenges such as leading in the digital era, managing environmental crises, bridging generational gaps, and leading in flatter organisational structures where traditional hierarchies are less relevant.

Leadership theories can generally be divided into two categories: those based on a leader's traits and those centred on the leadership process. (Antonakis and House, 2014) suggest that classical leadership theories tend to emphasise a leader's behaviour, while modern theories view leadership as a dynamic process. (Guillory, 2007, p. 53) asserts that to succeed in the 21st century, leaders must apply leadership skills in ways that promote business success, which he calls "quantum-thinking". This shift in perspective reflects the growing realisation that leadership is not just about traits or behaviours but involves managing complex social relationships and perceptions within changing environments. As (Lord, Foti, and Phillips, 1982; and Hunt, 1984) argue, leadership is inherently multidirectional, shaped by both characteristics and perceptions, making it a complex and evolving social relationship.

These observations highlight the necessity for an integrated leadership framework that considers the interaction of traits, processes, and contextual factors, particularly as organisations encounter increasingly complex and fluid challenges.

2.4. Leadership Traits

Leadership theories have long concentrated on understanding the mechanisms and dynamics of leadership. These theories provide a comprehensive framework that illustrates how leadership operates, while leadership traits concentrate on the specific qualities required for effective leadership. From the definitions provided, the qualities of a leader seem essential to leadership success. As (Armstrong, 1928, p. 2) notes, "The quality of a leader's exchange relationships with subordinates has important implications for leadership effectiveness." Leadership traits, therefore, provide practical ways to apply these qualities in real-world settings. This section will discuss two positive leadership traits, namely charismatic and authentic leadership, as they are central to understanding and developing effective leadership.

The researcher has selected two traits, charisma and authenticity, as focal points to explore the intrinsic factors of leadership (Vlachos, Panagopoulos, and Rapp, 2013). Charismatic leadership was chosen for its similarity to authentic leadership, as both traits require personal motivation to lead (Chen, 2016). After comparing these two traits, one will be selected as the lens for studying women in leadership within the Indian automotive industry context.

2.4.1 Charismatic Leadership

(Dayan and Chan, 2012) define charisma as "the ability of an actor to exercise diffused and intense influence over the normative power that ultimately depends on the power of an individual." Charismatic leadership has been viewed as a combination of warmth and strength in a leader. Scholarly research in this area has suggested that "charisma elicits strong emotions from followers, which encourages devotion and action" (Sy, Horton and Riggio, 2018).

Charismatic leadership is believed to inspire and influence followers, encouraging them to exceed expectations (Le Blanc *et al.*, 2021).

Charismatic leadership focuses on a leader who is not concerned with daily tasks but instead has a higher calling and vision, motivated not by material pleasures but by a desire for greater goals. An example of this is Lee Iacocca, the former CEO of Chrysler, who reduced his wages during a financial crisis at the company (Sverre, 2018). Charismatic leaders are often characterised as dynamic and warm. However, (Jay and Rabinder, 1998) criticised the theory for the lack of focus on the relationship between followers and leaders, a critical aspect that has often been overlooked. The key distinction between charismatic leadership and traditional leadership theories lies in its emphasis on the leader's visionary behaviour and their ability to inspire, giving followers a purpose and direction (Zhang *et al.*, 2020).

Although charisma is an important leadership trait, challenges arise when charismatic leaders neglect the day-to-day activities of the organisation. A charismatic leader may become so fixated on their own vision that they ignore the perspectives of their followers, potentially leading to an autocratic approach (Nassif *et al.*, 2021). Moreover, charismatic leadership has been criticised for a lack of ethical consideration. Unethical behaviour by charismatic leaders can have detrimental effects on employees (Dundes *et al.*, 2019). One example is Elizabeth Holmes, the convicted founder of Theranos, who was widely regarded as a charismatic leader in Silicon Valley. Holmes was once hailed as the next Steve Jobs, but she was convicted of fraud (Dundes *et al.*, 2019). While not all charismatic leaders are unethical, the absence of authenticity in leadership can lead to a loss of integrity and trust from followers. This underscores the importance of examining how authenticity in leadership enhances trust and serves as a catalyst for growth among women leaders.

It is crucial to critically evaluate both the advantages and disadvantages of charismatic leadership. As Ladkin (2006) suggests, while charismatic leaders can have a significant influence, their larger-than-life personas can sometimes be harmful to an organisation (Sinclair, 2007; Gardiner, 2015, p. 24) notes that "charismatic leaders sometimes could wreak havoc in an organisation," further emphasising the risks linked to excessive charisma. Additionally, charisma can be fleeting, leading to a dependency on the leader, which may cause others to perceive them as larger-than-life.

2.4.2 Authentic Leadership

(Walumbwa *et al.*, 2008) defines authentic leadership as *A pattern of leader behaviour that draws on and encourages both positive psychological capacities and a positive ethical climate, to enhance greater self-awareness, an internalised moral perspective, balanced processing of information, and relational transparency among leaders working with followers, fostering positive self-development.*

To lead effectively, a leader must first understand their own values and beliefs, as only then can they effectively share these with their followers. According to Spain (2019), self-awareness should be the foundation of leadership, as understanding oneself is vital for influencing others.

Authentic leadership theorists assert that "authenticity reinforces the concept of the ideal leader" (Fox, Gardiner and Storberg, 2017, p. 1). Researchers in the field of authentic leadership argue that "it is a concept of leadership development rather than a form of leadership" (Bryan, 2020). This concept highlights the interwoven relationship between self-clarity, expressed in behaviour, and the ability to influence followers (Neider and Schriesheim, 2011). Authentic leadership is often viewed as a trait, focusing on a leader's true self when interacting with subordinates, which in turn garners the confidence and trust of followers (Farid

et al., 2020). Authentic leaders are those who "say what they mean" (Laschinger, Wong and Grau, 2012). The transparency of revealing one's true self generates benefits for employees,

Table 4: Charisma vs Authentic leadership

Charismatic Leadership	Authentic Leadership	Reference
It's about being a role model by managing their own image	It's about purpose and values	(Nahavandi, 2009)
According to Max weber true charismatic leaders exhibit 'charismatic Authority'	Re-examination of oneself	(Davis and Vila-Henninger, 2021; Chully, Jose and Luthufi, 2022)
Charismatic leaders develop their self-confidence by encouraging their employees who in turn encourage their leader	Authentic leaders are self-confident because of their knowledge and by developing their strengths	(Nahavandi, 2009)
Appeal to employees purely through an emotional level	Knowing oneself as a person and leading by example	
Charismatic leaders must have an 'element of authenticity' to be successful	Authentic leaders do not need to be charismatic to be successful	

reinforcing positive behaviours that ultimately benefit the entire organisation.

Table 4 contrasts charismatic and authentic leadership approaches identified in the literature. It highlights key differences in leader orientation, ethical grounding, and leader–follower relationships. This comparison supports the rationale for selecting authentic leadership as the central lens of the study, as it aligns more closely with values, self-awareness, and relational leadership relevant to women leaders in male-dominated contexts.

From the comparison above, it is evident that charisma primarily focuses on influencing followers, while authentic leadership centres on using one's own knowledge and being true to oneself when leading employees. Charismatic leadership has garnered considerable scholarly attention over the years and has been shown to have a positive impact on team potency (Le Blanc, González, and Wang, 2021). In contrast, while authentic leadership has received comparatively limited scholarly attention, studies have demonstrated that leaders who lead authentically encourage effective communication and foster inclusion (Smith and Lindsay, 2014, p. 67).

A casebook authored by Arenas (2019) dedicated an entire chapter to women leaders, with one prominent example being the first female British Prime Minister, Margaret Thatcher. While Thatcher's leadership skills have been categorised as transformational, (Arenas, 2019, p. 92) highlights a particularly authentic conversation between Thatcher and Sir Frank Cooper, the Minister of Defence, in which she asks, "How do you actually run a war?" Another example is Amelia Earhart, the first woman to cross the Atlantic by plane in 1928, known for her courage and determination (Bix, 2010). While Earhart is often celebrated for her transformational leadership, her authentic personality was a key factor in transforming the portrayal of women in aviation. Taken together, these examples demonstrate how women leaders often embody both transformational qualities and authentic leadership elements. Arenas' (2019) work

therefore underscores that even when women are primarily categorised as transformational leaders, authenticity emerges as a defining trait that shapes their leadership legacy.

After conducting a comprehensive analysis of the two leadership traits, the researcher has chosen to adopt authentic leadership as the lens for this study. The reasons for selecting authentic leadership as Tables 5 and 6 outline core concepts and dimensions associated with authentic leadership.

Table 5: Authentic leadership concepts

Concept	Description
Underlying Paradigms	To reveal underlying paradigms of authentic leadership with regards to gender diversity and how they impact followers' perceptions.
AL as an open-ended project	Authentic leadership is one of those open-ended projects which makes it an ideal framework to be explored, just as Morwenna Griffiths mentioned that "authenticity has to be achieved and re-achieved, over and over again" (Salmela, 2005).
Positive relationship between AL and Authentic followership	Results from research have proven that 'authenticity is rising in women in comparison to men' (Mainiero and Gibson, 2018) study in the area of authentic leadership in India amongst cross level and multi-level followership, had resulted in a positive relationship with authentic followership (Nair, Prasad and Shreekumar, 2022).

<p>Leader from the individual</p>	<p>Women leaders are often disregarded in the gender hierarchy. This displacement could be one of the reasons why they are disregarded as leaders. Authentic leadership helps distinguish the leader from the individual resulting in bridging displacement.</p>
<p>AL as a lens in identifying social conformity</p>	<p>Gardiner (2015) indicated that authentic leadership could reveal more on social conformity. This is well suited for this study as it aims to use leadership trait as a lens in identifying social norms that are creating a complex landscape for women leaders.</p>
<p>AL and its value towards mindfulness</p>	<p>Evidence from scholarly study conducted by Avolio and Mhatre, (2011) states that authentic leaders are better able to achieve organisational goals and that they lead according to their values irrespective of the situation. In a VUCA world where mindfulness is becoming popular (Vago and Silbersweig, 2012). Equipping future leaders with this concept before they embark and during their journey of leadership is crucial.</p>
<p>AL's applicability towards the quest of meaning</p>	<p>A study conducted by Young (1990) contended that women lacked trust in their own abilities. Authentic leadership focuses on helping a leader identifying their own strengths and building on those strengths to empower others. Thereby this trait is well suited for women leaders.</p>
<p>Authentic leadership to authentic actions</p>	<p>Furthermore, authentic leadership is crucial as many leaders may have intentions that are authentic, and actions may not reflect those intentions. Thereby having a trait that encourages authentic</p>

	actions is necessary as appearing to others the way we appear to ourselves is an ethical responsibility.
AL combined with empathy and crisis management	Finally, studies conducted recently have proven that empathy in a leader has been viewed as essential predictors of the ability to handle crisis response (Monehin and Diers, 2022). Empathy is one of the known qualities of an authentic leader. A recent study by Moore and Maxey (2023) have found authentic leaders to be empathetic with a desire to make others successful. Crisis management in today’s volatile workplace is critical and leaders who can handle crisis make an ideal leader. A study conducted on delta airlines and united airlines by Varma (2021) reveals how crucial a leader’s skill in handling crisis impacts reputation and share prices. From this point we notice that authentic leadership attributes empathy which is one of the principal elements in crisis management.

Table 5 outlines the core concepts associated with authentic leadership. It explains key dimensions that underpin authentic leadership and highlights how these concepts relate to values, self-awareness, and ethical conduct. This table supports the conceptual grounding of the study by clarifying how authentic leadership is understood and operationalised within the research context.

Amongst the studies conducted in India, most have been general and not specifically focused on any particular industry. This study aims to bridge that gap by utilising authentic leadership

to examine women in the automobile industry within the Indian context. This makes the study unique, as it is the only research conducted through this lens.

Authentic leadership has faced criticism for portraying leadership as a masculine trait, which can make it challenging for women to bring their authentic selves to leadership roles. Ely *et al.* (2011) argue that, because authentic leadership emphasises staying true to oneself, women leaders who strive to remain authentic often face increased scrutiny. Considering this criticism, this study will explore how women promote their achievements and build confidence that is visible to others, who can help amplify these successes. This research will look at ways women can develop confidence as a natural trait, with colleagues helping to reinforce signals of assurance. Furthermore, this critique of authentic leadership highlights the importance of focusing on the new generation of the workforce, 'Gen Z', who expect leadership that goes beyond traditional control (conventional leadership) and charisma (modern leadership). As Zehetner *et al.* (2022) suggest, these challenges lead leaders to adapt their strategies by fostering a more supportive work culture. Recent research shows that Gen Z expects 'authentic and adaptive leadership' (Tidhar, 2023, p. 465). Ely *et al.* (2011) also found that Gen Z has distinctive traits, including a strong sense of autonomy. A sports study by Bandura and Kavussanu (2018) concluded that authentic leadership promotes autonomy, which makes it an ideal leadership trait for today's workplaces. Therefore, this study examines how women's unique leadership qualities can shape their identity, particularly through the development of self-confidence. Arendt (1958) suggests that authentic leadership can sometimes mask a person's personality, shifting focus to the role. This research addresses this issue by prioritising the individual leader and how their authenticity impacts leadership.

While authentic leadership has been studied in relation to improved performance and organisational culture, it is crucial to explore the connection between authenticity and women

leaders, particularly concerning intrinsic factors that enable the growth of women leaders within the industry. This study utilises the authentic leadership framework developed by Mayo (2018) in her book *Yours Truly: Staying Authentic in Leadership and Life*. The framework outlines three elements that help organise the variables necessary for information gathering.

Previous research studies have highlighted that gender plays a significant role in leadership, with gender often serving as a background influencer (Kubu, 2018; Wilson, 2025; Papadakou and Sternberg, 2025; Wu *et al.*, 2025; Sandretto *et al.*, 2025; Baker *et al.*, 2025; Mikkonen, 2025). Although gendered mindsets have been extensively discussed (Kray *et al.*, 2025; Pla-Julián, 2025; Maranges *et al.*, 2023), very few studies have focused specifically on one form of leadership trait that can positively influence these mindsets. This study addresses this gap by exploring the authentic leadership trait as a catalyst for self-authorship and its potential to help women cultivate their personal narratives and self-awareness. A recent study by Melanie and Eva (2021) on teachers' emotional authenticity and its impact on students revealed that students' emotional experiences in the classroom are influenced by the emotional authenticity of the teacher. The study found that the more students perceived their teacher as authentic, the higher their enjoyment and the lower their anxiety.

Salmela (2005) categorised emotional authenticity into two components: sincerity and emotions related to individual values. According to Mayo's matrix, emotions are linked to the heart, helping leaders reflect and foster their passion. This is a profound intrinsic factor that allows leaders to uncover their drive. Pullen and Vachhani (2021) give an example of the emotional authenticity of Jacinda Ardern, the former Prime Minister of New Zealand, who was recognised for her compassion and empathy. Despite facing challenges, she was celebrated for her 'heartfelt approach' to leadership. This example highlights the importance of emotional authenticity for women leaders.

Bennett and Hennekam (2018) argue that the process of self-authorship is crucial for career decision-making. This process plays a crucial role in authentic leadership, particularly for women, as it enables them to develop a sense of self-authorship, which in turn allows them to make informed decisions, such as entering leadership roles. Bennett and Hennekam (2014) further suggest that self-authorship challenges leaders to think critically and make effective decisions, marking a critical phase for women leaders. Studies have shown that emotionally strong leaders are more confident in their decisions, which enables them to positively influence others (Westaby *et al.*, 2010). This emotional strength makes women leaders resilient, enabling them to make decisions that have a positive impact and secure influential leadership positions. These leaders are not only passionate but also driven by a strong sense of purpose.

Previous studies have examined various aspects of organisational culture, and more recent studies have focused specifically on gendered leadership. For example, a 2016 study focused on how organisational culture can mitigate the negative impacts of stereotype threats (Hoyt and Murphy, 2016). Other studies have investigated age-based stereotype threats and other types of threats (Barber, 2017; Prasad, 2011; Chakraborty and Serra, 2024). Research on such threats has led to the development of internal and governmental policies aimed at supporting women in the workplace (Von, Kalokerinos and Zacher, 2017). However, limited studies have explored ways to overcome these threats by developing women leaders who actively seek feedback and habituate themselves to learning. This study fills this gap by investigating how women leaders seek feedback and how it fosters their growth mindset, enabling them to adapt and progress.

Crans *et al.* (2022) have demonstrated the importance of feedback in leadership, illustrating how it helps women leaders overcome stereotype threats. Feedback is a powerful tool in leadership, and when integrated into authentic leadership, it promotes continuous self-development and learning. A leader who actively seeks feedback and engages in learning

becomes a breath of fresh air to employees, demonstrating personal growth, interest in others' development, and motivating employees to follow suit. In this context, Mayo introduces behavioural authenticity as a habit, the habit of seeking feedback and engaging in continuous learning. Kea-Edwards *et al.* (2023) propose that receiving feedback enables leaders to leverage their strengths. However, studies have found that women leaders receive less feedback compared to their male counterparts. As such, feedback becomes a crucial element in the development of women into leadership roles. It provides a holistic view, helping women leaders understand what is expected of them, while encouraging them to lead conversations and advocate for their own leadership journey.

The quota system has emerged as a result of effective studies on gendered leadership, encouraging the global corporate world to restructure policies to enable more women in the workplace (Besley *et al.*, 2017). While these studies have gained significant scholarly and public attention, there is a dearth of research on the impact of women leaders, and how they, along with their teams, develop from within the organisation. A key characteristic highlighted in the literature is harmony. One important aspect of leadership is the desire to look after others, which is a hallmark of many leadership theories, including contingency theory. Hadfield and Jopling (2018) assert that proactive loops, such as seeking collaboration and harmony, can change the context of leadership. When a woman leader embraces this quality of looking after her team, she automatically elevates herself to a leadership position, gaining the support of her colleagues and team members. This, in turn, can reduce the reliance on quotas for gender diversity. As Kirton and Healy (2013) argue, a leader who cares for her team is often sponsored by them to grow into a senior role within the organisation. This reflects the creation of a collective identity that fosters solidarity and commitment within the team.

A collective identity, as demonstrated by de Santibañes *et al.* (2023), leads to the recognition of leadership skills. This offers an intrinsic pathway for women leaders to gain recognition and utilise their leadership identities, further supporting their career advancement.

Table 6: Emotional, Behavioural and Social Authenticity

	Emotional Authenticity	Behavioural Authenticity	Social Authenticity
Characteristics	Heart	Habit	Harmony
	Self-awareness	Growth mindset	Collective identity
Result	Contagious Passion	Optimistic outlook	Solidarity & commitment
Questions	Who you are?	What you do?	How you do it?

Table 6 presents the emotional, behavioural, and societal dimensions of authenticity identified in the literature. It illustrates how authenticity is expressed across individual, interpersonal, and social contexts, highlighting the multi-layered nature of authentic leadership. This table strengthens the study's theoretical foundation by demonstrating how authenticity operates beyond individual traits and is shaped by broader organisational and societal influences.

Placing authenticity within the broader context of leadership, it is essential to examine how intersections of identity influence leadership. This involves considering the relationships among leadership, authenticity, and gender.

2.5 Gendered Mindset and Leadership

2.5.1 Advantages of women-centric leadership

Intuitively, it is widely recognised that gender diversity is important. Although it could be argued that diversity does not automatically lead to profit, studies have shown a link between organisations that prioritise diversity in leadership and their ability to gain a competitive advantage (Winston, 2001). Gender diversity in the boardroom goes beyond merely having women present or achieving a balanced gender ratio. Research conducted in developed countries has demonstrated that women in the boardroom positively influence organisational governance, enhance team effectiveness, and foster innovation (Lafuente and Vaillant, 2019). It could be argued that for women leaders to impact organisational performance, they must hold significant positions within the organisation to exert meaningful influence. Studies have shown that while women in senior roles are often assigned riskier tasks, they tend to outperform their male counterparts (Francoeur *et al.*, 2008). Some researchers contend that diverse leadership support is essential, as it encourages an environment that nurtures talent (Smit, Schultz and Van, 2021).

Alongside the competitive advantage and performance that women leaders bring, a study conducted in India found that women in leadership roles have a high potential to boost the country's GDP (Laskar, Sahu and Choudhury, 2024). Eagley (2005) stated that female leaders are more vigilant regarding business ethics compared to their male counterparts. Eagley further argues that when female leaders adopt male-dominated behaviours, ethical issues continue within organisations. This analysis highlights the importance for women leaders to avoid adopting agentic leadership characteristics. Women leaders are often known to challenge normative, hierarchical frameworks (Domen, 2022), which may explain why, in the 21st century, there are still relatively few women in leadership positions. Rousseau (1953, p. 71) envisioned that women leaders “provide a civilising counterforce to the competitive nature of

men,” emphasising the importance of rethinking women’s roles for a just society. Additionally, studies suggest that treating women differently from men in leadership roles could lead to the creation of false moral rules, fostering social hypocrisy, which might be detrimental to organisational culture.

Although the benefits of women in leadership roles are widely recognised, there are barriers that restrict women’s progression into these positions. It is natural to form immediate associations and judgments about the expected behaviours of men and women. In Western society, for instance, when buying items for a baby boy, people usually pick blue, whereas pink is the preferred colour for a girl. These are cultural stereotypes and mindsets, which, although deeply rooted, can be challenged. Miola *et al.* (2023) argue that long-standing cultural views on the expected traits of men and women can obstruct women's advancement in the workplace.

Although these perspectives are evolving in many parts of the world, changing them still demands persistence and deliberate effort. Transforming ingrained cultural views requires new mindsets and skills; in a shifting culture, the process begins with the individual.

2.5.2 Challenges faced by Women Leaders

The main challenge women face in the workplace is the mindset spectrum. Women's mindsets can be divided into three segments. The first is a negative mindset, which restricts opportunities and keeps women confined within a gendered view. The second is a neutral mindset, where gender is not considered an obstacle to performance. This mindset can influence how a woman perceives herself. The final, positive mindset regards women's traits and characteristics as strengths that are valuable in leadership, seeing being a woman as an asset, and not feeling the need to adopt masculine behaviours (Fujimoto and Uddin, 2022).

Aaltio and Mills (2002) assert that a woman's experience in an organisation influences her position within the mindset spectrum. They describe organisations as "mini cultures" that serve

as "sources and sites of identification for individuals." Many women may not recognise these biases until they reach a certain position, and even if women maintain a positive attitude, it does not shield them from the real challenges the workplace may present (Seibel, 2022). Having a balanced and nuanced understanding of gender, shared by both men and women, can significantly impact the workplace and is vital for promoting inclusive leadership.

Cultural mindsets also greatly influence gendered behaviour. In many societies, stereotypical behaviours are deeply embedded: women are often associated with traits like cooperation and communalism, while men are generally linked with traits such as being directive, demanding, and dominant (Eagly and Karau, 2002). These perceptions shape communication styles, conflict resolution, decision-making processes, and leadership methods (Eagly *et al.*, 2012). When women display behaviours typically considered more masculine, they often face negative perceptions and backlash, whereas adopting more feminine traits may lead others to see them as weak or submissive. This creates a double bind (Johns, Inzlicht and Schmader, 2008), where women are forced to choose between behaviours each carrying potential disadvantages. If women are overly caring, they risk being dismissed as leaders; if they are too assertive, they risk being perceived as bossy. Ultimately, women are caught in a lose-lose situation dictated by gendered expectations.

Gender-related behaviours, as outlined by Young *et al.* (2007), indicate that combining both feminine and masculine traits helps leaders avoid reinforcing gender stereotypes. Successful leaders utilise a blend of traits, strengths, and competencies, regardless of whether they are classified as masculine or feminine. Leaders are encouraged to adopt characteristics that promote success in leadership, thereby preventing the perpetuation of traditional gender roles and stereotypes.

Unconscious bias is another major barrier. Research by Noon (2018) shows that everyone holds unconscious beliefs about different social identity groups, categorising people based on generalities and stereotypes. In the workplace, these biases can exclude individuals from opportunities (Williamson and Foley, 2018) and are a fundamental cause of gender inequality (Clar *et al.*, 2021). Gender bias may show in assumptions that women are more focused on family, less willing to take risks, or unable to make decisive decisions in crises, all of which can influence their chances of promotion.

Busch (2020) highlights the gender pay gap as an example of unconscious bias in the workplace. Other types of bias include reducing responsibilities assigned to women and their exclusion from roles traditionally held by men (Hogue and Lord, 2007). A pertinent question is how we would perceive a male secretary versus a female security officer. The point here is that, while research has extensively explored unconscious bias (Pennington *et al.*, 2023), studies have mainly focused on recognising biases rather than addressing them by building allies to challenge the physical biases women face at work.

Realists argue that the importance of gendered leadership has often been exaggerated due to stereotypes and biases embedded in the workplace (Vo *et al.*, 2013). This view emphasises the need to consider women in leadership roles, especially in countries like India where gender parity in leadership is still low. Research on the role of women leaders in such contexts is essential for raising awareness and advancing gender equality.

2.6. India

2.6.1 The Automobile Industry

The automobile industry is among the largest and fastest-growing sectors in India, playing a vital role in the country's economic development. From a consumer point of view, a car has

become a necessity, making the automobile industry a key driver of economic growth and leading to significant changes over the years.

The Indian automobile industry started in 1940 with passenger car production, and significant growth occurred in 1991 when foreign manufacturers were allowed to enter the market (Athukorala and Veeramani, 2019). This change reflects broader economic, technological, and policy shifts that have influenced the sector. The early 2000s saw a rise in incomes, urbanisation, and infrastructure improvements, which further spurred the industry's growth (Kaur and Kaur, 2016). The adoption of modern techniques, including fuel-efficient and environmentally friendly vehicles, has been a key factor in the industry's development. In China, research by Yu *et al.* (2022) shows that the automobile industry has contributed around 5% to the country's annual economic growth since 2002. The industry in India, like in other countries, operates within an oligopolistic market, which requires continuous innovation but also presents challenges such as diversity and inclusion (Becker, 2006). Understanding the industry's evolution is crucial, as it helps reveal how the Industrial Revolution influenced the development of the automobile sector.

However, the industry faces increasing operational challenges due to its complex environment. The COVID-19 pandemic, chip shortages, infrastructure problems, global supply chain disruptions, and trade issues have all driven up costs. Alongside these external pressures, the move towards electric and connected vehicles, as well as changing regulatory demands, have further unsettled the industry's stability. To overcome these challenges and maintain stability, quality, and efficiency, the industry must focus inward, especially on its talent pool. Research indicates that diversity can offer a competitive edge during uncertain times. A study by Pons, Ramos, and Ramos (2016) on organisational innovation behaviour suggests that innovation is often driven by intrinsic factors in women, while men tend to be more innovative based on job

demands. This variety of perspectives and ideas, particularly among diverse leadership, can help the industry seize opportunities within a volatile operating environment.

Despite the advantages of diverse leadership, a gender gap persists within the industry. Henry Ford, the founder of Ford Motor Company, famously stated, “Women were put on earth for the pleasure of man, women would take over the Ford Motor Company one day, and wreck it” (Iacocca and Novak, 1985, p. 108). This statement sharply highlights the need for further action to promote the inclusion of women in leadership roles within the industry. Research into women in leadership positions in the automotive sector has mainly focused on external factors such as women’s experiences as leaders in automotive dealerships in the USA (Bullock, 2019), work-life balance for women in the automotive environment (Detroit: Crain Communications, Inc., 2022), and gender harassment of female technicians within the industry (Foley *et al.*, 2022). These studies have predominantly examined external challenges; however, there is limited research exploring the internal factors that could empower women to ascend into leadership roles. More investigation is required into specific traits and internal motivators that could support women's advancement into decision-making positions within the industry.

Most studies on women in the automobile industry, with few exceptions focusing on supply chain and component manufacturing, are concentrated in the Western world, despite countries like India and China being among the largest producers of passenger cars. Moreover, most research has not concentrated on the core manufacturing units of the automobile industry, where women's representation as leaders is limited, but rather on dealerships and research and development units, where women's representation is relatively higher.

In India, the automobile industry is actively working to create an environment that offers more opportunities for women to advance their careers. However, despite these efforts, the transition to leadership roles remains slow. This is reflected in the static Gender Development Index

(GDI) for India, which stays at 0.63 for women, compared to 0.72 for men, indicating that women still lag behind in human development achievements (UNDP, 2024). The pressure on the industry to implement policies that support the advancement of women within organisations is increasing. Some positive effects of women's participation in leadership have been observed. For example, a study by Rastogi *et al.* (2022) on women entrepreneurs found a 16% increase in women's entrepreneurial activities due to the creation of job opportunities within organisations. Similarly, research by Mythili (2019) suggests that women are increasingly assuming leadership roles in the educational sector.

However, scholars such as Vasavada (2012) have highlighted the underrepresentation of women in senior leadership roles, with women holding just 6% of senior positions and 4.9% of board of directors' seats. Additionally, Rastogi *et al.* (2022) found that women's labour participation in India remains at 26.97%, a figure that has seen little improvement since 2012. According to the World Bank (2024), statistics showed a 33% increase as of 2022; however, when compared to 2005, when the percentage was 35%, this indicates a decline rather than an increase, which is troubling.

Despite being a traditionally male-dominated sector, the Indian automobile industry has made significant progress in enhancing gender diversity. For example, Renault Nissan's manufacturing facility in Chennai has established a dedicated production line for women, called the 'L line' (Boothem, 2021). Similarly, MG Motors India's "Drive Her Back" campaign motivates women to re-enter the workforce after career breaks (MG Motors, 2023). As Cyr *et al.* (2021) observe, women continue to make advances in an industry historically dominated by men, but they frequently face a cold reception at senior levels. While such initiatives at the grassroots are encouraging, they have yet to lead to substantial progress in higher leadership positions.

The representation of women in leadership roles is vital for the industry's development, and their inclusion in the boardroom would greatly benefit the Indian automobile sector. However, gender diversity in the boardroom largely remains absent from the industry's priorities. The patriarchal history of the automobile industry continues to influence perceptions of women in leadership positions. The industry needs to undergo an internal shift, fostering a gender-bias-free operational environment through strategies such as sponsorships, which align with international business practices.

Previous research on gender in the automobile industry has focused primarily on gender bias and its detrimental effects on women's success. This research has helped shape various policies that promote gender diversity, including robust recruitment policies designed to create diverse work environments. A study by Gupta and Roy (2023) highlighted that the introduction of government policies encouraging women's participation resulted in an immediate surge of women applicants. Such outcomes are more likely when the industry demonstrates a commitment to building a diverse workforce, although gender bias in leadership selection remains an issue. As a result, women in leadership positions remain scarce in the upper echelons of the organisation.

Kulkarni *et al.* (2023) indicated that studies on culture and its impact on women leaders have mainly focused on the societal pressures affecting women's advancement in India. While such research has helped understand the cultural barriers women face, it has been criticised for offering limited solutions. Although the results of these studies have led to the development of various policies aimed at promoting greater gender diversity, the approach to addressing cultural issues is often overly simplistic. A country's culture cannot be simply moulded into a framework for change; instead, it must be continuously observed. Therefore, it is more practical

to concentrate on intrinsic factors that can be adapted within a framework, producing results that are both controllable and measurable.

Through the study of literature, an intersectional analysis of leadership, gender, authenticity, and the automobile industry in India has provided a deeper understanding of inherent issues, such as structural inequalities. A notable gap identified in the literature regarding leadership was the lack of discussion on gender. This study further aimed to address this gap by identifying a leadership trait that could bridge the gender divide in leadership. Among various leadership traits, authenticity was considered a better fit than charisma due to its long-term benefits, including stability and the fostering of a strong organisational culture. However, the literature revealed several gaps, particularly in the investigation of gender and authentic leadership (Gardiner, 2015). Scholarly work on authenticity has largely focused on behavioural explanations (Larsson, 2021), with an emphasis on leaders' self-knowledge (Muafi and Pujiastuti, 2019), and often lacks cultural context, which is crucial for understanding authentic leadership in diverse settings.

When considering the gaps identified by other scholars, this study highlights the importance of viewing authentic leadership through the lens of gender and examining the differences in leadership experiences. This approach seeks to integrate authentic leadership within the intersectionality framework, addressing both leadership and gender simultaneously. The reviewed literature on gendered leadership also emphasised the advantages women have in leadership roles and the obstacles they encounter. The flexible nature of the concept of gender was further explored, offering a deeper understanding of gendered leadership. In line with Sinclair's (2013, p.249) call for "feminist research that exposes how authentic leadership has contributed to gender," this study recognises how the idea of authenticity is constructed and aims to interpret it through a gendered perspective. This approach emphasises a gender-

sensitive understanding of authenticity, which is crucial for women's leadership in India's automobile industry.

From the literature reviewed on India and the distinctive features of the automobile industry, it is evident that women should have a greater representation in leadership roles. In accordance with Kezar and Lester's (2010) academic work, this study does not aim to claim that women are inherently better leaders than men but seeks to encourage men to act as sponsors for women's advancement into leadership positions. This approach fosters gender equity and recognises the importance of sponsorship in progressing women's careers in male-dominated sectors. A key finding from the literature review is the absence of intersectionality between leadership, gender, and authenticity, highlighting a gap in current research.

As discussed through these concepts, the field of leadership lacks consensus on definitions and traits of effective leaders. While leadership has been studied in various contexts, research on gender and authenticity within a developing economy like India is limited. The literature suggests that leadership has evolved over time, and none of the identified traits are considered irrelevant. The focus now must be on creating inclusive, gender-aware leadership frameworks that reflect the complexities of modern workplaces, particularly within the Indian automobile industry.

Leadership is evolving, and the synthesis from the narrative literature review emphasises the importance of understanding how different aspects of a leader's identity, such as gender and culture, interact to make leadership effective. The role women play in leadership, as explained by Werhane and Painter (2011), has traditionally led to an understanding of the characteristics that define how women lead. However, to go beyond the established canon of characteristics that initially helped in studying the social barriers women face, such as metaphors like the glass ceiling (Carter, 2011), glass cliff, and the leaking pipeline, the literature has expanded its focus

to include possible alternatives, such as authentic leadership. This trait offers a framework through which women can develop from within, embracing their inherent strengths as leaders.

Several gaps identified through the narrative literature review highlight a substantial body of scholarly work that has examined the external barriers faced by women, including issues such as pay parity, equal opportunities in recruitment, government quotas, and relevant policies. Most of these studies have contrasted women's experiences with those of men (Eagly *et al.*, 2003). However, fewer studies have concentrated on the intrinsic factors that enable women to overcome these external barriers. As indicated by Pillay and Vermeulen (2023), despite facing these challenges, some women leaders are able to overcome societal constraints and successfully assume leadership roles. This suggests that an exploration of the internal, individual factors, such as traits, beliefs, and values, can provide a deeper understanding of women's leadership in a more holistic sense.

2.7. Systematic Literature Review

The narrative review utilised concepts such as leadership, gendered leadership, and authentic leadership, highlighting a gap in the literature concerning the lack of intersectionality between these concepts. The aim of the systematic literature review (SLR) is to apply prescribed methodological approaches to identify relevant literature on these concepts (Rosado, Paul, and Dikova, 2018). Understanding the relationships between these variables helps identify implicit biases that may contribute to the pipeline problem, which ultimately results in the scarcity of women leaders (Eagly and Carli, 2007).

As stated by Tranfield, Denyer, and Smart (2003), a systematic literature review must be reproducible. This study is designed to be replicated by others who follow the protocols of an SLR. To review a protocol, it is essential to formulate research questions that will be addressed. These questions establish a clear link between the evidence collected from the literature and

the recommendations and conclusions made (van, Tekinerdogan and Catal, 2021). A systematic literature review includes a protocol that details the methodology, defines the criteria for including and excluding studies, and specifies the databases, as well as the process for data extraction and synthesis (Ramalho *et al.*, 2021). To guide the systematic literature review, the research questions are framed according to the research aim (Efron and Ravid, 2019), ensuring a focused approach by excluding irrelevant information (Ghanem, 2008). By following these steps, the criteria for the study become clear. The review process follows the framework developed by Tranfield *et al.* (2003), which involves three steps: planning the review, conducting the review, and reporting and disseminating the findings.

Firstly, in planning the review to examine the scope and extent of the study, a scoping study was initially conducted to identify emerging trends within leadership, authentic leadership, and gendered leadership (Levac, Colquhoun and O'Brien, 2010). This scoping study helped in developing the questions necessary for the review. The following questions were used to guide this systematic literature review: What emerges from the interconnection among leadership, authenticity, and women leaders within the automobile industry in the context of India? What are the characteristics of successful women leaders, the challenges they overcame, and the impacts of authentic leadership among women in the Indian automobile industry?

Secondly, the evaluation criteria for selecting studies for the SLR are vital. Having a clear selection criterion is essential to identify relevant results (Tranfield *et al.*, 2003). To support this process, a predetermined checklist facilitates the systematic filtering of information into the literature review (Oxman, 1994).

Table 7: The inclusion criteria sought to address the search based on screening questions:

How relevant is this article to my specific topic?
What are the major relationships, trends, and patterns?
How credible is this source?
What are the similarities between the sources?

Table 7 outlines the inclusion criteria and screening questions used for participant selection in this study. It ensures that participants met the defined research requirements and possessed relevant leadership experience within the automobile industry. This table supports methodological rigour by demonstrating a transparent and systematic approach to sampling.

Table 8: Inclusion Criteria

Peer reviewed in the English language
Is relevant to the research aims
Articles focus on leadership/ gendered leadership/authentic leadership

Table 8 presents the inclusion criteria used for selecting participants in this study. It specifies the characteristics required for participation, ensuring alignment with the research objectives and the interpretive phenomenological approach. This table enhances transparency and credibility by clearly defining the boundaries of the study sample.

Table 9: Exclusion Criteria

Articles on other forms of gender other than women
Unpublished work

Articles without references
Grey research (Interviews, book reviews etc)

Table 9 outlines the exclusion criteria applied during the participant selection process. It identifies characteristics that disqualified potential participants to ensure the sample remained aligned with the study's scope and research objectives. This table supports methodological rigour by clarifying how irrelevant or unsuitable cases were systematically excluded.

The third part of the process involves conducting the review, where the research protocol offers a structured and pre-defined approach (Jesson, Matheson and Lacey, 2011). This stage includes creating a detailed protocol that outlines the study's objectives, design, methodology, and analysis plan. The study employed extensive searches that helped identify databases containing relevant information on leadership, authentic leadership, and gendered leadership. Some of the databases used included Scopus, Emerald, Science Direct, Google Scholar, Web of Science, Cochrane, Journal of Leadership, Wiley Online Library, the Academy of Management, BrowZine Library, and SAGE Publications. Electronic searches, hand searches, and peer-reviewed sources formed part of the search strategy, a vital phase in the literature review process. This approach was crucial in extracting data relevant to qualitative research (Finfgeld and Johnson, 2013).

Within the aforementioned databases, relevant search strings were employed to identify data pertinent to the research. The aim was to translate the research questions into explicit terms for the search engine, which would then provide resources related to the specific subject (Kable and Maslin, 2012). The search strings used in this process are provided below.

Table 10: Search String

Search String	Key words
Search string (01)	Leadership (in title)
Search string (01)a	Leadership Definitions (anywhere)
Search string (01)b	Leadership Theories (anywhere)
Search string (02)	Leadership Traits (in Title)
Search string (02)a	Charismatic AND Authentic leadership (anywhere)
Search string (02)b	Authentic leadership (anywhere)
Search string (03)	Gendered leadership (in title)
Search string (03)a	Women centric leadership (anywhere)
Search string (03)b	Challenges in women centric leadership (anywhere)

Table 10 presents the search string used for the systematic literature review. It outlines how keywords and Boolean operators were combined to identify relevant studies across academic databases. This table supports the transparency and replicability of the review process by clearly documenting the search strategy employed.

To ascertain key concepts, positioned on the research questions, search techniques such as algorithms (leadership* or women lead*) in combination with Boolean operators (Stapleton, 2020; Andrew, 2022) were used to combine the concepts. The searches included synonyms to gather wider material on “Leadership and Types of leadership”, and additional phrases using

Proximity search were used such as “women leadership, gendered Leadership”. The Search included using Truncation techniques such as “Leader*” and “women leaders#”.

Finally reporting and dissemination the articles found the following concepts which were subject to the inclusion and exclusion criteria.

Table 11: Keywords and results

Key word	Results
Leadership	383,790
Authentic Leadership	4425
Gendered Leadership	1786
Women in authentic leadership	238

Table 11 presents the keywords used in the systematic literature review and the corresponding search results. It provides an overview of how each keyword contributed to the identification of relevant studies across databases. This table supports the robustness of the literature review by demonstrating the breadth and effectiveness of the search process.

Top Journals serve as a final filter to ensure the feasibility of the systematic literature review, with a focus on the selected top research studies. Resulting in 150 articles.

2.7.1 Quality Assessment

For the critical appraisal of published systematic reviews, the PRISMA (Preferred Reporting Items for Systematic Reviews and Meta-Analysis) has been used as a quality assessment tool. The PRISMA framework was employed to develop the search strategy. The PRISMA quality assessment enabled the researcher to identify and select appropriate databases for articles

relevant to the study. Leadership, being a broad topic, attracted numerous references; however, the search on gendered leadership within the context of authentic leadership was narrowed to be more specific and to contribute to the overall study.

Figure 2 PRISMA flow diagram:

In the final set, the 150 articles were reviewed and analysed in detail. Within the SLR, the following areas were examined: type of articles, number of publications, and citations. From the analysis of narrative literature review concepts, sub-concepts were determined. This study will now analyse literature emerging within these concepts.

2.7.2 Leadership

“There is often confusion in leadership between prescription and description”- Gardiner (2015, p. 15)

Leadership scholars have put together myriads of concepts around leadership. From people to process, talent to trait, skills to style, leadership has evolved and continues to evolve with no one clear distinct standalone concept on leadership. This section aims to critically discuss what recent scholars have coined with regards to the terms on leadership.

Table 12: Leadership

Authors	Article Title
Alvesson (2020)	Positive Leadership: A Formula for or a Challenge to 'Successful' Leadership Research
Banks (2023)	Eight puzzles of leadership science
Collins <i>et al</i> (2023)	The Leadership/Management Concept Scale: Identifying Actions Unique to Leadership versus Management
Cheong, Spain, Yammarino and Yun (2016)	The Dual Facets of Empowering Leadership: Facilitating or Burdening
Collins and Jackson, (2015)	A Process Model of Leadership Self-Regulation: How Attention and Negative Emotions Shape Leadership Outcomes
Dansereau <i>et al.</i> (2013)	What Constitutes Leadership? Bridging Traditional and Modern Perspectives via Self-Expansion Theory
Day, Riggio, Conger and Tan, (2018)	21st-Century Approaches to Leadership Development: Integrating Theory and Practice
Elsaied (2022)	The Link Between Exploitative Leadership and Organisational Cynicism: The Mediating Impact of Emotional Exhaustion
Epitropaki <i>et al</i> (2017)	Identity Processes in Leadership and Followership: A Multilevel Perspective
Evans (2022)	Challenging the Myth of Leadership: A Critical Approach to Reshaping Educational Leadership

Fischer <i>et al.</i> (2023)	Rethinking Leadership Science: Moving Beyond Questionnaires
Gardner <i>et al.</i> (2010)	Scholarly leadership of the study of leadership
Halliwell, Mitchell and Boyle (2022)	The Role of Emotional Intelligence and Leadership Self-Efficacy in Task-Oriented Leadership: Evidence from a Coaching Study
Hogg <i>et al.</i> (2019)	Social Identity and Leadership
Hughes <i>et al.</i> (2018)	Leadership and Innovation Through Creativity: A Critical Review with Practical Guidance
Oc (2018)	The Role of Context in Leadership: A Systematic Review of Its Effects on Leadership and Outcomes
Olivola, Eubanks, and Lovelace (2014)	The Distinct Faces of Leadership: Predicting Leadership Domains from Facial Features
Orphanos and Orr (2014)	How Innovative Leadership Preparation Shapes Teachers' Experiences and Outcomes
Pietraszewski (2020)	The Development of Leadership: Enabling Effective Cooperation and Coordination Through Leadership and Followership
Rosing, Frese and Bausch (2011)	Ambidextrous Leadership as a Lens for Explaining Differences in Leadership–Innovation Relationships
Rudolph, Rauvola and Zacher (2018)	A Critical Review of Leadership and Multigenerational Dynamics at Work
Shamir (2011)	Time and Leadership: Understanding the Impact of Temporal Considerations in Leadership Research

Uhl-Bien and Arena, (2018)	A Conceptual Framework Linking Leadership to Organisational Adaptability
White, Currie and Lockett (2016)	Cross-Network Dynamics of Leadership in Complex Organisations: Linking Formal and Informal Leadership
Zacher and Rosing (2015)	Fostering Team Innovation Through Ambidextrous Leadership Practices

Table 12 summarises leadership-related literature identified through the systematic literature review. It categorises key studies to highlight dominant themes, theoretical orientations, and research focus within leadership scholarship. This table supports the identification of patterns and gaps in the literature that inform the study's conceptual and theoretical positioning.

Leadership is an evolving subject that is both complex and multifaceted, spanning anthropology, psychology, biology, and sociology (Pietraszewski, 2020). The modern understanding of leadership has evolved through various theoretical frameworks (Fischer *et al.*, 2023). Leadership is a crucial subject in organisational dynamics (Hogg *et al.*, 2019), influencing how goals are set and achieved, how teams collaborate, and how individuals grow and develop within their roles (Epitropaki *et al.*, 2017). Understanding the complexities of leadership supports both individuals and the organisation, enabling them to handle challenges successfully. When leaders demonstrate optimism and a positive attitude, they can inspire their teams, promoting resilience, purpose, and higher engagement and performance (Alvesson, 2020). However, challenges for leadership in the 21st century is immensely shaped by rapid technology advancements, globalisation and shifting societal expectations (Day *et al.*, 2018). The research by Zacher and Rosing (2015) is concerned with the ability of leaders to effectively

manage both exploration and exploitation, requiring ambidextrous leadership. Collins and Jackson (2015) outline a leadership self-regulation framework demonstrating how limited attention and negative emotions influence constructive versus destructive leadership actions.

Rudolph, Rauvola, and Zacher (2018) provide an evaluative review exploring the intersection of leadership and generational dynamics in the workplace, emphasising the importance of understanding generational dynamics in leadership to optimise organisational performance and foster a positive work environment. On the other hand, Shamir's (2011) work addresses the significance of time in understanding and practising effective leadership by taking a longitudinal view in recognising the developmental nature of leadership. Researchers and practitioners can gain deeper insights into leadership processes, enhance leadership effectiveness, and foster organisational resilience in a dynamic and evolving world. Leadership that takes time seriously integrates strategic foresight, relationship building, and continuous learning to drive sustainable success and create lasting organisational impact. Studies on leadership have resulted in terms such as 'Effectiveness of leadership', 'intersection of leadership', 'complexities of leadership', and 'challenges of leadership'. Theoretical perspectives on leadership effectively capture leader practices; however, contemporary interpretations may obscure the link between effectiveness and ethical responsibility.

2.7.2.1 Definitions

After examining the literature on leadership, it's unclear why contextual and cultural specifics have not been addressed. The lack of intersectionality in understanding the interconnected nature of social identities in shaping leadership experiences and outcomes is evident in the literature.

“Leadership is the practice of guiding and motivating people to work collectively toward meaningful outcomes “-Vroom and Jago (2007)

Tab13: Leadership Definitions

Author	Article Title
Bass (1997)	Personal Selling and Transactional/Transformational Leadership
Benzel (2021)	Leadership
Brent <i>et al.</i> (2019)	A Review of Leadership Concepts, Competencies, and Methods of Evaluation
Fondas (1990)	The managerial mystique. Restoring leadership in business
Ibacco (1989, p. 229)	Iacocca an autobiography
Lynham and Chermack (2006)	Exploring Responsible Leadership for Enhanced Performance: Model and Hypotheses
Rosari (2019)	Leadership Theories and Their Role in Supporting Lecturers' Leadership Growth', Universitas Gadjah Mada, Journal of leadership in organisations
Sellami <i>et al.</i> (2022)	Definitions of educational leadership - Arab educators' perspectives', London: Routledge, International journal of leadership in education

Table 13 summarises key leadership definitions identified through the systematic literature review. It consolidates how leadership is conceptualised across empirical and theoretical studies, highlighting similarities and variations in definitions. This table supports conceptual

clarity and informs the study's positioning of leadership as a relational and context-dependent construct.

The definition provided by Benzel (2021) on leadership highlights a key aspect by emphasising the art of influencing others to achieve outcomes that might not occur naturally. This definition underscores the idea that effective leadership inspires and guides individuals to work together and contribute towards a common goal. Similarly, Bass (1997), a well-known leadership scholar, emphasised the importance of leaders sharing a vision and a sense of mission with their followers. According to Bass, effective leadership involves not only articulating and communicating a vision but also engaging followers in the process of understanding and internalising that vision. This fosters collaboration, creativity, and a sense of ownership among team members, which are essential for organisational success and sustainable growth.

Further expanding on this concept, Sellami *et al.* (2022) emphasised that leadership is fundamentally about influencing others. This perspective emphasises that leadership extends beyond formal authority or hierarchical rank, being fundamentally rooted in the leader's capacity to inspire, guide, and influence the actions and decisions of others. Rosari (2019) and Brent *et al.* (2019) contributed to this discourse by offering a contemporary view of leadership, distinguishing it from management and underscoring its relational and transformative nature.

Across these definitions, several key themes emerge, such as leadership as influence, motivation, vision, and artistic skill. However, it is noteworthy that leadership has been conceptualised in many ways over time by both scholars and practitioners. The lack of a single, universally accepted definition reflects the complex and multifaceted nature of the concept, as well as its varying interpretations across different contexts. As such, leadership is often understood through the perspective of its formulators, shaped by personal, organisational, and cultural viewpoints.

This variation in definitions prompts an important question: how might the differences in the understanding of leadership affect the relevance of leadership studies across different cultural contexts? The inconsistency indicates that without cultural sensitivity, leadership theories and practices developed in one region or society may not be directly applicable or meaningful to another. This emphasises the importance of examining leadership through culturally responsive frameworks.

The next prominent sub-concept within the broader theme of leadership is leadership theories. From the review of literature, a noticeable gap has emerged in the lack of contextual consideration. Just as leadership definitions vary, so too do the theoretical frameworks, often developed in specific socio-cultural environments. To fully understand leadership and its influence on behaviour, it becomes essential to examine the prevailing leadership theories and how they relate to, or fall short of, addressing contextual and cultural dynamics.

2.7.2.2 Theories

“A recent review of literature on leadership theories resulted in 66 theories published since the year 2000” (Meuser *et al.*, 2016)

This count could indicate the maturity within the field of leadership or the lack of integration which would be studied in this section.

Table 14: Theories

Authors	Article Title
Derue <i>et al.</i> (2011)	Trait and behavioural theories of leadership: An integration and meta-analytic test of their relative validity’

Guarana and Avolio (2022)	Unpacking Psychological Ownership: How Transactional and Transformational Leaders Motivate Ownership
Glynn and Raffaelli (2010)	Uncovering mechanisms of theory development in an academic field: Lessons from leadership research
Kaptein (2019)	The Moral Entrepreneur: A New Component of Ethical Leadership
Luria <i>et al.</i> (2019)	Contextual moderators for leadership potential based on trait activation theory
Sims Faraj and Yun (2009)	When should a leader be directive or empowering? How to develop your own situational theory of leadership
Sobaih <i>et al.</i> (2022)	The impact of transactional and transformational leadership
Strauss (2012) Spector and Alan (2016)	Masters of Command: Alexander, Hannibal, Caesar, and the Genius of Leadership Carlyle, Freud, and the Great Man Theory more fully considered
Tortorella and Fogliatto (2017)	Triangulation, Respondent Validation, and Democratic Participation in Mixed Methods Research
Van (2011)	Servant Leadership: A Review and Synthesis

Table 14 presents an overview of leadership theories identified in the systematic literature review. It categorises the dominant theoretical frameworks used across studies and highlights their primary focus and assumptions. This table supports the critical evaluation of existing

theories and helps identify theoretical gaps relevant to gender, context, and authentic leadership.

An insightful exploration by Strauss (2012) highlights the military strategies and leadership styles of three of history's most renowned commanders, aiming to uncover the attributes that made them exceptional leaders. Strauss concludes that their exceptionalism can be attributed to a combination of vision, strategic brilliance, and charismatic traits that are possibly innate. Similarly, Spector and Alan (2016) examine the nuances of the Great Man Theory by exploring the contributions of thinkers such as Thomas Carlyle and Sigmund Freud, reinforcing the argument that leadership may originate from inborn qualities. However, Luria *et al.* (2019) challenge this static view by proposing that certain traits become more prominent in environments that activate them. According to their research, recognising contextual moderators allows organisations to create environments that foster the emergence of desirable leadership traits.

A more integrative approach is offered by DeRue *et al.* (2011), who conducted a meta-analytic study synthesising trait and behavioural leadership theories. Their findings highlight that both traits and behaviours are significant predictors of leadership effectiveness and that these are moderated by contextual factors. This perspective bridges the historical dichotomy between trait- and behaviour-based approaches. Similarly, Tortorella and Fogliatto (2017), along with Sims, Faraj, and Yun (2009), emphasise the importance of situational factors in leadership, aligning with the principles of situational leadership theory, which posits that a leader's actions and decisions should vary according to the demands of the specific context.

Shifting the focus from context to process, Guarana and Avolio (2022) advocate for understanding leadership as a more transactional and dynamic process. They emphasise the importance of striking a balance between structure and alignment in leadership practice.

However, Glynn and Raffaelli (2010) argue that leadership theories remain fragmented and overly proliferated, making it difficult to integrate a coherent understanding of the concept. This theoretical fragmentation is reflected in real-world failures of leadership, such as the Wells Fargo scandal, where leadership misjudgements, such as Caryl Athanasiu's divergent view on risk, resulted in significant reputational damage (Witman, 2018). Such examples suggest that the overabundance of theories may lead leaders to emulate prefabricated styles rather than developing an authentic leadership identity grounded in character and context.

This raises important questions about the study of leadership theories: Do the evidence supporting ideas such as innate leadership traits, the importance of ethical conduct, or situational responsiveness genuinely validate the effectiveness of these models? Are contrasting findings, such as cultural discrepancies or failures of leaders who strictly follow one model, underreported in the literature? Moreover, to what degree does culture influence the expression and success of these leadership traits and behaviours?

The research clearly demonstrates that the core concept of leadership, along with related sub-concepts such as definitions and theories, has undergone notable evolution. From trait-based origins to behavioural and context-dependent models, the literature shows a diverse and growing field. However, the lack of coherence and connection between leadership definitions and theories raises questions. It remains uncertain whether authors have sufficiently considered the impact of culture and gender in their theoretical frameworks. This gap highlights the need for more intersectional and culturally sensitive leadership studies.

2.7.2.3 Leadership Traits

Several articles emerged from the systematic literature review, which aimed to present theoretical work concerning leadership traits specific to charismatic and authentic leaders, is provided below.

“The reason why there is so much unethical leadership within leaders is because we look at them as heroes”-George (2003)

Tab 15: Leadership Traits

Authors	Article Title
Arenas (2019)	A casebook of transformational and transactional leadership
Avolio and Gardner (2005)	Authentic leadership development: Getting to the root of positive forms of leadership
Arendt (1958)	The origins of Totalitarianism
Bandura and Kavussanu (2018)	Authentic leadership in sport: Its relationship with athletes
Bass and Avolio (1994)	Improving Organisational Effectiveness through Transformational Leadership
Bix (2010)	Beyond Amelia Earhart: Teaching about the History of Women Aviators
Conger and Kanungo (1987)	Toward a behavioural theory of charismatic leadership in organisational settings
Chen (2016)	Linking leader personality traits to motivation to lead: A self-concept approach
Dayan and Chan (2012)	Charismatic leadership in Singapore

Ely <i>et al.</i> (2011)	Taking gender into account: Theory and design for women's leadership development
Farid <i>et al.</i> (2020)	The Impact of Authentic Leadership on Organisational Citizenship Behaviours
Ford and Harding (2011)	The impossibility of the 'true self' of authentic leadership
Fox, Gardiner and Storberg (2017)	Viewing Authentic Leadership Through a Bourdieusian Lens: Understanding Gender and Leadership as Social Action
Gardiner (2015)	Gender, authenticity and leadership
George (2003)	Authentic Leadership: Rediscovering the Secrets to Creating Lasting Value
Gardner <i>et al.</i> (2005)	Can you see the real me? A self-based model of authentic leader and follower development
Heidegger (1962)	Being in Time
House (1977)	A 1976 theory of charismatic leadership
Jay and Rabinder (1998)	Charismatic Leadership in organisations
Lauren <i>et al.</i> (2019)	Bad Witches: Gender and the Downfall of Elizabeth Holmes of Theranos and Disney's Maleficent
Laschinger <i>et al.</i> (2012)	Authentic leadership, empowerment, and burnout: a comparison of new graduates and experienced nurses

L.A., and Gibson (2018)	The Kaleidoscope Career Model Revisited: How Midcareer Men and Women Diverge on Authenticity, Balance, and Challenge
Le Blanc <i>et al.</i> (2021)	Charismatic Leadership and Work Team Innovative Behaviour
Le <i>et al.</i> (2021)	It's a Little Different for Men
Luthans and Avolio (2003)	Authentic leadership development
Mayo (2018)	Yours truly: staying authentic in leadership and life
Monehin and Diers (2022)	Pragmatic optimism, crisis leadership, and contingency theory: A view from the C-suite
Moore and Maxey (2023)	Inclusive organisations: developmental reciprocity through authentic leader-employee relationships
Nahavandi (2009)	The art and science of leadership
Naidoo (2014)	Enhancing validity when researching the 'Other' : insights from Pierre Bourdieu's Theory of Social Science Research Practice
Nair, Prasad and Shreekumar (2022)	Authentic Leadership and Team Members
Nassif <i>et al.</i> (2021)	Ethical, Virtuous, and Charismatic Leadership: An Examination of Differential Relationships with Follower and Leader Outcomes
Neider and Schriesheim (2011)	The Authentic Leadership Inventory (ALI): Development and empirical tests

Salmela (2005)	What Is Emotional Authenticity
Smith and Lindsay (2014)	Beyond inclusion
Spain (2019)	Leadership, work, and the dark side of personality
Sverre (2018)	Leadership and Organisation, A Philosophical Introduction
Sy, Horton and Riggio (2018)	Charismatic leadership: Eliciting and channelling follower emotions
Tidhar (2023)	Management and leadership for generation Z in an era of changing employee commitment
Walumbwa <i>et al.</i> (2008)	Authentic Leadership: Development and Validation of a Theory-Based Measure
Zehetner <i>et al.</i> (2022)	Generation Z's Expectations of Their Leaders: A Cross-cultural, Multi-dimensional Investigation of Leadership Styles
Zhang <i>et al.</i> (2020)	Heroes or Villains? The Dark Side of Charismatic Leadership and Unethical Pro-organisational Behaviour

Table 15 summarises key leadership traits identified in the literature. It highlights the characteristics most frequently associated with effective leadership across studies. This table supports the analysis of leadership traits and provides a foundation for examining authentic leadership as a critical intrinsic trait within the study.

A study conducted by Chen (2016) examines various personality traits associated with an individual's motivation to lead, asserting that these traits significantly influence the emergence

of leadership. Vlachos and Rapp (2013) examine charismatic leadership as a distinct trait, focusing on its impact on job satisfaction and interpersonal relationships within the workplace. Their findings suggest that charismatic leadership, when effectively reinforced, can enhance job satisfaction, benefiting both employees and the organisation.

Dayan and Chan (2012) add cultural depth to this discussion by investigating the impact of charisma in a multicultural context. Their study reveals that charisma can thrive across different cultural landscapes, indicating that its effectiveness is not culturally neutral but shaped by local norms and values. Further enriching this discourse, Sy, Horton and Riggio (2018) emphasise the emotional dimension of charismatic leadership. They propose that charisma functions not merely to harness emotions but to foster sustained motivation, highlighting the role of emotional engagement in leadership success.

Le Blanc *et al.* (2021) explore charismatic leadership through the lens of organisational innovation, positing that charisma can cultivate a more innovative culture. This perspective aligns with Jay and Rabindra (1998), who argue that charismatic leadership fosters creativity by encouraging bold thinking and openness to new ideas. However, Sverre (2018) provides a more philosophical interpretation, raising ethical concerns regarding the use of charisma in leadership. His work questions whether charisma, when unmoderated, can lead to manipulative or morally ambiguous leadership practices.

This concern is echoed in empirical studies such as Zhang *et al.* (2020), which explore how charismatic leaders may engage in unethical behaviour under the guise of achieving organisational objectives. This raises concerns about the darker potential of charisma, a critique also highlighted by Nassif *et al.* (2021), who caution that while charismatic leadership may be effective, it can become problematic without adequate ethical safeguards. Importantly, research by Lauren *et al.* (2019) and Spain (2019) suggests that the effectiveness of charismatic

leadership depends heavily on contextual factors, including the leader's authenticity and the alignment between their personal values and the organisation's goals.

The multicultural exploration by Dayan and Chan (2012) encourages critical reflection on how cultural differences affect the reception and practice of charismatic leadership. This raises broader questions: What are the implications of cultural diversity for the effectiveness of charisma as a leadership trait? How do these findings apply within organisational contexts across various sectors? Have scholars adequately addressed the impact of industry-specific factors on the success or limitations of charisma?

To provide a comparative analysis and identify the most suitable trait for this study, another positive leadership trait, authenticity, was chosen. Walumbwa *et al.* (2008) have significantly contributed to leadership scholarship by conceptualising, validating, and measuring authentic leadership. While their work advances understanding of authenticity, they also acknowledge limitations regarding the measurement's precision and the generalisability of findings across various organisational contexts. Nevertheless, their study lays critical groundwork for future exploration of authentic leadership in different sectors.

To fully understand the origins of the concept, it is essential to refer to George (2003), the practitioner who popularised the term 'authentic leadership'. George introduced the concept as a response to the growing number of ethical scandals in corporate leadership. He posits that authentic leaders operate with a strong moral compass, rooted in personal integrity and congruence with organisational values. Critics have questioned whether authenticity alone is sufficient to prevent unethical conduct. George (2003) addresses this by offering a framework in which the leader's values are deeply aligned with those of the organisation, thereby mitigating the likelihood of ethical breaches (as illustrated in Figure 3). This framework

positions authenticity as a buffer against unethical leadership, requiring leaders to act consistently with both their internal values and the external expectations of ethical conduct.

Figure 3: Authentic Leadership Value Circle

George (2003, p. 16)

George (2003) argues that authentic leadership encourages leaders to bring their true selves into the organisation, recognising that leadership can often be a lonely journey. When leaders possess a deep understanding of themselves, they are better equipped to navigate this solitude with maturity. This trait distinguishes authentic leadership from other leadership theories, which often focus on developing individuals for leadership positions but provide little guidance for those already in leadership roles.

Heidegger's (1962) philosophical text *Being and Time* explores authenticity as emerging from a determined desire to care, whereas Arendt (1958) suggests that authenticity is manifest through speech and action in relation to others. Collectively, their perspectives suggest that authenticity arises from a commitment to care for both self and others. Building on this, Fox, Gardiner and Storberg (2017) adopt a Bourdieusian lens to analyse authentic leadership sociologically, integrating Bourdieu's social theory (Naidoo, 2014) to enrich the understanding

of leadership dynamics. However, they acknowledge that findings from qualitative studies may be limited in terms of generalisability across wider organisational contexts.

Empirical work by Neider and Schriesheim (2011) makes a significant contribution to the field by developing a measurement tool for operationalising authentic leadership. Despite methodological limitations, this represents a meaningful advancement, underscoring the need for further research. Similarly, Farid *et al.* (2020) and Laschinger *et al.* (2012) examine the impact of authentic leadership on organisational outcomes using empirical methods. In contrast, Nahavandi (2009) discusses authenticity as an essential component of leadership but relies primarily on theoretical analysis rather than empirical evidence. Le *et al.* (2021) introduce a critical dimension by highlighting how societal biases influence leadership perceptions, particularly in relation to gender. Although authentic leadership is widely regarded as a practical theory for the workplace, Ford and Harding (2011) raise concerns about its potentially destructive aspects. Their critique, rooted in object relations theory, does not provide a comprehensive evaluation and instead focuses narrowly on selected scholars, rendering their argument less justifiable.

The existing literature collectively confirms the importance of authentic leadership within organisational contexts. Scholars such as Smith and Lindsay (2014), Mayo (2018), Bandura and Kavussanu (2018), and Moore and Maxey (2023) expand on its applications, discussing inclusion, personal identity, sport, and organisational culture. Meanwhile, Gardiner (2015), Ely *et al.* (2011), and L.A. and Gibson (2018) examine the intersection of gender and authentic leadership, emphasising the need for gender-sensitive leadership development initiatives and exploring how career satisfaction and choices vary between men and women.

Other studies have examined authenticity across different generations and cultures. For example, Zehetner *et al.* (2022) explore leadership expectations in Generation Z, while Tidhar

(2023) looks at how authenticity influences commitment and engagement. Additionally, Nair *et al.* (2014) and Naidoo (2014) offer valuable methodological insights by analysing historical perspectives on women's leadership, linking past contributions to current debates on gender and leadership.

When comparing charismatic and authentic leadership, clear differences become evident. Charismatic leadership, as explained by Bass and Avolio (1994), focuses on a leader's ability to inspire, influence, and motivate through charm and a persuasive vision. Such leaders display confidence, articulate a compelling mission, and energise followers (Conger and Kanungo, 1987; House, 1977). In contrast, authentic leadership is based on self-awareness, consistency, and relational transparency (Avolio and Gardner, 2005). Instead of depending on personal magnetism, authentic leaders establish trust through honesty and openness (Gardner *et al.*, 2005). They encourage moral reasoning and foster positive organisational environments that enhance employee engagement (Luthans and Avolio, 2003). Charismatic leadership is often criticised for its limited attention to leader character, potentially leading to integrity issues. Authentic leadership, however, embraces both strengths and vulnerabilities (George, 2003), representing a more holistic leadership model.

Although both leadership traits impact followers through vision, values, and emotional bonds, key differences explain why authentic leadership is preferred in this study. While charisma is often temporary and focused on the leader's personality, authentic leadership builds lasting relationships based on integrity. Authentic leaders emphasise ethical decision-making and ongoing personal development, whereas charismatic leaders may focus more on organisational results and persuasive influence.

The implications of both traits are evident. Charismatic leadership can inspire organisational culture through enthusiasm, but authentic leadership fosters a culture grounded in trust and

openness. Research indicates that authentic leadership fosters higher levels of employee engagement and long-term commitment, as opposed to the short-term motivation often associated with charismatic leadership. While integrating elements of both may benefit organisations, this study, based on an extensive literature review, positions authentic leadership as the most suitable theoretical lens.

2.7.3 Gender

“We need to abandon Plato’s question: who should rule us? And focus on Popper’s question ‘how can we stop our rulers ruining us’”-Grint (2005, p.40)

In the world of the mind, today’s employees are constructive dissenters who live in an era of work where they believe leaders are not omniscient beings. This beckons for diversity in leadership. This section focuses on scholarly studies of gender within leadership.

Table:16 Gender

Authors	Article Title
Aaltio and Mills (2002)	Organisational culture and gendered identities in context’. In Gender, identity, and the culture of organisations
Barnes (2017)	Climbing the Stairs to Leadership: Reflections on Moving Beyond the Stained-Glass Ceiling
Busch (2020)	Gender Segregation, Occupational Sorting, and Growth of Wage Disparities Between Women
Clar <i>et al.</i> (2021)	Unconscious bias in organisations: Discriminatory forces at work

Cho <i>et al.</i> (2015)	A woman CEO? You'd better think twice! Exploring career challenges of women CEOs at multinational corporations in South Korea
Domen (2022)	It's a man's world; right? How women's opinions about gender inequality affect physiological responses in men
Eagley (2005)	Achieving relational authenticity in leadership: Does gender matter
Fujimoto and Uddin (2022)	Inclusive Leadership for Reduced Inequality
Francoeur <i>et al.</i> (2008)	Gender Diversity in Corporate Governance and Top Management
Grint (2005)	Leadership: Limits and possibilities
Hogue and Lord (2007)	A multilevel, complexity theory approach to understanding gender bias in leadership
Johns, Inzlicht and Schmader (2008)	Stereotype Threat and Executive Resource Depletion: Examining the Influence of Emotion Regulation
Lafuente and Vaillant (2019)	Balance rather than critical mass or tokenism: Gender diversity, leadership and performance in financial firms
Laskar <i>et al.</i> (2024)	Impact of gender diversity on firm performance: empirical evidence from India
McCormick <i>et al.</i> (2020)	Unconscious Bias Interventions for Business: An Initial Test of WAGES-Business

Miola <i>et al.</i> (2023)	Orientation behaviour in men and women: The relationship between gender stereotype, growth mindset, and spatial self-efficacy
Noon (2018)	Pointless Diversity Training: Unconscious Bias, New Racism and Agency
Pennington <i>et al</i> (2023)	A mixed-methods evaluation of unconscious racial bias training for NHS senior practitioners to improve the experiences of racially minoritized students
Smit, Schultz and van (2021)	The relationship between talent management, transformational leadership and work engagement: An automotive artisan perspective'
Seibel (2022)	Shards of the Glass Ceiling
Vo <i>et al.</i> (2013)	Does female leadership matter in firm risk-taking and performance? Evidence from gender equality reforms in an emerging market
Williamson and Foley (2018)	Unconscious bias training: The 'Silver Bullet' for gender equity
Winston (2001)	The Importance of Leadership Diversity: The Relationship between Diversity and Organisational Success in the Academic Environment
Young <i>et al.</i> (2007)	Gender enactment at work: The importance of gender and gender-related behaviour to person-organisational fit and career decisions

Table 16 summarises gender-focused literature identified in the systematic literature review. It highlights key themes, benefits, and challenges associated with gender within leadership and organisational contexts. This table supports the study's gendered analysis by synthesising existing evidence and identifying gaps relevant to women's leadership in male-dominated industries.

As shown in Table 16, much of the existing literature on gender and leadership focuses on issues such as representation, gendered traits, and barriers to advancement. While these studies have made significant contributions to understanding women's leadership experiences, the table also reveals a tendency to treat leadership effectiveness and gender as separate analytical concerns. Limited attention has been paid to how women leaders actively construct leadership identities, enact authenticity, or navigate sponsorship relationships within male-dominated industrial contexts. These patterns highlight important gaps in the literature, which inform the focus and research questions of the present study.

2.7.3.1 Benefits

The literature highlights numerous benefits linked to gendered leadership. Winston (2001) examines how leadership diversity within academic institutions impacts organisational success, arguing that diverse leadership enhances decision-making by bringing a broader range of perspectives. This view is supported by Francoeur *et al.* (2008), who offer quantitative evidence of the positive effects of gender diversity in strategic decision-making roles, especially in fostering innovation and creativity. Lafuente and Vaillant (2019) contribute to this discussion by focusing on the financial sector, suggesting that balanced gender representation in leadership has a positive impact on firm performance. Collectively, these studies underline that diversity in leadership is crucial to organisational success, boosting innovation, creativity, and strategic decision-making.

A recurring theme across the literature is the strong intersectionality between gender theorisation and leadership studies. The context of gender, often deeply embedded in discussions within gender studies, appears to be underexplored or marginalised in traditional leadership literature. These insights suggest that organisations must move beyond tokenistic inclusion and instead strive for genuinely balanced representation in leadership positions. Further reinforcing the advantages of women-centric leadership, Laskar *et al.* (2024) present empirical evidence from India, examining how gender diversity influences firm performance. Their study highlights the significant impact of gender-balanced leadership on key performance metrics within the Indian context, strengthening the case for inclusive and diverse leadership structures.

2.7.3.2. Challenges

While the literature clearly demonstrates the organisational advantages of gender-diverse leadership, it also highlights ongoing challenges that hinder women's advancement. Miola *et al.* (2023) explore the impact of gender stereotypes on self-efficacy and performance, aligning with the findings of Johns *et al.* (2008), who show that exposure to stereotypical behaviour can deplete cognitive resources and negatively affect emotional well-being. A key factor influencing women leaders is the organisational culture in which they operate. As Aaltio and Mills (2002) argue, organisational culture can either challenge or reinforce traditional gender roles, significantly shaping women's leadership experiences.

Seibel (2022) sheds light on the tangible barriers women encounter at the top levels of leadership, metaphorically framed as the “shards of the glass ceiling”. In response to these barriers, Fujimoto and Uddin (2022) and Young *et al.* (2007) propose practical strategies, such as fostering inclusive leadership practices, to mitigate the impact of systemic obstacles. These studies vary in methodological approach Laskar *et al.* (2024), for instance, adopt an empirical

framework, whereas Aaltio and Mills (2002) engage in a more theoretical analysis. A further observation from the literature is its chronological breadth, with studies such as those by Seibel (2022) and Aaltio and Mills (2002) indicating gradual shifts in societal norms and organisational practices over time. However, questions remain regarding the generalisability of the findings, given the varying sample sizes, geographical contexts, and theoretical frameworks employed, which may not be universally applicable.

By addressing theoretical limitations, presenting empirical evidence, and considering ethical dimensions, the body of literature collectively underscores the need to advance gender equity in leadership. These scholarly contributions illuminate the complex interplay between context, gender, and leadership, underscoring their profound influence on organisational life.

2.7.4 Context & Intersectionality

Intersectionality offers a way of mediating the tension between assertions of multiple identities” -Crenshaw (2006)

This study employs the concept of intersectionality to describe the various ways in which gender, leadership, and authenticity intersect to shape the growth of women leaders within their organisations.

Table:17 Context & Intersectionality

Authors	Title of the Article
Athukorala and Veeramani (2019)	From Import Substitution to Integration into Global Production Networks: The Case of the Indian Automobile Industry
Avolio, Walumbwa and Weber (2009)	Leadership: Current theories, research, and future directions

Becker (2006)	High noon in the automotive industry
Boothem (2021)	Women power drives the automobiles industry
Bowleg (2008)	The methodological challenges of qualitative and quantitative intersectionality
Cyr <i>et al.</i> (2021)	Mapping social exclusion in STEM to men's implicit bias and women's career costs
Colmaire (2022)	Women's Leadership Alliance: An Informal Co-Mentoring Network and its Potential Impact on Second-Generation Gender Bias in Independent School Leadership
Crenshaw (1989)	Demarginalizing the intersection of race and sex
Crenshaw (2006)	Intersectionality, identity politics and violence against women of colour
Foley <i>et al.</i> (2022)	I'll never be one of the boys': Gender harassment of women working as pilots and automotive tradespeople
Gupta and Roy (2023)	What really empowers women? Taking another look at economic empowerment
Iacocca and novak (1985)	Iacocca an autobiography
Kaur and Kaur (2016)	Determinants of Profitability of Automobile Industry in India

Kulkarni <i>et al.</i> (2023)	A study on barriers to women's leadership in India
Kramer and Konrad (2006)	Erasing the gender gap: A critical review of the impact of gender-based preferences on women's progress
Mythili (2019)	Quest for Success: Ladder of School Leadership of Women in India
Mor Barak <i>et al.</i> (2016)	The impact of supervision on worker outcomes
Pillay and Vermeulen (2023)	Seeking support through solidarity: female leader's experiences of workplace solidarity in male-dominated professions
Pons and Ramos (2016)	Antecedent variables of innovation behaviours in organisations: Differences between men and women
Rastogi <i>et al.</i> (2022)	What does it take to be a woman entrepreneur? Explorations from India
Sarkar (2022)	Factors associated with general self-efficacy of women leaders in India
Vasavada (2012)	A cultural feminist perspective on leadership in nonprofit organisations: a case of women leaders in India
Werhane and painter (2011)	Leadership, gender, and organisation
Yu <i>et al.</i> (2022)	Circular economy practices and industry 4.0 technologies: A strategic move of automobile industry

Table 17 summarises literature relating to context and intersectionality. It highlights how factors such as culture, industry, and social structures intersect with gender and leadership. This table supports the study's intersectional approach by demonstrating the importance of contextual influences in shaping leadership experiences.

As highlighted by Avolio, Walumbwa and Weber (2009), context is critical to understanding leadership, particularly in analysing behavioural adaptation, effectiveness, varied perceptions, and navigating complexities and uncertainties. Without considering context, the study of leadership remains incomplete. In parallel, the concept of intersectionality, introduced by Crenshaw (1989), is indispensable, especially within gender-focused studies. Intersectionality elucidates how various forms of oppression, such as bias, stereotypical behaviour, and gendered expectations, interact and compound to create structural disadvantages for marginalised groups (Mor Barak *et al.*, 2016). Bowleg (2008) further asserts that intersectionality enhances education and awareness around the complexity of social identities, contributing to a more nuanced understanding of systemic inequalities.

Recognising the critical role of both context and intersectionality, this literature review aims to connect the study of authentic leadership with the Indian automobile industry. Yu *et al.* (2022) examine the evolution of the global automobile sector through the lens of the circular economy and Industry 4.0, highlighting synergies between sustainability practices and technological advancements. However, their focus on developed markets may overlook the unique constraints faced by emerging economies. Becker (2006) provides a historical analysis of the automobile industry, detailing the pressures of globalisation and technological innovation; however, the study does not address more recent developments, such as Industry 4.0. In contrast, Pons and Ramos (2016) explore gender dynamics within innovation ecosystems, complementing Foley *et al.* (2022) by offering broader organisational insights into gender-

related issues. Nonetheless, limitations in sample size reduce the generalisability of their findings.

In the Indian context, Athukorala and Veeramani (2019) provide a comprehensive historical analysis of the development of the Indian automobile industry, a perspective further enhanced by Yu *et al.* (2022) through their case study in an emerging market. Kaur and Kaur (2016) investigate profitability determinants within the Indian automobile sector, although their analysis is restricted to financial metrics, neglecting human capital and leadership factors. The autobiography of Lee Iacocca (1985) offers personal and historical insights into the industry from a prominent CEO's point of view; however, it may contain subjective biases and lacks academic rigour.

Foley *et al.* (2022) highlight the gender-based harassment that women may face in male-dominated sectors, such as the automobile industry, a theme echoed in the broader gender discourse of Pons and Ramos (2016). Sarkar (2022) investigates factors influencing women leaders' self-efficacy in India, offering rich insight into their leadership journeys. This work complements earlier contributions by Vasavada (2012), who adopts a cultural feminist lens to examine women's leadership in the Indian non-profit sector, and Rastogi *et al.* (2022), who explore the structural challenges faced by women leaders. Boothem (2021) provides practical examples to complement theoretical debates on gender and industry, while Gupta and Roy (2023) focus on economic empowerment for women, although their work is not sector-specific. Kulkarni *et al.* (2023) build on Sarkar (2022) and Rastogi *et al.* (2022), offering a comprehensive perspective on the challenges and opportunities for women in leadership roles in India.

Collectively, these studies provide a multidimensional understanding of the Indian automobile industry, incorporating themes of gender, leadership, and organisational change. However, the

literature tends to prioritise extrinsic challenges, such as organisational barriers and systemic bias, while under-examining the intrinsic factors that may act as catalysts for women's leadership development. This gap underscores the need for further exploration of internal dimensions, including personal values, authentic identity, and self-driven leadership development, particularly in the context of authentic leadership.

2.7.5 Gaps from the literature review and link to research questions: The critical review of the literature has identified several interrelated gaps that highlight limitations in existing scholarship on gender and leadership and provide the foundation for the present study. Each gap is explicitly linked to the relevant research question to demonstrate conceptual clarity and alignment between the literature review and the research design.

Gap 1: Limited empirical research on women's leadership experiences in male-dominated manufacturing sectors, particularly within the Indian context

This gap directly informs Research Question 1, which examines how women leaders experience, navigate, and sustain leadership effectiveness within India's automobile manufacturing industry. Existing scholarship on women's leadership has largely concentrated on service-oriented sectors such as education, healthcare, and finance, with significantly less attention given to capital-intensive and male-dominated manufacturing industries (Gininka, 2025). Within the Indian context, empirical research exploring women's lived leadership experiences in the automobile manufacturing sector remains particularly limited (Bharathkumar *et al.*, 2023; Singh *et al.*, 2021). As a result, current leadership literature offers an incomplete understanding of how women construct leadership legitimacy, negotiate authority, and navigate organisational cultures characterised by entrenched masculine norms and structural gender imbalances.

By addressing this empirical gap, Research Question 1 responds directly to the absence of context-specific insights and contributes to leadership and gender scholarship by foregrounding women's lived experiences within a traditionally masculinised industrial environment.

Gap 2: Insufficient exploration of authentic leadership as a lived and enacted experience for women leaders

This gap directly informs Research Question 2, which examines how women leaders conceptualise, interpret, and enact authentic leadership within their organisational contexts. Although authentic leadership has received considerable scholarly attention, much of the existing research has conceptualised and operationalised the construct through quantitative measures and psychometric instruments such as the Authentic Leadership Questionnaire (ALQ) and related scales (Walumbwa *et al.*, 2008; Avolio and Gardner, 2005). While these approaches have contributed to the theoretical development of authentic leadership, they tend to portray authenticity as a relatively stable and individualised trait. Consequently, limited attention has been paid to how authentic leadership is lived, negotiated, and enacted by women leaders within specific organisational, cultural, and gendered contexts.

Furthermore, existing literature has been criticised for insufficiently examining the gendered and contextual dimensions of authentic leadership, particularly how women leaders navigate authenticity in environments shaped by masculine leadership norms and role expectations (Gardiner, 2015; Sinclair, 2007). Studies that do engage with authenticity often overlook how women adapt, resist, or reframe authentic leadership practices in response to organisational power structures and social expectations (Eagly and Carli, 2007; Ford, 2010).

By addressing this gap, Research Question 2 responds directly to the lack of qualitative, interpretive research that captures women leaders' lived experiences of authentic leadership. This study contributes to leadership scholarship by advancing an understanding of authenticity

as a dynamic, contextually situated, and gendered leadership process rather than a fixed individual attribute.

Gap 3: Under-examination of sponsorship in relation to women's leadership development and progression.

This gap directly informs Research Question 3, which examines how sponsorship shapes women leaders' career progression and leadership experiences, particularly within male-dominated organisational contexts. While mentoring has received substantial scholarly attention within leadership and career development literature, sponsorship remains comparatively under-explored, despite its recognised importance in facilitating career advancement and access to organisational power (Ibarra, Carter and Silva, 2010; Hewlett, 2013). Existing studies indicate that mentoring relationships often focus on psychosocial support and skill development, whereas sponsorship involves the active use of organisational influence, advocacy, and reputational risk on behalf of protégés (Kram, 1985; Levin *et al.*, 2021). However, research examining sponsorship in relation to women's leadership progression, particularly within male-dominated industries such as manufacturing, remains limited.

Moreover, the interaction between sponsorship, leadership identity, and authenticity is especially under-theorised. Current literature seldom examines how women leaders' authentic leadership practices influence their access to sponsors or how sponsorship relationships are shaped by gendered power dynamics and organisational cultures (Ibarra *et al.*, 2010; Sealy and Singh, 2010). As a result, there is limited understanding of how women leaders navigate informal sponsorship pathways, how credibility and legitimacy are constructed, and how authenticity intersects with sponsorship in shaping leadership trajectories.

By addressing this gap, Research Question 3 responds directly to the absence of integrative and context-sensitive research on sponsorship. This study contributes to leadership and gender scholarship by examining sponsorship as a relational and power-mediated process that interacts with authenticity and leadership identity, thereby advancing understanding of women's leadership development within India's automobile manufacturing sector.

Narrative and systematic literature reviews have demonstrated that the intersection of authentic leadership and gender in leadership is an emerging area of scholarly interest. While the academic discourse in this field is still developing, there is a consensus on the importance of expanding research in this direction (Gardiner, 2015; Ely *et al.*, 2011; Le *et al.*, 2021). However, the current body of literature reveals that authentic leadership, when analysed in conjunction with gender dynamics and leadership within the automobile industry, particularly in the Indian context, has received limited to no focused academic attention. This notable absence highlights a significant gap in the existing literature (Foley *et al.*, 2022; Sarkar, 2022; Kulkarni *et al.*, 2023).

The dimensions of this gap are multifaceted. Firstly, while there is growing exploration of authentic leadership as a construct (Avolio and Gardner, 2005; George, 2003), few studies have examined how gender influences the enactment and perception of authentic leadership. Secondly, although gender and leadership studies have gained prominence in recent years, particularly in relation to inclusion and equity (Crenshaw, 1989; Bowleg, 2008; Mor Barak *et al.*, 2016), research focusing on women in leadership within industrial sectors, such as the automobile manufacturing industry, remains sparse. Finally, the specific contextual challenges and opportunities present in emerging markets, such as India, where gender norms, organisational culture, and industrial dynamics differ substantially from those in Western

contexts, have not been adequately addressed (Athukorala and Veeramani, 2019; Vasavada, 2012; Rastogi *et al.*, 2022).

Therefore, the intersection of authentic leadership, gender, and industry-specific context, particularly within India's automobile sector, presents a critical and under-researched area with significant potential for theoretical advancement and practical implications.

2.7.5.1 Evidence-based gaps

Despite the extensive body of research on leadership, several critical gaps remain. One notable omission is the limited exploration of leadership in relation to cultural variability and gendered contexts. As highlighted by Sinclair (2007), leadership necessitates thinking from diverse perspectives; yet these dimensions have not been sufficiently investigated. In particular, there is a distinct lack of research examining leadership within the Indian automobile industry, with much of the literature on women in leadership being rooted in Western contexts. This geographical skew raises important questions about the cross-cultural applicability and generalisability of existing findings (Foley *et al.*, 2022; Sarkar, 2022).

Secondly, inconsistencies persist in the definitional frameworks surrounding leadership. While some definitions emphasise inherent qualities and personal traits (Bass and Avolio, 1994), others focus on observable actions and behaviours (Conger and Kanungo, 1987). However, few, if any, definitions integrate these behavioural characteristics with measurable outcomes, resulting in a conceptual disconnect between leadership practices and their organisational impact (Avolio and Gardner, 2005).

Thirdly, traditional leadership studies tend to be dominated by abstract theorising with limited empirical grounding in specific organisational or industrial contexts. This represents a significant limitation, as leadership cannot be effectively understood or practised in isolation from its context. Without a contextual lens, whether cultural, industrial or geographical,

leadership traits and styles risk being irrelevant or inapplicable to real-world organisational dynamics (Avolio, Walumbwa and Weber, 2009; Crenshaw, 1989).

A fourth gap in the literature concerns the lived experiences and challenges faced by women in leadership positions. These experiences are often influenced by intersecting factors such as cultural norms, industry practices, and broader societal expectations, yet they remain insufficiently explored. Addressing this gap is vital for advancing gender equality in leadership. Without a detailed understanding of these gendered realities, leadership theories risk reinforcing systemic inequalities (Aaltio and Mills, 2002; Seibel, 2022; Fujimoto and Uddin, 2022).

Finally, although gendered leadership has received growing scholarly attention, significant gaps persist in areas such as sponsorship and the intersectionality of gender and leadership. As Ladkin and Taylor (2010) contend, leadership studies have traditionally focused on defining the traits of effective leaders, often overlooking how these leaders are perceived within the communities and cultural environments in which they operate. This underscores the need for more holistic, intersectional approaches that examine not only what leaders do, but how their leadership is interpreted and shaped by contextual dynamics (Bowleg, 2008; Mor Barak *et al.*, 2016).

Collectively, these identified gaps underscore the need to shift leadership research toward contextually rich, intersectionally informed frameworks that transcend generic constructs to reflect the complex realities of leadership in practice.

2.7.5.2 Theory-based gaps

Both Blackmore (2009) and Winkler (2010) offer critical insights into the empirical limitations of mainstream leadership theories. Blackmore (2009) argues that traditional leadership theories often fail to account for the rapidly changing organisational environment, rendering them

outdated and less effective in dynamic contexts. Similarly, Winkler (2010) critiques the empirical grounding of contemporary leadership theories, highlighting the persistent difficulty in linking specific behavioural traits to effective leadership outcomes. This indicates a significant gap between theoretical constructs and real-world leadership practices.

Theories such as transactional and transformational leadership, though influential, often present dichotomous frameworks that lack practical balance and integration in actual leadership scenarios. These models are criticised for their limited contextual adaptability, absence of inclusive frameworks, and insufficient empirical validation many have not been robustly tested or grounded in diverse, real-world settings (Sinclair, 2007). Sinclair (2007) further contends that leadership theories often impose rigid, oversimplified binaries, neglecting the need for nuanced and integrated approaches. Moreover, many of these theories lack cross-cultural applicability, limiting their practical relevance across different industries and societal contexts.

Charismatic leadership, while effective in the short term, has been critiqued for its inability to maintain sustained influence over time a critical shortcoming when considering the long-term needs of leadership (Winkler, 2010). On the other hand, authentic leadership, despite its potential for sustained impact, remains under-supported by empirical evidence, particularly regarding its long-term effectiveness in diverse cultural and organisational contexts (Avolio and Gardner, 2005).

Critics also note that authenticity in leadership is often treated as an isolated personal attribute, without sufficient attention to its interplay with cultural, gendered, and contextual factors. Chan (2005) proposes that authenticity should be viewed not as a standalone trait but as a leadership multiplier a dynamic quality that enhances the effectiveness of other leadership characteristics when appropriately developed. This reframing, positions authenticity as a complementary skill that strengthens broader leadership practices.

Irby (2002) raises a compelling critique regarding the persistent underrepresentation of feminine perspectives within leadership literature. She argues that leadership theory and practice have historically been shaped by male-centric paradigms, marginalising the contributions and experiences of women leaders. Addressing this gap is crucial for developing a more comprehensive and inclusive understanding of leadership. By incorporating feminine perspectives, future research can enrich the conceptualisation and application of authentic leadership, making it more relevant and impactful in diverse organisational contexts.

2.7.6. Chapter Summary

While existing literature highlights the importance of studying the various contexts of authentic leadership (Sinclair, 2013), this study will expand on these findings by exploring the intersection of authentic leadership with culture and gender. Based on the gaps identified in both the narrative and systematic literature reviews, this research will address questions about how authentic leadership can support the development of women within the automobile industry in India. Specifically, it will examine how authentic behaviours appear in women leaders' interactions and influence colleagues to foster their progression into leadership roles, thereby helping to challenge gender dichotomies. By incorporating the feminine voice, this research directly responds to the gap noted in the literature. The Indian automobile industry, as a context, has yet to be examined through authentic leadership, making this study a significant contribution to the field.

The review of existing literature emphasises the importance of developing a clear definition of authentic leadership, thereby providing a common framework for interpretation and discussion. This definition will build on current conceptualisations of authentic leadership, incorporating key traits identified in the literature (Avolio and Gardner, 2005; Walumbwa *et al.*, 2008) to ensure a consistent understanding of the term within the scope of this study.

Table 18: Working Definition analysis

Definition	Concept
The pattern of leader behaviour that draws upon and promotes both positive psychological capacities and a positive ethical climate, to foster greater self-awareness, an internalized moral perspective, balanced processing of information, and relational transparency on the part of leaders working with followers, fostering positive self-development – (Walumbwa <i>et al.</i> 2008)	-Positive -Self awareness
We need leaders who lead with purpose, values, integrity, leaders who build encouraging organisations, motivate their employees to provide superior customer service and create long term value for shareholders. (George, 2003, p. 9)	-Purpose -Values -Integrity -Motivate
Owning one’ own personal experiences, thoughts, emotions, needs, preferences, beliefs, processes captured by the injunction to ‘know oneself’ and ‘further implies that one acts in accord with the true self, expressing oneself in ways that are consistent with inner thoughts and feelings’ (Harter, 2002, p. 82)	-Self awareness -Beliefs -Consistent
The unobstructed operation of one’s true, or core self in one’s daily enterprise (Kernis, 2003, p. 13)	-Self -True

Table 18 presents a comparison of working definitions used across the literature.

It highlights similarities and differences in how key constructs are defined, supporting

conceptual alignment and clarity. This table informs the development of the study's working definitions by justifying the definitions adopted for the research.

Based on the above analysis on the various definitions coined by various authors, the working definition that would be used as a practical tool for this study has been provided below.

2.7.6.1 Working definition:

“Authentic leadership incorporates an internalisation of a leader's personal credibility enhanced through integrity, to foster social virtues through expressions of a distinctive vision, a sense of passion driven by purpose and care for followers”

As mentioned in previous sections, much of the academic research on leadership and authentic leadership has created an impression of 'genderless' leaders, rarely discussing how a leader's gender influences leadership (Braun, Peus and Frey, 2018). The next chapter outlines the methodology, which aims to demonstrate the skills and traits that have contributed to the development of current leaders within the automobile industry. This will be achieved through interviews with current women leaders in the industry, aiming to understand how gender has affected their leadership experiences and contributed to the growth of future women leaders. Fisher (2010) encourages women researchers to critique phenomenological traditions. This methodology addresses that call by examining the intersectionality of gender, leadership, and authenticity, and how these factors work together to influence sponsorship for women.

CHAPTER THREE: RESEARCH METHODOLOGY

3.1 Introduction

This chapter outlines the methodology that will be employed in this research study. Before discussing the methodology, it is essential to understand the concept of research. Creswell and Creswell (2018) define research as a systematic process of collecting, analysing, and interpreting data to understand a phenomenon and answer specific questions. The authors emphasise that research involves a series of steps, including identifying a problem or question, reviewing literature, designing a study, collecting data, analysing results, and drawing conclusions. Kumar (2019); Abutabenjeh and Jaradat (2018) highlight that research is a step-by-step process that includes identifying research problems, reviewing existing literature, formulating a research question, designing, collecting, analysing, and interpreting the results. From scholars, it can be summed up that research involves sifting through literature to generate knowledge. A methodology, therefore, is a critical component in the research process that enhances credibility (Yin, 2017); it establishes the vigour and validity of the study by providing a clear roadmap for data collection and analysis (Creswell and Creswell, 2018), ensuring transparency of information, and supporting other researchers in evaluating the reliability of the findings (Shadish, Cook and Campbell, 2002).

According to Frater *et al.* (2008), research is a process of structuring and presenting valid data. The interpretation of data largely depends on the researcher's knowledge of theory and literature in the field of study, which includes their experience and perspective. Hübner (2024, p. 2) states that "method in research is designing, thinking, planning, and carrying out while experiencing the process and finding a balance". While Reddy (2021) describes research methodology as a knowledge discovery, Jegede *et al.* (2020, p. 69) define research as a "concept that relates how we obtain the information we need to be able to construct a reality

around research”. Hübner (2024) emphasises the importance of the procedural nature of research and reinstates its reflective nature, suggesting that it’s not all about following a process but about refining the approach. Reddy (2021) defines research as a process of knowledge discovery, positioning it as the fundamental process and defining the essence of research as its ability to generate new ideas. Jegede *et al.* (2020) offer a conceptual perspective on defining research as a concept, suggesting that research is not just about collecting data but also about constructing a meaningful interpretation of the data. In summary, these perspectives highlight the multifaceted nature of research, encompassing both the procedural and outcome-oriented dimensions. From the study of literature, it can be summarised that applying the correct methodology to the study is essential to ensure the reliability of the results and, in turn, to uphold the rationality of the study.

3.2 Process to Accomplish

A qualitative, interpretive phenomenological approach was chosen as the methodology, as it aligns with the purpose of this research. With the intention of answering the research question, the study aims to collect and analyse data to understand the core benefits of authentic leadership in empowering women leaders. Scrutinising the literature helped to understand the current position of leadership and women in leadership, particularly through the lens of authentic leadership, within the automobile industry in the context of India. The analysis of the fact that women remain in lower management positions due to a lack of mentoring opportunities (Thompson, 2023) and the assumption that the glass ceiling has been shattered was made possible through analysing data (Barreto and Michael, 2009). As long as such stereotypes persist, women will continue to be underrepresented in leadership (LaReau, 2013; Mainali *et al.*, 2025; Chlouba, 2025; Kantorowicz-Reznichenko *et al.*, 2025; Mushtaq *et al.*, 2025; Mor Barak *et al.*, 2025). Although women have access to education and opportunities presented

through various government quotas and women-friendly policies created by industry, many opportunities seem to be missed at various levels within their career paths (Sujatha, 2008).

As argued by Rodrigues (2023), women tend to encounter glass ceilings, whereas men tend to ascend the glass escalator to leadership positions. Vinnicombe (2013) has emphatically stated that data proves companies with women in top managerial positions have been more lucrative. The fact that this analysis reflects the extent of the issue, considering these observed extrinsic outcomes such as education, opportunities provided by government, organisational policies, and upskilling of resources, suggests that exploring intrinsic factors, such as the development of authentic leadership traits among women leaders and focusing on leveraging colleagues as catalysts for their development, warrants further attention.

According to Maher (2018, p. 170), “qualitative research has advantages in terms of gaining access to and information from hidden populations”. This qualitative study involves gathering data through in-depth interviews, focus group discussions, and case studies to address what, why, and how of this research. The study would include women from managerial positions (manager and above) within the passenger car original equipment manufacturers (OEMs) across India. A sample size of five participants for the in-depth interviews, as mentioned by Higginbottom (2004, p. 12), is appropriate: “the type of methodological approach is often associated with small sample sizes because of the in-depth nature of the interview”. Research has proven that women are “highly qualified but nevertheless remain underrepresented in leadership posts” (Ernst, 2003, p. 2). This phenomenon of underrepresentation of women in leadership positions has led scholars to investigate various barriers, such as the glass ceiling (Mun and Jung, 2018), as well as external causes, including life commitments, contributing to the underrepresentation of women. Despite scholarly studies that have contributed to the

development of policies by government and organisations, gender disparity in the automobile industry has persisted.

Savela (2018) argues that qualitative research enables the in-depth exploration of complex phenomena, capturing the context and nuances that are crucial for understanding the subject. Whereas quantitative research generalises findings by reaching out to a large population, it results in the sacrifice of depth for breadth. Succinctly captured by House (2018), qualitative research aims to understand the interpretations of experiences, whereas quantitative research focuses on testing hypotheses, leading to the identification of patterns. These are some disadvantages of using quantitative research, as illustrated by Lundy (1996). Quantitative research is primarily focused on numerical data, which can obscure human experiences; complex social issues cannot be easily moulded into numerical values. For example, 50% of women leaders may state that they grew into leadership positions within the organisation; however, the study may fail to capture the factors that enabled these women to grow into leadership positions. Finally, quantitative research relies on statistical tests, meaning that data can be skewed if questions are formatted incorrectly (Chudleigh and Smith, 2015).

Mixed-method studies, on the other hand, as per McKim (2017, p. 1), “require time due to the need for the collection and analysis of two different types of data, requiring additional funding, a large population to interview, and knowledge from the researcher in both quantitative and qualitative studies”. One of the other limitations of mixed methods, apart from the time and cost aspects, is highlighted by Molina (2012, p. 34), who states, “we do not know if it really has a great impact”. Finally, mixed methods require in-depth methodological knowledge, as expressed by Mariani and Baggio (2020), and Fetters (2013) states, “despite the recognised benefits of data integration, the extent to which mixed-method studies implement integration remains limited”.

The grounded theory method, although it has advantages, has a main limitation, as shown by Cooke (2014, p. 20): “the researcher and participants need to be similar in beliefs, which runs counter to the openness of research questions and the search for truth to answer the research questions”. Therefore, the grounded theory method was not chosen, and a qualitative study was selected, as emphasised by Vass (2017, p. 299): “the key strength of qualitative research is being able to collate important contextual data”. This study will use in-depth interviews with open-ended questions to gather data from participants.

3.3 Methodological Justification: This study seeks to explore how women leaders in India’s automobile manufacturing industry experience and enact leadership, with particular emphasis on authenticity, gendered expectations, and sponsorship within a male-dominated organisational context. Addressing such objectives requires an approach capable of capturing subjective meaning, lived experience, and contextual interpretation, rather than measuring predefined variables. Consequently, a qualitative research design was adopted.

The study is situated within an interpretivist research philosophy, which recognises that social reality is socially constructed and understood through individuals’ interpretations of their lived experiences (Saunders *et al.*, 2019). Leadership and authenticity are not universal or static phenomena; rather, they are shaped by organisational cultures, power relations, and identity negotiations. An interpretivist stance therefore enables a deeper understanding of how women leaders make sense of their leadership roles within the specific socio-cultural and industrial context of the Indian automotive sector.

Within this philosophical orientation, the study draws on a phenomenological approach, which is concerned with exploring how individuals experience and ascribe meaning to phenomena as they are lived (Husserl, 1970; Heidegger, 1962). Phenomenology is particularly appropriate for

examining complex social phenomena such as leadership, where meaning emerges through reflection, interaction, and context rather than objective measurement.

This study is informed specifically by Interpretative Phenomenological Analysis (IPA), which combines phenomenological inquiry with an interpretivist and idiographic commitment to understanding participants' meaning-making processes (Smith, Flowers and Larkin, 2009). IPA was selected because it acknowledges the active interpretative role of the researcher and supports nuanced analysis of leadership experiences that are deeply personal, relational, and contextually embedded (Finlay, 2011).

Although IPA is typically associated with smaller samples, its idiographic principles were applied flexibly to a broader qualitative dataset in this study. This approach allowed for both detailed engagement with individual accounts and the identification of shared patterns across leadership experiences, aligning with the study's aim of generating analytical rather than statistical generalisation (Smith *et al.*, 2009; van Manen, 2014).

Semi-structured interviews were employed as the primary data collection method, as they provide sufficient structure to address the research questions while allowing participants to articulate their experiences in their own terms. This was particularly important given the subjective and evolving nature of authentic leadership. To enhance methodological rigour, focus group discussions were incorporated as a supplementary method, enabling exploration of collective sense-making and organisational perspectives, and supporting triangulation across data sources.

The study addresses qualitative quality criteria through transparency of design, systematic analysis, reflexive engagement, and clear documentation of analytic decisions. Emphasis is placed on credibility, dependability, and analytical coherence, consistent with established qualitative research standards (Lincoln and Guba, 1985).

Overall, the qualitative, interpretivist, phenomenologically informed approach adopted in this study is methodologically appropriate and well aligned with the research aims. It enables a rich, context-sensitive exploration of women's leadership experiences and contributes meaningful insights to the literature on gender, leadership, and authenticity.

3.4 Research Frameworks

In this regard, various frameworks have been proposed by researchers to aid in determining a methodology.

3.4.1 Creswell's Research Design

Creswell's framework combines quantitative, qualitative, and mixed methods for research, offering a comprehensive approach by integrating different methodologies. According to Creswell (2017), his framework incorporates philosophical worldviews and research methods to provide a detailed guide for designing research. The framework emphasises objective reality, using quantitative methods to test hypotheses, while also promoting understanding of the world from multiple perspectives through qualitative methods (Creswell and Creswell, 2017). This framework centres on practical solutions to the research problem, enabling the use of mixed methods to effectively address research questions (Creswell, 2014).

3.4.2 Kuhn's structure of scientific revolutions

Kuhn's (1962) work introduced the concept of a paradigm shift, which has significantly influenced our understanding of scientific progress and change. The characteristics of the framework include normal science, which involves theorising, observing, and experimenting within the limits of a dominant paradigm, and is characterised by puzzle-solving (Kuhn, 1970). A paradigm is a comprehensive model of understanding that determines how to approach and solve problems, guiding scientists in their observation, interpretation, and understanding of data. A model crisis occurs when problems arise that cannot be explained by current paradigms

(Hoyningen, 1993). These anomalies challenge the existing framework. Scientific resolution leads to a change in scientific consensus by adopting a new paradigm. After a revolution, this paradigm becomes the new framework for future research until another crisis triggers a subsequent revolution (Rouse, 1996).

3.4.3 Trochim's Research Process

This framework can be likened to glue that holds the research together by championing a systematic approach to research, encompassing everything from problem definition to data analysis and interpretation, and providing a structured sequence of steps for researchers to follow (Trochim, 2006). The process is depicted in a linear pattern. Problem definition involves identifying the specific issues by understanding the context and developing research questions and objectives. Research design is the planning stage of the overall research process, encompassing methodologies, sampling strategies, and data collection methods, such as case studies, experiments, and surveys (Trochim, 2020). Measurement develops and refines the tools and techniques of data collection by choosing reliable and valid instruments such as surveys, tests, and questionnaires. Data collection involves gathering data based on the research design by implementing the data collection plan, the instruments, and recording observations or responses (Trochim and Donnelly, 2006). Data analysis involves processing and analysing the collected data to answer research questions, using statistical methods for quantitative data or coding and theming for qualitative data (Trochim and Hamilton, 2016). The conclusion is drawn by interpreting the results, drawing conclusions based on the data analysis, discussing the findings, comparing them to the research questions, and considering the implications. Reporting and dissemination involve sharing the research findings with relevant audiences by preparing research reports, academic papers, and presentations to communicate results and conclusions. Evaluation and reflection assess the research process and outcomes to identify

areas for improvement by examining the research design, implementation, and results (Neuman, 2014).

3.4.4 Burrell and Morgan's Sociological Paradigms

This framework, introduced by Burrell and Morgan (1979), provides an understanding of the various perspectives and approaches within sociological research. The framework has two dimensions: the nature of social science (objective versus subjective) and the nature of society (order versus conflict). These dimensions form a matrix comprising the functionalist, interpretive, radical humanist, and radical structuralist paradigms. The functionalist paradigm seeks to explain social phenomena through the lens of laws and relationships. It emphasises stability, integration, and the functioning of social systems. Methodologies used within this paradigm include surveys, experiments, and statistical analysis. The interpretive paradigm focuses on understanding the meaning and experiences of individuals, emphasising the social construction of reality and the subjective interpretation of social phenomena. Methods within this paradigm include ethnography, phenomenology, and qualitative interviews. The radical humanist paradigm is characterised by its aim to understand and critique the ways social structures oppress and constrain individuals, emphasising human potential and radical change. The radical structuralist paradigm concentrates on the structural conflicts and contradictions within society, highlighting the role of economic and political power. Typical methodologies associated with this paradigm include historical analysis and structural analysis (Burrell and Morgan, 1979).

3.4.5 Tashakkori and Teddlie's Pragmatic Approach to Mixed Methods

This approach advocates for a mixed-method strategy, emphasising the use of both qualitative and quantitative methods depending on the research question (Wagner, 2009). The authors adopt pragmatism as the philosophical basis, which in turn rejects the dichotomy between

quantitative and qualitative methods. It concentrates on the research question and the outcomes of the research, rather than conforming to a specific methodology. The pragmatic approach highlights solving real-world problems and generating actionable results (Tashakkori and Teddlie, 1998).

3.4.6 Lincoln and Guba's Naturalistic Inquiry

It is a qualitative paradigm that emphasises understanding phenomena within a natural setting. This approach dismisses the positive notions of objectivity and generalisability, instead prioritising the complexity and uniqueness of human experiences. The authors' work is fundamental to the field of qualitative research, offering a comprehensive framework for conducting rigorous qualitative studies. The principles underlying the theory highlight that reality is multiple, constructed, and holistic, and it is perceived differently by each individual. Knowledge is subjective and context-dependent. The research design remains flexible and adapts as the study progresses, allowing for adjustments based on the data collected. Data is gathered in the participants' natural environment to capture real-world context, with the researcher acting as the primary instrument for data collection. Methods include interviews, observations, and document analysis to obtain in-depth, holistic data. Data collection is inductive, meaning concepts, patterns, and categories emerge from the data (Lincoln and Guba, 1985).

3.5. The Research Onion

Saunders and Thornhill (2009) introduced a framework titled the research onion, comprising six main layers: research philosophy, research approach, research strategies, time horizons, data collection methods, and data analysis methods. The research onion is a well-established framework that helps researchers develop a structured approach to their research, providing a layered approach that addresses different aspects of research methodology (Healey and Perry,

2009). Prior to selecting a research framework for this study, a comparative analysis was conducted to ascertain the similarities and limitations across the various frameworks.

Figure 4: The Research Onion (Saunders *et al.* 2007)

Tab 19: Methodology framework comparison:

Framework	Structure	Flexibility	Applicability
Saunders Research Onion	Emphasis on structured layers and coherent research design	A step-by-step approach	Encourages consistency within the chosen philosophy. Provides an in-depth road map

			from philosophy to technique
Burrell and Morgan's paradigms	Provides clarity but less granular	It provides a broader theoretical framework	Allows researchers to shift paradigms as the research evolves
Creswell's Research Design	More focused on the final methods rather than the philosophical and strategic layers that lead up to them.	It is flexible but less comprehensive	Highly applicable in guiding especially novice researchers
Tashakkori and Teddlie's Pragmatic Approach to Mixed Methods	Highly focused on practical applications and less on philosophical foundation	Flexible, similar to the research onion but lack of guidance like the layers of the research onion	Highly practical but the research onion layers guide researchers in a better way
Lincoln and Guba's Naturalistic Inquiry	Less structured in comparison with the research onion	Highly flexible with qualitative but does not integrate quantitative methods seamlessly	Useful for qualitative studies aimed at understanding complex phenomena
Kuhn's structure of scientific revolutions	Emphasis on clinical progression through paradigms	Allows flexibility within a structured framework that	Applicable to understanding the historical and

		accommodates different research philosophies and strategies.	philosophical development of scientific disciplines.
Trochim's Research Process	Structures around a clear set of phases	Focuses on ensuring vigour and validity in the process	Provides flexibility in choosing the design based on the research question

Table 19 compares methodological frameworks relevant to the study. It highlights strengths and limitations of each approach. The comparison supports the selection of an interpretive phenomenological design. This ensures methodological coherence. Table 19 compares commonly used research design frameworks in order to justify the methodological structure adopted for this study. While several frameworks offer valuable guidance for qualitative research, Saunders et al.'s research onion was selected because it provides a comprehensive, layered, and transparent structure for linking research philosophy, methodological approach, research strategy, and data collection methods within a single coherent framework.

The research onion is particularly well suited to this study because the research design required explicit alignment across multiple methodological decisions, including an interpretivist philosophical stance, a qualitative approach, a phenomenological orientation, and the use of semi-structured interviews and focus group discussions. Unlike more linear or method-specific frameworks, the research onion enables each layer of the research design to be clearly articulated and justified in relation to the research questions, thereby supporting methodological coherence and transparency.

Furthermore, the research onion is widely adopted in doctoral-level management and organisational research, making it a recognisable and credible framework for academic scrutiny. Its layered structure facilitates a clear audit trail, allowing readers to trace how philosophical assumptions inform methodological choices and how those choices shape data collection and analysis. This is particularly important in qualitative leadership research, where methodological rigour is demonstrated through reflexivity, coherence, and transparency rather than statistical validation.

Alternative frameworks considered in Table 19, while valuable, were less suitable for the present study's aims. Some focus primarily on procedural stages of research or on specific methodological traditions, offering limited guidance on the integration of philosophy, approach, and method. In contrast, Saunders' research onion accommodates methodological flexibility while maintaining structural clarity, which was essential given the study's use of interpretivism, phenomenology, and multiple qualitative methods.

In summary, Saunders' research onion was selected not as a theoretical model, but as a methodological framework that supports clarity, consistency, and rigour in qualitative research design. Its use enables the study to demonstrate a logically structured and transparent methodological approach aligned with the research objectives and the complex, context-dependent nature of women's leadership experiences in the Indian automobile industry.

3.5.1 Justification of Choice

It could be summarised from the comparative studies of the various frameworks that the research onion provides a more comprehensive, flexible, and structured approach, as it is inclusive and versatile. Compared to the other methods, it provides a detailed roadmap, ensuring coherence and alignment between stages of the research process. The research onion meets the characteristics of research as defined earlier in the introduction of this chapter, such

as it should be a ‘systematic process’ and ‘a series of steps,’ which is provided through the research onion method, offering the researcher a step-by-step process by unwrapping each layer based on the research. The layers represent the stages that transform the research question into a project of planning, implementation, and monitoring (Ko and Abdulmajeed, 2022). While other methods provide valuable insights and frameworks, the research onion offers a holistic view. Based on an in-depth analysis of various frameworks, examining their structure, flexibility, and applicability, this study has selected the Saunders research onion as the ideal method for this study.

The methodology has been influenced by the study’s overall aim to examine the lived experiences of women in authentic leadership within the Indian automobile industry, with the goal of determining how leaders with authentic leadership skills can influence their colleagues/teams in sponsoring them into leadership positions. The methodology begins with an examination of the approach adopted for this research, as it influences the overall methodology. The study would then discuss the paradigm selected by this methodology, before proceeding to discuss the research philosophy. The study then details the account of the research process and the strategy. The methodology will examine the methods used in the study and how the data will be analysed. It will discuss the quality criteria and ethical implications that were considered. This would lead to a conclusion regarding the study undertaken.

3.5.2 Research Approach

There are three approaches: inductive, deductive, and abductive (Tracy, 2020). The reasoning behind these approaches is provided below.

Table 20: Different research approaches -A comparison

	Deductive	Inductive	Abductive

Inference	Based on widely accepted facts (Saunders <i>et al.</i> 2009)	Based on an observation or a sample (Saunders <i>et al.</i> 2009)	Abductive involves collecting data to understand a phenomenon, an explanation based on a body of beliefs (Aliseda, 2006)
Applicability	If starting facts are true it is believed that the outcome would be true in deductive reasoning, quantitative research uses this form of reasoning (Barroga <i>et al.</i> 2023)	Suited for Exploratory research where existing theories are developed	Abductive reasoning is employed in qualitative research to develop theories from observed phenomena (Meyer, 2016). As a result, its popularity used in science involving experiences.
Benefits	This approach provides a structural framework for research, enhancing the reliability of the study (Bryman, 2016)	Flexibility in patterns (Gottfredson and Aguinis, 2017)	aims to generate the best possible hypothesis, it's a top-down approach (Themelis, Sime, and Thornberg, 2023) which helps in

			further understanding of the phenomenon (Ossenberg, Henderson, and Mitchell, 2020).
Weakness	<p>The approach has been criticised to be too rigid to capture the full complexity of the phenomenon (Flick, 2022)</p> <p>It may not adequately address unexpected findings or new insights that emerge during the research process (Perry, 2014)</p>	<p>Lack of generalizability as its specific to the context (Yegidis <i>et al.</i> 2012)</p> <p>Secondly, the potential of a researcher's bias is high in such an approach, imposing the researchers' perspectives during the analysis stage, potentially affecting the validity of the findings (Simmons <i>et al.</i> 2011).</p>	<p>Its reliability is on plausibility rather than certainty, its highly susceptible to bias and new information, making it less reliable where definite conclusions need to be considered (Schurz, 2008)</p>

Table 20 presents an overview of different research approaches discussed in the literature. It compares key characteristics of each approach, including their underlying assumptions and

suitability for different research contexts. This table supports the justification for adopting a qualitative, interpretive approach aligned with the study's aims and research questions.

As this study does not have an existing hypothesis nor a prior observation, it will adopt an inductive approach. Due to the lack of studies on women in authentic leadership within the automobile industry, this study will generate its own framework for the application of authentic leadership among women. Inductive reasoning is participant-centric, aligning the findings with the lived experiences of those being studied. This study involves human participants, from whom patterns are expected to emerge through discussions. Inductive reasoning involves recognising these patterns and making predictions, eventually resulting in the generation of a theory based on the observations (Easterby-Smith *et al.*, 2008). The purpose of this study is to develop new insights into authentic leadership, gender, and leadership, with a particular focus on the automobile industry in India. Therefore, the adoption of inductive reasoning would be beneficial for this study, as it is ideal for new or under-researched areas such as women in authentic leadership in the automobile industry in the context of India. The identified concepts of 'leadership', 'authentic leadership', and 'gender' have not been researched through an intersectional lens, making this study both new and a complex phenomenon. The justification for selecting inductive reasoning can be summarised through the characteristics coined by Sloman (1996, p. 17), who states that "inductive reasoning is that in which the premises make the conclusion more probable."

3.5.3 Research Philosophy

Saunders *et al.* (2015, p. 124) defined research philosophy as a set of beliefs and assumptions about the development of knowledge. According to Dougherty *et al.* (2019, p. 1), it reflects an individual's core research values and goals. Both definitions emphasise the fundamental role that research philosophy plays in shaping the research process. While Saunders *et al.* (2015)

emphasise a set of beliefs guiding how knowledge is generated, the authors suggest that research philosophy influences the way researchers interpret knowledge. Dougherty *et al.* (2019), on the other hand, emphasise the researchers' values and beliefs, reinforcing the idea that research is not solely about the theoretical foundations of knowledge, but about aligning research practices with the researcher's personal values. Research philosophy thus acts as the foundation of the research project, affecting the overall approach and shaping the study's outcomes. Paradigm provides insight, while limitations and unmet challenges drive the evolution of research paradigms (Seely, 2010). The study will now examine the philosophy employed, along with relevant justifications.

There are various philosophical positions that can be used in research, including ontological, epistemological, and axiological standpoints (Saunders *et al.*, 2015). Each of these positions holds unique assumptions that influence how a researcher defines the research process. Ontology focuses on the nature of reality, addressing the "what" and "how" of existence (Burrell and Morgan, 1979), and refers to the assumptions and belief systems held by the researcher. These beliefs influence how a researcher perceives the research problem and shape their approach to it (Scott and Usher, 2011).

Epistemology deals with the nature of knowledge and what counts as valid knowledge (Tolk, 2013). It explores questions like, "What is the relationship between the researcher and reality?" and "What contributes to the body of knowledge?" These are vital considerations, especially since research aims to add meaningful insights to existing knowledge. Epistemology includes three main perspectives: positivism, interpretivism, and pragmatism.

The positivist paradigm aims to interpret observations and make predictions based on measurable outcomes (Pradoko, 2019). It advocates for the use of quantitative methods, underpinned by the imperative to describe variables and examine relationships (Fadhel, 2002).

In the context of this study, a positivist paradigm would focus on interpreting measurable data to predict trends related to gender dynamics in leadership roles. Applying this paradigm would require the study to prioritise interpretive parameters such as the influence of policy frameworks. Positivism is validated through four criteria: internal validity (results are attributed to the independent variable), external validity (generalisation to other contexts), reliability (stability and consistency of results), and objectivity (researcher detachment and bias minimisation) (Burns, 2000). However, this paradigm is not applicable to the current study as it does not aim to measure variables or review policy impacts, but rather to understand real-time experiences of women leaders and their teams.

The interpretivist paradigm, in contrast, seeks to understand human experiences by immersing in the perspectives of participants to interpret their meaning (McChesney and Aldridge, 2019). It involves the researcher metaphorically placing themselves in the participants' shoes (Guba and Lincoln, 1989). Interpretivism is concerned with understanding the lived realities of individuals (Leitch *et al.*, 2010). In studying women in leadership, this paradigm allows for an in-depth understanding of their personal experiences and those of their teams. As Guba and Lincoln (1989) emphasise, this approach requires the researcher to be immersed in the social and professional contexts of women leaders. The focus is on understanding individual and group narratives and interpreting their roles, identities, and contributions within the industry.

The pragmatist paradigm aims to reconcile the dichotomy between positivism and interpretivism by advocating for a practical and problem-centred approach to research. It is typically employed in mixed methods research, allowing for the integration of both qualitative and quantitative approaches to address real-world problems (Alise and Teddlie, 2010). However, this paradigm is not suitable for the present study, which does not utilise a mixed methods design nor operate within a predefined theoretical framework.

The phenomenological philosophy, established by German philosopher Martin Heidegger, critiques Western philosophical traditions for neglecting the fundamental question of existence (Kockelmans, 1965). Phenomenology focuses on exploring the structure of human experience through directly investigating lived realities. It shares similarities with interpretivism in emphasising subjective human perception (Ierna *et al.*, 2010). Central to phenomenology is the belief that experience itself must be questioned and analysed (Cerbone, 2006). The philosophy values empathy, perception, and evidence in examining the connection between the phenomenon under investigation (e.g. leadership) and contextual factors such as gender (Stahl, 2014). This philosophy is particularly relevant to this study, as it aims to uncover how women leaders experience and interpret authentic leadership within their unique organisational contexts.

Table 21: Characteristics of Phenomenal

Characteristics	Explanation
Focuses on lived experiences	Emphasis on the importance of understanding how individuals experience a phenomenon from their perspective, it seeks to capture the richness of these experiences (Van Manen, 1990)
Bracketing	Researchers who use phenomenology engage in bracketing where they set aside their biases and assumptions to fully engage with and understand the participants experiences (Giorgi, 2012)
Essence	The key goal of phenomenology is in uncovering the essence of an experience, which refers to the core meaning shared by different individuals experience on the same phenomenon.

	This essence is the fundamental nature of the experience. (Moustakas, 1994)
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Table 21 outlines the key characteristics of phenomenological research. It summarises the defining features and philosophical assumptions underpinning phenomenology. This table supports the methodological choice of an interpretive phenomenological approach by clarifying its relevance to exploring lived experiences.

Table 22: Descriptive Vs Interpretive Phenomenology

Types	Overview	Focus	Method
Descriptive (Husserlain)	Developed by Husserlain this approach emphasis on the lived experiences without an interpretation (Giorgi, 2012). The primary goal is to uncover the essence of experiences as they are perceived (Liu, and Drummond, 2007)	Direct understanding of experiences (Liu, and Drummond, 2007).	Engage in bracketing to set aside preconceived notions (Liu, and Drummond, 2007).
Interpretive (Hermeneutic)	This approach combines descriptive with interpretive, focusing on understanding how individuals make sense of their	Exploring meanings individuals ascribe to their lived	Involves in-depth interviews, analysing narratives, interpreting texts to uncover deeper

	experiences within their specific context (Paley, 1948)	experiences (Paley, 1948)	meaning. (Paley, 1948)
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Table 22 compares descriptive and interpretive phenomenological approaches. It highlights key differences in philosophical orientation, analytical focus, and researcher involvement. This comparison supports the selection of an interpretive phenomenological approach as the most appropriate method for exploring participants' lived leadership experiences.

Phenomenology is widely used in qualitative research as a philosophical and methodological approach concerned with understanding how individuals experience and interpret phenomena in their everyday lives. In leadership research, phenomenology has frequently been employed to explore leaders lived experiences, identity construction, and sense-making processes. In this broader sense, phenomenology is discussed in this section as a commonly used approach within qualitative and organisational research.

In the context of the present study, however, phenomenology is not adopted as a generic or purely descriptive method. Instead, the study is specifically informed by Interpretive Phenomenological Analysis (IPA), which represents a distinct phenomenological methodology. IPA is grounded in phenomenological philosophy but extends it through a hermeneutic and interpretative orientation, recognising that access to participants' experiences is mediated through both their own sense-making and the researcher's interpretative engagement.

Accordingly, phenomenology in this study functions at two levels. First, it provides the philosophical foundation underpinning the research, guiding the study's focus on lived experience, meaning-making, and subjective interpretation. Second, at the methodological level, IPA constitutes the analytical approach actually employed to examine interview and

focus group data. This distinction ensures conceptual clarity between phenomenology as a broad research tradition and IPA as the specific method used for data analysis.

The adoption of IPA is particularly appropriate for this study given its emphasis on exploring how individuals make sense of complex and emotionally nuanced experiences, such as leadership, authenticity, and gendered expectations within a male-dominated industrial context. By clarifying this distinction, the study demonstrates methodological coherence while situating itself clearly within established qualitative research traditions. The main principles of phenomenological thought, as discussed by Husserl and Heidegger, differ in focus. Husserl's phenomenology emphasised the importance of a descriptive method, while Heidegger highlighted the centrality of interpretation, arguing that enquiry cannot be separated from interpretative understanding (Bruzina, 2014). A shared limitation of both perspectives is the challenge of "bracketing" one's bias. This issue was addressed by Arendt (1958, p. 8), who urged researchers using phenomenological studies to pursue their work with passion and determination, seeking what is new rather than relying on analogy. Fisher (2009) reinforced that phenomenological research can only be considered such if it offers a strong and evocative description of lived experiences, with the researcher maintaining an open and receptive attitude. Furthermore, Fisher (2009) advised that researchers tailor their work to their audiences, enabling readers to be moved by the findings. Having examined the characteristics and types of phenomenology, as well as the philosophical tenets underpinning them, this study adopts hermeneutic (interpretive) phenomenology, as it aligns with the overall aim of the research. In accordance with Todres (2007), this approach allows the study to offer a strong and intuitive interpretation of participants' experiences, thereby enabling readers to connect meaningfully with the findings expressed.

In addressing the role of values and ethics in research, Munz *et al.* (2023) and Hamidi *et al.* (2022) argue that researchers must decide what constitutes right and wrong behaviour in the conduct of research. Ethical practice in research involves determining the values that will guide the researcher, respecting participants, and securing confidence and trust. This includes questions such as: How will I ensure the confidence of participants? How shall I conduct the research respectfully? How shall I avoid harm or risk? (Finnis, 1980). These considerations are guided by four ethical criteria: teleology, deontology, morality, and fairness, as proposed by Mill (1969). The application of these criteria prompts questions such as: Do the methods make common sense? Has the researcher considered the potential consequences of the findings? And is the research truthful in its presentation? This study adheres to these principles within the ethical framework encapsulated by the acronym PAPA—privacy, accuracy, property, and accessibility (Sidgwick, 1907).

Privacy concerns the amount of personal information participants will be expected to share, particularly regarding their challenges in leadership roles. The researcher is mindful of what aspects of the dialogue will be analysed. For instance, when participants speak about their journey into leadership, some aspects may be too personal or sensitive. Participants will not be compelled to disclose anything beyond their comfort level, and anonymisation will be used to protect their identities. Additionally, participants will be fully informed about the study's aims, their role, and how their data will be used, with informed consent obtained via the University of the West of Scotland's (UWS) participant consent form prior to interviews.

To ensure accuracy, valid research methods will be employed. Interview and focus group questions will be clearly worded and unbiased. Triangulation will be achieved by utilising multiple data sources, including in-depth interviews with women leaders and focus group discussions with their teams. These steps enhance the credibility of findings. Accuracy will be

further ensured through regular auditing, which involves verifying data with participants before and after recording to allow for corrections and resolve discrepancies.

Regarding property, the data collected will be owned by the researcher, while participants and organisations involved will be appropriately acknowledged. The study also aims to be inclusive, involving not only women leaders but also their reporting teams, comprising both male and female members. To enhance engagement and accessibility, all interviews and discussions will be conducted in English, as it is the preferred language of the participants.

The primary aim of this study is to create a rich understanding of women's authentic leadership and the contextual dynamics of colleague sponsorship within the Indian automobile industry. Success in this research depends on human interaction and contribution, requiring a deep understanding of women's lived experiences of leadership. Women leaders are considered social actors through the lens of authentic leadership, and the study seeks to interpret the world from their perspective, employing appropriate methods of enquiry rather than behavioural observation. Phenomenological research philosophy emphasises the construction of social reality within the cultural contexts in which it emerges, enabling the researcher to interpret the deep, rich layers of meaning within participants' accounts (Leitch *et al.*, 2010).

The study adopts an epistemological stance that examines how knowledge is constructed and how the researcher relates to the reality being studied. It extends beyond interpretivism by employing hermeneutic phenomenology to explore the experiences of women leaders, aiming to reveal the essence of their leadership journeys. This is achieved by interpreting their feelings and perceptions and by bracketing the researcher's own experiences and biases regarding women leaders in the automotive industry (Gearing, 2004). The study combines depth and rigour, enabling participants to identify the core traits and meanings embedded within their leadership experiences.

3.5.4 Research Methodological Choice

Saunders *et al.* (2009) introduces six methodological choices. Mono method quantitative, mono method qualitative, multi method quantitative, multi method qualitative, mixed method simple and mixed method complex. The terms quantitative, qualitative and mixed are widely used terms in research.

Mono Method: Gather one type of data either using quantitative or qualitative methods.

Mixed Method: Permits the researcher to combine quantitative and qualitative methodology.

Table 23: Quantitative vs qualitative (Borrego *et al.* 2009)

Dimension	Quantitative	Qualitative	Relevance to the Present Study
Research purpose	Measurement, prediction, hypothesis testing	Exploration, understanding, interpretation	Study aims to explore lived leadership experiences, not test hypotheses
Ontological assumption	Objective, singular reality	Multiple, socially constructed realities	Leadership and authenticity are context-dependent and socially constructed
Epistemological stance	Positivist / post-positivist	Interpretivist	Aligns with interpretivist stance

			adopted in this research
Nature of data	Numerical, structured	Narrative, textual, experiential	Data consists of interviews and focus group discussions
Role of researcher	Detached, objective observer	Active interpreter of meaning	Researcher engages reflexively with participants' sense-making
Sample size	Large, statistically representative	Smaller, purposive, information-rich	Focus on depth rather than breadth of leadership experiences
Type of generalisation	Statistical	Analytical / theoretical	Study seeks analytical insights transferable to similar contexts
Treatment of context	Controlled or minimised	Central and integral	Organisational and cultural context is critical in Indian automotive sector

Evaluation of rigour	Reliability, validity, objectivity	Credibility, dependability, reflexivity	Rigour ensured through triangulation and transparency
Suitability for leadership identity research	Limited for capturing meaning and identity work	Strong for understanding identity, sense-making, and experience	Qualitative approach is methodologically appropriate

Table 23 demonstrates that quantitative and qualitative approaches are underpinned by fundamentally different philosophical assumptions and research purposes. While quantitative methods are appropriate for measuring variables and testing predefined hypotheses, they are less suited to exploring complex, context-dependent phenomena such as leadership identity, authenticity, and gendered experiences. The present study seeks to understand *how* women leaders interpret and navigate leadership within a male-dominated industrial environment, rather than *how often* particular behaviours occur.

A qualitative approach is therefore methodologically justified, as it enables in-depth exploration of lived experience, meaning-making, and contextual influences. By privileging participants' voices and interpretations, qualitative research provides insights that cannot be captured through numerical data alone. This alignment between research aims, philosophical stance, and methodological choice strengthens the overall coherence and rigour of the study.

Qualitative research typically focuses on understanding concepts, experiences, or phenomena from a holistic and in-depth perspective. It identifies data that is non-numerical, such as text, video, audio, or images. Data collection methods commonly include interviews, focus group discussions, observations, and content analysis, with the objective of understanding the

meaning behind participants’ experiences. This study has chosen to adopt a qualitative approach, as it is the most adaptable in capturing the lived experiences of women leaders. Since the study involves human participants, qualitative research is more appropriate than quantitative approaches, which concentrate on collecting statistical data.

The primary reason for not employing a mixed-methods approach is the limited accessibility to statistical data. This constraint informed the researcher’s decision to select a purely qualitative methodology. In the Indian context, the role of women leaders in the automobile industry is still evolving, and at this stage, gaining access to comprehensive datasets would be challenging and could pose limitations on the scope and depth of the research. Furthermore, mixed-method approaches can be both time-consuming and expensive to execute, particularly in sectors with restricted access to organisational data (Golicic, Davis and Flint, 2012). Given the security constraints and the time-sensitive nature of this study, a mixed-methods approach was not considered feasible.

The study also opted not to use a quantitative method, as this approach does not account for individuals’ motives, values, or the depth of their experiences (Morris, 1991). Quantitative research focuses on objectivity and measurement, often overlooking the rich subjective experiences that are essential to this study. Since the research requires an in-depth inquiry into the phenomenon of women in authentic leadership, it relies on understanding participants’ perspectives and lived realities. Therefore, this study employs a qualitative methodological approach, enabling a more nuanced and empathetic exploration of the subject matter.

Table 24: Previous studies using qualitative methods have been summarised below:

Author	Year	Topic	Method
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Jamjoom and Mills,	2023	Narratives of workplace resistance: Reframing Saudi women in leadership	Semi-structured interviews
Abadi, Dirani and Rezaei	2022	Women in leadership: a systematic literature review of Middle Eastern women managers' careers from NHRD and institutional theory perspectives	Semi-structured interviews
Gottenborg <i>et al</i>	2021	The experience of women in hospital medicine leadership: a qualitative study	Semi-structured Interviews
Smirles <i>et al</i>	2020	Japanese women's perceptions of gender roles and leadership and the effects of women & leadership courses: A qualitative analysis	Semi-structured interviews
Vu Barnett, Duong and Lee	2019	Delicate and durable: an analysis of women's leadership and media practices in Vietnam	In-depth interviews
Carbajal	2018	Women and work: ascending to leadership positions	Interviews

Bhattacharya, Mohapatra and Bhattacharya	2018	Women advancing to leadership positions: A qualitative study of women leaders in the IT and ITES sector in India	Semi-structured interviews
Soklaridis <i>et al</i>	2017	Gender bias in hospital leadership: a qualitative study on the experiences of women CEO's	Interviews
Showunmi, Atewologun and Bebbington	2016	Ethnic, gender and class intersections in British women's leadership experiences	Focus group and interviews
Mayer and Surtee	2015	The leadership preferences of women leaders working in higher education	Semi-structured interviews
Diko	2014	Women in educational leadership: the case of Hope High School in the Eastern Cape Province, South Africa	Interviews
Pryce and Sealy	2013	Mentoring: a model for cultivating leadership competencies in Kenyan women	Semi-structured interviews

Grant	2012	Advancing our legacy: a black feminist perspective on the significance of mentoring for African American women in education leadership	Semi-structured phone interviews
Wallis, Yammarino, and Feyerherm	2011	Individualised leadership: A qualitative study of senior executives' leaders	One-on-one interviews
Isaac, Griffin and Carnes	2010	A qualitative study of faculty members' views of women chairs	Semi-structured interviews

Table 24 summarises previous studies that have employed qualitative research methods. It highlights methodological approaches, research contexts, and key contributions of qualitative studies relevant to this research. This table supports the methodological justification for adopting a qualitative design by demonstrating its established use in exploring complex leadership and gender-related phenomena.

Specifically, Table 24 demonstrates that qualitative approaches particularly interview-based designs are widely used to investigate complex, context-dependent leadership experiences. This is especially relevant for studies focusing on identity, authenticity, and gender, where meaning-making and lived experience are central. By highlighting how previous researchers have employed qualitative methods to explore similar constructs, Table 24 provides methodological precedent and reinforces the appropriateness of the qualitative approach adopted in this study.

In addition, Table 24 helps to clarify the research gap addressed by the present study. While existing studies have examined women’s leadership experiences across various organisational and national contexts, the table shows that limited attention has been paid to women leaders in India’s automobile manufacturing industry, particularly through the combined lenses of authentic leadership and sponsorship. The present study therefore extends prior research by addressing this under-explored context and by integrating themes that have typically been examined in isolation.

Furthermore, the table supports the study’s methodological choices by illustrating how qualitative leadership research often relies on purposive sampling, in-depth interviews, and interpretative analysis to generate analytical insights. These methodological patterns informed the design of the present research, including the use of semi-structured interviews and focus group discussions to capture both individual and collective perspectives.

Overall, Table 24 serves a dual purpose: it validates the qualitative methodological approach adopted in this study and highlights the originality of the research context and focus. By linking prior qualitative leadership research to the specific aims and design of the present study, the table strengthens the coherence, credibility, and academic contribution of the research.

3.5.4.1 Research Strategy

Research strategy, as defined by Rowlinson *et al.* (2014), is the practical aspect of research. It involves the plan of action used to answer the research question.

Table 25: Different Research Strategies

Type	Context	Advantages	Limitations	Applicability
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Experiment	<p>As the title denotes, it tests a particular idea in an environment.</p> <p>Helping a researcher have a strong control over the variables by manipulating the independent variables to study the change in the dependent variables. (Bolinger <i>et al.</i>, 2022)</p>	<p>High control over variables and can establish causality (Creswell and Creswell, 2018)</p>	<p>Ethical constraints (Creswell and Creswell, 2018)</p>	<p>Used in natural sciences, Marketing (Creswell and Creswell, 2018)</p>
Survey	<p>A method of collecting data from a pool of respondents by asking the 'what', 'who', and 'where'. The collection of data is analysed.</p>	<p>Cost-effective for large samples and can be generalised (Babbie, 1990)</p>	<p>Limited depth (Babbie, 1990)</p>	<p>Best suited for descriptive or exploratory research (Babbie, 1990)</p>

	(Kriauciunas <i>et al.</i> , 2011)			
Case Study	An in-depth investigation of a single case with real-life context	Provided detailed, rich data, capturing complexities (Mizukoshi, 2023)	Time-consuming (Mizukoshi, 2023)	The most effective ways of using them are in an inductive way (Eisenhardt, 1989) An exploratory case study is the best as it plays into the strength (Siggelkow, 2008) Especially used when studying a phenomenon (Mizukoshi, 2023)
Action Research	Here, the researcher works with the participants to identify a problem, implement solutions and evaluate	Directly applicable to practice and encourages change (Stringer and Ortiz, 2021)	Lacks objectivity and is limited to generalisation (Stringer and Ortiz, 2021)	Often used in educational or organisational settings (Stringer and Ortiz, 2021)

	outcomes (Stringer and Ortiz, 2021)			
Ethnography	A study was conducted with a collective group of people through interviews. The study of this strategy shows how groups, organisations, and societies function. (Vesa and Vaara, 2014; chlegel <i>et al.</i> , 2021)	Provides deep cultural insights with context rich data (Vesa and Vaara, 2014)	Time consuming and possibility for researcher bias (Vesa and Vaara, 2014)	Useful in studying social phenomenon particularly in anthropology and sociology (Vesa and Vaara, 2014)
Grounded Theory	Construction of theory from data involves studies that systematically obtain and analyse behaviour, comparing the data to identify patterns.	Supports the generation of new theories and is very flexible (Oktay, 2012)	Time-consuming, requiring strong analytical skills (Oktay, 2012)	Ideal for research where a new theory needs to be created, such as social science, health research (Oktay, 2012)

	(Goulding and Lee, 2005)			
Archival	This strategy uses manuscripts and sound-video archives. This type of study is well-suited to documentary research, where documents serve as the primary source of data (Tamboukou, 2014).	Access to historical data	Potential for missing data	Used predominantly for legal studies or any research that requires an examination of past events (Das, Jain and Mishra, 2018)

Table 25 presents an overview of different research strategies discussed in the literature. It compares the key features, strengths, and applicability of each strategy to various research contexts. This table supports the selection of appropriate research strategies for the study and demonstrates informed methodological decision-making.

From the above analysis, it is evident that each research strategy has its own strengths and limitations. The choice of strategy was based on the research questions, the phenomenon being studied, and the available resources, namely, women leaders within the Indian automobile OEM manufacturing sector and their teams, comprising both male and female executives. The desired outcome of the study is to generate practical insights that could help foster sponsorship

opportunities for women within these organisations. These were the key influencing factors in selecting ethnography and case study as the most suitable research strategies (Yin, 2018; Hammersley and Atkinson, 2007). Both strategies are well-suited for exploring complex social phenomena in their real-life contexts and are especially effective when the boundaries between the phenomenon and context are not clearly evident.

Ethnography enables the researcher to immerse themselves in the social setting of the participants to understand their cultural and organisational experiences (Hammersley and Atkinson, 2007). Meanwhile, the case study method provides an in-depth exploration of a bounded system, offering rich contextual insights (Yin, 2018). The tools chosen for data collection, lead interviews, and focus group discussions align with both strategies and support the study's aim of gaining a nuanced understanding of women's lived experiences in leadership.

The following section provides a brief description of interviews and their various types, along with a rationale for their selection. It then discusses the value of focus group discussions and how they enrich the data and finally outlines details of the organisations that form part of the case study.

3.5.4.2 Interviews and types of interviews

As defined by Ellis (2016, p.1), “interviews are useful when the researcher is seeking to uncover people’s understandings and feelings about a particular topic or event.” This definition highlights the value of interviews in uncovering personal understandings and emotional responses. Ellis (2016) emphasises that interviews are particularly beneficial when the researcher seeks to gain deeper insights. Rowley (2012) provides a complementary definition, outlining the process, roles, and interpersonal nature of interviews, while emphasising the direct and interactive communication that occurs. While Rowley (2012) focuses on structure and interaction, Ellis (2016) emphasises the purpose and depth of insight, together offering a

holistic understanding of interviews as a flexible yet methodological tool in qualitative research, capable of yielding rich, contextual data.

There are three main types of interviews: structured, semi-structured, and unstructured. Structured interviews involve asking questions in a fixed order with consistent wording (Weaver-Hightower, 2019). Semi-structured interviews use a guide with prepared topics or questions, allowing for probing and flexibility during the conversation (Dearnley, 2005). These enable the interview to flow more naturally and adapt to the responses of the participants. Unstructured interviews rely on open-ended questions without a predetermined format and depend heavily on the researcher's skill to explore issues in depth (Chauhan, 2022). In-depth interviews, which are closely related to unstructured formats, facilitate focused exploration with fewer participants and often produce richer and more meaningful data through prolonged engagement (Morris, 2015). They are regarded as dialogues of mutual interest between the researcher and the participant.

This study has selected in-depth interviews after evaluating the advantages and limitations of the different formats. In-depth interviews align best with the study's objectives, as they provide a deeper understanding of the participants' lived experiences. They are preferred over structured interviews, which tend to constrain participants' responses due to rigid formats, thereby limiting the depth and richness of the information (Rowley, 2012). While both semi-structured and in-depth interviews have limitations, including potential bias and analytical complexity, and rely heavily on the interviewer's skill (Kausel, Culbertson, and Madrid, 2016), the benefits of in-depth interviews, such as flexibility, rapport building, adaptability, and the opportunity to clarify responses, make them particularly appropriate. As King and Horrocks (2012) suggest, in-depth interviews are one of the most widely used and effective methods in qualitative research.

The researcher’s prior experience and understanding of the Indian automobile industry will further aid in probing effectively and drawing out meaningful narratives. Through one-on-one interviews, the researcher hopes to capture descriptive accounts of how successful women leaders have navigated challenges and upheld their leadership identity. Additionally, these interviews aim to reveal internal barriers and facilitate comparative analysis regarding the intersection of authenticity, leadership, and gender in fostering sponsorship.

Having identified in-depth interviews as a primary tool, the researcher intends to prepare a detailed interview schedule that outlines key discussion areas (Creswell and Poth, 2023). The schedule will guide the process to ensure all relevant themes are addressed. The design of the interview questions has been influenced by the works of Gardiner (2015) and Mayo (2018), as well as themes identified in the literature review. These two authors were selected for their contemporary contributions to the field of authentic leadership, particularly in addressing gaps in earlier theories. According to Uwe (2022), interviews should begin with expressions of gratitude and a clear consent process, followed by literature-informed questions. This structure fosters trust and facilitate a deeper exploration of the topic. These protocols will inform both the scheduling and design of the interview questions.

Table 26: In-depth Interview plan (Patton, 2015)

Plan	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • List participants to be interviewed. • Identify the required information. • Ensure ethical research standards are followed. • Seek consent from Interviewees
Develop	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Introduction to interviewees

	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • During the interview • Translation if required. • Required probing techniques
Collect	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Method of collection of data (handwritten or Word document) • Summarise data collected
Analyse	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Read and look for patterns. • Group themes

Table 26 outlines the in-depth interview (IDI) process adopted in this study. It details the stages involved in planning, conducting, and analysing interviews. This table supports methodological transparency by clearly illustrating how interview data were systematically collected and managed.

After establishing the interview schedule, a key focus of the research process involves designing the interview questions. This phase is crucial, as poorly constructed questions can impair the quality of insights gathered during the interviews. Roulston (2010) emphasises the importance of anchoring interview questions in theoretical foundations, warning that neglecting this link between theory and practice may lead to superficial or misaligned data collection. Therefore, before engaging with participants, the researcher carefully considered the theoretical positioning of the questions to ensure they reflected the study's purpose.

The questions were shaped by four key philosophical concepts drawn from phenomenological inquiry: spatiality, corporeality, temporality, and relationality, as introduced by Van Manen (1997). These dimensions offer a rich and meaningful structure for exploring participants lived experiences, providing both depth and context.

The concept of spatiality refers to the environments and spaces where leadership experiences occur, promoting reflection on moments of empowerment and vulnerability. For instance, participants were asked to describe their leadership journey by recalling a time when they felt most confident leading and a time when they felt discomfort or intimidation. This type of question enables participants to place their experience within both physical and psychological space.

Corporeality, which refers to the embodied nature of experience, influenced the design of questions exploring how authenticity is physically or emotionally felt. A question such as “Have you had any emotional or physical sensations when you acted in an authentic way?” aims to prompt reflection on the embodied reality of leading as a woman in a male-dominated industry.

The theme of temporality encourages participants to reflect on how their view of leadership has evolved over time. Here, the past, present, and anticipated future are interwoven to examine the dynamic and continuous nature of leadership identity. A representative question asks: “Can you describe how your understanding of leadership has changed over time?”

Relationality, the fourth dimension, focuses on the relationships that shape a leader’s identity and values. To explore this, participants were asked: “Who influenced your thinking about leadership and authenticity?” This line of questioning encourages participants to identify mentors, role models, or peers who played a pivotal role in their leadership journey.

The interviews were designed to encourage storytelling, inviting participants to share their experiences in their own words and on their own terms. Storytelling is a recognised approach in qualitative research for eliciting authentic accounts of lived experience (Arendt, 1958; Vasterling, 2007). This narrative-driven approach supports the study’s goal of exploring the

intersection of gender, authenticity, and leadership within the context of India's automobile industry.

Data collection will be conducted through audio recordings and written notes taken by the researcher. The interviewer's role will extend beyond simply asking questions; it includes actively listening, observing verbal and non-verbal cues, and creating a safe and open space for participants to speak freely. The relationship between the researcher and the participant is central to the success of this method, as it fosters trust and depth in the conversation.

To ensure that each interview question aligns with the study's objectives, the researcher has mapped the questions against the research aims in a table (Table 25). This mapping exercise helps to demonstrate how each question contributes to answering the overarching research questions. Some of these questions are adapted from Gardiner's (2015) work, whose research on authentic leadership in gendered contexts has informed the design. Others are original, derived from the researcher's findings from both narrative and systematic literature reviews.

Following Creswell and Poth's (2023) guidance, the interview process will begin with an introductory segment, during which the researcher will express gratitude, obtain informed consent, and clarify the purpose of the interview. This protocol ensures that participants feel comfortable, respected, and well-informed before engaging in deep discussion. The development of the interview schedule and the sequencing of questions have been influenced by the works of Gardiner (2015) and Mayo (2018), whose studies provided contemporary insights into the gaps in existing literature on authentic leadership.

By designing the interviews in this way, the researcher aims to elicit rich, nuanced data that can reveal how women in leadership experience, understand, and embody authenticity in their roles, providing insights vital to the core purpose of this study.

Table 27: In-depth interview questions

In-depth Interview Questions	Research Questions
I would like to hear more about your journey within the automotive industry	How successful women leaders navigated and flourished in upholding their leadership fit within the automobile Industry?
How do you define authentic leadership and what qualities do you associate with it?	How authenticity, leadership and gender could intersect in building a culture of sponsorships, advocating women’s career advancement?
How do you describe your experiences of authenticity or the lack of it in the automobile industry?	How authenticity, leadership and gender could intersect in building a culture of sponsorships, advocating women’s career advancement?
Could you describe your leadership journey by relating to a time where you were most comfortable leading and a time where you felt intimidated?	<ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. How successful women leaders navigated and flourished in upholding their leadership fit within the automobile Industry? 2. What were some of the challenges they had to overcome internally?
Could you share all the development opportunities that was provided to you during this journey	How successful women leaders navigated and flourished in upholding their leadership in the automobile Industry?

<p>Have you had a sponsor in your career? If so, how did it impact your growth?</p>	<p>How successful women leaders navigated and flourished in upholding their leadership fit within the automobile Industry?</p>
<p>Who influenced your thinking about leadership and authenticity</p>	<p>How authenticity, leadership and gender could intersect in building a culture of sponsorships, advocating women's career advancement?</p>
<p>Can you describe how your understanding about leadership has changed over time</p>	<p>What were some of the challenges they had to overcome internally?</p>
<p>In what way have your colleagues/ your direct reportees contributed to your growth</p>	<p>How authenticity, leadership and gender could intersect in building a culture of sponsorships, advocating for women's career advancement?</p>
<p>What is important for an inclusive work culture</p>	<p>How authenticity, leadership and gender intersect in building a culture of sponsorships, advocating for women's career advancement?</p>
<p>How to do you respond to feedback</p>	<p>How successful women leaders navigated and flourished in upholding their leadership in the automobile Industry?</p>
<p>What advice would you give to aspiring women?</p>	<p>How do authenticity, leadership, and gender intersect in building a culture of</p>

	sponsorships, advocating for women’s career advancement?
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Table 27 maps the in-depth interview questions to the research objectives and research questions. It demonstrates alignment between the data collection instruments and the study’s aims. This table supports methodological rigour by ensuring that interview questions directly address the research objectives.

Having aligned the in-depth interview questions with the research aims, it becomes essential to define the criteria for selecting suitable participants. The participants for this study were drawn from five leading automotive organisations, each forming a case study within the research. Upon receiving formal approval from the legal departments of these organisations, the identified participants were senior women leaders, ideally holding titles such as Manager, Senior Manager, Director, or equivalent, with a minimum of five years’ experience within Original Equipment Manufacturer (OEM) automotive companies in India. This criterion is consistent with the guidance provided by Thomas and Pollio (2002), who emphasise the significance of selecting participants with lived experience of the phenomenon under investigation. Their framework underscores the importance of engaging individuals whose experiential depth enhances the interpretive value of qualitative research.

Once organisational consent was obtained, the researcher initiated direct communication with the identified women leaders, providing them with an overview of the study. Each potential participant received the University of the West of Scotland (UWS) Participant Information Sheet and Consent Form. Participation was strictly voluntary, and interviews were conducted only after formal consent had been received. Each of the five organisations committed to providing four to five participants, resulting in a total of twenty-five women leaders from across

the automotive sector. For example, 3 participants who had resigned from the automotive organisations were selected.

The structure and conduct of the interviews were guided by Benner (1994), who advocates for understanding the contextual background of participants' experiences. This approach aligns with the study's phenomenological focus and encourages a conversational, natural flow of dialogue. The significance of fostering openness and mutual respect in qualitative interviews has also been emphasised by Lugones and Spelman (1983), who argue that genuine understanding is rooted in empathy and relational engagement. As a result, the interviews were designed to resemble dialogues rather than formal interrogations, creating an environment where participants could feel safe to share deeply personal reflections.

With reference to Table 27, participants were not asked to generate definitions of authentic leadership in the absence of contextual grounding. To ensure informed and meaningful engagement with the concept, participants were provided with a brief definition of authentic leadership as part of the participant information and ethical documentation circulated prior to the interviews. This definition was intended to establish a shared baseline understanding of the concept rather than to shape or constrain participants' responses.

In addition, at the beginning of each interview, the researcher verbally reiterated a concise, non-prescriptive description of authentic leadership to confirm participants' familiarity with the concept and to address any initial uncertainty. Participants were then invited to reflect on authentic leadership in their own terms, drawing on their lived experiences and personal interpretations. This approach ensured conceptual clarity while preserving participants' agency and interpretive freedom, thereby supporting methodological transparency and credibility.

Each interview was scheduled for approximately one hour and thirty minutes and was recorded using a digital voice recorder. The recordings were later transcribed verbatim to preserve the

authenticity of participants' narratives. Anonymity was ensured through the use of participant codes (e.g., "Participant 1") instead of names or organisational identifiers. The conversation began with an invitation for the participant to share their preferred name for the dialogue, followed by an introductory question such as: "I would like to hear more about your journey within the automotive industry." This opening was deliberately framed to create a comfortable atmosphere and shift the emphasis away from rigid definitions of leadership and authenticity. The final question, "Is there anything else you would like to add?", was open-ended, encouraging participants to share any thoughts not covered during the interview.

During the conversation, the researcher was attentive to non-verbal cues and pauses, recognising that moments of silence may signal emotions or insights that are not immediately verbalised. Such sensitivity is vital in capturing the nuanced dimensions of lived experience.

Following the interviews, the transcripts were emailed to the respective participants for verification, a process aligned with best practices in qualitative research for ensuring credibility and accuracy (Creswell and Poth, 2023). Participants were invited to review, amend, or clarify any part of the transcript. Once validated, digital transcripts were stored securely on an external encrypted device, and printed copies were kept in a locked cabinet accessible only to the researcher. Hard copies were not retained by participants to ensure data confidentiality and consistency in storage.

3.5.4.3 Focus Group Discussions

In addition to individual interviews with women leaders, the study incorporated focus group discussions as a supplementary qualitative method. In terms of design, the inclusion of focus groups was a deliberate methodological decision aimed at enhancing analytical depth and strengthening the credibility of the findings through methodological triangulation, consistent

with established qualitative research guidance on multi-method designs (Morgan, 1997; Lincoln and Guba, 1985).

While interviews enabled an in-depth exploration of women leaders' individual lived experiences and sense-making processes (Ismail *et al.*, 2025), focus groups provided access to collective perspectives and shared organisational meanings generated through participant interaction (Kitzinger, 1995; Mkandawire-Valhmu and Stevens, 2010). Focus group participants were team members who reported directly to women leaders, allowing the study to examine leadership experiences from a follower perspective. This design enabled comparison between how women leaders described their leadership practices and how those practices were perceived and interpreted by others within the organisational context.

With respect to conduct, the focus groups were undertaken following the completion of individual interviews, allowing preliminary interview themes to inform the development of a semi-structured focus group discussion guide, as recommended for qualitative sequencing and analytic refinement (Krueger and Casey, 2015). This sequencing enabled a more focused exploration of emergent issues and facilitated examination of convergence and divergence across data sources. Five focus group discussions were conducted, involving a total of thirteen participants, with each session lasting approximately seventy-five minutes. Participants were selected using purposive criteria to ensure direct experience of working under women leaders, in line with qualitative sampling principles (Campbell *et al.*, 2020). Ethical safeguards were applied to minimise power imbalances, ensure voluntary participation, and protect confidentiality.

Analytically, focus group data were not treated as standalone findings but were integrated with the interview data to support triangulation and thematic refinement. The focus groups served to validate, contextualise, and, in some cases, challenge interpretations derived from the

interviews, thereby strengthening the robustness and credibility of the analysis (Lincoln and Guba, 1985; Braun and Clarke, 2021). This combined approach enhanced interpretive credibility by examining leadership experiences at both individual and collective levels.

Overall, the inclusion of focus groups complements the phenomenological and interpretivist orientation of the study by capturing socially constructed meanings and organisational dynamics that extend beyond individual narratives. Their use therefore represents a methodologically coherent and theoretically justified extension of the qualitative research design.

The second phase of data collection in this research involves focus group discussions (FGDs) conducted with the direct reportees of the women leaders, allowing the study to develop a collective perspective on the phenomenon under investigation. The inclusion of FGDs aims to complement the individual insights obtained from in-depth interviews (IDIs), facilitating a richer and more triangulated interpretation of the data. The comparative analysis of themes emerging from both IDIs and FGDs enhances the study's depth and credibility, providing a comprehensive and well-substantiated methodological approach.

Within the FGD setting, particular attention will be paid to group dynamics, including who contributes most actively to the conversation. These groups will consist of both male and female employees who report directly to women leaders. The researcher aims to explore how interactions in a collective context shape perceptions differently from those in individual interviews, especially regarding the third research objective: gaining comparative insights into how authenticity, leadership, and gender intersect to influence sponsorship within organisations.

Both the IDIs and FGDs will be conducted within the automotive organisations that have formally agreed to participate as case studies. Case study research is considered particularly

appropriate for examining contemporary social phenomena within their real-life contexts, especially when the boundaries between the phenomenon and its context are blurred (Yin, 2003). As such, the case study strategy is well aligned with the current research, which seeks to explore women's authentic leadership through human interpretations within their organisational settings (Oliver, 2004). Furthermore, the case study methodology enables the collection of data from multiple sources and offers a degree of flexibility that distinguishes it from more rigid designs, such as surveys (Yin, 1994). By adopting this approach, the study gains a holistic perspective that captures the complex realities of women leaders navigating the Indian automotive sector.

While single case studies are valuable for understanding unique or exceptional cases in depth, multiple case studies enable cross-comparisons, allowing researchers to explore whether similar patterns or themes emerge across different organisational contexts (Woodside, 2016). This study adopts Yin's (2013) multiple case study methodology to compare and contrast findings across five distinct automotive organisations. By doing so, the research not only captures the nuances within each case but also investigates broader patterns across the sector, enhancing the depth and relevance of its findings.

A key consideration when undertaking interpretive case study research is the issue of generalisability. As the data are subject to interpretation by the researcher, they may not be deemed objectively factual. Nevertheless, Walsham (1995) argues that interpretive case studies can generate four forms of generalisation: the development of concepts, the generation of theory, the drawing of specific implications, and the contribution of rich insight. These outcomes ensure that the findings, while context-specific, hold conceptual value that extends beyond the individual cases under study.

For a multiple case study approach to be effective, it was essential that the selected organisations shared certain functional similarities. The Indian passenger car manufacturing industry comprises a mix of national and multinational companies, yet not all organisations meet the specific criteria necessary for inclusion in this study. The organisations chosen are among the most prominent in the sector and have demonstrated leadership in promoting diversity. Each organisation had to meet several prerequisites: it must be a passenger car manufacturer operating within India, employ women in its workforce, have at least one woman in a leadership role, demonstrate active efforts to increase female representation in its talent pipeline, and have formal policies supporting diversity and inclusion. These conditions ensure that the organisations selected are both relevant to the research objectives and capable of providing the necessary depth and breadth of insight into women’s leadership experiences in the automotive sector.

Table 28: Organisation selected and summary of details.

Organisations	Summary of Details
1	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Amongst the top 10 manufacturers in the country • One of the youngest and fastest car makers • First to introduce diversity policies
2	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Amongst the top 10 manufacturers in the country • Amongst the top exporters in the country • First to introduce the “L-Line” for women
3	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Amongst the top 10 manufacturers in the country

	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • The first car made entirely by women engineers. • The first to introduce a scheme for young mothers.
4	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Among the global top 10 automotive manufacturers • Known for diversity and inclusion amongst its plants in Europe
5	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • New entry into the Indian market • A merger with some well-known global brands • Headquartered in Europe

Table 28 outlines the criteria used for selecting participating organisations. It specifies organisational characteristics relevant to the study's focus and ensures alignment with the research objectives and industry context. This table supports transparency and rigour in the organisational sampling process.

3.5.4.4 Time horizon

The parameters mentioned above were crucial in identifying the diversity in leadership, highlighting both the differences and similarities among the organisations. As Sweetman (2018) points out in a study on Black leadership, the identification of similarities often outweighs the exploration of differences, as it allows for a more meaningful understanding of shared experiences. In line with this, this study emphasised the similarities between organisations in selecting the case study participants. Limiting the scope of the case study to passenger car automobile manufacturing units ensured that the research criteria were clearly defined and comparable across organisations. The unit of analysis for the case study focused on the influence that women leaders, who exhibited authenticity, had on their male colleagues, who in turn could act as sponsors for their professional growth.

When selecting the appropriate strategy for the study, it is essential to align the chosen approach with the research's purpose. The aim of this study is exploratory, and the case study method is particularly suited to this purpose. The researcher seeks to understand, describe, and compare the leadership context for women in various automobile companies. The ultimate goal of the study is to provide the automobile industry with insights on how to elevate women from within the organisation. Case studies are valuable in answering the "how" questions and provide a concrete, in-depth understanding of the real phenomenon being investigated. Furthermore, case studies facilitate the identification of gaps in the current understanding, enabling comparisons to be made about why one strategy may be more effective than another, ultimately leading to the enhancement or development of a new theory. Additionally, this study seeks to examine real-life situations and compare these across different organisational contexts. The multiple case study method is ideal for achieving this objective, as it offers a more naturalistic understanding of women leaders within their work environment (Yin, 2003).

3.5.4.5 Research Techniques and Procedures

Data collection and analysis are based on the selected approach, which is phenomenology. The phenomenon explored in this study is authentic leadership among women. A comprehensive literature review will be conducted to understand the academic literature on women in leadership, the automobile industry, and authentic leadership, and to explore the intricacies within these areas, ultimately deriving theoretical propositions.

Data collection and analysis will take place in two stages. The first stage involves individual in-depth interviews through probing conversations (Guest, 1963; Namey and Mitchell, 2013) with women leaders, either individually or in groups, using the model by Wood *et al.* (2012), which suggests participants write their life story, focusing on trigger events and reflecting on them, with specific timelines. In-depth interviews aim to gather detailed information about the

thoughts and behaviours of women in leadership roles. This method was chosen as the first stage because it allows for the privacy and legitimacy of the data gathered, particularly in cases where women leaders feel apprehensive about sharing in a group setting. The data will help create an emotional tone chart that depicts the highs and lows of women leaders' journeys, shedding light on self-drive, passion, and self-actualisation.

There are two types of phenomenological interviews: descriptive (focusing on day-to-day life experiences) and interpretive (Thomas, 2021). This study will employ the interpretive phenomenological approach, where the researcher seeks to gain an in-depth understanding of women in authentic leadership as the phenomenon and interprets the experiences using a qualitative technique known as interpretive phenomenological analysis (IPA). IPA aims to understand the lived experiences of women leaders, making it well-suited for this study, as it involves a smaller sample of participants and utilises the knowledge and experience of the researcher to facilitate interpretation (Gibson, 2024). IPA was chosen because it focuses on participants' experiences with an emphasis on making sense of these experiences (Smith & Larkin, 2009). IPA will help answer the question of what it is like being a woman leader in the automobile industry. It will explore the experiences of individual women leaders, leading to thematic connections. Unlike thematic analysis, IPA focuses on the rich perspectives of lived experiences rather than categorising themes based on predefined criteria. IPA is also highly supportive of verbatim transcript data, which this study will use (Larkin, Eatough and Osborn, 2011). Methodological devices and concepts such as the role of the researcher in interpreting and bracketing are integral to this approach. The process will be carried out through a unique IPA device known as the hermeneutic circle. This process of interpretation adds validity to the findings. IPA uses the researcher as a tool, creating a link between the reported experiences of participants and the interpretative role of the researcher, thus adding value, research integrity,

and depth to the findings. This approach promotes transparency, thereby reducing the likelihood of injustice in the findings.

3.6 Data Collection

The research aimed to identify the essential components required to provide a valid representation of women in leadership. This question led the researcher to understand various types of sampling to ensure the recommendations of IPA were maintained. Purposive sampling, as mentioned by Barratt *et al.* (2015), "relies on the researcher's knowledge of the field and a good rapport with the targeted members," which, as indicated by Campbell *et al.* (2020), enables representation of the context. The study adopted a purposive sampling strategy, consistent with its qualitative and interpretivist research design. Purposive sampling was selected because the aim of the research was not statistical representation, but the identification of information-rich participants who possessed direct experience of leadership within India's automobile manufacturing industry. This approach is widely endorsed in qualitative leadership research, particularly when exploring complex, context-dependent phenomena such as gendered leadership experiences and authenticity.

Participants were selected based on clearly defined inclusion criteria. Women leaders were required to hold or have held managerial or leadership roles within automobile manufacturing organisations operating in India. This criterion ensured that participants had substantial experience navigating leadership in a male-dominated industrial environment. To enhance the depth and diversity of perspectives, the sample included participants from different organisational levels, functional areas, and types of automotive organisations. This diversity enabled the study to capture variations in leadership experience while remaining aligned with the research focus.

In addition to individual interviews with women leaders, focus group participants were purposively selected from teams reporting directly to women leaders. This sampling decision enabled the study to examine leadership experiences from both the leader and follower perspectives, thereby strengthening analytical depth and supporting triangulation. Participants in the focus groups were selected based on their direct working relationship with women leaders and their ability to reflect on leadership behaviours and organisational dynamics.

The sample size was determined using the principle of information power, whereby the adequacy of the sample depends on the richness and relevance of the data rather than numerical thresholds. Given the study's focused research aims, the specificity of the participant group, and the depth of the semi-structured interviews, the final sample was considered sufficient to generate robust analytical insights. Data collection continued until thematic saturation was evident, with no substantially new themes emerging from additional interviews.

This sampling strategy supports the study's methodological rigour by ensuring alignment between research aims, data collection methods, and analytical approach. Rather than seeking generalisability, the sampling design prioritises depth, contextual sensitivity, and credibility, consistent with qualitative research standards. Overall, the purposive and strategically diversified sampling approach adopted in this study is well-justified and appropriate for exploring women's leadership experiences within the Indian automobile manufacturing sector.

The researcher therefore chose to use purposive sampling, rather than a study of the public. Purposive sampling includes participants who can provide direct insight into the phenomenon being studied (Campbell *et al.*, 2020). The rationale for the selection stems from the need to align with the research perspective and the study's objectives. The strata (groups) are divided based on participants shared roles, such as women leaders and male colleagues within the automobile industry. The researcher aims to gather an information-rich sample while ensuring

that no one segment is championed, such as only women employees, but instead seeks to understand both women leaders and their male counterparts. This study will include five samples (the probable number, as determining the exact sample size at the design stage is difficult), and these samples will be used to understand the lived experiences of women in the automobile industry who have risen to leadership positions. As Grbich (1999) mentioned, it is tempting to champion one type of group, such as many studies done by feminist researchers advocating for the underdog; however, this study ensures a diversity of perspectives is included. To identify the organisations relevant to the study, a set of criteria has been developed for organisations.

Table 29: Organisation Criteria

The organisation must be in India
The organisation must have a manufacturing unit in India
The organisation must have women working in its factories
The organisation must be a passenger car manufacturer

Table 29 presents the organisational criteria applied in this study. It details the specific organisational characteristics considered during selection to ensure relevance to the Indian automobile industry. This table supports consistency and rigour in organisational sampling and contextual alignment of the research.

3.7 Data Analysis

This section of the study provides an overview of how the data collected will be analysed. Qualitative research employs various types of data analysis methods, including framework analysis, content analysis, discourse analysis, thematic analysis, and interpretive phenomenological analysis (IPA), among others (Lester, Cho, and Lochmiller, 2020).

Framework analysis is a structured analytical process that ensures a thorough and logical outcome, incorporating both logic and intuitive thinking (Ritchie *et al.*, 2002). However, this analysis is not suitable for this study, which requires a deep understanding of an emerging phenomenon, such as women in leadership. Additionally, it lacks a holistic view, as it is fragmented into themes that do not align with the requirements of this study. Content analysis supports interpreting context within texts by categorising them. One of the core benefits of this analysis is its ability to handle large amounts of data (Dhillon, 2016). However, this could also lead to contextual nuance, as overlooking the broader context within the content could result in a potential loss of meaning. Discourse analysis facilitates an understanding of the context in which language is used, offering rich insights into the cultural, societal, and political influences on communication (Wood and Kroger, 2000). However, the neglect of non-linguistic factors makes it unsuitable for this study.

Thematic analysis is relevant in qualitative research and is ideal for analysing large data sets (Nowell *et al.*, 2017). This analysis involves identifying themes within a data set and helps in examining the perspectives of different participants by highlighting similarities and differences (Braun and Clarke, 2006). The disadvantage of thematic analysis is the lack of literature on the structure for performing such an analysis (Roulston, 2001). As a novice researcher, using an analysis that is rarely acknowledged but widely used may pose a challenge in conducting a rigorous analysis when there is a lack of structure. The core goal of IPA is to describe the meaning of lived experiences, which is then interpreted in relation to the phenomenon of interest (Starks *et al.*, 2007). This study focuses on individuals who have experienced the phenomenon by observing participants in the environment where it has occurred. It involves a deep understanding of the lived experiences of participants, as in phenomenology, reality is grasped through experience (Sokolowski, 1999). The core of the analysis is to capture meaning through the essences of the experience gained (Stewart and Mickunas, 1974). Based on the

analysis of various methods, this study will utilise IPA, as it aligns with the use of in-depth interviews to identify significant statements from women leaders and their experiences within the automobile industry.

Based on the research goal, the question for IPA would be: how do women in leadership roles within the automobile industry make sense of their leadership roles? What has been their journey towards the top? These questions would be posed to a small sample of women (5) in leadership positions who have experienced being a leader in the automobile industry. The data would be collected through in-depth interviews as explained in the previous section. The audio-recorded interviews would be listened to and re-listened to in order to understand the descriptors, the type of language used, tone, and style of voice. Themes would then be clustered into categories and later developed into a narrative, which would be defined as the essence of the study, using verbatim quotes where required.

NVivo qualitative data analysis software (Houghton *et al.*, 2017) was used as a data management and analytical support tool to facilitate the systematic organisation, coding, and retrieval of qualitative data generated through interviews and focus group discussions. The use of NVivo supported transparency, consistency, and rigour in the analysis process, while interpretative decision-making remained firmly grounded in the principles of Interpretative Phenomenological Analysis (IPA).

All interview and focus group transcripts were imported into NVivo following verbatim transcription. An initial phase of open coding was conducted, during which transcripts were read repeatedly and coded line-by-line to capture significant statements, meanings, and experiential insights relevant to the research questions. NVivo was used to store and organise these initial codes, enabling efficient comparison across transcripts while preserving links to the original data.

As analysis progressed, related codes were clustered into broader conceptual categories within NVivo. This facilitated the identification of patterns, convergences, and divergences across participants' accounts, while maintaining sensitivity to individual experiences in line with IPA's idiographic orientation. NVivo's querying and node-organisation functions supported iterative refinement of codes and assisted in tracing how themes evolved across the dataset.

Higher-order thematic development was undertaken through interpretative engagement with the coded data rather than automated processes. NVivo was used to visualise relationships between themes and to support auditability of analytic decisions; however, the interpretation and meaning-making processes were conducted manually by the researcher through reflexive analysis and repeated engagement with the data.

NVivo also enabled the integration of interview and focus group data, supporting methodological triangulation by allowing themes to be examined across data sources. This facilitated comparison between leaders' accounts and collective perspectives expressed within focus groups, strengthening the credibility of the findings.

Overall, NVivo functioned as a supportive analytical tool rather than a substitute for interpretative analysis, enabling systematic data handling while preserving the depth, reflexivity, and contextual sensitivity required for phenomenological qualitative research

To enhance credibility and interpretation, this study will utilise respondent validation, as explained by Torrance (2012), which involves participants reviewing their previously provided data to verify accuracy. Allowing the participants to reflect on their answers reduces the researcher's bias, as it includes the participant in confirming the results (Birt *et al.*, 2016). The researcher chose respondent validation as it would improve the participation rate (Huybrechts *et al.*, 2011), and the participants' viewpoints would add additional value to this study. The researcher would review the emergent themes with the participants. A foreseeable challenge is

that participants may change their views; however, this could be addressed if respondent validation is conducted immediately after data collection as a second stage. This validation is crucial for this study, as it affords ownership to the participants and underscores the value their words bring to future policies and development for women in the industry. It gives them a sense of pride and responsibility; it also brings a sense of authenticity from the researcher's perspective, ensuring that the data collected is validated by the participants. Given that this study focuses on authentic leadership, this stage contributes to its authenticity. The entire process is illustrated in Figure 5.

Fig 5: IPA & Respondent Validation process

Source: Author's own

3.8 Ethical Considerations

Creating honest, transparent, and rigorous knowledge is what this study's integrity is founded on. Since this research is carried out within the institution of the University of the West of Scotland, the university's ethics, principles, and guidelines from the University's Ethics Committee (2019) have been adhered to. Research integrity has provided the framework for guiding this study's approach. As Knottnerus and Tugwell (2018) highlight, ethical considerations influence 'designing the study, research questions, consent method, and interpretation of results. Guillemin and Gillam (2004) describe two aspects of ethics:

"procedural and ethics in practice". At the beginning of this study, procedural ethics would be observed by seeking approval from the organisation's compliance and HR teams regarding research requirements. Once approved, written consent forms would be sent to participants before the interview. After receiving the written consent, a suitable time and place would be communicated to the participants via email. This allows participants to make an informed decision about their involvement and to understand the confidentiality terms.

Prior to conducting the direct interviews with the participants, the study would follow "ethics in practice", as this study involves interviewing women who will share their leadership journey. They could reveal vulnerability or moments of discomfort, and the researcher would decide on how far to probe the participant. The researcher chooses to acknowledge these dimensions in the ethical approaches and take stock under a concept developed by Mason (1996), termed reflexive research. The research, employing the critical reflexivity model, would not only adopt this process in the method but also with participants, by not only reporting the findings but also taking a step back and reflecting on my role as a researcher in this study. As defined by McGraw *et al.* (2000, p. 68), "Reflexivity is a process whereby researchers place themselves and their practices under scrutiny, acknowledging the ethical dilemmas that permeate the research process and impinge on the creation of knowledge". All methodologies described in this study would be submitted to UWS for ethical approval prior to data collection. UWS ethical principles, such as honesty, rigour, transparency, respect, and care, have been taken into consideration (University of the West of Scotland, 2020).

3.9 Conclusion

This chapter outlines the research methodology that will guide this study in achieving its aim and objectives. Using this methodology, the study can provide insights for women in middle managerial roles who aim to seek promotions into leadership roles with the support of sponsors.

As indicated by Rao *et al.* (2021), the lack of sponsorship has been directly linked to the underrepresentation of women in leadership positions. Martínez-Martínez *et al.* (2021, p. 2) found that “perceivers have female leaders in mind when prompted to think of authentic leadership. For women, this leadership is more congruent with their gender group”. This study aims to explore the potential of sponsors in enabling women to develop authentic leadership traits that enhance their identity.

CHAPTER FOUR: FINDINGS AND RESULTS

4.1. Introduction

The previous chapters extensively covered the literature through both narrative and systematic reviews of concepts and sub-concepts, along with the methods adopted for the study. This chapter will present the findings from the lead interviews and focus group discussions. The lead interviews involved 25 participants, and five focus group discussions were conducted across five different organisations ranked among the top original equipment manufacturing (OEM) plants in India. All participants in the lead interviews are assigned pseudonyms such as P1, P2, and so on, while the FGDs are referred to as FGD1, FGD2, etc., with the names of the companies remaining confidential. This approach was adopted to ensure adherence to the research's ethical guidelines. The chapter is divided into several subsections, namely, a summary of the lead interview participants, themes and a summary of the FGD participants

The above sections address the specific research questions and objectives highlighted in Chapter One. For emphasis, the same has been provided below:

Research Questions:

RQ 1: How do successful women leaders navigate and flourish in upholding their leadership in the automobile Industry?

RQ 2: What were some of the challenges they had to overcome internally?

RQ 3: How authenticity, leadership and gender could intersect in building a culture of sponsorships, advocating for women’s career advancement?

Research Objectives

Research objective 1: to identify the skills and traits that have contributed to women leaders’ success, how these skills/ traits were developed and in what manner a fresh approach could be created in empowering women leaders in the future.

Research objective 2: to investigate some of the challenges women face within the workplace and how these challenges could be reduced.

Research objective 3: to obtain comparative insight into how authenticity, leadership and gender intersect in creating sponsorship.

4.2. Summary of the participants

Table 30: Participant Demographic Details

Participants	Role	Department	Age	Region	Type	Overall experience	Automotive experience	Date of Interview
1	Deputy General Manager (DGM)	HR	47	South India	Former employee	27	3	12 th Oct 2024
2	General Manager (GM)	PR	53	South India	Former employee	31	12	19 th Oct 2024
3	General Manager (GM)	HR/Compliance	45	Iran	Repatriate	23	12	25 th Oct 2024
4	General Manager (GM)	PR	44	South India	Current	17	5	02 nd Jan 2025
5	Manager	Production	48	South India	Current	20	15	02 nd Jan 2025
6	Director	Legal	54	South India	Current	25	9	02 nd Jan 2025
7	Deputy Manager (DM)	Procurement	37	West India	Current	15	3	06 th Jan 2025
8	Assistant General Manager (AGM)	Production	41	West India	Current	20	7	06 th Jan 2025
9	Assistant General Manager (AGM)	Procurement	40	West India	Current	19	8	06 th Jan 2025
10	Deputy Manager (DM)	Production	26	West India	Current	4	4	06 th Jan 2025
11	Deputy Manager (DM)	Production	26	West India	Current	4	4	06 th Jan 2025
12	Senior Manager (SM)	Production	34	West India	Current	14	14	07 th Jan 2025
13	Manager	Production	34	West India	Current	13	13	07 th Jan 2025
14	Deputy Manager (DM)	Production	34	West India	Current	13	13	08 th Jan 2025

15	Manager	Production	25	West India	Current	6	6	08 th Jan 2025
16	Senior Manager	IT	44	West India	Current	18	18	08 th Jan 2025
17	Deputy General Manager (DGM)	Production	44	West India	Current	19.5	18.5	08 th Jan 2025
18	General Manager (GM)	Production	44	West India	Current	21	20	13 th Jan 2025
19	Senior Manager (SM)	Production	29	West India	Current	6	6	13 th Jan 2025
20	Senior Manager (SM)	Production	34	West India	Current	12	12	13 th Jan 2025
21	Senior Manager (SM)	HR	35	West India	Current	13	5	14 th Jan 2025
22	Chief Diversity Officer (CDO)	DE&I	47	West India	Current	30	10	14 th Jan 2025
23	Director Diversity	DE&I	43	South India	Current	20	8	17 th Jan 2025
24	Deputy General Manager (DGM)	HR	43	West India	Current	20	16	22 nd Feb 2025
25	Manager	HR	35	West India	Current	10	7	25 th Feb 2025

Table 30 presents the demographic details of the interview participants. It provides contextual information regarding participants’ roles, experience, and organisational positioning. This table supports transparency and enhances the credibility of the qualitative findings by situating participant perspectives within their professional context.

To get a panoramic view, the data collection was conducted in two parts. The first part of the data collection focused on women leaders who had resigned from the automotive industry in India. The interviews took place via Microsoft Teams. The second part was conducted with current women leaders of the core manufacturing units from five major brands in India, including an Indian multinational automotive company, a joint venture alliance plant in India, and three multinational foreign car brand manufacturers operating in India (Fig. 6).

Figure 6: Lead interview data collection phases

Figure 6 illustrates the phased approach adopted for lead interview data collection in this study. The figure is intended to provide a visual overview of the sequencing, mode, and contextual

constraints associated with the interview process, thereby enhancing transparency of the research design.

The lead interview questions remained the same, with the similar criterion of participants having worked in leadership positions within the automobile sector. The participants were first contacted via email with details of the interview, consent form, and interview guidelines. Once they had accepted, a suitable time for the interview was decided, and meeting invites via Teams were shared. Three participants were selected for this set of interviews, which included two Indian women and one expatriate from Iran who worked in the Indian automobile core manufacturing unit. All the women had a master's degree, either in science, engineering, or human resources. The women were from HR (Human Resources), Production, and PR (Public Relations) functions. They had previously worked within the manufacturing units of two companies that are among India's top automotive manufacturing units. The participants' ages ranged from the early 30s to the late 50s. The expatriate participant was deputed on a special project assignment in India, and her perspectives added a unique dimension to this study. Visual cues were very evident during certain questions that were pertinent to this inquiry. Though five participants were initially invited for the interview, three interviews were successfully completed, while the other two could not attend due to current project constraints.

The study later included lead interviews with women currently employed within the automobile industry. The majority of the interviews were directly facilitated at the organisations where the participants worked, with three interviews facilitated via Teams due to time constraints. As part of the study, five well-known local and multinational manufacturing units participated. Table 30 indicates the participants' demographics. All departments from the automobile passenger car manufacturers have been represented, with further details provided in Table 31.

Table 31: Participant department representation

Department	Percentage representation
Production	48%
Human Resources	20%
Procurement/Supply Chain	8%
Public Relations/Communications	8%
Diversity and Inclusion	8%
Compliance/Legal	4%

Table 31 presents the departmental representation of interview participants. It illustrates the range of functional areas represented within the sample. This table supports the credibility and richness of the findings by demonstrating diversity in organisational roles and perspectives.

This demographic information provided essential context to support the findings derived from 25 professionals working in the Indian automobile passenger car original equipment manufacturer (OEM) sector (Smith *et al.*, 2018).

Figure 7: Demographic profile of participants

Initially, the interviews were coded manually. After each day of interviews, the transcripts were analysed, allowing time before progressing to the next set of participants for the following day. Transcripts were uploaded using the software package NVivo 12 for further analysis. The QSR-NVivo was used as a tool for coding data. Prior to the study, the researcher read books on the software (Gibbs and Bryman, 2002; Bazeley and Jackson, 2013; Flowers and Larkin, 2022) and attended online training on the software's use. NVivo 12 was utilised not only for coding

but also for data management and the final thesis write-up. Each interview was coded and compared with the initial manual coding completed during the collection process. Coding the interviews with the 25 participants to compare aided constant comparative analysis techniques, helping the researcher stay consistent in highlighting key points during coding. The open coding yielded 69 codes and 8 themes, as shown in Figure 8.

Using NVivo 12 software, the researcher employed word count queries (Figure 8) and source code data as additional tools to identify selective codes within the data. To analyse the depth of the codes and the number of vignettes assigned to a set of codes, or a group of open codes, selective codes emerged from the data. Theoretical coding was derived from the relationships within and across codes, utilising mind mapping to facilitate the analysis. When building the mind map, each time a vignette was linked with a code, it was reviewed for relationships with other codes. Constant comparison was used to ensure that no single code was given more weight than others. For example, every participant was asked about their journey into the automotive sector, but not all were asked why they transitioned to the auto industry. The latter was asked about why they transitioned, as the node change and opportunity arose from Participant 5. Another example was when participants with an engineering background worked in HR departments and were asked the reason for this transition. This question was specifically posed to Participants 21 and 25.

At this stage, the visibility of word frequency through the word frequency query (Figure 8) was helpful. These words formed the code structure. The ease of retrieving data to check coded segments, as well as the ability to rename, merge, split, and group codes, were all crucial. Words with high frequency, such as leadership, time, and women, were all part of the code creation.

Figure 8: Tree map showing word frequency query results.

Frequency Codes							
Name	Files	References	Created On	Created By	Modified On	Modified By	
Acceptance		11	38	01/03/2025 19:15	B	08/03/2025 20:49	B
Authentic		20	54	01/03/2025 19:13	B	11/03/2025 10:10	B
Automotive Industry		21	86	01/03/2025 19:12	B	11/03/2025 10:10	B
Bias		7	19	01/03/2025 19:15	B	10/03/2025 20:13	B
Boss		21	107	01/03/2025 19:12	B	11/03/2025 10:11	B
Capability		16	28	01/03/2025 19:16	B	11/03/2025 10:12	B
Challenge		20	64	01/03/2025 19:14	B	11/03/2025 10:12	B
Change		18	72	01/03/2025 19:13	B	11/03/2025 10:13	B
Colleague		22	48	01/03/2025 19:14	B	11/03/2025 10:14	B
Confident		18	35	01/03/2025 19:15	B	11/03/2025 10:14	B
Consistent		4	4	01/03/2025 19:17	B	09/03/2025 19:26	B
Contribute		11	17	01/03/2025 19:17	B	10/03/2025 20:30	B
Conversations		9	22	01/03/2025 19:16	B	10/03/2025 20:32	B
Counselling		3	4	01/03/2025 19:17	B	09/03/2025 19:27	B
Culture		18	61	01/03/2025 19:14	B	11/03/2025 10:15	B
Diversity		13	33	01/03/2025 19:15	B	10/03/2025 20:35	B
Equality		6	9	01/03/2025 19:17	B	08/03/2025 19:42	B
Ethics		6	8	01/03/2025 19:15	B	09/03/2025 20:01	B
Experience		19	105	01/03/2025 19:13	B	11/03/2025 10:16	B

From the above word frequency results, it was evident which words stood out, allowing them to be used as codes for the study. Words such as mentoring, mentors, and mentorship were merged under the code "mentorship". Similarly, words such as "learning" and "learnt" were merged under the code "learning", thereby reducing the 150 most frequently used words into 46 codes.

The initial coding process generated 46 codes, from which themes and subthemes were identified that related to the research questions, ensuring a clear alignment between the findings and the research focus. Research question one examines how women succeed, with codes such as navigating leadership, authenticity, and inclusion. Research question two addresses internal barriers, with codes such as confidence, struggles, work-life balance, and overcoming bias. Finally, research question three investigates authentic leadership for women's career advancement, including codes such as sponsorship, mentorship, and inclusive leadership.

The forty-six codes have been grouped into eleven major themes, which are further subdivided into subthemes. The codes have been grouped into four major categories, reflecting the progressive leadership journey that women have made within a male-dominated industry. It follows a logical flow from internal developments to external navigation and finally towards

growth and support. The themes have been mapped under four categories, namely intrapersonal leadership formation, external barriers and organisational realities, leadership growth and advancement, and support mechanisms and relational capital. The discussion integrates participants lived experience quotes.

Figure 9-Themes subthemes with categories

The eleven themes were consolidated into four overarching meta-categories to enable a broader understanding of the data. This categorisation allowed for the identification of interconnections at a macro level, as illustrated in Figure 9, and the emergence of thematic triads at a more granular level, depicted in Figure 10. Notably, the meta-categories themselves were closely interconnected. To effectively navigate external barriers and internal organisational realities, women leaders must engage in intrapersonal leadership development, anchored in authentic

leadership and the formation of a strong professional identity. This intrapersonal grounding facilitated their leadership growth and advancement, ultimately enabling them to build the support systems necessary to succeed in a male-dominated industry (Adams, 2023; Guillemin and Gillam, 2004).

Figure 10: Interconnection between four meta-categories

4.3 Category A: Intrapersonal leadership Formation

This category captures the intrapersonal processes through which women leaders construct and sustain their leadership identity, encompassing personal beliefs, values, emotions, and self-concept prior to and during leadership enactment. Rather than perceiving leadership as a function of positional authority, participants described leadership as grounded in intrinsic worth, ethical self-regulation, and ongoing self-reflection.

Participants emphasised the importance of being recognised for their contributions rather than their formal titles. As articulated by P1, feeling valued beyond the role was central to her sense of career progression. Interpretively, this reflects a form of identity-based leadership legitimacy, where self-worth and leadership confidence are internally anchored rather than

derived from organisational hierarchy. This finding aligns with authentic leadership scholarship that foregrounds internalised values and intrinsic motivation as foundations of leadership effectiveness (Martínez-Martínez *et al.*, 2021).

Family values and early upbringing emerged as formative influences shaping leadership behaviour. Participants P12, P15, P18, and P22 highlighted how family norms informed their ethical standards, confidence, and decision-making approaches within corporate environments. Theoretically, this suggests that intrapersonal leadership formation precedes organisational socialisation, reinforcing the view that leadership authenticity is rooted in pre-existing identity structures rather than developed solely through professional experience (Adams, 2023). Leadership, in this sense, is experienced as an extension of the self rather than a role adopted in response to organisational expectations.

Despite strong self-awareness, women leaders reported persistent internal and external questioning of their competence within male-dominated industries. Accounts from P17, P3, P1, P2, and P14 illustrate a continual need to prove knowledge and capability, often through ongoing learning and over-preparation. This pattern can be interpreted as gendered identity labour, where women leaders must actively manage legitimacy in contexts structured by masculine norms. Rather than reflecting individual insecurity, these narratives reveal structural conditions that compel constant self-validation and reflexivity, consistent with ethical and reflexive challenges identified in gendered organisational contexts (Guillemin and Gillam, 2004).

Emotional intelligence, empathy, and ethical decision-making were consistently described as integral to leadership practice. While these qualities were reflected across all participants, P6 and P3, both working within legal functions, particularly emphasised ethical judgement as central to their leadership roles. Interpretively, ethical decision-making functions as both a

moral orientation and a leadership stabiliser, enabling women leaders to navigate complexity while maintaining authenticity. This supports interpretive perspectives that view leadership as a meaning-making process shaped by values and relational awareness (Smith and Larkin, 2009).

Participants also described consciously evaluating the alignment between their personal values and organisational culture before fully committing to leadership roles. Narratives from P10, P12, and P16 demonstrate how autonomy and trust enabled creativity, confidence, and engagement. Autonomy can therefore be understood as a validating condition, allowing leaders to enact leadership in ways congruent with their values. This finding reinforces arguments that empowerment enhances leadership effectiveness by enabling authentic self-expression rather than compliance-driven performance (Rao *et al.*, 2021; Braun and Clarke, 2006).

However, persistent organisational biases, particularly maternity-related discrimination, were reported to undermine leadership sustainability. Participants P24 and P16 described the emotional toll of such bias on their wellbeing. These experiences highlight the fragility of leadership legitimacy for women when gendered assumptions intersect with life-course events, necessitating renewed efforts to prove commitment and competence (Thomas, 2021). Organisation-wide biases thus contribute to an ongoing cycle of justification and self-surveillance (Gibson, 2024).

Despite these challenges, participants acknowledged gradual organisational shifts towards more inclusive leadership models. Some organisations were perceived as increasingly recognising the positive influence of women leaders on ethical practice, decision-making, and workplace culture (Larkin and Eatough, 2011). This aligns with broader transitions away from rigid, authoritative leadership models towards more inclusive and adaptive forms (Nowell *et*

al., 2017). While resistance remains, participants' accounts suggest growing recognition of the long-term value of diverse leadership teams (Birt *et al.*, 2016).

Overall, the findings indicate that intrapersonal leadership formation among women leaders is an ongoing interpretive process, shaped by early identity formation, ethical self-concept, and sustained reflexivity in response to gendered organisational contexts. This category extends leadership theory by foregrounding the internal work required to maintain authenticity and legitimacy within structurally unequal environments.

Following this category, the subsequent sections present the themes and sub-themes derived from the qualitative data. These themes were developed through a systematic and iterative analytic process supported by NVivo qualitative data analysis software. NVivo was used to organise, manage, and interrogate the dataset, enabling clear structuring of themes and sub-themes and supporting transparency in the presentation of findings.

Fig 11: Themes and subthemes using NVivo

Name	Files	Referen
Theme 4 Bias	9	162
Personal strategies for handlin	10	147
Theme 5 Leadership Development	19	307
Breaking career barriers and se	22	344
Continuous self-development,	18	278
Theme 6 Professional Growth	12	184
Strategic career planning and	6	88
Theme 7 Building Support Systems	20	308
Creating a strong support syst	20	308
Seeking allies and advocates w	3	66
Theme 8 Mentorship in Career	11	127
The role of mentorship, and ne	13	180
Theme 9 Navigating Organization	20	311
Dealing with gender stereotyp	9	162
Strategies to create inclusive w	13	213

Name	Files	Referen
Theme 1 Authentic Leadership	22	344
Developing confidence, authen	14	231
How self-perception influences	13	190
Theme 10 Gendered Expectations	14	199
Challenging gendered expecta	14	199
Theme 11 Navigating Leadership i	15	227
Advocating for diversity and in	12	172
Overcoming systemic barriers	8	102
Transforming male-dominated	6	123
Theme 2 Professional Identity	12	184
Balancing personal values with	16	283
Theme 3 Overcoming Internal Cha	13	205
Managing emotional resilience	16	253
Self-doubt, imposter syndrome	13	191
Theme 4 Bias	9	162
Personal strategies for handlin	10	147

4.3.1 Theme One: Authentic leadership: This theme explores how women leaders cultivate their internal sense of identity as leaders, grounded in values, confidence, resilience, and authenticity. All twenty-five participants emphasised the crucial role personal values played in fostering belief in their abilities. These values not only strengthened their ethical behaviour but also boosted their self-confidence, shaping their leadership style and helping them develop a professional identity that enabled them to navigate internal challenges.

4.3.1.1 Subtheme: Developing confidence, authenticity, and ethical leadership

The overarching concept throughout the interviews has been mainly demonstrated through self-awareness and value-driven leadership. The code “value” was mentioned 20 times,

emphasising its connection with self-awareness, leadership, and organisational values. Several participants expressed these aspects in their interviews.

Women leaders actively align their personal values with their leadership identity, shaping their decisions and interactions. P1 illustrates this link by showing she felt most valued when recognised for her intrinsic worth and contribution rather than simply her role.

“So, the role I was playing with the organisation, it was a short-term role that was the best time of my life, because my boss respected me for who I am, what value I bring to the table” p1.

Several participants attribute their leadership mindset to values ingrained in their upbringing, shaping their confidence and initiatives. P25 highlights how her values naturally led her to take on leadership opportunities.

“The value system the way I have been brought up, so I always see myself as a leader, so I always take initiatives, I always grab opportunities “p25.

P1 reinforces that leadership is tied to behaviours learned during childhood.

“I believe leadership is awesome dependent it also comes from the values that you are brought up with at home, because that’s what values and behaviours are, ingrained when you’re a child” p1.

Despite their strong values and self-awareness, women leaders in the automobile sector often find their worth questioned. P23 shares her experience of feeling intimidated when her value to the organisation is questioned, reflecting the external pressures women face in proving their leadership credibility. P6 describes the persistent internal questioning about her contributions. Similarly, p22 questions the perceived necessity of women’s contributions in a historically male-dominated industry, highlighting the unexplored potential women can bring. This

illustrates how authentic leadership is challenged in a male-dominated environment where women feel the constant pressure to defend their worth, are expected to justify their contributions, and face barriers in fully realising and demonstrating their potential.

“I recall those years where I mean was literally difficult and challenging for me because every now and then I was questioned in terms of my competency in terms of what value I add to the organisation, and I felt intimidated” p23.

“It’s where to tap things, where to get the information and how do you use the information for the organisations benefit, how do you add value? This is where people are going to look at you right?” p6.

“What value are we adding if the business is already running well? The idea is that you haven’t even unlocked the potential. I realise that women are a terrific value add to the organisation” p22.

Women leaders also evaluate the alignment of personal and corporate values, which impacts their commitment and engagement with an organisation. This was explained by P2 and P4, who also highlighted how she valued the liberty that an organisation gave her.

“So, I do notice if the company’s value aligns with my values, I tend to be positive towards the organisation, I actually look at the value the organisations represent” p2.

“I find that I have been given a lot of liberty to be kind of do new things. And those are like things I really value” p4.

This illustrates how organisations that prioritise value-driven leadership and grant autonomy to women leaders are more likely to see higher retention, job satisfaction, and leadership effectiveness, gradually unlocking the potential women bring to the industry. As Srivastava and Dhar (2019) discuss, the framework of an authentic leader is rooted in behaviour based on

core values. The findings from these interviews confirm that women leaders develop self-awareness through personal values, face external challenges in proving their worth, and seek alignment between personal and organisational values to enhance their leadership capabilities.

4.3.1.2 Sub Theme: How self-perception influences leadership style

Despite the challenges women leaders faced in demonstrating their value, their dedication to improving their leadership effectiveness without adhering to traditional masculine traits was clear. They adopted a balanced leadership style that incorporated empathy, recognised non-acceptance, promoted collaboration, and showed decisiveness. P1 and P2 highlight leadership grounded in empathy and human connection. Instead of adopting an authoritative and inflexible approach, women leaders focused on the human side of leadership by valuing empathy and professionalism. P1 highlights the significance of emotional intelligence in leadership.

“The most important is acceptance, awareness and knowledge. These things automatically drive the rest of it, and I think human behaviour standpoint would be empathy and sensitivity” p1.

Similarly, p2 links professionalism with emotional awareness.

“It has to do with the human side of it, empathy, by professionalism I mean you should look at work delivery at the same time you should have empathy” p2.

Empathy also played a role in understanding workplace dynamics and leadership decision as p8 explains:

“My boss has given me additional responsibilities that may be logical also or it may be too much for me also, but I need to understand his perspective also. Sometimes you need to look the other side and empathise” p8.

These examples underscore how women leaders skilfully integrate emotional intelligence into their leadership practice, striking a balance between delivering on performance expectations and adopting a human-centred approach. They demonstrate an acute awareness of the importance of empathy, active listening, and relationship-building in fostering effective leadership. A recurring theme among the participants was the ongoing challenge of gaining acceptance within the male-dominated automotive industry. Rather than reacting with resistance or disillusionment, these women acknowledged this reality early in their careers, which enabled them to develop resilience and remain steadfast in their leadership journeys. Participant 1 reflected on how this early recognition of the industry's dynamics empowered her to persevere, adapt, and sustain her role with determination and a clear sense of purpose.

“I think the acceptance to women is still very low, Acceptance is never easy, but from an HR standpoint, I think that’s the only way not to give up” p1.

P2 emphasises the importance of mental preparedness.

“Only 50% is going to accept you, 50% is not so you have to live with that, you have to live with the idea that your gone be criticised and scrutinised, all the time” p2.

Women leaders have encountered scepticism and ridicule for remaining true to their authentic leadership styles, particularly when these positions conflict with conventional gender roles.

P24 shares her difficult experience during pregnancy, highlighting the industry’s struggle to accept women’s realities:

“They just don’t, they won’t accept that authenticity. I had a very tough time with the organisation, very tough time, so many times I was mocked at, my boss would negotiate about my maternity and how many ultrasounds I should be taking, he would make sure I don’t leave

the organisation on time, while I use to be vomiting he would give me 5 minutes and ask me to come back” p24.

Similarly, p16 describes how maternity leave was perceived as an indulgence rather than a necessity.

“Perspective from a maternity leave, they think they are going on enjoyment holiday. They don’t truly accept this” p16.

These experiences illustrate how systematic bias impacts women leadership journeys, reinforcing the need for organisational culture change.

P8 attributes this resistance to unconscious bias.

“So, from the very start I think, the industry takes time to accept you as a lady, there are unconscious bias” p8.

Despite these barriers, women leaders remained authentic to their values, demonstrating resilience, commitment, and self-development as their primary tools for success.

P9 explains how staying true to herself ensures strong leadership.

“I am a very authentic person, so what I believe in, is whatever I commit to, I deliver” p9.

P15 emphasis self-improvement as a path to eventual acceptance.

“Developing yourself and one day they will accept a person who can learn. I think people would be accepted for that” p15.

Interestingly, some organisations began recognising the positive impact of women's leadership as seen by the example of P21.

“They themselves realised that by brining women there was a lot of positive changes, the language used changed, a lot more discipline when women where employed” p21.

This suggests that although resistance exists, the long-term benefits of diversity in leadership are becoming evident. A key factor in women leaders’ ability to remain authentic was the presence of strong support networks, whether through their organisations or personal development teams.

P3 credits her success to an organisation that actively supported female leadership:

“What is important to be successful is support, you can’t be a successful leader, just by yourself, for me my company was my supportive of female leadership” p3.

Similarly, p23 compares leadership to running a marathon, emphasising the need for a strong team.

“You cannot run the marathon alone, you need to have people around, strong and positive people around you, my team, I made a great support team” p23.

This highlights how women leaders strategically built networks of allies, mentors, and sponsors, recognising the importance of surrounding themselves with individuals who can offer encouragement, guidance, and advocacy. These support systems played a vital role in helping them navigate the complex challenges of leadership within a traditionally male-dominated industry. For these women, embracing empathy, fostering acceptance, and staying committed to authenticity greatly enhanced their leadership impact even in environments where support was limited or inconsistent. At organisational level, providing structural support mechanisms and actively addressing unconscious bias are key steps towards enabling women to realise their full leadership potential. For the industry as a whole, recognising the long-term value of

women's leadership can act as a catalyst for meaningful organisational change, promoting a more inclusive culture and a broader acceptance of authentic, value-driven leadership styles.

Women leaders who lead authentically promote inclusivity, transparency, and ethical decision-making, fostering a working environment where diverse perspectives are valued. Their leadership influences industry culture by challenging traditional norms and ensuring a more ethical, inclusive and adaptive workplace.

While KPI's are essential in organisations, women leaders emphasise that leadership should extend beyond numerical targets and encourage deeper reflection to shape a more inclusive organisational culture.

"You have your KPI's that drive you, but they should not be the only metrics. Whatever you do, you must ask the 5why's and 1 H, whatever you do you have to ask that question. Why you want to do it? What are you going to do? where are you going to do it? how are you going to do it? As long as you have the answers to these questions then you realise your being inclusive" p1.

The automobile industry carries historical biases and rigid perceptions that can hinder progress. Women leaders recognise the need to break away from outdated norms and embrace authenticity in shaping organisational culture. P2 urges the industry to shed its traditional mindset to create an open and progressive work environment.

"I think the automobile industry first must get rid of its baggage; they have a certain perception. The culture of the organisation I think needs to be authentic" p2.

However, authenticity does not mean rigidity. P23 emphasises the need for a balance between staying true to oneself and adapting to the organisation's culture.

“You have to tweak yourself, your style with the different organisations and its culture but at the same time you cannot lose your authenticity” p23.

This suggests that organisational culture should be a dynamic space, allowing leaders to stay true to their values while aligning with company goals.

Women leaders place a strong emphasis on ethical decision making which directly influences workplace culture.

P5 defines authenticity in leadership as taking responsibility for decisions and standing by them.

“I am very brave and bold in taking a decision and whatever I am standing on, I don’t go back on it. This is both my strength and weakness” p5.

Similarly, P4, who leads communications in her organisation, highlights how personal integrity and work ethics drive leadership impact.

“And you know I am not even going to be held accountable because managements priority is selling cars. No one is going to come and ask a communication person what did you deliver? i can get away with my task but my work ethics will not allow me” p4.

These insights reflect the concept of ethical leadership as described by Iszatt-White Et al (2019), which positions ethical leadership as a fundamental component of authentic leadership.

The ability to influence organisational culture ethically and transparently is crucial in creating an environment where values are prioritised alongside organisational objectives.

Women leaders can strengthen their leadership identity through intentional self-reflection, allowing them to gain deeper insight into their values, strengths, and areas for growth. Actively engaging with mentors and sponsors further supports their professional journey, offering guidance, constructive feedback, and access to opportunities that might otherwise remain out

of reach. Building resilience is essential, and this is often achieved through a commitment to continuous learning, professional development, and cultivating strategic networks that provide both practical support and emotional encouragement. By practising emotional intelligence and adhering to principles of ethical leadership, women enhance their capacity to influence others and establish credibility in decision-making processes.

At the organisational level, integrating value-driven leadership principles is crucial. This includes the creation of leadership development programmes that centre on authenticity, self-awareness, and emotional competence. Human resource policies must be reimaged to support women from the early stages of their careers, introducing structured mentorship initiatives, promoting flexible working arrangements, and ensuring fair and unbiased maternity policies. Companies must go beyond traditional key performance indicators (KPIs) to develop a culture of accountability, one that embraces inclusivity, ethical conduct, and holistic leadership evaluations.

To drive real change, organisations must challenge outdated paradigms of leadership that favour conformity and hierarchy, and instead embrace authentic leadership models grounded in inclusivity, values, and ethics. Industry associations play a critical role in advocating for policies that increase women's representation across all functions, particularly in male-dominated areas such as plant maintenance and production. Furthermore, industry-wide diversity and leadership training initiatives should be implemented to dismantle unconscious biases and foster inclusive, supportive leadership cultures.

Theme one and its related sub-themes revealed how women leaders navigated resistance by embracing acceptance, demonstrating that authenticity, although often met with challenges, was central to their leadership journey. Participants highlighted the ongoing bias faced during maternity and the resilience needed to continue leading despite systemic resistance. Their

success was frequently supported by strong support systems and influenced by the prevailing organisational culture, which could either impede or promote their leadership development. These insights collectively emphasise the complex interplay between individual agency, structural support, and cultural context in shaping women's leadership experiences in the automotive industry.

These accounts illustrate that intrapersonal leadership formation among the participants is deeply rooted in ongoing self-reflection and identity negotiation. Rather than describing leadership as a fixed set of traits, participants frame their leadership development as an evolving internal process shaped by personal values, self-awareness, and contextual challenges. This suggests that leadership formation operates at an intrapersonal level before it is enacted interpersonally, reinforcing the importance of internal sense-making in leadership practice.

From a theoretical perspective, these findings align with interpretivist and authentic leadership perspectives that emphasise self-awareness as a foundational component of authentic leadership. Participants' narratives indicate that authenticity is not merely expressed through behaviour, but is actively constructed through reflection on personal experiences, values, and gendered expectations. In the context of a male-dominated industry, this intrapersonal work appears to function as a mechanism through which women leaders reconcile professional authority with personal identity.

4.3.2 Theme 2: Professional Identity

This theme explores how women leaders incorporate their personal values with professional expectations. It highlights critical aspects of the ingrained authentic values that women bring into the workplace and how these integrate with the expectations of the various leadership roles they occupy. Among the twenty-five women interviewed, 11 emphasised the positive impact

of personal values on their authenticity within leadership roles, which in turn guided ethical decision-making and actions. This balancing act between personal values and professional expectations resulted in teams feeling more motivated, with the leader remaining anchored and resilient during times of uncertainty, both in their professional responsibilities and personal lives.

4.3.2.1 Sub-theme: Balancing personal values with professional expectations

The development of professional identity, especially for women leaders in the automotive industry, is closely linked to balancing personal values with professional expectations.

P1 reflected on one of her most positive professional experiences, underlining how her leader's respect for her personal values significantly impacted her sense of belonging and effectiveness at work:

“One of the best experiences of my life was with this French boss who respected me for who I am and valued what I brought to the table” P1.

She further reiterated the critical role of ingrained values in leadership:

“Leadership is awesome, dependent it also comes from the values you are brought up with at home, because that's what values and behaviours are ingrained when you're a child and very difficult to change” P1.

P1 also offered a thoughtful insight on how leaders must maintain flexibility to meet professional demands but cautioned against compromising one's core values:

“Leadership is about being who you are, you might have to compromise here and there but as long as it does not compromise on your values” P1.

Summarising her stance, P1 advised future leaders to remain anchored in their values while contributing constructively to organisational goals:

“You have to pick up the best, there will always be people who will pull you down, you should just let that go and focus on what you can learn and how you can add value” P1.

P2 examined values through a broader lens, emphasising how alignment between personal and organisational values enhances positive engagement. Using a consumer-oriented example, she remarked:

“The more we know a company does certain things that align with your personal values, you tend to be more positive towards the organisation. As an example, using ecofriendly products if this aligns with your values you tend to buy that product. You would actually look at their values that the organisations represent” P2

She elaborated on how her family-instilled values translated into workplace ethics and creativity:

“I come from, you know, certainly brought up with certain values and ethics. You step out into the world and think some of it is not necessary. So, I think having worked around the country I think it’s good to mix and match and pick the best and see what works for you and create something new out of it” P2

P3 underscored how embracing diversity and valuing differences are core aspects of leadership effectiveness:

“The value for me is in who they are, and that is diversity. To like differences, unless you understand the value of being different it’s difficult to penetrate into leadership” P3

P23 offered an alternate perspective, explaining how her values were frequently questioned, which initially intimidated her but ultimately strengthened her resolve and leadership courage:

“So those years where I mean was literally difficult and challenging for me because every now and then I was questioned in terms of what value I bring to the organisation. I felt intimidated,

when I use to be invited for meetings, or outbound programs, there where eyebrows raised. They I mean always had a question mark on their foreheads that you know whether she will deliver or not? So those were very challenging years of my career, but then you know I took this positively, I developed myself during those years, I had that managerial courage” P23.

P25 provided a nuanced interpretation, highlighting how personality plays a key role in balancing personal values with dynamic team environments:

“For me, it’s more about myself, but then you know there are dynamic changes, so the way one leader treats everybody in the team may not be the same with the other leader, the dynamics of the team changes, but for me you know it’s all down to your personality” P25

P4 and P6 offered distinctive viewpoints on the values that mattered to them in their leadership roles. P6 highlighted autonomy as central to her leadership identity:

“So, I have been given a lot of liberty to kind of do new things, and those are the things that I really valued” P4.

Meanwhile, P6 underscored the value of shared understanding and communication at work:

“When you talk to somebody who shares the same values, similar to what you have it brings out an excellent experience” P6.

P11 took a definitive stance, arguing that the value she brings should be self-evident through her contributions:

“I think they should know my values, if not they will realise the value at some point of time” P11.

Lastly, P22 questioned the necessity of women justifying their values in the workplace, contending that these should be self-evident and naturally integrated:

“Why should I justify what value women bring” p22.

Across participant narratives, it is clear that the interaction between personal values and professional expectations plays a key role in shaping the professional identity of women leaders. Although organisational cultures and leadership environments varied, participants consistently highlighted the importance of staying true to intrinsic values as a basis for genuine leadership. This alignment not only improved ethical decision-making but also built resilience, credibility, and motivation within their teams. However, when organisational expectations or cultural biases challenged these values, participants managed these tensions either by asserting their boundaries, adapting flexibly without abandoning core principles, or, in some cases, seeking different roles. Therefore, balancing personal values with professional expectations appeared as a dynamic, ongoing process, essential for maintaining authentic and effective leadership in the Indian automotive industry.

4.3.3 Theme 3: Overcoming internal challenges

This theme examines how women leaders overcame internal challenges to ascend to leadership positions. These challenges include imposter syndrome, gender norms that fostered self-doubt, and stress. However, the theme reveals how these women conquered these obstacles to become the leaders they are today. Out of the twenty-five women leaders, each shared unique challenges they faced and how these challenges played a pivotal role in their personal growth. All twenty-five leaders demonstrated how they leveraged these challenges to drive their own development and achieve success.

4.3.3.1 Subtheme: Self-doubt, imposter syndrome and internalised Gender norms

This theme highlights the deep-rooted internal challenges and biases that women in leadership face, particularly in a male-dominated industry. These challenges stem from workplace biases,

stereotypical mindsets and personal experiences, requiring women to develop resilience, confidence and strategic coping mechanisms to navigate their careers successfully.

Women struggle with preconceived notions about what roles they can or cannot take on. These gendered industry perceptions create invisible barriers that women constantly challenge within the industry.

P1 highlights that certain industries and functions are still considered for women, limiting opportunities.

“I don't know globally how they look at it but at least in India they will say, ok this particular industry is for women and in that industry this particular function is for women, and in that function these roles are for women, so I was fighting against this mindset” p1.

P3 talks about reverse discrimination where a leader denied women any privileges believing equality meant treating them exactly as men. Though this is progressive in nature the participant mentioned at the stage where women were still not in equal proportion treating them equally would not be the right way to follow.

“I remembered because I heard that a few times from this senior leader about reverse discrimination, his mindset that women should not be given any privileges, which I did not agree to cause women were not in equal situation and needed some extra privileges” p3.

P23 and p24 describe lack of progressive thinking in manufacturing and the clan like mindset resisting change.

“I feel that you know it's still way too traditional ok, people do not have that mindset. Progressive mindset, because they are wired in that way, it's more to do with manufacturing” p23.

“The automobile industry mindset change has to happen, which has not happened, anybody who shakes the system would be challenged by clans within” p24.

One of the ways women leaders have learned to cope with the pressures of a male-dominated industry is by quietly, yet powerfully, pushing back against rigid gender norms not through confrontation, but by consistently proving their worth. They build credibility day by day, not only by mastering their roles with skill and determination but also by showing resilience in the face of ongoing scepticism. Many have taken it a step further, using their own journeys to advocate for broader change, encouraging a shift in mindset at the leadership level and across the industry as a whole.

Yet, despite the growing number of organisations that promote diversity and inclusion, bias still lingers, often in subtle but deeply embedded ways. The evaluation of women’s competence remains fraught with unspoken doubts. As Participant 25 reflected, while companies may outwardly strive for inclusivity, there are still leaders who quietly question whether women are truly up to the task. This quiet resistance, more difficult to challenge than overt discrimination, makes the road to leadership all the more complex but also all the more meaningful for those determined to walk it.

“We do a lot of things to be an inclusive workplace, but then it all comes down to the mindset. As HR we do include women, but then you know there are a few leaders who still have this mindset is she able to do? is she capable, or what are her future plans? Will she part of the organisation, so yes lots of work needs to be done” p25.

P13 expresses frustration at how efforts to change mindsets are often undermined.

“They have that mindset, so someone who is coming to change this, it’s not going to happen, thereby destroying this culture” p13.

From these experiences, it becomes clear that one of the key ways women leaders cope with the pressures of leadership is by consistently demonstrating excellence. Rather than demanding recognition, they earn it through a steady commitment to delivering high-quality work, gradually building the credibility needed to thrive in environments where their capabilities are often under scrutiny. Alongside this, many have found strength through the support of senior leaders, those who not only recognised their potential but actively advocated for them, opening doors through sponsorship and pushing organisations to confront the unconscious biases that continue to shape hiring and promotion decisions.

What stood out, however, was the contrast between the biases women faced at work and the unexpected support they often received at home. While the challenges within the workplace were significantly marked by doubt, stereotyping, and a constant need to prove oneself, many women described their families as sources of encouragement rather than resistance. Contrary to common assumptions, it was not always the home, but the office, where their leadership journeys met the greatest resistance. This contrast highlights how mindsets are shifting in private spaces even as some professional environments remain slow to catch up.

P10 grew up in a remote village yet faced no pressures to conform to traditional roles.

“Even my family does not have this kind of mindset that you have to get married and then have some kids and you don’t have to work. Even my parents are also like if you want to do, you can do” p10.

P9 and P24 came from conservative, protected families yet faced more resistance at work than at home.

“I myself come from you know a very conservative family, certainly brought up with certain values and ethics” p2.

“I come from a protected family environment” p24.

“Actually, my family background was not that good” p9.

This contrast suggests that while families are evolving to support women’s ambitions, organisations are still catching up in breaking gender biases. These illustrations demonstrate the coping strategies of women leaders by leveraging family support, using encouragement as motivation, and breaking industry stereotypes by showcasing their capabilities through skill, knowledge, and leadership presence.

Despite stereotypical industry perceptions, biased evaluations, and traditional mindsets, women leaders continue to break barriers by challenging gender norms and demonstrating their leadership abilities. They seek mentorship and sponsorship to combat workplace bias and leverage emotional resilience to navigate adversity.

4.3.3.2 Subtheme: Managing emotional resilience, stress, and confidence

Emotional resilience, stress management, and confidence are critical factors influencing decision-making, professional relationships, and overall leadership effectiveness. These aspects are particularly important for women leaders navigating their leadership skills within a male-dominated industry such as the automobile industry. The following insight from the interviews highlights the strategies women leaders use to cultivate resilience, manage stress and build confidence.

By developing a deep understanding of their own triggers and stressors, many women leaders have learned to manage their emotional responses with greater clarity and composure. Through self-awareness and regular reflection, they are able to navigate high-pressure situations more thoughtfully, maintaining their sense of balance and responding with intention rather than impulse. P1 emphasises self-awareness and the importance of filtering feedback.

“I know myself very well, any feedback that is coming repetitively will be something that I work on” p1.

P6 from a legal background explains how self-reflection helps her analyse her responses.

“Before I do anything, it will be on my mind, so that you know before I speak, I check what I am saying is right or wrong, it’s a self-reflection” p6.

P5 illustrates how self-reflection fosters assertive communication:

“Then I started thinking about my speech. So, I modify myself, I change the ways of saying no, then analyse data, because of this everyone understood the work” p5.

P23 highlights the importance of marketing her work to create sponsorship opportunities.

“I want to create my own brand image; I have to sell myself. And how do I sell myself is to create, do my work and market that work myself and that’s how you create sponsors” p23.

P2 uses the example of female athletics as an illustration on how success attracts recognition.

“You know you have to stay to yourself, you must have seen the recent sports winners, once they are at the top companies are running to them to sponsor them. Where were these companies before” p2

To cope with stress, many women leaders lean on a positive outlook and a strong sense of self-motivation. Rather than allowing pressure to overwhelm them, they approach work-related challenges with determination and clarity, finding practical ways to stay grounded and move forward. This mindset not only helps them manage daily demands but also reinforces their resilience in the face of ongoing professional pressures.

P8 focuses on recognising the positive aspects of the situation.

“You need to accept it, and you need to find ways to handle those challenges. But then you need to look at the positive aspects also. You have good friends, good colleagues, good support. So, you need to look at the positive things and keep yourself motivated” p8.

P14 stresses the importance of self-motivation.

“Motivate yourself, nobody will motivate you, you need to motivate yourself. Because if you do not motivate your self-people will come and demotivate you” p14.

P13 shares a personal experience of dealing with a difficult boss.

“I would go home crying. Another boss had a word with me, saying the person won’t change you change yourself, you will not change him, but you can change yourself. This happened cause people could see I was not happy, I sometimes cry at office, I even fainted at office it was so stressful. So, after that discussion, I tried to change myself. That helped me a lot, then I survived very blissfully” p13.

For many women leaders, confidence isn’t something that appears overnight; it grows steadily over time, rooted in knowledge, shaped by experience, and strengthened by a mindset open to learning and growth. It’s this quiet assurance, built through challenges and continuous development, that allows them to lead with authenticity and conviction. P11 highlights how expertise builds confidence.

“I don’t like to butter people; I have that confidence in myself that I have the knowledge, and I know how to explain to seniors as well as how to showcase my work which has helped me in the past” p11.

P4 shares how overcoming intimidation strengthened her leadership.

“So, my leadership journey it’s not the work that was intimidating. It’s just every day I have to tell myself no you have done your research, you know what you’re doing, your right do not let

anyone else make you question yourself. I feel like this is my biggest learning. It's just that I should not feel intimidated, I should trust myself "p4

P7 emphasises learning from decision making challenges.

"My role involves me to take decisions then and there because if you're not taking this decision then it will delay the work. So, during these times though I don't have much experience in this role, this is the phase I am learning as well as leading. So, both the things I am doing" p7.

P12 views daily challenges as learning experiences.

"In supply chain particularly logistics, there are challenges which comes on a daily basis. I look at it as if its learning something new" p12.

P22 a diversity and inclusion director, underscores the importance of learning from past experiences.

"It came from the realisation and from past learnings that don't shoot arrows. Go to the ground meet people at the plant. So, first year I spent visiting all the plants" p22.

A study by Van den Bosch and Taris (2018) supports the idea that employees who embrace authenticity tend to exhibit higher levels of intrinsic motivation. This was certainly evident among the women leaders interviewed for this research. Rather than depending on external motivators, they drew strength from within, finding a deep sense of purpose and drive that fuelled their leadership journeys. Their ability to stay focused and committed, even in the face of challenges, highlights the power of authentic leadership in fostering self-motivation.

P22 encapsulates this perspective by acknowledging the struggles women leaders face and the responsibility to continue in pushing boundaries.

“You know sometimes you get tired, and you have to break your head against the wall, and you sometimes question yourself and say why I don’t shut up. The only thing that keeps me going is the recognition that if it weren’t for women before us who were difficult, noisy who pushed boundaries I wouldn’t be educated, we would not have had a chance to be employed. So, the point where women were difficult taking the heat for us and thereby it’s up to us to keep pushing” p22.

The interviews showcase various coping mechanisms women leaders employ to build resilience, manage stress and maintain confidence. Key themes include self-awareness, self-motivation a growth mindset and leveraging knowledge to overcome challenges. Their self-determined motivation enables them to persist despite adversity, shaping them into strong effective leaders within the automotive industry.

The experience of these women leaders demonstrates that mentorship and strong networks with colleagues are invaluable tools for professional growth. While some faced challenges in securing mentors, those who did, benefited from guidance, advocacy, and skill development. Similarly building alliances with like-minded colleagues provided emotional support, knowledge-sharing and collective progress in the workplace. These strategies not only foster individual success but also contribute to a more inclusive and supportive professional environment for women in leadership.

From the second sub-theme, women in leadership within the male-dominated automotive industry face deep-rooted gender biases, including internalised societal norms and workplace discrimination. Despite increased efforts towards inclusivity, significant barriers remain, including scepticism about women’s capabilities, rigid industry perceptions, and resistance to change. However, many women leaders overcome these challenges through resilience, strategic advocacy, and strong support systems such as mentorships and peer networks.

To drive meaningful change, organisations can implement the following strategies.

Mentorship and sponsorship play a crucial role in supporting women's growth into leadership roles within the automotive industry. Many of the women leaders interviewed shared how structured mentorship initiatives, especially early in their careers, provided not only guidance but also the technical expertise necessary for their roles. Having a mentor within their own department ensured they received relevant support and advocacy, helping them navigate the complexities of the industry. Yet, as many participants pointed out, mentorship alone is not sufficient for career progression. To truly drive advancement, sponsorship must take precedence, particularly when a woman is ready for leadership opportunities. A comprehensive support structure within the industry needs to seamlessly integrate both mentorship and sponsorship, with sponsorship acting as the critical bridge to higher leadership roles.

What stood out in the interviews was that mentors and sponsors do not necessarily have to be women. In fact, many women leaders shared that the invaluable support they received came from male colleagues and supervisors who actively championed their career development. By involving men as mentors and sponsors, organisations can foster a more inclusive culture where the advancement of women into leadership becomes a shared responsibility, rather than solely the goal of women themselves.

Flexible work policies emerged as another key factor in ensuring that women are not penalised for family commitments. The women interviewed shared how their career growth often seemed to stagnate when they prioritised family responsibilities. Rather than viewing personal choices as obstacles, organisations should implement flexible work arrangements that allow women to balance their professional ambitions with their personal lives, without sacrificing career progression. This approach not only fosters inclusivity but also enables organisations to retain skilled talent and enhance overall employee well-being. By valuing flexibility, the industry can

support diverse career paths, ensuring women can thrive in their roles while maintaining a healthy work-life balance.

Encouraging collaboration between men and women within the workplace is another essential element for women's growth. As one participant, Participant 24, highlighted, the foundation of a successful and sustainable career lies in both happiness and health. A truly inclusive workplace recognises the power of allyship, where men and women work together as partners, rather than competitors. This shift in mindset not only promotes a culture of mutual respect but also helps drive organisational success. To further strengthen this culture, organisations should actively promote and reward allyship, recognising collaborative efforts rather than limiting recognition to women's achievements alone. By celebrating the collective contributions of both men and women, organisations can foster a more inclusive and dynamic environment that drives diversity, equity, and inclusion forward.

Furthermore, fostering allyship leads to a healthier work environment where employees feel valued and supported, reducing stress and enhancing overall well-being.

P24 as aptly states "Whether male or female anybody it impacts the family, cause the fundamental required is happiness and your health, if it's not taken care it will impact".

By embedding allyship into the fabric of workplace culture, organisations can foster a more balanced and supportive environment, setting high standards of performance across the industry. As highlighted in Theme 3, the research revealed several key insights into the biases surrounding women's capabilities, which often persist despite their evident strengths. There was a stark contrast between the commonly expected challenges that women face at home, particularly in balancing family responsibilities, and the unexpected support they often received from their families, which proved to be a powerful source of encouragement.

At the same time, women leaders demonstrated remarkable emotional resilience, crafting strong personal and professional brands that allowed them to navigate the complexities of their careers. They found ways to handle stress, staying motivated through difficult moments by focusing on their long-term goals and drawing strength from within. Confidence-building strategies also played a crucial role, with many women sharing how they worked to develop both their leadership strength and self-belief, often by taking deliberate steps to assert their capabilities and challenge industry stereotypes.

The theme also highlighted the importance of self-determined motivation. It became clear that many women leaders thrived not through external recognition but by cultivating a deep, internal drive to succeed anchored in their values, purpose, and unwavering commitment to their roles. This internal motivation, supported by both mentorship and occasional sponsorship, proved essential in helping them overcome the challenges they faced.

4.4. Category B: External Barriers and organisational realities

4.4.1 Theme Four: Bias

This theme highlights the various strategies women leaders employed to overcome bias and criticism. Sixteen leaders emphasised the use of selective feedback as a key approach to counter bias. Nine leaders underscored the importance of allyship through mentorship as a powerful strategy, while thirteen leaders stressed that building strong networks with colleagues was crucial in navigating bias and criticism.

4.4.4.1 Subtheme: Personal strategies for handling bias and criticism

Women leaders within the automotive industry often face bias and criticism that impact their confidence and their career progression. However, as seen from the previous sections, women leaders' resilience, self-awareness, and strategic actions enable them to navigate these challenges effectively. The interviews highlight various strategies employed by women leaders

to overcome bias and criticism, helping them maintain their professional credibility and mental well-being.

One of the most significant strategies identified is the selective processing of feedback. Women leaders demonstrated strong self-awareness, allowing them to distinguish between constructive feedback and biased opinions.

Discretion in accepting feedback: P1 highlights she uses her discretion with feedback she receives.

“So, where I am today is that I know who I am, I am not really interested to know about feedback on who I am. I invest time in analysing where the feedback is coming from, what’s the background” p1

This highlights how p1 filters feedback, accepting only what is relevant to her professional growth.

Work-related feedback acceptance: P2 takes a different approach. She suggests that professional rather than personal feedback is valuable.

“I would say that if its work related, I’d be open. But unfortunately, I have never had that in my entire career.” p2.

Situational acceptance of feedback: P3 reflects on her evolving relationship with feedback.

“I can’t say I always welcomed feedback, half of the time I was open, but it depends on the mood, my situation at that time” p3.

Maintaining authenticity with adaptation: p23 states

“I take it very positively and that’s where you know you tweak your style with different organisations but at the same time maintaining your authenticity” p23.

This highlights the balance between adapting to different environments and staying true to oneself.

Considering the source of feedback:

P24 "Depends on who is giving, so if it is coming from somebody who has somewhere influenced me, then I would work on it. But if it's coming from somebody who doesn't matter to me at all then I would definitely not take it"

P4 "If it is honest feedback that's coming from a good place i am totally willing to take it".

These insights indicate that feedback is only valuable when it comes from a credible source.

Skill-based and growth-oriented feedback:

P25 states "If I get feedback where I need to improve on my skills, then of course you know I will work on it and I will make sure that you know that feedback does not come again".

P5 & p 9 emphasises that feedback should contribute to personal and career growth.

"If really it will help for our growth or career then we need to think and change" p5.

"So, if it is meant for improvement, I will take it from the person. So, whatever it needs to be focused on betterment then I will take it" p9.

Emotional regulation in feedback processing

P6 shares "I learned one thing if somebody is giving feedback don't take it with your heart but with your brain and then analyse it and then you would know if you needed to accept it or not".

Using feedback as a tool for improvement: Some women leaders use feedback, whether positive or negative, as a way to prove themselves and enhance their professional journey.

Embracing feedback as a motivation:

“If it is negative also, I have to work on that which means I don’t like people talking negative things about me, so I have to prove myself, it’s not about yourself it’s about how you feel when someone gives negative feedback” p7.

“I am very much open to feedback. And I use it to change myself” p13.

“I yearn for feedback, to change myself” p14.

Reflection and outside input: p8 offers a distinctive view on reflection.

“My husband gives some negative feedback; he makes sure he says I am wrong when I am wrong. So, I take time to reflect on it” p8.

P10 takes a balanced approach to feedback. Whether positive or negative she gives a way in which it should be taken.

Balanced approach to feedback: *“One thing which I personally learned that you should not like if someone says something good you should not float on the clouds, similarly if someone says something negative you should not get demotivated” p10.*

Feedback as perspective rather than absolute truth: *“All feedback is not right or wrong, it is their perspective, they have identified something and telling you, however you need to analyse it, pick whatever is most relevant to you and you feel you can work on” p17*

Validity of feedback based on investment in growth: p21 emphasis *“Know sincerely when a person has invested some time in me, why? Because if you have not invested tome in me your feedback will not be valid, simple right so I do that analysis” p21.*

The insights from these interviews highlight that women leaders in the automotive industry do not shy away from feedback. Instead, they apply selective feedback strategies to refine their skills and maintain their authenticity. While some welcome feedback with open arms, others

assess its relevance based on their professional development needs and the credibility of the source. Regardless of their approach, these leaders use feedback as a means to navigate criticism and bias. Ultimately, they will strengthen their leadership positions in the industry.

Leveraging allies through mentorship: Mentorship has played a crucial role in the growth and success of women leaders across various industries. Many have leveraged mentors to overcome internal challenges and biases, enabling them to navigate their careers with greater confidence and clarity.

P1 shares the impact of her previous boss, who was also her mentor, in shaping her career.

“The HR leader is my mentor; he was the one who pushed me to my limit” p1.

P2 highlights the value of reverse mentorship in fostering team growth and building alliance.

“As a team, I believe people should come with complementary skills. They should also reverse mentor you to an extent. Because otherwise neither will grow” p2.

For some women, mentorship came in the form of tough leadership that ultimately led to their development. P3 & p24 reflect on their bosses, who, despite being tough, played a significant role in their growth:

“My boss she was very assertive, she was not like trusting me, like suspicious on everything. And then the managing director asked her to be my mentor and told her it’s her responsibility to develop me to become a good director” p3.

“My boss she was a good mentor in the sense that I learned how to be strong and stand” p3.

Others, like P25, emphasise how supportive mentors helped guide them into new leadership roles:

“My boss was my mentor, supported and guided me as well as mentored me to take up this new role and the responsibility” p25.

However, not all women had the fortune of finding a mentor. P4 expresses her struggle in growing into leadership without one:

“I’ve not been fortunate in getting that kind of mentor, but I feel like you need to have some kind of mentor because otherwise it becomes a struggle when you’re growing into leadership” p4.

P6 demonstrates how proactively seeking mentorship led to strong advocacy for her growth within the organisation:

“I went back to the person who corrected me and said can you be my mentor; he said don’t use such big words, but you can feel free to talk to me. He actually corrected me in so many different ways and that made others advocate for me” p6.

Mentorship can also come from personal relationships, as seen in p8’s experience:

“So, I talk to him my husband he is my guide, mentoring me, my critic too” p8.

However, p22 provides a contrasting perspective, finding mentorship overwhelming at times when what she really needed was advocacy.

“Like many a time I was bombarded with mentorship, and I didn’t like it because I just didn’t think I needed it. Right, I have wanted somebody to go talk for me” p22.

Overall, seeking support from like-minded individuals through mentorship has proven to be a key path to success for women in leadership roles.

Beyond mentorship, women leaders have also found strength in building networks with their colleagues. These relationships played a crucial role in overcoming challenges and fostering professional growth.

P25 underscores the importance of knowledge-sharing with colleagues:

“From colleagues I gain knowledge, I get to learn a lot of things” p25.

P24 highlights how colleagues provided mental and emotional support, particularly in male-dominated environments.

“Oh, from colleagues, I gained a lot of support, you know mentally, we were three women, we were always like one, one against many, so whether it was sharing your heart with them to understand their perspective, sharing their perspective and your perspective with them I think I guess that was a major support” p24

P23 compares career growth to running a marathon, emphasising the need for a strong support system.

“If you want to run a marathon you cannot just do it alone, you need to have people around you. Strong positive people around you. I made great support with them you know, as you move forward you know this should be the strategy we should focus on” p23.

For expatriates like p3, colleagues played a vital role in helping them navigate cultural differences and providing constructive feedback.

“I think in many ways by their differences, by their culture, by sometimes giving feedback to me, sometimes by just opposing me. This is what I learned” p3.

Several women acknowledged that they could not have succeeded without the support of others. P1, p7, and p15 credit their colleagues for providing the necessary support in their work.

“So, I always believe that I am not a superhuman, I got to know about assessment centres through colleagues” p1.

“I am an electrical engineer in the automobile industry mainly focused on mechanical so whenever I start something I have colleagues to help me” p7.

“Two colleagues who were there, they helped me a lot they taught me from zero like documentation everything and they never got frustrated” p15.

P5 acknowledge how crucial colleagues are in a professional setting.

“Without colleagues support, we can't do anything” p5.

P8 draws a parallel between workplace and home support systems.

“See support system is required right? Support system is required at the workplace also, where you can share, I have colleagues. We need something with whom we can discuss, who can guide us, maybe right or wrong. If not guide at least listen to us” p8.

P21 reinforces this sentiment, referring to colleagues as a second family.

“That is very important because it is like a second family to us, the organisation our workplace. The first thing which is required is camaraderie between colleagues. It is very difficult to survive in this atmosphere an atmosphere of competition and I don't believe in competition. So, colleagues play most important role people don't leave only for bosses but also leave for colleagues” p21.

P12 acknowledges that her colleagues played a role in shaping her professionalism.

“Coming to the role of a senior manager is not an easy thing. Thanks to my colleagues they taught me how to be a professional” p12.

P14 shares her experience of being one of the first women in her team and the support she received:

“Both the departments, no females, so when I joined colleagues supported me” p14.

P17 introduces a unique perspective, emphasising the interconnectedness of personal and collective growth.

“It’s a combined effort which gives visibility to even my colleagues including myself. Because we are connected” p17

These persistent biases indicate that systematic change is necessary within organisations to foster a genuinely inclusive work environment. While individual resilience and advocacy are crucial, the burden should not solely rest on women. Leadership teams and corporate policies must actively address unconscious bias, create equitable growth opportunities, and recognise the unique challenges women face. Additionally, companies should acknowledge the evolving family dynamics that are more supportive of women’s careers and ensure that workplace culture aligns with this progress.

Implementing training programs focused exclusively on preventing unconscious bias is essential for fostering an inclusive culture within the automotive organisations. Interviews have revealed that unconscious biases significantly hinder women's career growth, affecting both their professional advancement and mental well-being. For this to be effective, these training programs must be delivered to all employees, creating awareness of blind spots and fostering a deeper understanding of how unconscious biases develop. By incorporating real workplace scenarios, employers can recognise and address biases in decision-making, leadership opportunities and daily interactions.

The impact of bias-awareness training reaches far beyond individual understanding it has the potential to reshape the culture of an entire organisation. When workplaces take active steps to mitigate unconscious bias, they lay the foundation for fairer career progression, which in turn boosts morale, strengthens collaboration, and fosters a deeper sense of belonging among employees. An inclusive environment not only enhances day-to-day working relationships but also contributes to greater retention, sparks innovation, and helps position the organisation as a leader in equitable workplace practices.

Theme 4 revealed how women leaders navigated feedback in a highly intentional way. Rather than accepting all feedback at face value, they became discerning, filtering what was constructive and aligned with their goals, while discarding what was unhelpful or rooted in bias. This ability to selectively engage with feedback allowed them to maintain focus and self-belief. Alongside this, many women cultivated strong networks with like-minded colleagues' relationships that offered encouragement, insight, and solidarity. These connections proved instrumental in their leadership development, offering a sense of shared purpose and mutual support that helped them grow and thrive within often challenging organisational contexts.

4.4.2 Theme Five: Leadership Development

This theme examines how women in the Indian automotive industry strive for self-development, enhance their skills, overcome career challenges, and devise strategies for professional growth. Insights from interviews with women leaders reveal both the obstacles they faced in accessing formal training opportunities and the approaches they used to promote their own development. All 25 participants emphasised the importance of self-initiated learning, with twenty specifically highlighting the advantages of independently gained on-the-job experience. Additionally, twenty-two participants critically pointed out the lack of

sponsorship and stressed the urgent need for stronger advocacy, while 12 highlighted the crucial role of self-identified mentors who supported their progress.

4.4.2.1 Subtheme: Continuous self-development, learning, and skill development

Many women leaders emphasised the importance of self-development for career growth. However, a key finding was the lack of structured training programs offered to them. Most had to take the initiative to upskill independently, leveraging available opportunities.

Several participants highlighted how they had to seek their own learning paths. P4, for instance, was not provided any formal training but took the initiative to visit a plant in another country for self-development.

“I was not given any training or specific development opportunities. I made my own case to go and meet people” p4

Similarly, p2, despite holding a high-ranking position, received training related to her expertise in work but nothing specific to leadership.

“So, nothing that was conscious for the position that I was in, but since I was part of the entity and I had to recruit, I was given the training for high level leadership” p2

Some women leaders within the HR department, such as P24 & p25, found ways to learn by participating in training programs they arranged for others.

“I would talk here as a HR, in the process of you know developing interventions for others you know, I’ve learned a lot. So, there is a first-time manager program that we have for all the people new to the role. So, in the process of organising these trainings I have learnt a lot” p25.

“So, I was involved in planning training for others while I was planning training for others. I would say I was a bit bias and plugged in my agenda. So that’s how I got trained” p24.

Many participants mentioned that while structured training was limited, they learned through their work responsibilities. P7 emphasised that job challenges raised questions, which led to learning through guidance from colleagues.

“Training wise I received from HR for first time manager, but it’s generally on the job training cause your given a task and when you do a task, you have queries in your mind and there are people to solve your query and guide you” p7

While most participants lacked structured training, some exceptions existed. An expatriate received specialised training on leading across cultures before taking up her assignment in India.

“I really got good training, one of it was like for high potential and it was related to leading across cultures. It was really one of the best and it was very interesting” p3.

Likewise, p5 working in production was provided leadership training by management.

“of course, from management side they had given me training, leadership training” p5.

P6, a legal professional, received external training from the court of law, which she found highly beneficial.

“So, there was a training program in court where you had to be politically savvy, that was an interesting concept, very interesting, that taught me a lot” p6.

Despite the industry traditionally being male-dominated, some organisations have implemented structured training and development programs specifically for women to bridge the gap.

P9 noted that her company provided training opportunities with the specific goal of increasing the ratio of women in leadership.

“So, growth opportunities like training and development were given for all female candidate to have a higher ratio of women” p9.

A few participants recalled leadership training programs designed exclusively for women. P14 participated in a women-focused leadership development program, while P17 attended a women's leadership program, although it was only available to top-rated employees. However, p17 questioned the long-term impact of such programs, emphasising that real growth comes from experience.

“In this company, not that much training was given. But yes, in this company I did one training that was related to shaping women” p14.

“So back to company x we had one training titled women leadership program that was not for everyone, it was based on our ratings, based on our past 2-3 years performance. Somehow, I feel other than training, like on the day of the training I feel energetic, after that like a balloon it goes down, I don't remember anything from the training, so I think it's all down to experience” p17.

P15 stressed that organisations must invest in structured training programs to mould women employees for leadership roles.

“We need to give the training; we need to mould them” p15.

Women who actively sought development opportunities found structured pathways for career progression within their organisations. Some organisations offered schemes that supported a woman's career growth. P22 shared how her company's “earn while you learn program enabled her to gain both credentials and industry experience, fuelling her ambition for future growth.

“I'm so glad my company has a scheme that is earn while you learn which allow me to learn and get the credentials that would help me build my credentials to the next level” p22.

Several participants including P10 & p11 noted that while they received technical training, they lacked managerial training which they believed would have helped them better handle leadership responsibilities.

“My opinion on that I can say that if I get some of the managerial training would be helpful” p10.

“Yes, I got a lot of technical training but no other trainings” p11.

Some organisations provided limited professional growth training, primarily focusing on ethics and team building rather than leadership development. P12 recalls attending such programs but found them lacking in support for career progression.

“If I can recall team building was there and ethics training” p12.

The experience of women within the auto industry reveals the unequal access to training programs and the resilience of self-driven learning for career growth. While some organisations have implemented women-centric training initiatives, their impact remains debatable. The findings highlight the need for structured leadership training, a shift from purely technical to managerial skill building and inclusive development programs to ensure sustained professional growth and leadership opportunities for women within the industry.

4.4.2.2 Subtheme: Breaking career barriers and seizing leadership opportunities

Women in the automobile industry face significant challenges in breaking career barriers and advancing into leadership roles. Interviews reveal that gender bias, lack of sponsorship, the need for self-advocacy and workplace culture are key obstacles that women must navigate. However, women have also developed strategies to seize leadership opportunities, including self-driven learning, strategic networking, and organisational collaboration for gender diversity.

Many women feel their career progression is impacted by their parental status. Women in leadership roles face resistance when they are seen as potential candidates for senior positions.

“During my maternity phase, I was going through a tough time with my boss. So many times, I was mocked at. He would make sure I don’t leave the organisation on time. He never wanted me to sustain” p24.

“In diversity lens you see their development, you see their growth opportunities, you see the ecosystem whether they are supporting or not. So, it’s from holistic view that you know one has to create and that’s what I created even I suffered during my maternity. They started calling me back to work within one month, so that insensitivity is still within me” p23.

“The challenges start from the leave perspective. They think you are going on an enjoy holiday but actually that’s not the case. Then once you return, they think you will take multiple leave due to personal reasons. So, this kind of assumptions are only for the female candidate. I fought through everything even with the management because I was not given growth because of my maternity leave” p16.

“If your life stage is pre-children then you are fine, marriage and children become a problem and the sheer absence of women in leadership also made me question. What about premenopausal and when I look at leadership especially women in leadership and how are they dealing with the symptoms of premenopausal there is no conversation, imagine being in a meeting and having hot flushes, we don’t have an eco-system to survive this reality. So, when need sponsorship to have more women on the table to consider all these challenges” p22.

The testimonies illustrate the emotional and physical stress women endure alongside their professional responsibilities. Despite these barriers, women demonstrate immense grit in sustaining and advancing their careers.

Women leaders express frustration over having to repeatedly prove themselves, while male counterparts receive promotions despite making mistakes.

“It’s not about capabilities, because I saw also male counterparts, they are messing up on different projects, but they got promoted and they moved up and some even got regional roles” p1.

“You know this typical male chauvinist, and who cannot tolerate women in Industry, so he was like mentioning that I was an individual contributor and when I asked him why he said he could sense it from the way I spoke. At that time, I had 32 people reporting into me. It was a two-year struggle with this guy. He said he was going to stop my salary if I did not come in the time, he wanted me to” p24.

“Male colleagues you know said that no we should not hire this female candidate as she is a single parent” p2

“women leaders definitely you know will pave the way. They might not have to struggle as much as we did. And you know this will definitely open the eyes of male leaders to start thinking differently” p1.

“It’s a male dominated industry, especially the car industry and that’s my observation” p3.

Women also face resistance when expressing disagreement in the workplace:

“My boss was a male. He would not take a no from me. He was like he mentioned in one conversation you said no. that is very disrespectful” p6.

“This lady boss was there in between one level which will be less than a minus one level which is usually filled with men. Do we have an option to elevate this lady? Why you can’t? Because there are some unconscious biases, there could be several reasons for not elevating her but until you give a chance how will you know” p8.

Many women emphasise the importance of sponsorship, specifically having a senior advocate speak on their behalf during career advancement discussions. However, limited sponsorship opportunities hinder growth.

“I got a promotion after 12 years and that also because I threatened, I would leave. It was more HR completing their thing, I think there where many people who were unhappy about it” p2.

“It happened but it did not really do well for my career. They wanted someone who is authentic to rescue it” p1

“When I was working for this company, I had this manager was exactly that kind of a person who would nominate me. Unfortunately, I have not been fortunate in getting that kind of a boss, you have to be extremely fortunate” p4.

“We had very limited resources, because no one was there, they nominated me. Otherwise, I don’t know if would have recognised me, so no option was there” p8.

“In that organisation even after coming from maternity leave, I was recommended for the next level, so I would say it’s because of that country culture in which the organisation is from. If I consider the same situation here, I am already here for 2 ½ years and not noticed any advocate for me” p13.

“Sponsorship definitely is something that we should tell leaders that it’s on you to get women on the table and if you don’t wait for it to happen organically it too unfair, it’s also its already biased and it’s also unfair” p22

The interviews highlight that while sponsorship is desired, it is often provided due to HR formalities or the unavailability of other candidates. Women who break career barriers still struggle to advance due to a lack of advocacy at leadership tables.

Women often experience subtle exclusion from important decision-making and face hostile work environments.

The queen bee phenomenon: In some cases, women in leadership positions are unsupportive of female employees, reinforcing workplace resistance to women's advancement.

"She never hired a female in her team and now she has all men, she forgets to complement women" p24

"I had been in a situation where I was you know facing few challenges, I was not getting settled as well there where issues, you know the irony is that the boss is a female" p22.

However, structured mentorship can reverse these dynamics.

"So, she did not trust me, she was suspicious of everything and mentioned that she is good for what she is doing but not for this role. But when the managing director said you're going to be responsible for her to be a good HR director it is your responsibility, he made her be my mentor. We used to work closely, and she helped me a lot. After 6 months she was very happy with me, and we became good friends" p3.

Workplace policies and gender equity: Investing in gender equity over the long term is essential for sustainable progress.

"I think women it's a long-term decision. If you want women to come in you need to create a culture, that infrastructure which means cost. You need to be ready to invest in long term. So, unless you're willing to put your money where your mouth is, you won't have women" p4.

Breaking through career barriers and stepping into leadership roles within the Indian automobile industry demands not only resilience but also self-advocacy and thoughtful strategic positioning. While systemic obstacles still remain, there is a growing recognition of the need for gender diversity, more structured sponsorship, and leadership development

initiatives, all of which are gradually opening doors for more women to rise into senior roles. Today's women leaders are doing far more than navigating existing systems; they are actively challenging the status quo and shaping a more inclusive and equitable future for the generations of women who will follow in their footsteps.

Theme 6 highlighted the vital role of self-learning in women's leadership journeys. For many, learning was not limited to formal training programmes; in fact, quite the opposite. While some HR professionals gained insights through the very development programmes they facilitated for others, it was the hands-on, on-the-job experiences that stood out as the most impactful. These practical learning moments often filled the gaps left by limited access to formal leadership development initiatives. Many women spoke of the hurdles they faced in securing places in such programmes, with access often being inconsistent or influenced by internal sponsorship, which was not always readily available to them.

This lack of structured support made advocacy and sponsorship even more critical. The women who progressed often did so because they found sponsors who believed in their potential and were willing to speak up on their behalf. Without such advocates, navigating the deeply entrenched cultural and organisational challenges would have been far more difficult. What emerged was a powerful portrait of determined women who, in the face of limited formal support, took ownership of their growth, sought learning wherever they could find it, and, in doing so, redefined what leadership development could look like in a space not yet fully designed with them in mind.

4.4.3 Theme 6: Professional Growth

This theme examines how women advanced in their careers within organisations, tracing their journeys and highlighting the various routes they took to attain leadership positions. All twenty-five participants consistently emphasised that they relied on self-directed methods to

foster their growth. Four participants sought international experience to boost their skills and competencies, while eight highlighted the importance of self-branding for their professional development. Furthermore, thirteen participants pointed out the value of gaining multidisciplinary experience as a key strategy that supported their progression into leadership roles.

4.4.3.1 Subtheme: Strategic career planning and progression

Strategic career planning and advancement emerged as a key subtheme in the interviews, illustrating how women in the Indian automobile industry navigate their career journeys amid systemic barriers, limited mentorship, and a male-dominated work environment. The findings show that women adopt self-motivated career strategies, personal branding, and develop multidisciplinary expertise.

Many participants observed that career advancement opportunities were not explicitly offered to them, prompting them to manage their own development.

Some women proactively sought out international exposure, skill-building opportunities, and leadership visibility to strengthen their career trajectories.

“I wasn’t given any training or specific development opportunities, so I made my own case to go meet people and go visit the other plants, and you know how bureaucratic it is to get travel approvals” p4.

Several participants stressed the importance of self-promotion and ensuring their work was recognised.

P1 illustrates this self-branding by encouraging women to fight for their place at the table through their capabilities and by challenging themselves.

“Own it up, fight for it, someone gives feedback about your capabilities, you have to question why you’re not capable, what is it that I am missing. Challenge, challenge at any point fight for your place at the table” p1.

P3 urges women not to pretend to be a strong man in leadership but to believe in themselves and their capabilities.

“Men naturally have more self-confidence than women, and women kind of underestimate themselves in their capabilities. So, I would say trust yourself for who you are and honestly, I feel we should not pretend to be a strong man” p3.

P4 advises women to brand themselves to make a path within the industry.

“Nobody is going to look out for you and your work will not speak for itself you have to speak for your work. You need to go out there sometimes it feels like bragging but no that’s not called bragging you have to speak up for it, I need to build my own personal brand” p4.

P6 mentions that for progression, it is important not to lose one’s authenticity.

“So, at any point of time, do not lose your authenticity and become diplomatic” p6.

One of the key strategies employed by women leaders in the automobile industry is the pursuit of knowledge and skills across various functions. This fearless approach not only enhanced their expertise but also played a crucial role in self-branding. Women leaders actively sought out learning opportunities and seized every chance to grow, even if it meant moving to a different department, relocating to another city, or taking on challenging projects. They demonstrated resilience and determination in proving their ability to lead.

Many women leaders fearlessly took on challenging roles, often in difficult circumstances.

P24 took charge of a special project despite union-related resistance that led to her car being vandalised.

“I have seen in times in this company, my car was broken, the union broke my car I got into this special project” p24.

P23, a Diversity and Inclusion Director, emphasised the importance of raising one’s hand for new opportunities.

“I think you need to be yourself and you know you just need to explore the opportunities, always raise your hand. Be open to explore and experience new things” p23.

P1 pursued additional certifications and took on dual roles to enhance her industry growth.

“What are the learning opportunities, or do I need to do any certifications, they gave me a dual role and that’s how I moved to a new city” P1.

P3, an HR Director, accepted an overseas opportunity in India, showcasing her willingness to gain international experience.

“And then when I became head HR, they offered me the role to go to India” p3.

P4 diversified her knowledge across finance, accounting, marketing, and HR, preparing herself for a robust career.

“Just doing different aspects, I did finance, accounting, marketing and HR that kind of prepared me better for my career so that you kind of understand how business works” p4.

Women leaders navigated career transitions across various departments to strengthen their expertise.

P5 moved from a supplier company to the manufacturing sector, transitioning from operator level to assistant engineer to manager. She also moved between production, purchasing, and planning, refining her communication skills along the way.

“Nearly 14 years I was in vehicle planning so at the time every member knows about me so they wont say no so I did not face any problem but after moving from there to here I faced some issues that is my way of talking is very straight no means no. I got a lot of complaints about myself from seniors, then I started thinking about the way I speak and I started modifying myself” p5

P6, a legal professional, took on the challenge of rebuilding a disintegrated legal department within a struggling organisation.

“The legal department was disintegrated, so they recruited me to rebuild it and why should we rebuild the department because they wanted to rebuild the company. That made me think and I said ok they were transparent and giving me that genuine reason I was happy to accept the role” p6.

P7 re-entered the corporate world after a five-year gap due to COVID-19, overcoming a lack of confidence to lead a significant project.

“So, five years of corporate gap, so my confidence was very low. Last year I was given to lead a big project with my boss in another country I have to take key decisions then and there so this is the phase where I am learning as well as I am leading. Anything that comes to me I am ok, I can do it” p7.

P8, an assistant general manager with 20 years of experience, shared her journey of being the only woman in her electrical engineering class and department.

“I would say that you cannot be very emotional thought I was a very emotional person. Definitely, to survive in this industry you have to behave like a man. I have to put that shield that yes, I am a strong lady, inside I am weak, I am struggling but then that is required” p8.

P9 consistently embraced new roles, moving from supplier departments to purchase planning to program management, even taking an assignment in Australia.

“From supplier department to purchase planning to program management, I also had to move to Australia for a few months I also took the opportunity to lead in-direct purchasing, it was a great learning” p9.

Many women leaders entered traditionally male-dominated fields, proving their capabilities through persistence and expertise. P10 transitioned from quality engineering to electrical engineering and successfully led the organisation’s quality month initiatives.

“I got to learn and understand all the issues; I use to present everything and the best beside all this is like I got the opportunity to host the quality month for the organisation” p10.

P11 was among the first women to join her organisation’s maintenance department, defying stereotypes about women in such roles.

“In maintenance department I got to know many things and then I realised I got to join a very good department. My seniors also said that we did not expect any female to perform the way you did” p11.

P12 worked in logistics, a role requiring her presence at ports and 24/7 availability. She challenged gender biases and demanded equal treatment.

“The job demanded for me to be available 24/7 as the volumes were very huge sometimes flights would come in by 2:00am and thereby I need to be available to receive the parts and make sure it’s available for production. My bosses said see you’re a woman you should not do

this; you may have to be screamed at if shipment does not arrive in time. When they start screaming it's because of the job there is no bar between man and women because I have not done something I prefer this equality" p12.

These interviews provide profound insights into the diverse strategies women in the automobile industry have employed to upskill, reskill, and establish expertise in a traditionally male-dominated field. By embracing challenges, crossing disciplines, and continually learning, these women leaders have paved the way for future generations to follow. Based on the theme, some key points that can be applied by automotive organisations and future women leaders are provided below.

For women in the Indian automobile industry, career advancement often requires more than just technical expertise; it demands foresight, initiative, and a strategic approach to growth. Theme 7 revealed how many women leaders took ownership of their development by actively seeking opportunities to expand their capabilities across functions. This self-directed approach to career progression involved building multi-disciplinary expertise, often by stepping beyond traditional role boundaries and embracing varied assignments that broadened their industry understanding and professional credibility. Such versatility not only enhanced their confidence but also positioned them more favourably for leadership roles.

At the organisational level, there remains an urgent need to support these efforts through structured learning and development programmes. Women should be equipped with a blend of technical, behavioural, and leadership skills aligned to the roles they are stepping into, particularly as they progress through different stages of their careers. Formal programmes that evolve with career milestones can ensure women are not just prepared for leadership, but fully empowered to thrive in it.

As women move into middle management, inclusive sponsorship initiatives become especially critical. Senior leaders, regardless of gender, must play an active role in advocating for high-potential women, helping to create visibility and open up opportunities that might otherwise be overlooked. But inclusion cannot stop at sponsorship alone. Organisations must also tackle gender bias head-on by investing in conscious awareness workshops that unpack the impacts of unconscious bias, and by cultivating cultures where equitable practices become the norm.

Policy reform is equally vital. Many women continue to feel the professional consequences of taking maternity leave or navigating menopause, with career momentum often stalling as a result. Introducing and normalising family-friendly policies, ones that actively prevent career penalties for caregiving responsibilities, can go a long way in retaining talented women and fostering loyalty.

Yet alongside organisational change, women themselves continue to play a proactive role in shaping their journeys. Many embrace self-learning through certifications, mentorships, and cross-functional exposure, seeking out knowledge that helps them stay competitive and confident. Developing a personal brand through self-advocacy, strategic networking, and raising visibility within leadership circles was another recurring strategy among the participants. By taking control of their narratives and making their achievements visible, women were better able to secure recognition and influence.

Strengthening resilience and sharpening negotiation skills were also essential tools. Navigating bias and workplace resistance required not only emotional stamina but also the ability to assert one's value and advocate for fair treatment. Ultimately, while the road to leadership remains uneven, the combination of intentional organisational investment, sponsorship, and proactive career planning has the potential to accelerate the growth of women leaders across the Indian automobile sector, creating space for more inclusive, effective, and future-ready leadership.

4.4.4 Theme 7: Building Support Systems

This theme highlights the support networks women have created to progress their careers within organisations. Ten participants stressed the importance of seeking allies in senior management to support their development. Additionally, eight participants emphasised the importance of peer and colleague support in advancing towards leadership roles.

4.4.4.1 Subtheme: Seeking allies and advocates within the organisation

Women leaders emphasised the importance of securing allies within the workforce for professional growth. Many proactively sought support from senior leaders who advocated for them.

“Be vocal about your needs, be confident with your manager, that’s how we can make this place a safe place” p24.

“I work with a lot of fairness and transparency, and my line manager knew everything, I would keep him updated” p1.

“I created a positive relationship by my interpersonal skills. My manager spoke well of me and because of my work, all spoke well of me and because of that I got roles within the organisation” p23.

“So, I would go back to my manager and tell him listen I am not happy” p24.

“My boss was like a father figure to me. I would share what are all the challenges I am facing; we use to discuss” p8.

“Whatever I commit I will deliver, so my boss use to say if something is given to me, they can close their eyes” p9.

“I used to call my boss and ask for support and acknowledge my mistake when I mess up. I got a very supportive manager” p10.

“I just go and talk to my manager and share my opinions” p11.

“My boss use to give different, different requirements, I completed all and he gained confidence over me” p15.

“My super boss gave me the responsibility of my manager who had left. He went to the HRO and mentioned she is performing very well she is capable to take on this role” p21.

“Again, this organisation, I’ve kind of kept it low and my boss keeps telling me, Think more big scale” p22.

These responses illustrate that women effectively communicated with their managers and built strong professional relationships, focusing on their capabilities, commitment, and communication rather than gender biases. Some organisations had women led initiatives, but participants felt these programs needed more depth and long-term commitment.

“When promotion is given, it should not be because of gender and about increasing percentage. Suppose I am getting promotion others will say because I am a girl, she got promotion. But I got promotion because of my hard work” p17.

4.4.4.2 Subtheme: Creating a strong support system for leadership success

To succeed in leadership, women emphasised the importance of building robust support systems, including peer support, mentorship networks and leadership training.

“You need to have people around you, strong people, positive people, my team have been that support. I made a great support, as you move forward, you know its strategy” p23.

“So, you know whether it’s sharing your heart with them, to understand their perspective, sharing my perspective with them I guess that’s the major support when you build string teams” p24.

Some women, like p4 and p13, found support from their peers within the same function within the global units.

“I am very lucky from the people working within regions of the organisations across the world. She is always willing to listen to me and provide advice and that helps me a lot” p4.

“I got support from teams from other plants” p13.

Family support also played a crucial role for some participants. P8 found encouragement from her husband, who works in the same organisation, while P14 spoke of the guidance she received from her father.

“So, I talk to him, he also guides me, mentors me. He also discusses his problems with me, sometimes he is guiding me, sometimes I am guiding him, so we are supporting each other” p8.

“My father always supported me; I was sent from a village to get educated in engineering” p14.

Many participants found strong support from their managers.

“If you have a supportive manager, you get to learn a lot” p10.

“There were mistakes which I had done, but my general manager and my boss they supported me” p12.

The interviews reveal that women in the Indian automobile organisations have creatively developed their own support systems, leveraging networking and workplace allies to navigate challenges and achieve career success. While informal mentorship and personal initiatives have played a critical role, there is a clear need for structured programs to ensure sustainable and equitable career growth for women in the industry. Insights derived from the interviews

indicate that the following strategies may offer significant benefits to both future women leaders and their organisations and could be effectively integrated into their strategic frameworks.

Building a personal brand is increasingly recognised as a critical step in enabling women to gain visibility and recognition within their professional spheres. For women in male-dominated industries, especially, actively engaging in networking events, participating in leadership training, and showcasing achievements can be powerful strategies to assert their presence and credibility. These efforts not only help in gaining acknowledgement from peers and superiors but also in creating opportunities for career progression.

Alongside this, taking ownership of one's career trajectory through proactive management is essential. Women who actively seek feedback, negotiate the terms and scope of their roles, and advocate for promotions based on merit are more likely to overcome institutional and informal barriers. This intentional navigation of the workplace landscape challenges traditional norms and shifts the narrative from passive progression to deliberate advancement.

At the organisational level, there is a clear need for structured support systems tailored to women in professional roles. Professional associations and corporate bodies should lead by example in introducing mentorship and leadership development programmes specifically designed to support women at different stages of their careers. Early-career mentorship, ideally provided by reporting managers or experienced women within the organisation, can set a strong foundation of support, learning, and confidence. As women progress into mid-level management, targeted sponsorship initiatives become increasingly important. These should focus on ensuring that women are not only mentored but also actively championed for leadership roles and high-visibility assignments.

The value of cross-organisational collaboration cannot be underestimated. Establishing mentorship programmes that span across companies would enable women to access a broader and more diverse network of mentors and sponsors, thereby enriching their perspectives and expanding their career possibilities beyond their immediate organisational boundaries.

Alongside these targeted programmes, there is an urgent need for the industry to adopt comprehensive diversity and inclusion frameworks. These frameworks should motivate organisations to implement policies that actively promote sponsorship, leadership training, and unbiased recruitment and promotion practices. Leadership development for women must incorporate executive coaching, strategic skill-building workshops, and access to high-level networking opportunities that are often gatekept within informal male networks.

Equally important is the role of male allies in transforming workplace cultures. Managerial training should include a strong emphasis on allyship, with male leaders being sensitised and equipped to advocate for women's growth and to recognise and eliminate unconscious bias in decision-making processes.

Lastly, companies must commit to transparency in their promotion and evaluation processes. Ensuring that promotions are based strictly on merit, with clear and objective criteria, helps eliminate the gendered assumptions that often influence perceptions of leadership potential. Only through a combination of individual agency, organisational commitment, and industry-wide collaboration can meaningful progress be made towards gender-equitable leadership.

Women must be proactive in seeking networking and career growth opportunities. At the organisational level, structured programs and collaborations are needed to create a more inclusive environment. Companies must implement policies that provide formal sponsorship and leadership training to ensure equitable career progression for women.

4.5 Category C: Leadership growth and advancement

4.5.1 Theme 8: Mentorship in Career

This theme highlights the critical role of mentorship, with seven participants attesting to the benefits of informal mentorship, and three others leveraging networking to foster alliances and secure advocacy in pursuit of their career progression.

4.5.1.1 Subtheme: The role of mentorship and networking

Mentorship has become a crucial yet underused tool for women's career development. Many women leaders observed that they did not receive formal mentorship but instead depended on informal mentors or self-directed learning to progress in their careers.

“And then when this group company merged, that’s when I actually went into the HR department, and that HR leader was also my mentor, because he was the only one who kept pushing me” p1.

“And hence I would say she was a good mentor in that sense, that I learned to be strong like her” p24.

“I have not been that fortunate in getting that kind of a mentor, but I feel like you need to have some kind of mentor, because women get stuck when they don’t have a mentor” p4.

“I asked the person, I will need this kind of feedback more often, can you be my mentor for some time?” p6

Informal Mentorship as a Growth Enabler: Several participants found mentors in their male colleagues or senior leaders who guided them through workplace challenges.

“We look at our leaders as our role models, as our mentors” p7

“I would have definitely liked to have an experienced mentor in my career to have guided me” p15

“At this stage of my career I would like to have a sponsor but 10 years earlier I would have liked to have a mentor who can say come on you can do it your capable” p16.

Some women leveraged networking to build their career growth strategies.

“So, I think, learning and networking is very important that’s how when I got this position in this organisation, so networking is important, selling your projects is important” p23.

“I think, you have to build your network of support” p4.

“I have this experience on my own, you need to develop connections, you need to develop networking” p21.

Findings from the interviews highlight that none of the women are formally provided with career growth support, yet they actively used mentorship and networking strategies to build allies, market themselves, and showcase their achievements for career progression.

4.5.2 Theme 9: Navigating organisational culture

Women in Indian automobile organisations face distinct challenges rooted in deeply ingrained gender norms that influence workplace culture. The male-dominated organisational structure often reflects broader societal expectations, compelling women to confront systemic biases, redefine traditional leadership roles, and advocate for more inclusive policies. Four women leaders highlighted the presence of biases in recruitment and promotion practices, which hindered their progress into leadership positions. Twelve women leaders identified unconscious biases that required them to adjust their behaviour to match that of their male counterparts. Furthermore, twenty-five women leaders described strategies to improve organisational inclusivity. Of these, ten recommended shifting from gender-based to skill-based hiring practices to ensure equal opportunities, while fifteen stressed the need for fair access to responsibilities and involvement in decision-making processes.

4.5.2.1 Subtheme: Dealing with gender stereotypes and workplace biases

Women often encounter preconceived notions about their skills and competencies, which can lead to them working harder than their male counterparts to establish credibility and recognition.

P2 criticises diversity and inclusion policies for being diluted by bias, stressing that hiring should be based purely on skill.

“This diversity and inclusion thing is getting diluted, and this is due to bias, so I think the first thing is that you know people should be hired based on their skill and nothing else” p2

P24 highlights how her boss subjected women candidates to stricter scrutiny than men and how informal male bonding (e.g., smoking, drinking) excludes women from leadership circles.

“I have seen that bias in my boss, he would have 10 questions for a lady compared to a man. As a guy associated with the boss over smoking points, boozing together, which in a women’s case is not feasible” p24

P13 recounts how a female leader in her previous company was denied a promotion for seven years despite her qualifications and contributions.

“In my previous organisation there was a lady she was working within the HR department, I have seen her and supported her she was in a AGM level for seven years she did not get promotion, she even knew a foreign language that helped the company, but she never got a promotion and eventually left the company” p13

“So, people don’t understand, they have their perceptions, oh you use to be like this” p13.

“Automotive is a male dominated industry, that we cannot change, it is male dominated” p13.

P22 highlights affinity bias, where hiring preferences tend to favour candidates with a similar background, thereby limiting diversity.

“Unfortunately, there is affinity bias which makes us hire people who are either are like us or from a similar background. The organisation wants people who only think like the automotive” p22.

P8 acknowledges that acceptance of women in the industry is slow, often due to unintentional unconscious biases.

“So, from the very start, I think the industry takes time to accept a lady employee, everybody takes time. I would not say it is intentional; these are unconscious bias” p8.

P1 states that male colleagues perceive female employees differently, reinforcing the need for male leaders to rethink their biases.

“Again, a male colleagues look at me differently, male leaders to start thinking differently” p1.

P12 argues that workplace expectations should be uniform if men face criticism for mistakes, women should too, rather than being treated differently due to gender.

“If a male is doing a job in place of me a woman. If a man is in a job and he is getting scolded and if I am not because a woman, then something is wrong because it’s about the job” p12.

Women often find themselves adjusting their behaviour to fit into the industry’s male-dominated environment.

P3 observes that many women in leadership roles exhibit tough, serious, and traditionally masculine traits to be taken seriously.

“Just look at the women who are on top positions, they’re tough. They are like very serious, and this is really like behaving like a man. So, in this industry if you are even if you are not

really like a man, you have to show it. You have to act like a man. You have to like pretend and pre-show yourself as a strong man to be successful in this world. Because it's a male dominant industry especially the car industry" p3

P21 warns against adopting male behavioural traits such as raising one's voice to assert dominance, emphasising that women should remain authentic.

"Do not lose your own traits, do not try to become like a male, speaking in high voice, don't copy male traits, don't try to mimic somebody" p21.

P16 discusses her fight for freedom of speech in male-dominated workplaces.

"But in case of male bosses. I have always fought for my freedom and my freedom of speech" p16

P22 shares that she had to strategically navigate male ego to advance in her career.

"I have to navigate through a male ego" p22.

P6 describes how her male boss was unable to accept a female subordinate saying "no" to him, highlighting ingrained gendered authority biases.

"My boss at the point of time was a male. He could not take a no from me." P6

P21 characterises the industry as a "fight for survival," where women must continuously assert their place.

"I think as a woman you know you have to fight a lot. Fight for survival you have to fight to make your own place" p21

The gendered expectations and biases in the automobile industry take a mental and emotional toll on women. P2 expresses frustration over the slow acceptance of women in the automotive sector, contrasting it with the success of women in leadership roles in India's liquor industry.

“I don’t think I feel intimidated, but I think I did feel frustrated because you know auto industry is fairly male dominated. But you see, like in India you see a lot of women leading the liquor industry. Ideally that industry should be male dominated” p2.

P4 highlights high attrition rates, where many women leave the industry due to its male-dominated nature rather than a lack of interest.

“So, let’s say theoretically you recruit 200 women to work in the shop floor, because the plant is so male dominated. You are going to have a drop of about 85% women only 30 stays, that should not make people say women don’t want to work here” p4.

P8 discusses how workplace exclusion and lack of support led to feelings of depression and regret about joining the industry. She also highlights confusion surrounding POSH (Prevention of Sexual Harassment) policies, which some male colleagues see as a barrier to interacting with women, resulting in further isolation.

“So that time, it was like a situation where I was feeling depressed. Because my boss was not ready to accept me first of all. So that time I was like it is my wrong decision, I came here. So that I felt very low, I could not sleep also”. p8

“There is one more reason, could realise for this unconscious bias could be the policies which we have the sexual harassment polices yeah, the POSH policies due to which male colleagues are afraid to make a late-night call due to work emergency would that be like POSH”. P8

Women often face systemic challenges that hinder long-term career progression in the industry. P9 notes that engineering colleges have a low female enrolment in mechanical engineering, yet companies set a 50% gender diversity target, creating a contradiction between educational access and hiring expectations.

“Out of the 30 people only 2 women in the mechanical engineering in engineering college. So that’s how I landed in automotive industry. Yes, in this company the vision was clear from top management that they want 50% female” P9.

P11 asserts that women must repeatedly prove their capabilities to be accepted as equals in the industry.

“So, there are two types of people, one type of people who join in because they got the job and who are willing to do the job in the auto industry. The industry is worth it as the industry talks about inclusiveness” p11.

“People should be ready, to accept that yeah women can also do the work men can do” p11.

Women in the Indian automobile industry face significant challenges, including recruitment biases, cultural exclusion, leadership stereotypes, and emotional struggles. While some women adopt masculine traits to succeed, others advocate for authentic leadership and systemic change. Addressing these barriers requires policy reforms, unbiased hiring practices, mentorship opportunities, and inclusive leadership development programmes to foster long-term gender equity in the industry.

4.5.2.2. Sub-theme: Strategies to create an inclusive work environment

Women in the Indian automobile industry face unique challenges due to deeply embedded gender norms. To foster a truly inclusive workplace, companies must shift their focus from mere diversity metrics to creating a culture of acceptance, empowerment, skill-based opportunities, and respect. The insights from women leaders highlight key strategies for achieving this transformation.

Inclusion begins with genuine acceptance of employees as individuals, rather than merely meeting diversity targets. P3 emphasises the need to appreciate employees for who they are, without forcing them to conform to gender-based leadership expectations.

“Appreciate them for who they are. We do not appreciate so if we appreciate people for who they are and let them be who they really are” p3

P1 and P24 argue that while KPIs drive business outcomes, true inclusion comes from accepting individuals and valuing their contributions.

“Most important is acceptance, you have KPI’s that drive but they should not be the only metrics” p1.

“I think acceptability of authenticity and a system that accepts this authenticity” p24.

P2 advocates for the removal of outdated industry perceptions, emphasising that hiring decisions should be based on skills, not gender.

“I think the automobile industry first has to get rid of its baggage. They have certain perceptions. They are employing people based on gender but based on skills. Skill should be more important than gender” p2

P25 challenges organisational leaders to stop questioning women's capacity to succeed in the industry.

“Leaders in the organisation who still have this mindset in questioning where will she be able to do? Will she be part of the organisation? is she capable” p25

A workplace is truly inclusive when employees feel safe to express their ideas and concerns without fear of discrimination. P23 highlights that a leader should be able to speak freely without fear, regardless of gender.

“When you feel you do not have fear of speaking anything. You say whatever your mind tells you, your heart tells you. It’s not about women, man when in business that’s when inclusion comes into play” p23

P4 stresses that organisations must recognise biases and commit to continuous improvement, as no workplace is perfect, but all can strive for better inclusion.

“You have to be aware first of all that you’re starting from a place of imperfection so there is no perfect workplace, some workplaces are better than others, but you have to realise there is work to be done” p4.

True inclusivity means removing gender as a determining factor in hiring and leadership decisions. Hire and Promote Based on Skills, Not Gender: P5, P15, and P16 advocate for a gender-neutral approach to hiring and leadership, reinforcing that a manager is a manager, regardless of gender.

“For me gender is not a matter. Gender is only with appearance. Work is the same for both genders. But they think women leaders can’t do work in the industry. This is not correct” p5.

“Inclusivity is about being gender neutral take thoughts from both genders” p15

“Inclusive work culture means a manager is a manager whether it is male or female” p16.

P17 adds that equal opportunities should be based on skillsets, ensuring meritocracy in hiring and promotions.

“It means equal opportunity to everyone. It should be based on skillset” p17.

P7 and P11 emphasise that women should be included in all critical work decisions, just as their male counterparts are.

“If any work is planned then we both should be included in that. That is a male and a female colleague” p7.

“People should be ready to accept that female can also do the work that men do” p11.

P10 introduces a unique perspective, stating that women should also have the right to decline roles they are uncomfortable with and provide feedback on improving job assignments.

“It’s not about recruiting women; your number will increase. But the way your approach women. It’s not that you hire them and give them all the opportunities. No if they are not comfortable in a job they should be asked why, what kind of activities are they happy to do. Listen to the pros and cons” p10.

Theme 9 reveals the deep-rooted challenges that women face in navigating leadership pathways, many of which stem from entrenched biases and cultural perceptions within organisational structures. At the heart of these challenges lies a persistent bias in promotions, often shaped by unconscious prejudice and the internalised belief that leadership must conform to traditionally masculine traits. This has, in many cases, compelled women to adapt their behaviour to act like men in order to be seen as competent or capable leaders.

Such expectations are not only professionally limiting but also take a significant psychological and emotional toll. Women have often found themselves navigating fragile male egos and leadership hierarchies that resist inclusivity. The constant need to prove their worth, defend their competence, and assert their place at decision-making tables, without adequate support or validation, creates a draining and isolating experience.

These pressures do not arise in isolation; they are nurtured by workplace cultures that discourage openness and vulnerability. As a result, many women suppress their authentic

selves, fearing that any perceived imperfection might be interpreted as weakness. This not only hinders individual growth but stifles the broader evolution of inclusive leadership.

To address these challenges meaningfully, it is necessary to foster environments characterised by open communication and psychological safety, where individuals feel secure in expressing themselves without fear of judgment or reprisal. Promoting freedom of speech within organisations and creating space for diverse voices and perspectives is essential. Leadership must move away from rigid archetypes and embrace authenticity by acknowledging that imperfection is part of the human experience, not a disqualifier for leadership.

A cultural shift towards skill-based hiring and genuinely equal opportunities is critical. Women must have equitable access to responsibilities and decision-making roles, not as a favour, but as a right earned through ability and skill. Ensuring that responsibility is distributed fairly and that women's contributions are valued on equal footing will help dismantle the invisible barriers that have held many back. Only through such systemic change can organisations begin to undo the legacy of exclusion and create a leadership culture where women can thrive without having to compromise their identity.

4.6 Category D: Support Mechanism and relational capital

4.6.1: Theme 10 Gendered Expectations

This theme elucidates the ways in which women leaders contested prevailing gender expectations. Six women leaders emphasised the importance of redefining traditional leadership styles, while seven highlighted the need to move beyond mere diversity initiatives toward genuine empowerment. They further articulated how organisations can support women leaders without compelling them to adopt traditionally masculine behaviours.

4.6.1.1 Sub-theme: Challenging gendered expectations of leadership and performance

To succeed in leadership, women had to push back against traditional expectations of how a leader should act.

Women across the interviews described how they struggled to showcase a single style of leadership. Either way, they were criticised for either being too soft or too tough.

P3 mentions that she wanted to be known as a soft leader because otherwise, people would make fun of her.

“I was always wanted to be a leader, kind of softer not very aggressive” p3

P1 mentions how her personal life became a question to her leadership style in which she struggled.

“First of all being single and what are you doing in a leadership role? So, I was struggling for acceptance” p1.

P23 mentions how her leadership style brought forth a lot of discomfort due to the challenges she faced.

“I was leading the business unit for an organisation, those five years within that I was totally uncomfortable, the reason being I was always challenged. My competency was always challenged” p23

P4 mentions how imposter syndrome affected her leadership and was one of the biggest challenges she had to face in making her opinion heard.

“women leadership in India like there is always this element of imposter syndrome and I think that’s the biggest challenge for me its always fighting this imposter syndrome to say no my opinions matter” p4.

P5 was given a nickname in the workplace depicting her style of leadership. She was called a lady warrior.

“The team call me rajamata (warrior lady), so whatever she does we will do” p5.

P7 mentions how as a women leader she urges women not to judge oneself, as the possibilities of not being responded to, is natural within the industry.

“So, this is the thing, don’t judge yourself because others are not responding to you” p7.

From the participants, it is evident that it has been very difficult for women to adopt a particular leadership style, as they constantly faced challenges questioning their abilities. Hiring women is not enough; organisations must empower them with real opportunities, authority, and professional growth. Create conditions for Women to feel empowered: P6 differentiates between diversity (hiring women) and inclusion (ensuring they have power and influence). She argues that empowerment isn’t about “giving” power, but about creating an environment where women naturally feel empowered.

“Diversity is what you bring, inclusion is what you do with it. You can have all the women, but if they don’t have power and if they are not empowered, then they are not included. So, if you say inclusivity, I will say empower and empowerment is not a baton, like saying here I am giving you empowerment. Empowerment is creating the situation that make women feel empowered, it’s a feeling, it’s a title” p6.

P21 advises women not to mimic male behaviours to succeed but instead embrace their unique leadership qualities. P21 defines inclusion as respecting people regardless of their background and actively listening to their perspectives.

“I believe inclusion means respecting others. If someone comes from another background, are you respecting that? If you respect you will listen” p21

A professional, inclusive workplace is built on mutual respect, understanding, and fair treatment. P9 highlights how an inclusive culture positively impacts workplace behaviour, reducing foul language and promoting a more professional and welcoming environment. Foster a Culture of Respect and Listening: P9 highlights how diversity improves workplace culture, reducing toxic behaviours like foul language and exclusionary practise

“Once you have an inclusive work culture, your productivity would increase. The culture would improve, I have seen as a male dominated industry where a lot of fowl langue is used when there is a diversity ratio all these bad behaviour gets reduced.” P9

The strategies outlined by women in the Indian automobile industry reinforce a powerful message: inclusion is not about meeting quotas, but about creating a workplace where employees, regardless of gender, feel valued, empowered, and respected.

- Acceptance and appreciation should be prioritised over diversity metrics.
- Freedom of speech and psychological safety must be ensured.
- Hiring and promotions should be based on skills, not gender.
- Women should be empowered with real decision-making authority.
- Respect and fair treatment must be embedded in workplace culture.

By adopting these strategies, organisations can move beyond surface-level diversity initiatives and build a truly inclusive, progressive work environment.

Supporting women in leadership within the automotive industry requires a multifaceted approach that addresses both internal and external barriers. One of the most pervasive challenges faced by many women is imposter syndrome, the persistent feeling of not being good enough despite evident competence. Counselling and coaching can play a pivotal role in

helping women manage these feelings, providing them with a safe and constructive space to explore internal doubts, build confidence, and reinforce their sense of self-worth. Such support is not just remedial; it is developmental, empowering women to take ownership of their achievements and lead with confidence.

Beyond individual support, access to professional networks is vital. Women leaders benefit immensely from being part of broader professional communities, particularly when these include women from diverse industries. These cross-sectoral connections offer fresh perspectives, shared learning, and a sense of solidarity that can be deeply affirming. Networking opportunities not only open doors to mentorship and sponsorship but also counter the isolation that many women in male-dominated spaces experience.

Equally important is cultivating psychological resilience. Confidence-building exercises, imposter syndrome workshops, and peer support mechanisms help women build inner strength and better navigate the often challenging and ambiguous situations that come with leadership roles. These tools equip women to respond with clarity and self-belief, even in the face of subtle or overt resistance. The role of media in shaping societal and organisational perceptions cannot be overlooked. When media narratives consistently describe the automotive industry as "male-dominated," they reinforce the idea that women are exceptions rather than equal participants. This framing, though often unintentional, perpetuates unconscious bias and limits young women's aspirations by implying that they do not naturally belong in the sector. A more balanced and inclusive narrative, which highlights the contributions and successes of women, can play a transformative role in normalising female leadership in this space.

Organisations themselves must also evolve. It is essential that leadership is not seen through a singular lens. Redefining leadership expectations to value a diverse range of styles and strengths is key to building inclusive cultures. Training programmes should not only develop

women leaders but also support men in understanding and embracing inclusive leadership practices. This shift helps dismantle the stereotype that leadership must always look or sound a certain way.

Ultimately, companies must move beyond merely performing gestures of diversity. Skill-based hiring and promotion practices are crucial to ensuring that women are not hired or promoted merely to meet quotas, but because their talent and capabilities merit it. Fair and transparent recruitment and advancement policies send a powerful message that all employees, regardless of gender, are valued for their contributions. Only through such intentional and systemic change can the workplace become a genuinely inclusive space where all leaders, irrespective of background, can thrive.

Creating lasting change in gender representation within engineering and the wider automotive industry demands an industry-wide cultural shift one that goes far beyond surface-level initiatives. Professional organisations and policymakers have a vital role to play in challenging entrenched stereotypes and shaping an inclusive narrative that reflects the evolving nature of work. Too often, diversity initiatives remain compliance-driven, focused on ticking boxes rather than transforming mindsets. True inclusion requires collective commitment, where all stakeholders are engaged in reimagining the workplace as one that genuinely values difference.

One of the persistent barriers lies in the unconscious bias surrounding what roles women are deemed suitable for, particularly in technical fields like engineering and maintenance. These assumptions, often unspoken, limit opportunities and reinforce outdated perceptions about gender and capability. Addressing these biases at the institutional level is essential. A strong partnership between industry and educational institutions can help shift these narratives from an early stage. When young women are encouraged to see themselves in roles across the full spectrum of the industry, from design to diagnostics, they are more likely to pursue and thrive

in these careers. By showcasing the contributions of women in all areas of engineering and embedding inclusive messaging into education and training, industries can help dismantle the long-standing barriers that have kept women at the margins.

Within companies, there must be a conscious move beyond diversity metrics and towards building a culture rooted in acceptance, empowerment, and respect. An inclusive culture is not just about representation; it is about ensuring that all employees feel valued and able to bring their full selves to work. This includes cultivating psychological safety, a crucial element in any high-performing organisation. When employees feel safe expressing concerns, offering ideas, or admitting mistakes without fear of judgment or retribution, innovation and collaboration flourish. Leaders play a central role in setting this tone, and must be intentional in fostering open communication and trust at all levels.

Recruitment practices are another critical area where unconscious bias can either be reinforced or disrupted. Simple yet effective measures, such as removing gender identifiers from application forms, can help ensure candidates are evaluated purely on their skills, qualifications, and experience. By designing recruitment protocols that actively mitigate bias, organisations send a clear message that inclusion is not an afterthought but a fundamental principle guiding decision-making.

Together, these measures represent more than individual actions; they form the foundation of a broader cultural transformation. Through meaningful collaboration between organisations, institutions, and policymakers, the industry can transition from performative inclusion to a genuinely equitable future, where every individual is recognised for their potential, rather than being limited by their gender.

Theme 10 highlights a shift in how leadership is being redefined by women in the Indian automobile industry. Rather than conforming to traditional, often masculine, models of

leadership, women participants expressed a clear desire for genuine empowerment where they are supported into leadership roles without being expected to adopt traits that do not reflect their authentic selves. They emphasised the importance of fostering a workplace culture built on respect and positive behaviour, where toxic practices and discriminatory attitudes are actively challenged.

The barriers women encounter remain closely connected to deeply rooted gender norms, which continue to shape perceptions of leadership and capability. Overcoming these challenges requires a comprehensive approach, involving change at the individual, organisational, and industry levels. Promoting skills-based recruitment methods, investing in inclusive leadership development, and creating environments that value and respect diverse perspectives are essential steps. Only through such measures can the industry move towards a genuinely fair and progressive culture that allows women to lead on their own terms.

4.6.2 Theme 11: Navigating leadership in a male-dominated Industry

Women in the Indian automobile industry encounter substantial challenges as they navigate leadership roles within a traditionally male-dominated sector. Despite increasing initiatives aimed at promoting gender diversity, women leaders continue to face entrenched biases, organisational barriers, and persistent pressures to demonstrate their competence. Their progression into leadership positions necessitates resilience, adaptability, and strategic networking, enabling them to challenge prevailing stereotypes and create pathways for future generations. More than ten women leaders articulated their experiences of overcoming systemic barriers; notably, one participant's journey was particularly impactful, as she was the first woman to achieve several milestones in her career. Five participants provided concrete examples of advocating for diversity and inclusion within their respective organisations.

Furthermore, all twenty-five participants emphatically underscored the significance of transforming the automotive industry through influential and inclusive leadership.

4.6.2.1 Sub Theme: Overcoming systemic barriers and cultural resistance

The Indian automobile sector has long been influenced by entrenched gender biases, making it challenging for women to rise to leadership positions. Organisational cultures, rigid societal norms, and a lack of structured support for career development create substantial barriers.

Many women in the industry face inherent cultural challenges at work. While they have already overcome societal resistance to enter a male-dominated field, they still struggle to gain acceptance and recognition.

This was exemplified by P14, the first female engineer from her village. Despite discouragement from her community, her father believed in her talent and supported her decision to pursue engineering:

“So, when I started this diploma from my village no girl had gone thus far. But my father always supported me” p14

P14, from a remote village, overcame societal resistance to enrol in a mechanical engineering diploma. However, her struggles did not end there. As the only female student in her programme, she faced mockery and exclusion from her male peers.

“After that when I went to college, and I saw all boys then I got completely frustrated. They kept questioning why she came to this study, they shouted, they laughed stating what she will do what she will achieve” p14.

Even faculty members were unsupportive of her decision to study mechanical engineering:

“My class teacher even they were not interested in teaching me, even teachers where not supportive” p14.

Despite these obstacles, P14 persevered. With no encouragement from her teachers and opposition from her village, she worked hard and became a rank holder in her college, earning the highest marks in mechanical engineering. She was also the first female student from her college to be selected by one of India's largest automobile companies:

"My score was the highest in the college, I was the first female from my college to be selected by this large organisation" p14

However, the challenges continued. As the first woman in production at a leading passenger car manufacturer, she faced harassment and resistance in the workplace. One of her initial tasks was counting bins assigned to her because she was a woman. Though she now recounts this with a smile, her words reflect the mental strength and determination she needed to endure:

"When I joined this company, the first department I got was production with no female in this department. People around me started passing comments. I thought here also you people are torturing me" p14.

"The first job I was given was dustbin calculation, I said OK I will do it, because they were thinking they can't give technical work for female" p14.

Despite the workplace challenges, P14 never stopped proving herself. Over time, she gained acceptance, moved between companies, and grew within the industry. Today, with 13 years of experience, her journey stands as a testament to resilience and determination.

Similarly, P13 faced struggles when balancing work and personal life. When her mother was hospitalised, she was denied leave, and when she left work regardless, she was reprimanded:

"Once I had a fight with my boss because my mother was hospitalised, I told him I needed to leave, he said no. But I left office, I need to go to my mother. He called me halfway and asked how I could leave. All these actions would reflect either in my increment or promotion" p13.

For some women, the constant battle for recognition and respect became too exhausting. P1, after nearly five years in the industry and 20 years overall experience, ultimately chose to leave:

“Once I realised it was a lot of struggles, I felt like I was fighting against myself, cause at the end of the day when I put my head on the pillow, I should be able to sleep” p1.

P13 recalls a boss who used to share his story of having to report to a female boss and how he would mention negative things about her to her, giving her the feeling that she needed to be careful in the way she spoke to him and that he did not believe in women’s leadership.

“My boss had a female boss in his earlier job. So, when I use to have discussions with him he use to say negative things about her to me. This is a male ego reporting into a female. A women may be educated but still people try to pull her down” p13.

The stories of these women showcase their unwavering resilience in overcoming societal norms and workplace discrimination. Some have continued to forge ahead, creating their own spaces in the industry, while others have chosen to step back. Their journeys emphasise both the progress made and the ongoing challenges women face in the Indian automobile sector.

4.6.2.2 Sub-theme: Advocating for diversity and inclusion

Women leaders in the automobile industry are not only overcoming personal challenges but also actively working to create a more inclusive environment for future generations. They are driving policy changes, cultural shifts, and mentorship initiatives to ensure that women in leadership no longer face the same barriers.

P22, the head of diversity and inclusion, has taken proactive steps to support the growth of women’s leadership. She recognises that self-promotion is often a challenge for women and has implemented a strategy whereby women actively advocate for one another. This means

ensuring that a woman's name is mentioned in rooms of opportunity, a practice that men have long excelled at through informal networking.

"Women can't promote each other; women can't fix each other's crown. So, we said we will mention each other's name in room of opportunities, talk about each other's good work, sponsor each other and the ecosystem will manoeuvre itself brilliantly. Because men have figured this out, they fight go have a drink and become friends" p22.

Similarly, P24 shared how she and her two female colleagues built a support system within their department. They recognised the strength in standing together in an environment where they were significantly outnumbered.

"We gave each other a lot of support. We were three women; we were always like one against many" p24.

Advocating for diversity also means shifting the focus from gender to skills in hiring practice. P2 pointed to supplier companies within the automobile industry as a strong example of inclusive hiring. She hopes that this approach will also extend to core manufacturing roles.

"So, I am very happy to see the supplier companies to employ people not based on gender but skills" p2.

Another way women are driving diversity is by stepping out of their comfort zones and taking on roles traditionally not associated with women. P23 shared how she actively pushed herself into new functions to demonstrate that women can succeed in all areas of the industry.

"I want to come out of my comfort zone. So, I picked up this role" p23.

Women in the automobile industry are not just breaking barriers for themselves; they are paving the way for others by promoting workplace diversity, mentoring colleagues, and advocating for cultural change. Whether through sponsorship, solidarity, or challenging

traditional hiring norms, they are transforming the industry to be more inclusive for future generations.

4.6.2.3 Sub-theme: Transforming male-dominated industries through leadership influence

Women leaders in the automobile industry are not only breaking barriers but also reshaping leadership standards and instigating systemic change. Their leadership approaches focus on inclusion, empathy, collaboration, and adaptability, demonstrating that effective leadership need not conform to the traditional command-and-control model.

Women leaders have demonstrated that success in leadership extends beyond authority and control. Empathy, respect, collaboration, and adaptability are emerging as key leadership traits that foster inclusivity and long-term success. P23 shared her personal transformation from a controlling manager to an empathetic leader, learning to trust and empower her team:

“I was a controlling manager, I wanted to know where my team are, what he or she are doing. But now I am a totally different person, totally different leader” p23.

Similarly, P1 and P15 emphasised that leadership is deeply rooted in values and respect:

“I believe leadership is internal, leadership is all about respect. Leadership is all about stepping out of your comfort zone and giving the extra mile to make a difference to people that you lead” p1.

“Technically leaders may be sound but people management such as treating employees with respect, having a conversation, having faith is important” p15.

Several leaders highlighted the importance of collaboration in fostering an inclusive workplace.

P3 and P17 stressed that leadership is not an individual pursuit but a collective effort:

“You can’t be a successful leader, just by yourself. You have to set people for success” p3.

“It’s a combined effort, which gives visibility to both the leader and the team” p17.

P4 reinforced this by emphasising that leaders should listen and understand situations rather than being confrontational:

“There are different sides to a story so even if somebody is not doing something. Take time to calm down and not be confrontational” p4.

P6 highlighted how strong decision-making naturally leads to recognition:

“I never knew until now that recognition is the byproduct of making decisions that is useful for all” p6.

Similarly, P7 and P21 emphasised a leadership style that balances delegation with support and recognises the importance of gaining buy-in from male colleagues for inclusivity:

“As a leader I am delegating and supporting” p7.

“I learnt that I have to be supportive not just to women but male colleagues too. I realised that men need more understanding on how to deal with a women leader” p21.

As industries evolve, so must leadership styles. P9 spoke about the necessity of adapting leadership approaches to suit the changing workplace environment:

“So, the leadership style which I was following seven years down the line is not the same as I would need to adapt to the environment and whatever improvements is needed in me to adapt to this environment” p9

Meanwhile, P11 and P12 emphasised confidence and encouragement as essential leadership traits:

“Be more confident, I learned to understand about the type of people around you” p11.

P12 calls for leaders to be vocal, especially about anything positive, and to be more encouraging.

“You should be vocal and encourage your team. That’s the main thing as while they are growing in their career, they need that motivation. This calls for leaders to stay calm and be more understanding and to guide their teams through the mistakes they may make” p12.

P8 reinstates on the importance of hard work and as a leader taking responsibility and always being in a receptive mode.

“Hard work and taking responsibility, you should be in receptive mode” p8.

The insights from these women leaders reveal a new model for inclusive leadership, built on Empathy and respect, collaboration and support, confidence and adaptability, effective decision-making, delegation and encouragement. Through their leadership influence, women in the automobile industry are shaping workplaces that are not just diverse but truly inclusive.

Women leaders must continue to develop strong support networks, enhance their self-advocacy skills, and strategically navigate the complexities of workplace politics. Initiatives such as peer mentorship (P24) and sponsorship (P22) can empower women to uplift one another. Furthermore, building resilience through skill development, adaptability, and leadership training can help women maintain their confidence in male-dominated spaces.

Implement policies that promote fair task distribution and opportunities for career advancement for women. Educate male colleagues and leaders on inclusive leadership to reduce unconscious bias and enhance collaboration with female leaders. Promote voluntary job rotation across different departments, empowering women and fostering an inclusive culture.

For organisation-wide change, the focus should be on expanding hiring pipelines to include more women in technical and leadership roles. Encouraging companies to adopt transparent

promotion policies based on merit rather than gender. Creating organisation-wide forums for women leaders to share their experiences, support each other, and push for cultural change. Recognising and amplifying the voices of women leaders through awards, conferences, and media representation, where they are open in sharing their leadership stories.

Many participants expressed deep appreciation for this study, emphasising the value of having their stories brought forward. They recognised its potential to support future women in the industry and drive meaningful change.

“This study can have a bigger impact on the industry” p24.

“Thank you for taking up this study, this is so important. They might not have to struggle by the way we did. I am sure this study will definitely open up the eyes of the male leaders to start thinking” p1.

“Giving a platform like this for women to share their story is great” p21.

Additionally, some women found the process of sharing their journeys to be a moment of self-reflection:

“It was quite interesting; it refreshed and reminded me about my journey” p23.

These responses underscore the importance of platforms that amplify women’s voices, not only to inspire and guide future leaders but also to help women recognise their own growth and achievements.

Women must continue to cultivate resilience, adaptability, and peer support. At the workplace level, organisations must actively dismantle biases and implement inclusive policies. Systemic barriers can only be broken through structural reforms, increased representation, and cultural transformation. Women leaders in the automobile industry are not just surviving in this male-

dominated space; they are redefining leadership and reshaping the industry for future generations.

The eleven themes identified in the lead interviews were found to be deeply interconnected. This interconnectedness is visually represented in Figure 12, where three distinct thematic triads emerge. The first triad addresses research question 2, which sought to explore the internal challenges women face in navigating a male-dominated industry. The intersection of bias, gendered expectations, and navigating leadership in a male-dominated industry emerged as the core challenges. These themes reveal that the most significant internal struggles were not purely psychological but were shaped by persistent external gender-based barriers that women internalised and had to consciously overcome.

The second triad addresses Research Question 3, which examined how authenticity, leadership, and gender intersect to create a culture of sponsorship and advocacy for women's advancement. This triad highlights that a woman's professional identity was closely linked to her capacity for authentic leadership. By remaining authentic, women were better able to navigate organisational cultures marked by bias and gendered norms. This process made a meaningful contribution to their leadership development, enabling them to influence the culture from within.

The third triad addresses Research Question 1, which examined how successful women leaders navigated and thrived in asserting their leadership in the Indian automotive industry. This triad connects leadership development, building support systems, and mentorship in career. As women developed as leaders, they actively sought out and built support networks that included mentors and allies. These systems played a catalytic role in their professional growth, enabling them to sustain and expand their leadership roles within a traditionally male-dominated industry. It was observable that the themes were associated with one another; the correlation

between themes made it evident that they are interconnected and cannot be analysed in isolation. It's this interconnection that answers the research questions and helps answer the research objectives.

Figure 12: Cross relationship between nodes

4.7. Focus Group Discussion

The lead interviews offered detailed stories of personal leadership paths, providing individual views on how twenty-five successful women leaders steered their careers in the automotive industry. These stories gave a thorough analysis of the internal obstacles they faced, emphasising key barriers to their progress, such as the lack of advocacy, limited opportunities, and widespread unconscious biases.

The choice of focus group discussions (FGDs) as an additional data collection method in this study is both methodologically and contextually appropriate, especially given the exploratory nature of the research and the complex, nuanced subject matter being examined. The study aims to explore the lived experiences, perceptions, and leadership paths of women in Indian automotive organisations, a sector historically characterised by male dominance and structural gender inequalities. To effectively explore such detailed social phenomena, a secondary approach capable of eliciting rich, contextualised insights is crucial, making FGDs an appropriate selection.

Focus groups offered a distinct methodological advantage by fostering interactive dialogue, in which participants reflected upon, elaborated on, and built upon each other's viewpoints (Morgan, 1997). This collective dynamic was especially valuable for uncovering shared experiences, divergent opinions, and social constructions surrounding gender, leadership, and organisational culture within the automotive sector. Additionally, considering the relative paucity of research on women's leadership experiences in this domain, FGDs enabled the co-construction of meaning within a setting where participants felt affirmed and empowered by engaging with peers who shared similar professional trajectories.

Moreover, the collectivist cultural context of India further justifies the appropriateness of focus groups. According to Hofstede's cultural dimensions theory, Indian society exhibits a collectivist orientation, wherein group interactions and consensus-building represent culturally consonant modes of communication (Hofstede, 2001). Utilising such culturally embedded communication practices through FGDs enhanced participants' comfort, engagement, and willingness to disclose sensitive insights. This consideration is particularly pertinent in discussions of gendered leadership, where cultural and social sensitivities may inhibit candid expression during individual interviews.

Furthermore, FGDs allowed the researcher to observe group dynamics, non-verbal cues, and emergent themes, which were subsequently compared with findings from the individual interviews (Krueger and Casey, 2015). The triangulation of these data sources bolstered the robustness and credibility of the research outcomes. In sum, the adoption of focus group discussions is justified by their capacity to (i) generate rich and contextually embedded data, (ii) facilitate participant interaction that surfaces both collective and contrasting perspectives, (iii) align with cultural communication norms within the Indian context, and (iv) complement individual interviews to enhance methodological triangulation. This approach thereby strengthens the depth, validity, and interpretive rigour of the inquiry into women's leadership experiences in the Indian automotive industry.

The primary objectives of the focus group discussions were to identify shared workplace challenges, explore participants' perceptions of leadership styles, and examine how teams respond to women in leadership roles.

In this qualitative study, a total of 13 participants participated in five focus group discussions (FGDs) conducted within the premises of the participating automotive companies. These FGDs were scheduled subsequent to the completion of lead interviews, facilitating a comparative analysis between individual leadership perspectives and team dynamics. The primary objective was to explore the congruence between women leaders' self-perceptions and their teams' experiences, thereby providing a comprehensive understanding of leadership efficacy within the organisational context.

Each FGD session lasted approximately 75 minutes and comprised team members who reported directly to the women leaders previously interviewed. This methodological approach enabled an in-depth examination of subordinate perspectives on leadership styles, cultural influences, and organisational practice.

However, certain teams, particularly those consisting of technical staff, were excluded from participation due to ethical considerations raised by the organisation. This decision aligns with established ethical guidelines in qualitative research, which emphasise the importance of minimising potential harm, ensuring confidentiality, and obtaining informed consent, especially when discussions may involve sensitive topics or hierarchical dynamics.

The integration of FGDs following lead interviews provided a robust methodological framework for triangulating data, thereby enhancing the validity and reliability of the findings. This analysis of lead interviews and focus group discussions was aligned with hierarchical linear modelling (HLM) (Zhang, Zyphur, and Preacher, 2009), which helped partition the variance of the outcomes into within-group variance and between-group variance. In the case of this study, leadership traits such as authenticity, as observed in lead interviews, impacted team dynamics. This approach facilitated a nuanced exploration of how women leaders influence organisational culture and team development within the automotive sector.

Among the women leaders, 77% had teams reporting to them, while 23% were individual contributors. Fifty per cent of those with direct reports managed technicians (blue-collar employees), who were not included in the FGD. Teams not composed of blue-collar workers took part in the discussions.

Regarding team sizes under women leaders: 55% had fewer than five reportees. 9% had between six and ten reportees. 14% had more than ten reportees.

Table 32: FGD demographic details

Group	Department	No of members in the group	Women leader Participant	No of Male reportees	No of female reportees
1	Production	4	5	3	1
2	Communications	1	4	1	-
3	Compliance	3	6	3	-
4	Purchase	3	9	2	1
5	Product engineering	2	8	2	-

Table 32 presents the demographic details of participants involved in the focus group discussions (FGDs). It provides contextual information regarding participants' roles, experience, and organisational positioning. This table supports transparency and enhances the credibility of the focus group findings by situating participants' perspectives within their professional and organisational context.

The analysis was conducted using NVivo 12, where all five transcripts were uploaded, and constant words and themes were identified.

Figure 13: Word Frequency using NVIVO

Name	Files	References	Created On	Created By	Modified On	Modified By
Attitude		3	4 02/04/2025 19:39	B	02/04/2025 19:39	B
Challenges		5	14 28/03/2025 17:33	B	28/03/2025 17:33	B
Communication		4	12 02/04/2025 19:34	B	02/04/2025 19:34	B
Compliance		3	17 02/04/2025 19:39	B	02/04/2025 19:39	B
Fight		2	7 02/04/2025 19:55	B	02/04/2025 19:55	B
Leaders		5	105 28/03/2025 17:28	B	28/03/2025 17:28	B
Leadership		5	97 28/03/2025 17:28	B	28/03/2025 17:28	B
Operations		0	0 02/04/2025 19:33	B	02/04/2025 19:33	B
Perspective		5	46 28/03/2025 17:31	B	28/03/2025 17:31	B
Qualities of women leaders		0	0 02/04/2025 19:31	B	02/04/2025 19:31	B
Sponsorship		0	0 02/04/2025 19:32	B	02/04/2025 19:32	B
Straightforward		2	2 02/04/2025 19:37	B	02/04/2025 19:37	B
Tenacity		1	1 02/04/2025 19:38	B	02/04/2025 19:38	B
Trust		1	4 02/04/2025 19:38	B	02/04/2025 19:38	B
Vision		2	9 02/04/2025 19:35	B	02/04/2025 19:35	B
Women		5	196 28/03/2025 17:28	B	28/03/2025 17:28	B

The analysis follows themes and subthemes illustrated in Table 33.

Table 33: FGD-Themes-sub themes

Themes	Sub-theme 1	Sub Theme 2
1. Interrogating Gendered Assumptions in Organisational Contexts	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Breaking the Mould 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Facing Bias and Resistance
2. Influence of Leadership Approaches on Team Functioning	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Collaborative and Inclusive Approaches 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Empathy and Emotional Intelligence
3. Professional Competence: Establishing Credibility	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Earning Respect Through Results 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Overcoming the “Prove It Again” Bias

4. Mentorship as a Catalyst for Empowerment	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Investing in People 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Encouraging Career Growth
5. Transforming Organisational Culture	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Driving Culture Shift 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Need for Structural Support
6. Understanding Current Outcomes to Inform Future Trajectories	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Raising the Bar 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Inspiring the Next Generation

Table 33 summarises the themes and sub-themes emerging from the focus group discussions. It provides an organised overview of key patterns identified across the focus group data. This table supports analytical clarity by linking collective participant perspectives to the broader thematic structure of the study.

For the majority of the team, this was their first experience reporting into a woman leader, except for one member who had reported into women leaders, and that participant was from the communication department. From the various themes, the link between them was transparent. It was clear how similar to the lead interviews, gendered assumptions played a central role and how professional competencies were built on self-requested mentorships, which in turn contributed to women leaders influencing their teams. This resulted in an evidential transformation within the organisational culture. The lead interviews highlighted authentic leadership as the main ingredient in developing a woman leader's professional identity. In FGD, it's seen that the professional competency gained through authentic leadership has been the core in influencing the team. Overall, these themes led to an

understanding of the current outcomes and how the future of women leaders would impact automotive organisations. This interlink is evident in Figure 14.

Figure 14: Interconnected links within FGD themes

Using NVivo 12, a parent node was created, which formed the main theme; the child node formed the sub-theme, as provided in Figure 15.

Fig 15: FGD themes and subthemes using NVivo

4.7.1 Theme 1: Interrogating Gendered Assumptions in Organisational Contexts

This theme underscores the proactive efforts of women leaders in the automotive industry to challenge and transform entrenched gender stereotypes. Insights from Focus Group

Discussions (FGDs) reveal a dual narrative: while these leaders are redefining traditional roles and expectations, they continue to encounter implicit biases and resistance within their organisations. The FGDs highlighted various ways in which women leaders are breaking the mould.

One group shared how their female leader's cross-functional transitions acted as a catalyst for team support and cohesion. Another group expressed admiration for leaders who had advanced through the organisational ranks, finding their journeys both inspirational and motivating. Two groups, who had previously not worked with female leaders in their departments, were impressed by their leaders' commitment to project delivery and their ability to navigate diverse situations. Lastly, a final group described the experience of being led by a female boss as a refreshing and much-needed change, bringing unique perspectives and positive transformation to the department. These narratives illustrate the multifaceted impact of women leaders who, by stepping into roles traditionally held by men, not only challenge existing norms but also inspire and drive meaningful change within their teams and organisations.

4.7.1.1 Sub-theme: Breaking the Mould

Participants consistently emphasised the exceptionalism and adaptability of their women leaders. These leaders were praised not only for meeting expectations but often for exceeding them, particularly in environments traditionally dominated by men. Their ability to demonstrate both technical and strategic acumen was frequently cited as a key factor in dismantling gender-based assumptions.

FGD 1 recounted the story of their boss, the first woman to transition from a production role into engineering. They highlighted her strong decision-making skills and how her leadership enabled seamless collaboration across teams.

“She was moved to our department only last year from production to engineering. As a women leader she took some bold decisions. The interaction with her is very good. The operations with production, engineering and quality team are going smoothly” FGD 1

FGD 2 spoke about a former boss who had risen through the ranks, from a Graduate Engineer Trainee (GET) to head of operations an impressive trajectory in a male-dominated industry:

“She joined as a GET and when I met her, she was the head of operations that’s a huge progression in that organisation” FGD 2

FGD 3, part of the legal and compliance team, noted that this was the first time they had a female leader in their department. They recognised the significance of having a woman in such a position of authority:

“Here you can now see for the first time in women leadership our boss” FGD 3

FGD 4 expressed strong admiration for their first female leader in the purchasing department, underscoring her capabilities:

“As a women leader she can manage anything” FGD4

FGD 5 reflected on how the technical nature of work in the automobile industry had previously limited women's representation in leadership. They acknowledged their current experience with a female boss as a meaningful change:

“Earlier we did not encounter women bosses due to the nature of the work being more technical” FGD 5

Across various departments, including production, procurement, legal, compliance, and engineering, participants highlighted the emergence of women in leadership positions, often as the first female representative in those roles. Their stories reflect a broader shift in the industry,

where women are not only entering but excelling in domains once considered off-limits due to gendered expectations. These narratives of growth, from entry-level roles like GET (graduate engineering trainee) to senior leadership, illustrate how women are breaking the mould and redefining what's possible within the automotive sector.

4.7.1.2 Subtheme: Facing Bias and Discrimination

The focus group discussions reveal that women in leadership within male-dominated industries, such as automotive, frequently encounter subtle forms of bias and discrimination. These experiences span a spectrum from microaggressions and stereotypical assumptions to more covert limitations shaped by societal and organisational norms. While some responses initially appear to frame differences in gendered leadership styles as beneficial, a deeper analysis reveals underlying unconscious biases that can hinder women's growth.

In FGD 1, participants discuss how interactions differ based on the gender of the leader. An example was shared comparing conflict resolution styles between male and female bosses. While it may appear that female leaders face less resistance, the discussion revealed a more complex dynamic.

“If a male boss handles the situation with production and quality team, there will be conflict. In the same scenario for example a female boss if she comes and talks to the team, there will be no conflict. They will be polite, so all will shut their mouth frightened that it will come under harassment” FGD 1

This response points to a fear-based politeness rather than genuine respect or engagement. Team members often avoid open dialogue with female leaders out of concern that any disagreement might be misinterpreted as harassment. This protective silence inadvertently restricts female leaders from acquiring the same conflict management experience as their male counterparts, thus creating a barrier to their professional growth.

FGD 2 sheds light on the impact of preconceived notions about women in authority. A participant shared how his initial impression of a female boss was shaped by negative comment from colleagues, labelling her as a “terror” and “taskmaster.” However, personal experience shifted this perception:

“The tenacity of this women was completely different. Before I met her the information, I got about her that she is a terror, a work master, a task master that’s the perspective I got. But until and unless you know them personally you cannot come with a preconceived notion” FGD 2

This highlights how negative labelling and cultural narratives about assertive women can obscure their capabilities, even when they are breaking barriers and redefining leadership norms.

In FGD 3, participants from the compliance and legal teams recognised the challenges of being led by their first female superior in a historically male-dominated environment. They acknowledged progress in organisational efforts to include more women in leadership but still cited persistent biases:

“Still, you can see only our boss is the senior most women in leadership, but actually the organisation is doing its best to bring more women. Maybe if they have family, work life balance because sometimes we work until midnight, but women can’t do that” FGD 3

The assumption that women are unable to commit to extended working hours due to family responsibilities is a recurring unconscious bias. This belief, while often unspoken, affects women’s visibility and eligibility for higher roles.

FGD 4 brought forward perceptions around leadership behaviour. Participants described female leaders as emotional and prone to micromanagement, in contrast to male leaders who were perceived as emotionally controlled.

“Women leaders micromanage and are more impulsive unlike male bosses who are able to control their emotions” FGD 4

Such perceptions reflect a gendered framing of emotional expression and reinforce the notion that traditional masculine traits are more suited to leadership.

Lastly, FGD 5 discussed structural barriers related to industry norms. Participants attributed the underrepresentation of women in automotive leadership to the technical and physical nature of the work, which they claimed begins at the educational level.

“We have not encountered with a female boss before; you see the automobile industry is very technical and involves physical work this could be the reason why women have not been able to grow. Its more or less down to the engineering colleges” FGD 5

This view demonstrates how gendered assumptions about the nature of work and technical competence continue to reinforce exclusion. Across the discussions, a few key unconscious biases emerge:

Misunderstandings about harassment policies have led to a reluctance to engage in open dialogue with women leaders. There are also negative preconceptions surrounding women’s leadership styles, compounded by cultural tendencies to view assertive women in a negative light. Biases surrounding emotional expression further complicate perceptions, as emotions are often deemed less suitable in leadership roles. Additionally, there are deeply ingrained perceptions that technical and physical work is inherently male, a belief rooted in the educational pipelines that shape career paths.

Together, these biases form an ecosystem that subtly, but powerfully, limits the advancement of women in leadership, particularly in traditionally male-dominated industries. Some of the points that could be applied by automotive organisations are provided below.

Encouraging cross-functional exposure to women leaders can help normalise their presence and reduce novelty bias. Additionally, creating team-level mentoring programmes where women in leadership share their experiences with junior employees can support the normalisation of female authority and career progression. It is essential to design and implement leadership pipelines specifically aimed at women, particularly in technical departments, to ensure more inclusive representation. Showcasing the success stories of women leaders through internal communications can shift organisational culture and inspire others. Workshops and training sessions on key policies, such as the Prevention of Sexual Harassment (POSH), diversity and inclusion, and workplace harassment, should be conducted to raise awareness and prevent misconceptions. Finally, engaging in outreach initiatives by representing the organisation at universities and senior schools can introduce students, particularly girls, to the automotive industry, encouraging more women to pursue careers in automotive and mechanical engineering. These efforts will foster early awareness and challenge existing biases and stigma surrounding the industry.

4.7.2 Theme 2: Influence of Leadership Approaches on Team Functioning

This theme examined how leadership styles shape team dynamics, with a particular emphasis on collaboration, inclusion, empathy, and emotional intelligence. Participants shared two distinct perspectives within this theme: their direct experiences working with women leaders, and their broader observations about leadership in general.

The focus group discussions (FGDs) highlighted various approaches women leaders used to foster inclusion within their teams. For example, one group emphasised that their woman leader

used effective communication to cultivate an inclusive team culture. This same group also identified inclusive communication as a key leadership quality they valued in general.

FGD 2 underscored their leader's advocacy for the team as central to fostering inclusion, and noted that assurance from leadership was something they particularly appreciated. FGD 3 described their leader's dedication, sharing concrete examples to illustrate this quality, and observed that commitment to the team was an important leadership trait for them.

FGD 4 spoke positively about their leader's ability to manage challenging situations and highlighted her respect for each team member's individuality as an important leadership characteristic. Finally, FGD 5 emphasised their leader's provision of personal support, noting that her display of high emotional intelligence stood out compared to their previous male supervisors.

Throughout the FGDs, the sub-themes highlighted qualities that teams valued in their women leaders, which also matched their broader expectations of effective leadership. These shared values helped foster inclusive team cultures.

4.7.2.1 Sub-theme: Collaborative and Inclusive Approaches

Across all focus group discussions (FGDs), participants highlighted the importance of collaborative and inclusive leadership approaches. They particularly valued leaders who actively engaged in communication, decision-making, and support, fostering a positive and high-performing team environment.

FGD 1 highlighted the impact of effective communication by their woman leader. This strong communication facilitated smooth operations across various departments, including production, engineering, and quality. The leader's proactive decision-making, such as

proposing inventory reduction strategies, was seen as instrumental in overcoming technical challenges and enhancing teamwork.

“Interaction was very good and mainly the operations with support to production, engineering and quality teams, so the line operations are going smoothly. Also, she has good decision and good ideas. For example, change of reduction and the inventory reduction. This was the idea from our women boss, due to which it supported our work” FGD1.

FGD 2 appreciated the resilience and upward mobility of his woman leader, who rose from a Graduate Engineer Trainee (GET) to director of operations. Her acknowledgement and advocacy of team members’ work created a strong sense of trust and belonging.

“The tenacity of this women leader is completely different. Imagine she joined the company as a GET and when I met her, she was the director of operations which is a huge progression. I was given job by her which she very well appreciated and also built the trust between us” FGD2.

FGD 3, comprising members from the legal and compliance team, shared their first experience working with a female boss. They highlighted her dedication, particularly during a critical compliance deadline when she stayed with the team until late at night, reinforcing a sense of shared commitment and inclusion.

“Recently we had a very tough situation, we as a team including our lady boss, we completed app% compliance. We left office around 01:30 in the morning she stayed with us, and we completed the job” FGD 3

FGD 4 participants, also working with a female leader for the first time, emphasised her caring nature and ability to manage any situation. This nurturing yet capable style helped foster confidence and cohesion within the team.

“She can manage anything and very caring” FGD 4

FGD 5 reflected on how their female boss provided exceptional personal support during their onboarding process, helping them feel more comfortable and connected. They noted her empathetic understanding of team members’ mindsets as a distinguishing quality compared to male leaders.

“When we joined, she helped us personally by supporting in finding accommodation, showing us around the city. I think women are better in understanding mindset compared to male bosses. For sure women bring a different dimension to leadership” FGD 5

Across the five FGDs, several key leadership qualities emerged as particularly impactful in shaping positive team dynamics:

Effective leadership is founded on clear, frequent, and supportive communication that ensures smooth operations. Empathy and caring are essential, with leaders demonstrating emotional intelligence and genuine concern for their team members' well-being. Commitment and dedication are just as vital, as leaders are willing to go the extra mile, even in high-pressure situations. Trust and appreciation foster an environment of recognition and advocacy, which in turn boosts morale and strengthens team cohesion. An understanding of diverse perspectives and a commitment to inclusion create an environment where all team members feel valued. Finally, resilience and tenacity are key qualities of strong leadership, inspiring teams through a leader’s unwavering presence and pursuit of career growth.

These qualities collectively helped team members feel valued, supported, and empowered, ultimately improving collaboration and performance.

4.7.2.2 Sub-theme: Empathy and Emotional Intelligence

Leaders who demonstrated empathy and emotional intelligence were consistently described by participants as more effective, especially during high-pressure situations or when navigating interpersonal dynamics within teams. The ability to understand, connect with, and support team members emotionally was seen as a defining trait of successful leadership.

FGD 1 emphasised the importance of inclusive communication and equal treatment within teams. Participants criticised selective engagement by leaders, where only those deemed useful were given attention, arguing instead that empathy involves treating all team members with equal respect and regard.

“According to us interacting with all is very crucial, as an example only talking to people who we seek benefit from and ignoring the ones who may not be of use would not be considered as a good attitude of a leader. Empathising and talking to all is very important” FGD 1

FGD 2 shared how their woman leader provided guidance and reassurance during their early days in the organisation. Her empathetic approach and strategic clarity made a strong impact, with the participant describing how she handled larger responsibilities while still offering direction and support to new team members.

“For me as a newcomer, it was a cumbersome process. I think she nailed it, it was more like she took me under her tutelage and said there are big stuff I will handle don't worry, but kindly ensure you support me on all other activities and the kind of direction I get, the vision I get is pinpoint” FGD 2

FGD 3 illustrated their leader's emotional intelligence through her physical presence and commitment during critical project moments. Her willingness to stay late alongside her team was seen as a powerful expression of support and empathy.

“She stays up with us during crucial projects ignoring other constraints which is commendable” FGD 3

FGD 4 highlighted how working with a female leader positively influenced workplace culture. They appreciated the healthier, more respectful communication dynamics pointing to a reduction in the use of inappropriate language and an overall more thoughtful environment.

“We can have a good conversation with our boss in fact we have avoided using swear words at work” FGD 4

FGD 5 emphasised the emotional perceptiveness of their woman leader, especially in recognising unspoken personal challenges. They strongly felt that women leaders are more attuned to emotional cues and capable of responding with empathy often without needing explicit communication.

“They understand feelings, things going on at home compared to a man. A man does not have this speciality, he cannot figure out these things” FGD 5

Participants across the FGDs consistently valued leaders who could read and respond to the emotional landscape of their teams. Key expressions of empathy and emotional intelligence included:

Inclusive interaction involves engaging with all team members, regardless of their perceived utility, ensuring that everyone feels valued. Providing support during transitions is essential, offering assurance and mentorship to new employees as they settle into their roles. A strong leader maintains their physical presence during demanding times, rather than simply delegating tasks. Cultural sensitivity plays a key role in fostering respectful communication and promoting healthier workplace norms. Finally, emotional awareness is vital, with leaders recognising and responding to the unspoken personal and emotional needs of their team members.

Such leaders not only built trust and respect within their teams but also contributed to a more humane and supportive work environment, especially during periods of stress or uncertainty.

Individuals can model effective leadership by practising active listening, recognising the needs of their peers or juniors, and being emotionally present in team settings. Aspiring leaders should strive to strike a balance between strategic decision-making and empathy, treating people as valuable assets beyond their productivity. Additionally, feedback mechanisms can be introduced to encourage leaders to reflect on their emotional and inclusive engagement with their teams, fostering a more supportive and connected work environment.

4.7.3 Theme 3: Professional Competence: Establishing Credibility

The findings of this theme show that competency and credibility are essential prerequisites for women leaders seeking to build trust, respect, and secure sponsorship within their teams and broader organisational settings. Participants in the study consistently emphasised that, regardless of gender, leadership effectiveness depends on demonstrable abilities to deliver measurable outcomes, articulate a clear vision, and maintain credibility through consistent and high-quality performance.

Nevertheless, a recurring theme that emerged from the data is the heightened scrutiny faced by women leaders, reflective of the “prove-it-again” bias wherein women are required to repeatedly substantiate their competence to be regarded as equally capable as their male counterparts. Insights gleaned from the Focus Group Discussions (FGDs) elucidated various mechanisms through which women leaders actively cultivated credibility. Participants across all five FGDs unanimously acknowledged that women leaders demonstrated a pronounced result-oriented mindset, which contributed positively to perceptions of their leadership effectiveness.

However, the data also revealed that women leaders were frequently compelled to re-establish their competence on an ongoing basis. This phenomenon was predominantly attributed to the pervasive influence of unconscious bias, which subtly but persistently shapes evaluative standards and expectations within organisational settings.

4.7.3.1 Sub-theme: Earning Respect through Results

Across all focus group discussions (FGDs), a recurring narrative emerged that respect in leadership is earned through performance, rather than gender. FGD 1 stressed that leadership quality and attitude are essential attributes, independent of gender.

“A leader should have quality, irrespective of gender quality and attitude is very important”
FGD 1

FGD 2 reinforced this view, emphasising that leadership is judged by deliverables.

“It’s not just about representing here; at the end of the day you need deliverables. Nobody is going to debate whether you are a woman or a man unless and until you deliver projects” FGD 2

FGD 3 echoed this sentiment, highlighting the importance of vision and advocacy for the team.

“It’s not different for men or women, Leaders should be able to stand up for their teams, leader should have a clear vision. They should be able to guide us” FGD 3

FGD 4 provided specific examples of technical competence, highlighting that women have demonstrated their capabilities in core manufacturing areas, including challenging environments such as the welding shop.

“Women have proved themselves in core manufacturing even in shop floors which are difficult such as the welding shop” FGD 4

FGD 5 highlighted the multifaceted approach women bring to leadership, noting their comprehensive perspective and multitasking abilities.

“A women leader looks at perspectives in a 360 angle, so that alters how she approaches things resulting in her being a multitasker” FGD 5

Collectively, these insights demonstrate that teams are highly focused on the results achieved by women leaders. Respect and recognition are granted not based on gender, but on outcomes. Women who encountered challenges and transitioned between departments showed confidence and skill, particularly in technical roles within the industry. It is through these visible results and their consistent performance that women earn credibility and respect from their peers and teams.

4.7.3.2 Sub-theme: Overcoming the prove it again

While competency was acknowledged as a fundamental requirement for all leaders, several participants reflected on the higher burden placed on women to continuously “prove themselves” in order to gain and sustain the same level of credibility more readily afforded to men. This recurring need, to demonstrate competence reflects the broader “prove it again” bias that women often face in male-dominated industries.

FGD 1 offered an interesting paradox. When asked about the challenges faced by their woman leader, participants instead highlighted a perceived benefit, reduced conflict. They explained that departmental tensions, especially between production and quality teams, were more easily diffused under a woman’s leadership. While this was viewed positively, it subtly revealed an unconscious bias suggesting that teams were cautious about confronting a woman leader for fear of being perceived as inappropriate, possibly triggering harassment concerns.

“Actually, our observation, you asked us the question what challenges? But that is the reverse in our team, if our lady boss addressed a situation such as conflicts between production and quality team which always has a lot of conflict. In this situation a lady boss when she talks there is no conflict. They will be polite so it’s an advantage they are worried it would come under harassment” FGD 1

FGD 2 focused on the importance of career progression from technical roles. Participants noted that many male leaders had advanced from entry-level technical roles, gradually establishing their credibility as they progressed through the ranks. In contrast, women often lacked these early opportunities to showcase their technical expertise, which limited their advancement into leadership roles. The group emphasised that without placing women in technical roles early on, their ascent to leadership risks becoming performative, merely fulfilling diversity quotas rather than recognising true merit.

“Where the challenge lies are starting from scratch, today you look at the leadership level people have grown from operator level, it’s not about the capacity of the gender but without placing the gender in the right place if women want to pursue leadership they should be allowed to grow within the technical realm. Till know fortunately or unfortunately only men have been able to do these jobs” FGD 2

FGD 3 shared a more personal dimension of the challenges women face. During a high-pressure project, participants expressed concern for their woman leader’s safety, ensuring she reached home safely, an extra layer of responsibility that wouldn’t have been considered if the leader were male. This highlights the additional, often invisible burdens women carry in mixed-gender teams, which can create subtle barriers to equality in leadership.

“Only thing is we were worried about the ladies about how they will go and when they reach to message. Men mean we would not have to bother” FGD 3

FGD 4 drew attention to emotional expression, noting that women are often perceived as more emotionally expressive, whereas men are considered better at masking their emotions. This perceived difference was seen as a challenge for women leaders, who may feel pressured to suppress their emotions in order to align with traditional, agentic models of leadership.

“Women are very impulsive whereas men have better control over their emotions” FGD 4

FGD 5 acknowledged the emotional resilience women bring to their roles. While women may experience emotional breakdowns under pressure, they do not retreat. Instead, they continue to manage stress, multitask, and remain focused often better than their male counterparts. This constant pressure to perform and manage emotions serves as yet another channel through which women feel compelled to “prove” their capability.

“Women are multitaskers, they know how to handle situations, how to handle pressure, they know it better, they do have a breakdown, cry, but they will not step back. They still are able to handle the pressure better than a man. They are more focused.” FGD 5

Across the discussions, it became evident that women in leadership roles are subject to heightened scrutiny and a continuous expectation to validate their competence, whether by managing emotions, ensuring their own safety, or demonstrating technical expertise. Most participants compared their current or past experiences with male bosses, underscoring an unavoidable gendered lens through which leadership performance is assessed. Women leaders, therefore, navigate a complex landscape where exceeding expectations becomes the norm, not the exception, in order to be seen as equally capable. The following initiatives are recommended for automotive organisations aiming to promote gender equity and support women's leadership development:

To support and strengthen women's leadership in the workplace, organisations can adopt a multi-layered approach. Regular sensitisation workshops should be conducted to build awareness, unpack implicit biases, and normalise emotional expression across genders. Creating a psychologically safe environment is key, where women leaders can express themselves without fear of judgment, and safety concerns are addressed in a structured and non-paternalistic manner. Performance narratives that highlight the impact and credibility of women leaders should be documented and shared to reshape perceptions. Teams that have worked under women leaders can contribute to group mentorship programs, helping to reinforce inclusive leadership models. Structured peer feedback mechanisms should replace repeated competence tests, offering constructive and equitable growth opportunities. Career progression frameworks must intentionally place women in foundational technical roles early on, establishing clear pathways to leadership. Performance evaluations should include bias training for reviewers and revise KPIs to value emotional intelligence, conflict resolution, and team advocacy. Additionally, systemic policy interventions such as flexible working hours and safe transport should ensure women's autonomy and safety. Finally, organisations must shift the leadership narrative by publicly recognising not only outcomes but also the unique strengths women bring to leadership, such as resilience, adaptability, and multitasking.

4.7.4 Theme 4: Mentorship as a Catalyst for Empowerment

Mentorship has emerged as a critical mechanism in advancing women's leadership, serving not only as a conduit for professional development but also as a catalyst for empowerment and organisational transformation. Participants in this study consistently underscored the multifaceted role of mentorship, highlighting its capacity to provide guidance, instil confidence, and foster intentional growth among emerging women leaders.

Evidence from lead interviews revealed a perceived deficit in advocacy for women within leadership trajectories. Contrastingly, focus group discussions (FGDs) illuminated a more nuanced narrative, wherein participants recounted instances of their women leaders actively championing team development. Across all five FGDs, women leaders were portrayed as proactive mentors who invested time, care, and influence to elevate their teams, thereby cultivating environments conducive to personal and professional advancement.

Notably, two FGDs emphasised the presence of empathy as a salient quality among their leaders, suggesting that emotional intelligence played a pivotal role in effective mentorship. This aligns with existing literature that posits relational leadership characterised by empathy, support, and shared growth as instrumental in fostering inclusive organisational cultures.

The collective insights from these discussions provide demonstrable evidence that mentorship, when executed with intentionality and empathy, serves as a powerful tool for empowerment. Women leaders who embrace mentorship not only facilitate individual growth but also contribute to the broader objective of achieving gender equity in leadership positions.

4.7.4.1 Sub-theme: Investing in People

Across focus group discussions, women leaders were consistently recognised for their deep investment in people, which manifested in multiple ways, from advocating for team members' work to management, to attending to their personal and technical growth, and even prioritising emotional well-being and safety.

Women leaders were seen as active sponsors, often taking ownership to spotlight team members' contributions and enabling their advancement.

“I am from computer science background, I joined here for interpretation, but after doing my work I was admired and asked if I can shift to technical work, and I was moved to production”

FGD 1

This transition from contractor to full-time employee highlights how women leaders create opportunities based on merit.

FGD 2 emphasised how strategic guidance and advocacy opened doors.

“When my boss and I are working together no matter what the timelines, we genuinely plan a lot, she gives direction with pinpoint plan which I like a lot. She took my work to the management, and I was well appreciated for it” FGD 2

FGD 3 reflected on the importance of intentional sponsorship in promotion pathways.

“Without sponsorship, it would be difficult to get promotion. So, without sponsorship it’s not possible. A justification should be made before sponsoring” FGD 3

These instances show that empowerment is not passive it’s a deliberate act of recognition, representation, and support.

Women leaders were also observed to prioritise relational care, checking in on team well-being, offering emotional support, and fostering open communication.

FGD 4 underscored women’s empathetic engagement.

“In comparison to men women care more and understand more” FGD 4

FGD 5 illustrated how this concern translated into real-time support.

“In our work we have to be available 24/7 or till the line is running to be able to handle any issues we have to make ourselves available. Whenever we are in the plant, or in the car or

working on something she will always check on us and see if we have reached home, if we are following safety protocols, though these are small things, it matters” FGD 5.

These reflections portray a holistic approach to leadership where concern for outcomes is matched by care for people. Women leaders mentor by doing, they advocate, guide, and build others up with intention. Empowerment is personalised and contextual; it includes technical development, emotional support, safety assurance, and career sponsorship. The effectiveness of women leaders is closely tied to their investment in people, reinforcing trust, loyalty, and high performance within teams.

4.7.4.2 Sub-theme: Encouraging career growth: Career growth is not solely dependent on skill or opportunity.

it flourishes in environments that actively nurture learning, recognise individual potential, and provide support for taking on new challenges. Within the automotive manufacturing sector, these elements are particularly crucial for women, whose professional trajectories are often shaped by leaders who foster inclusion and empowerment.

Across the FGDs, participants highlighted how women leaders played a vital role in enabling career development, often by going beyond traditional managerial responsibilities to create a supportive, motivating, and inclusive team environment.

Women leaders were observed to create diverse and collaborative team cultures, intentionally mixing backgrounds, experiences, and skills.

FGD 1 illustrated a team composed of members from diverse backgrounds, including a newly joined employee, someone who had shifted from computer science to engineering, and a senior team member, all led by a woman leader who had herself transitioned from a core production role to a new department.

“I moved to this department two years back, the other team member was sponsored from computer science to this department and the other team member is fairly new. Our lady boss who moved from core production moved to this team last year. We feel very close to our boss, the closeness at work and personal life” FGD 1

This reflects a culture of inclusivity that strengthened team bonds and effectiveness.

Encouragement came not only from emotional support but also through careful planning and vision, enabling team members to excel in their roles. FGD 2 highlighted how the woman leader’s precise guidance and planning helped unlock creative potential.

“When me and my boss are working together, we genuinely plan a lot, the direction she gives is pinpoint. I am able to deliver the most creative output possible” FGD 2

This kind of structured empowerment allowed team members to feel both capable and motivated.

Women leaders also promoted collaboration across departments, encouraging broader exposure and skill development.

FGD 3 shared an example from the compliance and legal team, where the woman leader coordinated with a female colleague from finance to deliver a successful audit project.

“We as a team including our boss, we completed 100% non-compliance, we stayed up to 01:30 along with a lady from finance team who supported us, it was a joint work, we went happy home.” FGD 3

This underscores how cross-functional teamwork, led by inclusive leadership, created a sense of shared accomplishment and pride.

Empowerment was also deeply embedded in day-to-day interactions, where women leaders demonstrated empathy, inclusivity, and a shared sense of responsibility. FGD 5 illustrated how small acts of solidarity during high-pressure situations made the team feel valued and supported.

“Some we get a task at 12:00 it takes two or three hours to finish the task, and we sometimes miss to have our lunch at the canteen, but our lady boss during pressure times she will also skip for us, or she permits us to take a quick break and get back to work” FGD 5

Such behaviour builds trust and emotional connection, reinforcing a workplace culture where team members feel seen and cared for. Women leaders encourage career growth by creating inclusive spaces, planning strategically, and leading collaboratively. Their influence extends across technical empowerment, emotional encouragement, and cross-functional exposure. Through simple but consistent actions, whether through sponsorship, direction, or shared effort, they foster a culture where people are empowered to learn, grow, and succeed. The subsequent analysis identifies key elements that automotive organisations may leverage to enhance their operations:

To foster inclusive and empathetic leadership practices, organisations should embed supportive systems into everyday team culture. Peer coaching and shadowing programmes can encourage experienced team members to mentor newer colleagues, modelling behaviours demonstrated by effective leaders. Establishing a check-in culture where emotional and well-being check-ins are normalised during team rituals such as stand-ups or reviews further reinforces psychological safety. Structured planning sessions that value collective input can reflect the collaborative direction-setting often practised by women leaders. Recognition systems, such as “contribution spotlights” or team shout-outs, help build a culture of visibility and appreciation. Formal sponsorship programmes should be integrated into talent development frameworks to

ensure high-potential individuals receive advocacy at senior levels. Leadership evaluation metrics should include empowerment KPIs, capturing efforts in mentorship, cross-functional exposure, and team development. Inclusive leadership training across all management levels should focus on empathy, active listening, and coaching-based approaches. Additionally, internal mobility programmes can provide pathways for non-traditional talent, such as transitions from customer support to engineering, based on capability and interest. Finally, it is essential to recognise emotional labour and relational leadership behaviours as critical competencies, not secondary or “soft” skills.

The findings demonstrate that women leaders are not just managing, they are transforming their teams through deliberate, relational, and inclusive empowerment. Their methods offer replicable practice that can be scaled across teams and embedded into organisational culture. By investing in people, advocating for them, and modelling collaborative leadership, they elevate not just individual performance but collective capacity.

4.7.5 Theme 5: Transforming Organisational Culture

In traditionally male-dominated sectors such as the automotive industry, organisational culture has historically been shaped by technical roles, physical labour, and hierarchical decision-making structures. Within such environments, the inclusion of women in leadership positions is increasingly seen not merely as a compliance-driven policy shift but as a catalyst for deeper cultural transformation.

Focus Group Discussions (FGDs) carried out in this study revealed that women leaders have played a crucial role in transforming organisational cultures within the automotive sector. Participants highlighted several cultural changes attributed to the presence of women in leadership roles. Notably, two FGDs emphasised that the inclusion of women leaders led to the development and implementation of policies and processes specifically designed to support

female employees. One FGD mentioned a noticeable shift in organisational culture, attributing this change to the influence of women in leadership positions. Furthermore, two FGDs reported that the presence of women leaders enhanced authenticity in leadership practice, fostering a more inclusive and transparent organisational environment.

Despite these positive developments, participants underscored the necessity for structural support to sustain and amplify the impact of women leaders. Two FGDs highlighted the significance of mentorship programmes, particularly during the early stages of women's careers, as a means to facilitate professional growth and leadership development. Additionally, FGD 2 cited the role of educational institutions in reshaping gender attitudes towards the automotive industry, suggesting that early interventions could help challenge prevailing stereotypes and encourage more women to pursue careers in this field. FGD 3 outlined the importance of providing emotional support for women leaders, recognising that such support mechanisms are crucial for their sustained success and well-being.

These findings collectively suggest that while the inclusion of women in leadership roles has initiated positive cultural changes within automotive organisations, there remains a critical need for comprehensive structural support. Implementing mentorship programmes, engaging educational institutions, and providing emotional support are essential strategies to ensure the continued advancement and empowerment of women leaders in the automotive industry.

4.7.5.1 Sub-theme: Driving culture shift

Participants across focus group discussions (FGDs) emphasised that fostering cultural change requires deliberate and sustained organisational efforts. This includes enhancing gender representation, improving workplace infrastructure, and most importantly, shifting perceptions regarding women's capabilities and contributions.

FGD 1 noted the current underrepresentation of women in the workforce, with most sections reflecting a 90:10 male-to-female ratio. However, participants acknowledged that the organisation is actively promoting women into leadership roles.

“In our organisation most of the sections has a 90:10 ratio so only 10% comprises of women employees. The organisation is promoting women leadership with our leaders focused on the same” FGD 1

FGD 2 cautioned against over-engineering DEI initiatives merely for compliance or KPI fulfilment. Instead, they advocated for a culture where inclusivity is rooted in performance and outcomes, irrespective of gender.

“Let’s say we take India as a country we are inclusive with so many official languages and dialects. However, from a company point of view inclusivity should be about results. Anyone who is able to provide results they should be elevated irrespective of gender” FGD 2

FGD 3 underscored the value of balanced gender representation, stating that women bring different perspectives that can enhance decision-making and add business value.

“Actually, inclusive work means both men and women should be in equal proportion. As women may give some different kind of thinking that will help the company make the right decisions” FGD 3

FGD 4 emphasised that driving cultural change is about creating equal opportunities for everyone, regardless of gender.

“It’s about providing equality of opportunity and change irrespective of gender; this makes a huge difference to the culture of the organisation” FGD 4

FGD 5 suggested developing an authentic skills map that recognises individual capabilities and integrates diverse viewpoints into the organisational culture.

“Treat employees as shareholders, create an authentic skill map and take everyone’s point of view and define the culture accordingly” FGD 5

While DEI initiatives are acknowledged as steps in the right direction, participants stressed that true cultural transformation hinges on a shift from gender-based metrics to skill-based evaluations. Inclusion, they argue, should not be symbolic but grounded in competence, ensuring that all individuals have equal opportunities to contribute and grow. Cultural evolution in such traditionally masculine industries is possible when merit becomes the core measure of progress.

4.7.5.2 Sub-theme: Need for structural support

Across all focus group discussions (FGDs), participants emphasised that cultural transformation in traditionally male-dominated sectors such as manufacturing and automotive requires more than attitudinal changes and leadership advocacy. Robust structural support is crucial for maintaining long-term inclusivity. This includes not only workplace infrastructure and equal opportunity mechanisms but also softer forms of support such as mentorship, sponsorship, and emotional safety.

Participants in FGD 1 highlighted the importance of mentorship, particularly when women leaders transition between departments. One example shared was of a woman leader who moved from production to planning and had to make critical decisions without adequate support. Despite having a diverse and strong team, the absence of mentorship posed challenges:

“I think mentorship is very important our boss had moved from production to planning and we are a fairly new team that came together we are strong, but our boss would have benefited from a mentor. Though women need good facilities this kind of mentorship is even more important” FGD 1

FGD 2 emphasised the foundational role of educational institutions in preparing women for technical leadership roles. Participants noted that low female representation in core engineering disciplines like mechanical and automobile engineering limits their opportunities to prove technical capabilities and rise in their careers:

“If you take mechanical, automobile engineering areas you have limited representation of girls, so when they are less there how can they prove their skills technically to be able to grow into leadership roles in the industry” FGD 2

Participants in FGD 3 highlighted safety concerns for women, particularly during late working hours. Despite existing protocols, safety concerns often lead to informal redistribution of responsibilities and added emotional burdens for male colleagues:

“When we finished the work at 01:30 we were worried about our boss and the finance lady if they reached safely home which would not have been a concern if it was a man” FGD 3

FGD 4 underscored the importance of emotional support for women leaders. They discussed the need for safe spaces where women can express emotions without judgment, noting that societal expectations around emotional restraint differ by gender:

“Since women are more impulsive, they are not in a position to control their emotions like a man does” FGD 4

FGD 5 highlighted the distinction between mentorship and sponsorship. While mentorship is beneficial early in a woman’s career, sponsorship, having someone advocate for them at decision-making levels, is viewed as a more powerful enabler of career advancement:

“Mentorship in the beginning of their career is good. But actually, women need someone to sponsor them, talk for them” FGD 5

The insights across FGDs reveal that structural support for women in male-dominated sectors must go beyond policy and infrastructure. Key components include: Supporting women's leadership requires intentional strategies across different stages of their careers. Providing mentorship during transitions or the early stages of new roles is crucial for building confidence and competence. Developing educational pipelines ensures sustained representation of women in technical domains, addressing long-term gender imbalances. Workplace safety measures must be designed in a way that does not unintentionally burden others or restrict women's opportunities. Emotional support systems should recognise and accommodate diverse styles of emotional expression, fostering an inclusive environment. Furthermore, structured sponsorship is crucial for enhancing women's visibility and credibility within leadership circles, enabling them to gain the recognition and influence they deserve.

Collectively, these elements form a comprehensive support system critical to fostering and sustaining gender inclusivity in the workplace.

Addressing the systemic challenges women face in leadership roles requires a comprehensive and inclusive approach. Teams have observed mentorship gaps when women transition into unfamiliar roles, often resulting in underperformance or isolation. To counter this, peer buddy systems and cross-departmental mentoring should be implemented, alongside formalised onboarding support for internal role changes. Safety concerns, which often place emotional and logistical burdens on teams, can be alleviated through flexible work hours, safe transportation options, and equitable workload distribution, without making assumptions based on gender. Tackling gendered emotional norms is equally vital; organisations should conduct emotional intelligence training, promote psychological safety, and normalise emotional expression as a sign of strength. Day-to-day inclusion can be strengthened by encouraging diverse input in decision-making, ensuring equal speaking time in meetings, and holding

regular check-ins on inclusion. Authentic DEI integration must go beyond diversity metrics by embedding inclusive practices into performance reviews, leadership KPIs, and talent development systems. Strengthening the talent pipeline is also essential; this includes partnerships with universities and STEM institutes to deliver targeted outreach, internships, and scholarships for female engineering students. Structured sponsorship programmes should be introduced, with senior leaders actively championing high-potential women, and sponsorship responsibilities embedded in leadership development frameworks. To build a skill-based culture, organisations should develop transparent, inclusive skill-mapping systems that reward collaboration, innovation, and measurable outcomes over titles. Finally, leadership culture must shift through targeted training on inclusive behaviours such as equitable delegation, active listening, and bias-free evaluation, underpinned by clear accountability mechanisms.

To achieve true cultural transformation in male-dominated sectors like manufacturing and automotive, organisations must address both structural and cultural levers. At the team level, this means fostering mentorship, ensuring emotional and physical safety, and embracing authentic inclusion. At the organisational level, it requires going beyond compliance, investing in educational pipelines, embedding sponsorship, and building a performance-driven but inclusive culture. The shift from symbolic diversity to sustainable inclusion hinges on one key idea: Meritocracy thrives when all individuals, regardless of gender, are supported to perform at their best.

4.7.6 Theme 6: Understanding Current Outcomes to Inform Future Trajectories

Within the automotive manufacturing organisations, women in leadership roles are increasingly recognised as transformational agents who not only influence organisational culture and performance but also redefine standards of effective leadership. Their leadership

approach, often characterised by meticulous attention to detail, unwavering commitment, and empathetic vision, challenges conventional leadership paradigms and inspires future generations of leaders.

The analysis of this theme underscores the pivotal role of women leaders in shaping the future trajectory of leadership within the automotive sector. Focus Group Discussions (FGDs) revealed that women leaders are perceived as setting higher benchmarks for leadership excellence. For instance, participants in FGD 1 highlighted how women leaders elevate leadership standards through their performance and dedication. FGD 2 participants emphasised the extraordinary commitment exhibited by women leaders, often extending beyond standard working hours. FGD 3 sheds light on the significant strides women leaders have made in technical domains, leading critical projects and dismantling entrenched unconscious biases that previously confined certain tasks to their male counterparts.

A recurring sentiment across FGDs was the imperative for organisations to foster environments where women can lead authentically, without the pressure to emulate traditionally male leadership styles. Participants advocated for organisational cultures that embrace diverse leadership approaches, recognising that authenticity enhances leadership effectiveness and organisational cohesion. Moreover, several FGDs called upon organisations to proactively create opportunities for women to demonstrate their capabilities, thereby facilitating equitable pathways for career advancement.

All five FGDs collectively emphasised the necessity for organisations to actively promote sponsorship and delineate clear internal growth trajectories for women. Such initiatives are vital in cultivating a robust pipeline of female leaders and ensuring sustained gender diversity in leadership roles. This aligns with existing literature that underscores the transformative impact of women in leadership positions within the automotive industry, highlighting their role

in driving innovation, enhancing decision-making processes, and fostering inclusive workplace cultures.

In summary, the findings advocate for a paradigm shift in organisational practice, urging the adoption of strategies that support authentic female leadership, facilitate equitable opportunities, and institutionalise sponsorship programmes. Such measures are instrumental in harnessing the full potential of women leaders, thereby propelling the automotive organisations towards a more inclusive and dynamic future.

4.7.6.1 Sub-theme: Raising the Bar

Participants emphasised that women in leadership are elevating expectations across several dimensions: technical competence, emotional intelligence, commitment to team success, and the creation of new leaders. These women are not just fitting into existing norms but reshaping what effective leadership looks like.

Participants admired their female leader's willingness to step out of her comfort zone by transitioning from production to planning an area outside her original expertise. Her readiness to learn and take bold decisions was seen as a hallmark of progressive leadership:

"Initially our boss took a bold decision to move across these departments is not easy" FGD1

FGD 2: From Entry-Level to Entrepreneur: An inspiring journey was shared of a woman who rose from a Graduate Engineer Trainee (GET) to Director of Operations and eventually an entrepreneur. Her story reflects resilience and operational excellence, despite facing criticism early in her career:

"I know her capacity she has been in the industry; she is in a different level when it comes to operations" FGD 2

FGD 3: Commitment Beyond Hours: Participants recalled a project where their woman leader worked late into the night with the team, demonstrating unwavering dedication. Her presence was not symbolic but active, reinforcing her commitment to team success:

“The commitment with the same intention towards results, so we are happy, and we all left happy” FGD 3

FGD 4: Breaking Barriers in Technical Spaces The presence of women in roles like welding, once considered off-limits, stood out as a powerful example of how women are redefining the boundaries of what’s possible in the workplace:

“Women can manage anything; you will find women even in wielding shops in our company” FGD 4

FGD 5: Creating New Leaders. Leadership was also seen in the ability to recognise and elevate others. A woman leader was praised for delegating a major project and sponsoring another employee to take charge, fostering leadership in others:

“She recommended my name and said I have the potential, so previously she was leading that project, but she gave the project to me and said I can do it” FGD 5

Women leaders, as illustrated across the FGDs, are raising the bar, driving change by boldly embracing unfamiliar challenges with a growth mindset, and pursuing transitions that push boundaries. They demonstrated remarkable resilience, rising from entry-level positions to senior leadership and entrepreneurial roles, frequently in the face of scepticism. Their unwavering commitment to delivering results and supporting team success, even under high-pressure conditions, sets a powerful example. By breaking technical stereotypes and venturing into traditionally male-dominated areas such as welding, they are reshaping perceptions around gender and capability. Moreover, by actively developing and sponsoring future leaders, they

empower others and create a lasting ripple effect of inclusion across their organisations and industries.

These examples showcase not only the current influence of women in leadership but also an inspiring vision for the future. By embodying courage, competence, and collaboration, women are setting new standards for leadership. Their journeys motivate a redefinition of workplace norms and signal a future where gender is no longer a barrier to success but a catalyst for broader organisational excellence.

4.7.6.2 Sub-theme: Inspiring the Next Generation

Across the focus group discussions, a common thread emerged: the powerful ripple effect of women in leadership. Participants emphasised that visibility matters when women lead authentically, they inspire others to believe in their own potential. To nurture the next generation of women leaders, several key enablers were highlighted.

Encouraging Authenticity in Leadership: Participants in FGD 1 stressed the importance of allowing women to lead authentically, without the pressure to conform to traditionally agentic leadership styles. They highlighted that organisation must foster environments where women feel safe to be themselves.

“Women leaders needs to be themselves; this needs to be supported by organisations” FGD 1

Early Engagement and Exposure in Education: FGD 2 participants discussed the importance of engaging girls in technical subjects like physics from an early stage particularly in senior school and college. This exposure can spark interest in technical careers, creating a natural pipeline into leadership roles. Additionally, they emphasised the need to view diversity and inclusion more broadly.

“Today’s parents are not that narrow minded, it’s all about the personal choice and I think we need to start at schools and colleges to understand what girls want of their careers. It could be a basic dislike or misunderstanding of the industry” FGD 2

Creating Opportunities for Women to Prove Themselves (FGD 3): FGD 3 highlighted the need to provide women with tangible opportunities to demonstrate their capabilities. Without these chances, potential remains untapped.

“Give opportunities for them to be able to prove themselves” FGD 3

Building a Friendly and Non-Judgemental Culture (FGD 4)

Creating a safe and supportive organisational culture was a key point in FGD 4. Participants noted that a culture where women feel comfortable, accepted, and free to express themselves is essential. They cited the positive example of a woman leader who cultivated such an environment.

“Give them a culture that is friendly and non-judgemental were the mindset of employees in accepting women the way they are is crucial and also women leaders should not be bothered about what others say but keeping giving their best. Women create a friendly culture” FGD 4

FGD 5 emphasised the role of internal sponsorship in combating unconscious bias. By enabling women to grow within the organisation, others witnessed their journey and success, which can help break down gender-based assumptions and ego-driven resistance.

“Women can prove they have earned it if they are given an opportunity to grow within the organisation. This will enable women to grow in front of their eyes answering the male ego that she proved it and deserves the growth” FGD 5.

Across the discussions, participants agreed that to inspire the next generation of women leaders, organisations must:

Create authentic leadership environments for fostering genuine engagement and trust. Supporting early interest in technical fields encourages diverse talent from the outset, while providing growth opportunities ensures continued development and advancement. It is important to foster inclusive, non-judgemental cultures that celebrate individuality and encourage collaboration. Additionally, offering sponsorship programmes can help promote internal progression, ensuring that emerging leaders have the support and visibility needed to advance within the organisation.

Together, these strategies create a foundation for future women leaders to rise authentically, confidently, and visibly. Automotive organisations stand to gain significantly from the inclusion of women in leadership roles. To harness these benefits, companies can implement the following strategies:

To promote inclusive and sustainable leadership development, organisations should encourage current leaders to share their personal growth journeys with their teams, demonstrating courage and adaptability. Peer-led mentorship groups can enable women leaders to informally coach team members, while structured delegation practices allow emerging leaders to gradually assume responsibilities under guidance. Promoting skill development in underrepresented areas, such as technical or planning departments, through stretch assignments helps broaden capabilities. Team leaders should be encouraged to view leadership as an evolving journey rather than a fixed identity, and managers should be trained to actively identify and sponsor potential within their teams. Inclusive behaviours at the team level, such as empathy-driven feedback and open forums for idea-sharing, must be fostered to create a psychologically safe environment. Career path frameworks should support cross-functional movement and experiential learning, especially for women. Documenting and publicly recognising the achievements of women leaders through case studies can provide valuable learning resources

for internal development as well as external audiences like MBA cohorts or job candidates. Inclusive leadership criteria should be integrated into performance appraisals and succession planning processes. To increase women's representation in operational and technical areas, tailored talent pipelines are essential, supported by partnerships with educational institutions to promote Women in Automotive (WIA) awareness and industry immersion programmes for young girls. Structured sponsorship programmes should be designed to pair emerging female talent with senior leaders, and internal policies must be reviewed to ensure they support authenticity, flexibility, parental leave, and fair performance evaluations. Finally, leadership development programmes should incorporate core competencies such as emotional intelligence, resilience, and storytelling to cultivate well-rounded, inclusive leaders.

4.8 A systematic comparison of the lead interviews and focus group discussions

Findings revealed a strong convergence of themes, demonstrating the robustness of the study's findings through methodological triangulation. While the two formats differed in structure, with interviews capturing individual narratives and focus groups fostering collective dialogue, both methods surfaced remarkably consistent insights that reinforced and validated each other. This coherence not only strengthens the credibility of the research but also offers a more comprehensive and nuanced understanding of the lived experiences of women leaders in the Indian automotive industry.

Across both sets of data, participants consistently emphasised the central role of authentic leadership rooted in personal values, ethical conduct, and self-awareness. Whether shared through personal stories or echoed in group conversations, women leaders described how their upbringing and intrinsic value systems shaped their professional identities and leadership styles. Authenticity was not viewed as a mere leadership attribute but rather as a necessary strategy for navigating the male-dominated automotive sector landscape. Aligning personal

values with organisational culture was seen as vital for enhancing engagement, improving the quality of decision-making, and building leadership resilience in the face of persistent challenges.

There was also a unified recognition of systemic organisational barriers embedded in gender bias. Participants, whether speaking individually or in groups, shared vivid accounts of unconscious bias, maternity discrimination, and exclusion from critical decision-making spaces. These experiences were marked by a common theme of having their competence, commitment, and leadership potential questioned due to prevailing gendered assumptions. The consistency of these narratives across both methods underscored the pervasiveness of patriarchal norms within the industry and reinforced participants' calls for a cultural and structural transformation that would enable more equitable career pathways.

Another area of alignment was the importance attributed to mentorship and the distinct, yet complementary, role of sponsorship. Participants from both methods detailed how mentorship, whether formal or informal, had contributed to their confidence, skill development, and readiness for leadership. Yet, they also highlighted that sponsorship was what often led to actual advancement. The shared view was that mentorship supports growth, but sponsorship opens doors. Both data sources collectively called for organisations to institutionalise structured mentorship and sponsorship programmes, viewing them as crucial tools for addressing leadership gaps and promoting women's career progression.

The accounts further converged on the strategies women employed to overcome internal and external obstacles. Emotional resilience, self-motivation, and strategic networking emerged as core mechanisms through which women sustained and advanced their careers. Across the board, participants described how they selectively engaged with feedback, pursued continuous self-improvement, and built support networks within and beyond their organisations. These

approaches not only helped them navigate adversity but also contributed significantly to their leadership credibility and presence in a highly competitive industry.

Finally, there was a shared vision among participants for a more inclusive and values-driven organisational culture. Women across interviews and focus groups expressed a belief that companies which align corporate values with ethical leadership, offer autonomy, and embrace diversity are more likely to attract, retain, and empower women leaders. Flexibility in the workplace, transparent policies, and a willingness to move away from rigid, hierarchical structures were seen as essential ingredients for enabling women to thrive. Both formats echoed the need for an industry-wide shift towards inclusive, adaptable, and ethically grounded leadership models that reflect and support the evolving realities of today’s workforce.

Table 34: Comparative study of similarities between lead interviews and Focus group discussions:

<u>Themes</u>	<u>Insights from lead interviews</u>	<u>Insights from Focus Group Discussions</u>
Authentic Leadership Anchored in Personal Values	Participants emphasised personal values, ethical decision-making, and authentic leadership as central to identity.	Group consensus highlighted authenticity and values-based leadership as key to navigating industry.
Organisational Barriers Stemming from Gender Bias	Narratives detailed challenges such as maternity bias, unconscious bias, and	Discussions reinforced similar barriers, calling for systemic change and inclusive practise.

		exclusion from decision-making.	
Mentorship Sponsorship	Alongside	Participants recounted impactful mentorship experiences and noted the scarcity of formal sponsorship opportunities.	Collective advocacy emerged for structured mentorship and active sponsorship to promote women's advancement.
Resilience Through Coping Strategies		Described self-reflection, selective feedback processing, self-branding, and strategic learning as resilience tools.	Echoed similar strategies, emphasising peer support, allyship, and networking for overcoming challenges.
Culture of Inclusivity within Organisations		Linked job satisfaction and leadership motivation to alignment between personal and organisational values.	Groups stressed the importance of inclusive, flexible, and ethically oriented workplace cultures.

Table 34 presents a comparative analysis of themes identified from the lead interviews and focus group discussions. It highlights areas of convergence and divergence between individual and collective perspectives on women's leadership experiences. This comparison strengthens analytical rigour through triangulation and enhances the credibility of the findings by demonstrating consistency and nuance across data sources.

4.9. Integrated Summary

The deep alignment between insights from the lead interviews and FGDs reinforces the credibility, dependability, and transferability of the study's findings. This methodological triangulation confirms that the perspectives and strategies articulated have not isolated individual experiences, but rather shared, systemic realities faced by women leaders across diverse organisational contexts. The synthesis of both datasets provides a comprehensive and nuanced understanding of how women navigate leadership, confront gendered challenges, and advocate for inclusive organisational reforms within India's automotive organisations.

This convergence across methods lends robust empirical support to the study's argument that advancing women's leadership in male-dominated sectors necessitates interventions grounded in authentic leadership, structural inclusivity, and strategic advocacy mechanisms.

Fig 16: Leadership, authenticity and gender a Conceptual Framework

CHAPTER FIVE: DISCUSSION

5.1 Introduction

In recent years, while the presence of women in the Indian automotive sector has grown, leadership representation remains disproportionately low. This study, drawing on interviews with 25 women leaders and focus group discussions with their teams, aligns with Role Congruity Theory, which explains how societal norms and gender stereotypes hinder women's leadership progression (Eagly and Karau, 2002). Although prior research highlights the value of vocational training and mentoring in enhancing technical competence (Zavala *et al.*, 2025; Fana *et al.*, 2024), this study finds that such interventions often fall short of enabling leadership advancement, sometimes perceived as tokenistic rather than transformative.

Findings also align with those of Sriram, Drisya, and Giridhar (2022), who identified lower retention rates of women in automotive roles compared to other sectors. Despite the implementation of gender-specific policies, such as flexible work arrangements and extended leave, participants in the present study noted that these often reinforced feelings of isolation. A key barrier remains the lack of internal sponsorship and the pressure to conform to dominant masculine leadership norms, restricting authentic leadership expression.

Consistent with Bullock (2019), women found validation through their technical expertise, yet many struggled to align this with organisational expectations. By integrating perspectives from both leaders and their teams, this research offers a nuanced understanding of how authenticity is enacted in male-dominated settings. The findings support the relevance of authentic leadership theory, particularly in terms of the roles of self-awareness and value-based leadership in enhancing resilience and performance (Howard, 2025).

The discussion explores each theme, contextualising the findings within the intersectionality of gender, leadership and authenticity.

5.2 Theme One: Authentic Leadership

The findings of this study indicate that authentic leadership functions both as an intrinsic personal orientation and as a deliberate strategic approach among women in India's automotive sector. Participants consistently articulated their understanding of authentic leadership as being grounded in core values, self-awareness, and emotional openness closely aligning with Walumbwa *et al.* (2008) model, which defines authentic leadership through relational transparency, internalised moral perspective, balanced information processing, and self-awareness.

More than just a leadership style, authenticity emerged as a subtle yet powerful form of resistance to dominant masculine norms embedded in organisational cultures, echoing the arguments put forward by Ely *et al.* (2011). For example, participants such as P1 and P24 highlighted that adhering to personal values not only enhanced their credibility and trustworthiness within teams but also acted as a counter-narrative to traditional masculine leadership ideals. These insights support broader scholarship suggesting that authentic leadership offers women a way to assert influence and legitimacy in environments shaped by hegemonic masculinity (Gardiner, 2015; Fox *et al.*, 2017).

In addition, the study's findings correspond with Mayo's (2018) triadic model of authenticity emotional, behavioural, and social. Emotional authenticity was evident in participants' clarity of purpose and psychological resilience; behavioural authenticity emerged through actions such as soliciting feedback and adapting flexibly to change, while social authenticity facilitated trust-building and the development of a shared team identity. These dimensions collectively expand upon Avolio and Gardner's (2005) conceptualisation by showing that authentic leadership is not simply an internal disposition but a relational and context-sensitive process, especially critical within gendered and hierarchical organisational structures.

The significance of continuous development and learning emerged strongly across all twenty-five participants in this study, supporting Bryan's (2020) proposition that authentic leadership is both a developmental and transformative journey. Participants such as P1, P13, and P22 underscored the interconnectedness between self-awareness and behavioural influence, a relationship further validated during focus group discussions (FGDs 1 and 3). This aligns with Neider and Schriesheim (2011), who argue that clarity of self, directly informs leadership behaviour and, in turn, strengthens influence.

Nevertheless, the enactment of authenticity was frequently met with unconscious gender bias. For instance, P14 recalled being labelled "bossy" for expressing her views, while P5 was referred to as a "warrior lady" for assertive communication illustrating the gendered penalties associated with women's authentic self-expression, as highlighted by Laschinger, Wong and Grau (2012). Despite these challenges, authentic leadership was perceived to foster inclusivity, echoing Smith and Lindsay's (2014) findings. In this study, participants' authenticity translated into increased organisational loyalty. All five participating organisations had formalised diversity, equity, and inclusion (DEI) goals, with leaders such as P22 and P23 appointed to head DEI departments an indication of institutional impact. Notably, two additional automotive firms approached the researcher during data collection, seeking to use the study's findings to enhance their DEI efforts.

Participants also demonstrated humility and transparency in acknowledging limitations. A notable example is P7, a logistics professional who proactively sought guidance from government authorities to understand regulatory frameworks. This behaviour resonates with Arenas (2019), who cites Margaret Thatcher's candid inquiry "How do you actually run a war?" as an act of authentic leadership that exemplifies vulnerability and strength.

The findings further validate Nair, Prasad and Shreekumar's (2022) claim that authentic leadership encourages authentic followership. When FGDs were asked whether they would support their leaders' promotion, responses were thoughtful and merit-based. Rather than offering blind endorsement, participants expressed willingness to advocate for leaders who demonstrated empathy, vision, and ethical clarity. This mirrors the work of Monehin and Diers (2022), who highlight empathy as critical to effective leadership, particularly in times of crisis, and is echoed by Moore and Maxey (2023), who position empathy as central to authenticity. FGD 3 provided a vivid example of how their leader's attentiveness to emotional nuance fostered team trust and cohesion.

Authentic leadership also played a key role in crisis management. Consistent with Varma's (2021) assertion that adaptive and resilient leadership is essential in a BANI (Brittle, Anxious, Nonlinear, Incomprehensible) environment, twenty-one participants in this study were assigned high-stakes projects during times of organisational crisis. Their leadership not only salvaged failing departments but, in several cases, revitalised entire companies. P4's leadership in rebuilding a disbanded compliance unit illustrates the far-reaching impact of authentic leadership. It is noteworthy that all twenty-five participants were the first women to hold their respective roles or lead departments, suggesting that navigating adversity had become a defining aspect of their leadership journey.

Yet, as Ely *et al.* (2011) caution, authenticity in women is often subjected to intensified scrutiny. This was affirmed by twenty-four participants who recounted being held to higher standards and regularly challenged. P4 shared how her data was questioned during board presentations, and her legitimacy was only accepted after repeated justifications. Meanwhile, P1, after achieving the role of Deputy General Manager, ultimately exited the industry due to

emotional exhaustion and a lack of ongoing support underscoring the emotional toll of persistent scrutiny.

Encouragingly, recent studies (Tidhar, 2023; Ely *et al.*, 2011; Bandura and Kavussanu, 2018) indicate that younger employees increasingly expect authenticity and adaptability from their leaders. This sentiment was echoed by the five FGDs, who expressed admiration for their leaders' ability to remain authentic while adapting to team needs. For example, FGD 1 recounted how their leader's transition from a production role to their current department fostered enhanced collaboration, productivity, and shared purpose.

As noted by Van and Jacobs (2017), the development of authentic leadership necessitates a deep intrapersonal transformation, a conclusion supported by the twenty-five interviews conducted in this study. However, Harung *et al.* (2009) argue that conventional training programmes are insufficient in fostering such transformation. This was corroborated by the participants, none of whom reported gaining intrapersonal insight or authentic leadership capacity through formal training initiatives. While Baron and Parent (2015) have proposed structured frameworks for developing authentic leadership, these were largely unfamiliar to the women leaders in this study.

Despite the absence of formal models, participants described experiencing a five-step developmental process: cultivating self-awareness, identifying and testing new behaviours, recognising their positive effects, and ultimately integrating these behaviours into everyday leadership practice. These findings suggest that authentic leadership among women in the Indian automotive industry evolved organically, independent of prescribed frameworks indicating that rigid models were not central to their leadership journeys.

This study also reflects the considerations outlined by Cooper, Scandura and Schriesheim (2005), who identified four key categories for researching authentic leadership: (1) defining

and measuring the construct, (2) determining its discriminant validity, (3) identifying relevant outcomes, and (4) assessing whether it can be taught. The findings contribute to category (2) by illustrating how authentic leadership is distinct from other leadership styles, with traits such as self-awareness, emotional transparency, and inner clarity consistently emerging as defining characteristics. With respect to category (3), the data revealed clear outcomes of authentic leadership including enhanced team cohesion, effective crisis management, and the ability to challenge bias and gender stereotypes thus enabling women to ascend to senior leadership positions.

Regarding category (4), the evidence strongly suggests that authentic leadership is not a teachable skill in the traditional sense. None of the participants reported receiving training in authenticity, yet all displayed resilience, confidence, and integrity. These attributes appeared to have developed through lived experiences in male-dominated environments rather than through external instruction. Consequently, it may be argued that authentic leadership should be viewed not as a skill to be taught, but as a quality to be recognised, nurtured, and allowed to emerge (Cooper, Scandura and Schriesheim, 2005; Harung *et al.*, 2009; Van and Jacobs, 2017).

5.3 Theme Two: Professional Identity

The construction of professional identity among women leaders in India's automotive sector is a deeply personal yet socially situated process. This theme highlights the critical interplay between the leaders' intrinsic value systems and the external expectations placed upon them within corporate environments particularly those shaped by historically masculine norms. The narratives gathered underscore the profound role that personal values play not only in shaping leadership identity, but also in influencing ethical decision-making, relational authenticity, and resilience during times of organisational turbulence.

A dominant thread that emerged was the grounding influence of values inherited from early life experiences. These values were not regarded as incidental but rather as the very foundation upon which professional identity was forged. As Participant 1 reflected, leadership was inseparable from the moral compass cultivated during childhood: “Leadership is awesome, dependent it also comes from the values you are brought up with at home, because that’s what values and behaviours are ingrained when you’re a child and very difficult to change.” This echoes the work of Shamir and Eilam (2005), who argue that authentic leaders act in ways consistent with their self-concept, often rooted in formative life experiences.

For many, the integration of personal values into the workplace was not only a matter of integrity but also a source of professional strength. Leaders like P1 and P2 pointed out that respect and alignment between individual and organisational values significantly enhanced their engagement and performance. P1 described a deeply affirming experience with a former boss who recognised and respected her for who she was, not merely for her output. This sense of value congruence has been shown in literature to promote intrinsic motivation and job satisfaction (Kernis, 2003; Van den Bosch and Taris, 2014), contributing to sustainable leadership effectiveness.

However, this ideal of alignment was not universally experienced. For others, such as P23, value incongruence gave rise to feelings of intimidation and marginalisation. Her repeated need to justify her presence and competence in leadership forums illustrates the pressure women face when their leadership identity challenges normative expectations. This tension is reflective of what Ibarra *et al.* (2013) term “identity work” the ongoing negotiation between one’s internal sense of self and externally imposed professional roles. P23’s account also reveals that such friction, though psychologically taxing, can serve as a crucible for growth and courage, reinforcing the adaptive strength of women leaders.

Interestingly, while some participants like P11 believed that one's values should be evident through their work, others like P22 questioned the systemic bias that demands women justify their value in the first place. This critical stance raises deeper concerns about how professional identity is validated in organisations. Ridgeway (2011) posits that gender stereotypes often act as "expectation states" in professional interactions, requiring women to continually demonstrate competence before gaining legitimacy. Within such a context, the silent labour of proving one's value becomes an additional burden uniquely experienced by women leaders.

Diversity of thought emerged as a valued leadership trait. P3's emphasis on appreciating differences as essential to leadership effectiveness reinforces current thinking in inclusive leadership literature (Nishii and Mayer, 2009). Moreover, P25's nuanced interpretation of identity as shaped by personality and team dynamics highlights the flexible, situated nature of professional identity one that adapts to context while remaining anchored in self-awareness.

Autonomy and liberty, as noted by P4 and P6, were also vital in the process of aligning personal values with professional roles. Their experiences suggest that empowering work environments can create the psychological safety necessary for leaders to be authentic. This resonates with Deci and Ryan's (2000) self-determination theory, which emphasises autonomy as a key driver of motivation and well-being.

Collectively, these narratives show that balancing personal values with professional expectations is not a straightforward or fixed process. Instead, it is dynamic, relational, and often filled with tension. However, it is precisely this balancing act that seems to foster leadership authenticity, moral clarity, and organisational influence. Women leaders who stay true to their values, even while navigating changing organisational landscapes, exemplify a form of leadership that is both resilient and inclusive.

Importantly, the findings indicate that while some organisations have started to value authenticity and diversity, many still operate within structures resistant to these changes. The burden, therefore, remains disproportionately on women to bridge the gap between their true selves and the expectations of the professional world. For leadership identity to be genuinely inclusive, organisational systems must develop to recognise, reward, and support the authenticity women bring to leadership roles.

5.4 Theme Three: Overcoming Internal Challenges

This theme reflects the roots of the gendered psyche; it is important to explore how individual psychological makeup is influenced by historical and cultural factors. In the context of women in the automotive sector, research has offered valuable insights into the phenomenon of the ‘woman behind the wheel’. For example, Song *et al.* (2024) found that persistent negative stereotypes about women drivers lead to increased anxiety and lower self-efficacy, negatively affecting their confidence. Similarly, Lezotte (2021) emphasises how gendered expectations are culturally ingrained in automobile consumption patterns, where women are encouraged to drive family-oriented vehicles and men are associated with performance-focused cars. Lezotte argues that cars are not merely practical objects but symbolic extensions of identity, especially for women, with car choices reflecting themes of resilience, transformation, and empowerment.

Levitt (2019), in her exploration of the pioneering British driver Dorothy Levitt, dubbed “the fastest woman on earth,” reveals how women’s capabilities have been historically dismissed through superficial judgments. One expert reflects this view: “Looking at Ms Levitt, one can hardly imagine that she could drive a car at such speed” (Levitt, 2019, p. 1). Yet, Levitt encouraged women to see motoring as both accessible and empowering, urging them to drive with unapologetic confidence.

Such gendered stereotypes about driving extend into professional domains, including leadership within the automotive industry. This study revealed that women leaders in India's automotive sector often contend with internal psychological challenges, such as imposter syndrome, emotional dissonance, and self-doubt, which are well-documented in leadership scholarship (Clance and Imes, 1978; Amo, 2023). These internal struggles are often exacerbated by the gendered expectations that continue to influence perceptions of effective leadership. However, authenticity emerged as a powerful counter-narrative, allowing participants to validate their lived experiences rather than conform to traditionally masculinised leadership ideals.

Findings from the interpretative phenomenological analysis (IPA) indicate that the process of self-authorship enabled participants to craft leadership identities rooted in their personal values (Bennett and Hennekam, 2018). For instance, P23 explained that recognising her intrinsic value allowed her to advocate for resources more confidently and lead with greater conviction. These findings support Salmela's (2005) argument that sustainable leadership development must incorporate psychological and identity-based dimensions.

Moreover, the study supports the idea that authentic leadership serves as a strategic mechanism for navigating the 'double bind', the tension wherein women are penalised for being either too assertive or too relational (Johns *et al.*, 2008). Participants reported that authenticity enabled them to transcend these binaries, reshaping leadership practices beyond conventional gender norms. This reinforces Binns and Kerfoot's (2011) critique of the supposed neutrality embedded within mainstream leadership paradigms, which often mask gendered assumptions.

The role of organisational culture in reinforcing or mitigating stereotype threat was also evident. Consistent with Hoyt and Murphy's (2016) findings, participants such as P1, P2, P19, and P22 reflected critically on how workplace norms either challenged or perpetuated gender

bias. For example, P1 described being discouraged from questioning a decision during a meeting, as her assertiveness was perceived as threatening to male colleagues. Conversely, P20 highlighted the unintended consequences of well-meaning gender-based policies, noting that such initiatives often reinforced notions of women as a ‘protected’ group. This reflects the critique by Hippel, Kalokerinos and Zacher (2017), who argue that quota systems and preferential policies can sometimes undermine women’s credibility by fostering perceptions of unearned advantage. These findings collectively illustrate that authentic leadership is not merely a personal disposition but a dynamic practice that challenges gendered norms and transforms organisational cultures.

These tensions were echoed in the focus group discussions (FGDs), particularly in FGD 2, where participants observed that their leader was perceived as receiving preferential treatment based solely on her gender. Such findings indicate that organisational initiatives aimed at promoting gender inclusion may inadvertently backfire if not implemented with nuance and fairness. The current study, therefore, provides evidence that the binary framing of gender-focused policies as either supportive or exclusionary can produce unintended consequences that deepen, rather than dismantle, gendered divisions.

A key finding of this study involves the complex role of feedback in both addressing and reinforcing stereotypical threats faced by women leaders. While all 25 participants recognised the importance of feedback for professional growth, 20 explicitly indicated the need to filter feedback based on its credibility and relevance. This selective practice often arose in response to the problematic nature of the feedback received, much of which focused on personal characteristics, such as physical appearance or post-childbirth weight gain, rather than on substantive, role-related skills.

These findings provide a nuanced perspective that challenges the conclusions drawn by Kea-Edwards *et al.* (2023), who emphasised a quantity deficit in feedback given to women. Conversely, the current study indicates that the more pressing issue relates to the quality and relevance of the feedback rather than how often it is provided. In many instances, the limited feedback women received was disconnected from their actual job performance, reducing its developmental value and reinforcing deep-seated gender biases. The main challenge, therefore, is not just the lack of feedback, but the prevalence of feedback that does not align with professional expectations, ultimately undermining women's perceived legitimacy and obstructing their progress within organisational structures.

Previous research on women's leadership in the automotive industry in China by Horak and Cui (2017) recommended that both men and women should be given equal opportunities to enter the sector. This recommendation followed findings that demonstrated the positive impact of women in leadership roles on firm performance. Such studies have influenced automotive organisations, as reflected in the lead interviews conducted with 25 women leaders in this study. While participants acknowledged that they had been offered opportunities to join the industry, many expressed that these initiatives often felt like a 'tick in the box exercise' rather than a genuine effort to recognise and value women's contributions to the sector.

While prior scholarship, such as that by Besley *et al.* (2017), has framed quota systems as effective tools for increasing women's representation in leadership, the present study offers a more critical and contextually grounded perspective that challenges this assumption. Participants in this study frequently positioned quotas not as enablers but as impediments to meritocratic progression. Rather than feeling empowered, many participants expressed that quota diminished their accomplishments by attributing success to policy-driven advantages rather than skill, competence, or performance. For instance, participants P21 and P23

highlighted the centrality of expertise and demonstrated their capability in securing leadership opportunities and addressing sponsorship factors they believed were overshadowed by tokenistic interpretations of quota-based advancement.

This sentiment was echoed by FGD 3, who highlighted the unintended consequence of quota policies in generating discomfort and defensive behaviour among male colleagues. The perception that women were advancing due to gender-based entitlements rather than earned merit created a climate of mistrust, inhibiting open collaboration, a crucial element for inclusive leadership development. These findings cast doubt on the long-term viability of one-dimensional interventions and reveal how inclusion policies, if not carefully implemented, can inadvertently reinforce gender divides rather than bridge them.

Furthermore, the study identifies a significant gap in the existing literature. While much research has focused on the role of quotas in increasing the entry-level participation of women in male-dominated industries, there has been far less attention paid to their impact on the long-term leadership development of women. Over ten participants in this study explicitly highlighted the critical role of male allies in their leadership progression. In such contexts, rigid quota systems have the potential to alienate these allies, thereby undermining the collaborative networks essential for women's advancement.

While gender-related policies, such as maternity leave, have facilitated some progress for women in the workplace, P8's experience provides a stark example of the limitations of such policies. After returning from maternity leave, she faced criticism for not losing her "baby bump". This situation exemplifies how existing research, which often focuses on extrinsic factors like formal policies, fails to address the sustainability of these initiatives and their lack of alignment with deeper cultural shifts within organisations.

A key finding of this study is that the long-term success and sustainability of women's advancement in the automotive industry are not solely determined by external policies or quotas. Instead, it is the self-initiated efforts of women, such as ongoing self-development through learning and seeking out sponsors within their organisations, that have proven to be the most sustaining factors in their leadership journeys. This reinforces the argument that intrinsic cultural changes and proactive personal development are critical components of women's sustained growth within male-dominated industries.

Thus, this study problematises the uncritical valorisation of quota systems and calls for a more nuanced, intersectional approach that moves beyond numerical inclusion to foster environments where both women and men can contribute meaningfully to sustainable gender equity in leadership.

Moreover, scholars such as Hadfield and Jopling (2018) have argued that proactive relational dynamics, such as fostering collaboration and harmony, can reshape the leader–follower relationship. The present study supports this view, revealing that authentic leadership functions not only as a reactive mechanism to counter bias but also as a proactive strategy for fostering inclusive organisational cultures. Women leaders demonstrated that authenticity, characterised by empathy, ethics, vision, and commitment, naturally led to stronger team cohesion and mutual sponsorship. This corroborates Kirton and Healy's (2013) argument that leaders who invest in the collective good are more likely to be endorsed by their teams.

Overall, the findings indicate that internal psychological barriers faced by women leaders are not effectively mitigated through exclusive, top-down gender policies or quota systems. Instead, the comparative insights from lead interviews and FGDs illustrate that authentic leadership rooted in self-development, self-authorship, and consistent values offers a more resilient pathway through which women can navigate and transcend these internal and external

barriers. Rather than numbing stereotypical threats through compliance or avoidance, authenticity enabled these leaders to neutralise such threats through identity congruence and relational integrity. This reinforces the broader argument that truly inclusive leadership emerges from personal transformation and relational empowerment, rather than from structural intervention alone.

5.5 Theme Four: Bias

The findings of this theme demonstrate how women leaders have developed various strategies to overcome bias and criticism, which often include seeking feedback and creating support networks. Although leaders were receptive to feedback, they all agreed that it was a learning experience. They acknowledged that they had to filter the feedback they received, discarding comments that did not contribute to their career development. This suggests that much of the feedback earlier in their careers focused more on their personalities than their professional abilities. P1 illustrated this point by stating, “So, where I am today is that I know who I am, I am not really interested in knowing about feedback on who I am.” This sentiment was echoed by P2, who remarked, “I would say that if it’s work-related, I’d be open. But unfortunately, I have never had that in my entire career.” These statements reveal how feedback was often directed at women’s personalities rather than being constructively aimed at their work performance, a view supported by P4, P5, and P9, who all highlighted that feedback should be career-oriented.

The recurring use of the term "if" by the participants further underscores the uncertainty they felt about the feedback they received. As illustrated by P4, “*If really it will help for our growth,*” P9 said, “*If it is meant for improvement,*” P6 stated, “*If you needed to accept it,*” and P7 added, “*If it is negative also.*” According to Brown and Levinson (1987), the word "if" signifies a level of uncertainty, highlighting how women leaders, despite reaching high

leadership positions, were still not receiving structured feedback aimed at advancing their careers. This, in turn, indicates that bias remains a pervasive issue within the workplace. The theme further reveals that women leaders, such as P23 and P24, have adapted to this culture of uncertain feedback. As P23 explained, *“I take it very positively and that’s where you know you tweak your style with different organisations but at the same time maintaining your authenticity.”* This reflects how these women have learned to remain positive while accepting feedback that might not be directly beneficial to their growth. P24 and P4 also stressed the importance of the source of the feedback, indicating that they placed greater value on feedback from trusted individuals.

These findings align with Jampol, Rattan, and Wolf (2023), who highlighted that women often use feedback as a tool for learning and growth. The participants in this study seemed to filter the type of feedback they received, checking its source and mentally discarding feedback rooted in bias. Additionally, the women in the study recognised the importance of informal mentorship in combating bias. They created their own mentorship networks, with each woman outlining specific criteria for selecting mentors. For example, P1 chose mentors based on their ability to challenge her and push her skills, while P2 valued reverse mentorship from her team. P3, P25, and P24 received mentorship from their direct supervisors, focusing on learning from the strengths and qualities of their mentors. P6, on the other hand, sought mentorship from a cross-functional manager who provided constructive feedback for her growth. P22, however, found mentorship in someone who could simply listen. The findings reveal that women leaders actively sought their own mentors, with criteria focused on pushing boundaries, strength, support, and correction. This mirrors the findings of James, Rayner, and Bruno (2015), who also emphasised the importance of personality fit when choosing an informal mentor.

Another key finding from this theme was the emphasis on building networks with like-minded individuals, particularly colleagues from other teams. P25 and P24 noted that common ground in gender often provided the basis for these networks. As P23 pointed out, *“It’s a marathon and therefore, to run the marathon, you need the mental support of other women, even if they don’t necessarily work in the same team.”* This is supported by statements from P1, P7, and P15, who acknowledged that without these networks, it would have been difficult to sustain their leadership roles. P8 presented a unique connection between workplace networks and the support system at home, highlighting how both can complement each other. P21 reiterated that the network built at the workplace often felt like a second family. The importance of these networks was not only for emotional support but also for informal induction, as seen with P14, who credited her informal network for helping her settle into her role as the first woman in her department. While male-dominated industries often rely on ‘boys’ networks,’ as highlighted by Barkhuizen, Masakane, and Van der Sluis (2022), women in this study had bridged this gap by establishing their own networks, making them feel more connected.

In conclusion, the theme identified various strategies employed by women to combat bias. They had created their own mechanisms for handling feedback, set specific criteria for self-chosen mentors, and built supportive networks to navigate their careers. The focus group discussions (FGDs) echoed these findings, illustrating how women earned respect through their results. The FGDs further emphasised that it was these results, not their gender, that garnered them the respect of their peers. FGD 2 particularly pointed out that when results were produced, gender often became irrelevant. The FGDs also agreed that women were compelled to prove their worth in the workplace. FGD 1 noted that having a female boss meant employees from other teams were less likely to oppose decisions, although it was also noted that this dynamic arose from the policies governing women, such as the Prevention of Sexual Harassment (POSH) policy. The lead interviews highlighted the specific strategies employed by women, while the

FGDs underscored the broader, more institutional biases that women faced, many of which were beyond their control. As illustrated by FGD 3, where women leaders often felt the need to stay back due to project emergencies, the stigma surrounding the safety of women leaders and the expectations placed on them were still prevalent. This experience, although not voiced by the female leader, reflected the biases ingrained in the workplace culture.

5.6 Theme Five: Leadership Development

The narratives shared by the women leaders in this study illustrate a compelling and deeply personal journey of leadership development, shaped not by structured programmes but by self-motivation, perseverance, and adaptive resilience. Learning, as identified across all twenty-five participants, emerged as a critical factor in their leadership evolution. However, this learning was predominantly self-directed, echoing the findings of Kittel and Seufert (2023), who contend that self-regulated learning is central to successful development, particularly in complex, real-world environments. The absence of formal leadership training, especially within the companies themselves, highlights a significant gap in organisational learning ecosystems. Even among those who received formal development opportunities, such as P2, the training was mostly technical in nature and disconnected from the soft skills and strategic competencies necessary for leadership growth.

Interestingly, leadership development for some women, such as P3 and P5, took the form of tailored interventions. However, these were isolated instances and not the norm. HR leaders themselves admitted that their learning often stemmed from organising programmes rather than participating in them. Despite this, most participants championed on-the-job learning as a highly effective means of growth. The majority were united in their view that training programmes exclusively for women, while well-intentioned, risk being counterproductive.

This aligns with broader critiques in the literature that such programmes can reinforce difference rather than dismantle systemic barriers (Ely *et al.*, 2011).

A deeper undercurrent within the participants' stories was the emotionally taxing journey through gendered career barriers. Many spoke of deeply painful experiences around maternity, not as a joyous occasion, but as a moment that undermined their professional identity. P23 recounted how her maternity leave was viewed as extended absenteeism, attracting derogatory remarks, while P16 experienced stalled promotions during this period. These lived realities reinforce the systemic nature of workplace bias, particularly in how maternity is culturally constructed and institutionally unsupported in male-dominated industries (Baird and Hill, 2019).

Compounding these experiences was the "prove it again" bias an entrenched pattern where women leaders were forced to repeatedly demonstrate competence in ways that their male counterparts were not. P1's story exemplified this: while male colleagues received promotions despite errors, her every move was scrutinised. Similarly, P24's experience of being perceived as an individual contributor, despite leading a team of 32, highlights the subtle ways in which women's authority is minimised. This echoes the findings of Williams and Bogdanowicz (2022), who emphasise the pervasive nature of "prove it again" bias and its cumulative toll on women's careers.

A particularly striking insight was the widespread acknowledgement of the lack of sponsorship. While mentorship is often positioned as a panacea for women's advancement, what these women craved was not guidance alone, but powerful advocacy. P2 shared how, despite consistently high-performance ratings, she waited 12 years for a promotion. Others, such as P1, P4, and P13, described how their so-called "promotions" were actually rescue missions' opportunities to clean up failing projects rather than genuine career advancement. This aligns

with research suggesting that women are more likely to be placed in high-risk leadership roles, known as the “glass cliff” phenomenon (Ryan and Haslam, 2005).

Another invisible yet critical barrier discussed was cultural exclusion. Participants such as P6 and P8 reflected on their inability to express disagreement freely, an important dimension of authentic leadership. Furthermore, the insidious presence of the “queen bee” phenomenon, where senior women distance themselves from or actively undermine other women, surfaced as a particularly disheartening experience. P22 and P24 both shared how female leaders in their organisations refused to recruit or support other women, reinforcing masculine norms rather than challenging them. These findings resonate with Derks, Van Laar and Ellemers (2016), who argue that the queen bee behaviour stems not from inherent rivalry, but from structural and cultural pressures that push women to assimilate into male-dominated leadership archetypes.

Despite these barriers, what remains most remarkable is the persistence of the women in seeking continuous learning, often without institutional support. Self-regulated learning not only equipped them with skills but also became a coping mechanism to manage the emotional labour of bias, exclusion, and unfair scrutiny. This finding contributes to a growing body of research advocating for greater autonomy in leadership development and the need for organisations to create environments where such learning is recognised and rewarded (Boyatzis and McKee, 2005).

In conclusion, the leadership development of women in the Indian automotive industry, as revealed in this study, is less a story of formal training and more a narrative of resilience, self-direction, and strategic adaptation. Yet the emotional burden and systemic barriers they continue to face, particularly the lack of sponsorship, the persistence of gendered biases, and internalised cultural constraints, underscore the urgent need for organisations to go beyond

surface-level diversity initiatives. Real change requires not only empowering women to lead but also transforming the systems that continue to resist their leadership.

5.7 Theme Six: Professional Growth

The sixth theme emerging from the data highlights how women actively navigated and shaped their career paths, often through intentional efforts in self-education, self-advocacy, and interdisciplinary exploration. Throughout the interviews, participants consistently described how professional growth was not simply a matter of opportunity, but of persistent self-drive. Women were not passive recipients of career progress; they deliberately designed growth trajectories for themselves, often in environments that did not easily accommodate or recognise their potential.

Participant 4, for instance, shared how she created an opportunity to engage with colleagues in another country within the same organisation. By proactively seeking such exposure, she deepened her expertise and widened her influence, thereby catalysing her own career development. This example highlights a pattern observed in several accounts: women were often the architects of their growth, building bridges across organisational boundaries and knowledge domains.

Self-branding emerged as a prominent strategy women employed to gain visibility and credibility in the workplace. As Participant 1 noted, women often had to “challenge until you find a place at the table,” indicating that career advancement required assertive positioning and visible competence. Participant 3 echoed this sentiment, urging women to display the kind of self-confidence often exhibited by their male counterparts. Similarly, Participant 4 commented that “no one would advocate for women; it’s women who have to self-advocate,” underscoring the necessity of self-branding in a system where formal sponsorship or mentorship may be lacking.

However, while self-branding was frequently presented in a positive light, participants also conveyed an underlying tension between promoting oneself and staying true to one's values. Several women expressed the importance of maintaining authenticity amid efforts to be visible. This dual expectation of being both competent and genuine resonates with Psarras's (2022) argument that self-branding, particularly for women, can constitute an additional burden. Rather than a neutral tool for professional advancement, self-branding becomes another layer of emotional and cognitive labour that women must manage alongside other workplace challenges.

The second strand of findings within this theme concerns the strategic development of multi-disciplinary skills. Participants such as P1, P4, P5, P23, and P24 described how they intentionally pursued roles and projects outside their primary domain of expertise. These cross-functional experiences not only enriched their skillsets but also positioned them as versatile contributors within their organisations. In many cases, these lateral moves became pivotal turning points in their careers, enabling them to break through conventional role expectations and become strong contenders for leadership roles.

These findings align with the conclusions of Blank (2015), whose study of women in the pharmacy industry revealed that women often had to advocate for themselves to attain leadership positions. In both contexts, the act of stepping beyond one's comfort zone, whether through self-branding or multi-disciplinary engagement, emerged as a necessary strategy for career progression. Yet, this also reiterates a broader issue: the extent to which women must continually assert and validate their professional worth in order to be seen and supported within male-dominated sectors.

5.8 Theme Seven: Building support systems

This theme examined the various ways women leaders actively built their support networks, emphasising the importance of seeking allies both within and outside their immediate professional circles. One key finding was that many participants highly valued cultivating relationships with allies and advocates within their organisations, particularly among senior leadership. For example, participants P24 and P11 highlighted the importance of openly communicating their professional needs to their direct supervisors, suggesting that transparent dialogue with superiors was vital in securing support. Meanwhile, others such as P21, P22, P15, P11, and P10 noted that their dedication and tangible results spoke volumes, thereby attracting recognition and advocacy from leadership without necessarily having to pursue it overtly.

These strategies are closely aligned with the themes of self-branding and visibility that emerged in the later stages of the research. Theme six demonstrated that women leaders deliberately employed self-branding as a means to advance their careers, while Theme 7 explained how this self-branding was implemented through effective communication and making their contributions visible within organisations. This supports Rampersad's (2008) claim that authentic personal branding, when approached holistically, allows individuals to present a trustworthy and consistent image of themselves across various professional interactions. The study found that such branding efforts helped women leaders craft a positive story about their work, which in turn fostered support and recognition from others.

Support systems, however, extended beyond formal hierarchies. Several participants described seeking support laterally from peers and colleagues within their teams and functions. For instance, P23 and P24 described their immediate teams as their "backbone," highlighting the emotional and professional support they received from their own staff. Participants such as P13

and P4 found solidarity among peers working in similar functions across global locations, often turning to them for critical listening and informal advice. Additionally, others highlighted the value of familial and personal support systems; P8 and P14 specifically referred to family members who played a significant role in their leadership journey. Moreover, several participants acknowledged the importance of learning from supportive managers, whose mentorship and insights contributed meaningfully to their development.

5.9 Theme Eight: Mentorship in Career

This theme emphasised the vital role mentorship plays in the career development of women leaders, with particular focus on the timing, purpose, and agency involved in seeking mentors. While mentorship was consistently recognised as a valuable support mechanism, what stood out was the stage at which it becomes most impactful. Rather than being limited to the early stages of one's career, mentorship was seen as essential during transitional points, challenging moments, or decision-making phases where strategic guidance is especially needed.

Another key finding was the understanding of mentorship as a form of networking. Women leaders viewed mentors not just as sources of support but also as connectors individuals who opened up opportunities, increased visibility, and provided access to wider professional circles. Importantly, this mentorship was self-initiated and not formally structured. Participants demonstrated a clear and purposeful approach to selecting mentors, based on well-defined personal criteria. For example, mentors were chosen for their ability to challenge, guide, and inspire learning. Participant P4 described how vital mentorship had been during periods of professional uncertainty, when a mentor's intervention was instrumental in helping her find direction. Similarly, P6 recalled proactively approaching someone for mentorship after receiving insightful feedback, recognising the value of ongoing learning and development.

Mentors were not only sources of support but also served as role models and strategic allies. Participants such as P4 and P21 characterised mentorship as both a learning experience and a networking strategy. In doing so, they leveraged these relationships not only to build credibility and allies within their organisation but also as a means to market themselves and drive forward their professional advancement.

These findings align with the work of Lazoroska, Palm, and Kojonsaari (2024), who found that within entrepreneurial contexts, women utilise networking, including mentorship, as a source of knowledge acquisition and legitimacy. This parallels the experiences shared by participants in this study, who found that mentorship provided both developmental and reputational benefits. Crucially, the support systems built through mentorship were rarely offered formally; instead, women actively sought out these relationships themselves, using informal structures to reinforce their legitimacy and influence within male-dominated organisational contexts.

5.10 Theme Nine: Navigating Organisational Culture

Despite individual resilience and competence, women leaders in this study encountered persistent structural constraints within their organisations, particularly in areas related to maternity, career progression, and access to leadership pipelines. These barriers were often embedded within organisational cultures that, although formally committed to diversity and inclusion, continued to reflect implicit gender hierarchies. This finding reinforces prior research by Ridgeway (2001) and Hoyt and Murphy (2016), which suggests that symbolic inclusion, without corresponding structural transformation, tends to sustain gender-based inequities.

Participants repeatedly expressed the need to overperform to be considered for leadership roles and reported significantly limited access to sponsorship. While mentorship was often self-driven, the advocacy required for advancement characteristic of sponsorship was notably

absent. This supports Levin *et al.*'s (2021) differentiation between mentorship and sponsorship, highlighting a structural deficiency that restricts women's leadership progression in male-dominated sectors like the automotive industry.

Interestingly, a minority of women who successfully secured sponsorship, such as P21 and P22, achieved this by strategically aligning their authentic leadership identities with increased visibility and influence. This aligns with the findings of Ibarra *et al.* (2010), who argued that authenticity, when paired with political skill, becomes instrumental in negotiating identity within hierarchical structures. In this context, authenticity functioned not only as a personal value but also as a strategic asset that facilitated career progression.

The study's findings are congruent with Chowdhury's (2020) argument that the automotive sector presents a uniquely complex environment for women. However, there is a deficiency of studies detailing what constitutes this complexity. Through direct interaction with 25 women leaders from within the industry, this study clarified that the complexity is characterised by rigid gender norms and institutionalised masculine cultures. For example, participant P14 recounted being assigned the task of counting bins during her induction, despite being the first female engineering graduate in her cohort and holding high academic distinction. This task, unrelated to her engineering qualifications, was not given to her male counterparts and reflects the subtle yet pervasive forms of exclusion that persist within organisational norms.

Further compounding these challenges, participants in Focus Group Discussion 3 (FGD 3) shared how male employees often felt constrained in their interactions with female colleagues, particularly in light of internal POSH (Prevention of Sexual Harassment) protocols. This dynamic, while rooted in legal compliance, inadvertently created barriers to open communication and collegial relationships. One example involved a female leader who struggled to establish role clarity and team cohesion due to her team's limited understanding

of POSH frameworks. This exemplifies how organisational cultures may inadequately prepare for or respond to gender integration. A study conducted by Tan *et al.* (2020) identified two types of organisations in relation to POSH: supportive and unsupportive. Supportive organisations have clearly defined policies against sexual harassment, whereas unsupportive ones tend to ignore such issues. In the case of the 25 lead interviews conducted in this study, all the women were part of supportive organisations that had active coping strategies in place. However, despite the existence of these strategies, a lack of understanding regarding their purpose and impact emerged as a barrier to transparent communication with women leaders.

Although POSH was intended to protect women, it often led to feelings of exclusion rather than inclusion. This reflects how POSH, which is ideally a gender-neutral safeguard, is commonly perceived and implemented as a women-centric policy. These findings are consistent with the study by Malhotra and Srivastava (2016), which highlights the need not only for regular sexual harassment training but also for greater clarity around what constitutes harassment.

These findings reinforce Mies's (2019) critique that gender-focused organisational research has disproportionately emphasised demand-side interventions such as recruitment quotas and diversity metrics while neglecting the deeper structural and cultural transformations required for sustained inclusion. Participants consistently highlighted that academic qualifications and external support mechanisms, while necessary, were insufficient for advancement within the automotive industry. Crucially, the progression of women into leadership roles was contingent upon organisational receptiveness to diverse, authentic leadership styles and the cultivation of genuinely inclusive environments.

A compelling illustration of this tension was provided by P19, who originated from a highly conservative religious community that initially resisted her pursuit of a career in engineering.

Through resilience and consistent performance, she not only secured familial and societal approval but also became a mentor and role model for other women in her village. Despite these accomplishments and the recognition, she received from her community, P19 reported persistent difficulties in earning equivalent validation within the automotive sector. Her narrative underscores the paradox wherein external socio-cultural barriers were overcome more readily than the entrenched gender biases embedded within organisational structures. She described this as an “ongoing battle,” highlighting the enduring nature of institutional resistance to the full inclusion of women leaders.

Notably, participants P1, P2, and P3 cited structural barriers rather than a lack of competence or aspiration as their primary reasons for exiting the automotive sector, despite having attained leadership roles. P2, for instance, pointed to informal male-dominated networks such as smoking areas or after-work social gatherings as exclusionary spaces where critical decisions were often made. Similarly, P20’s experiences with requesting maternity leave reveal how formal policies may be undercut by managerial resistance and gendered attitudes.

These observations affirm the work of Aaltio and Mills (2002), who conceptualise organisations as “mini cultures” that deeply shape individual identity and experience. While all 25 participants cited strong personal values and resilience attributes fostered through their upbringing as key enablers of perseverance, they also acknowledged that unconscious bias and stereotypical behaviours remained pervasive.

The findings also corroborate the enduring presence of the “double bind” phenomenon, as articulated by Johns, Inzlicht, and Schmader (2008), whereby women are penalised for expressing emotions perceived as signs of weakness and for exhibiting assertiveness viewed as aggression. This dynamic was particularly evident in FGD 2, where participants critiqued their leader’s emotional expression, associating it with ineffective leadership. Conversely, in FGD

1, a strong female leader, P6, was praised for demonstrating traits typically associated with masculine norms, such as assertiveness and decisiveness. However, despite being labelled as arrogant for her assertiveness, P6 acknowledged that her ability to deliver tangible results frequently mitigated such negative perceptions. This highlights the complex interplay between gendered expectations and leadership effectiveness, where women are often compelled to navigate between contradictory behavioural standards to gain acceptance and recognition within organisational contexts.

These varied accounts demonstrate that while automotive companies are taking steps toward inclusive cultures, deeply entrenched stereotypes and informal norms continue to pose substantial internal barriers to women's advancement. Even senior leaders in DEI (Diversity, Equity, and Inclusion), such as P22, revealed the subtle policing of female behaviour, recounting how her appearance was scrutinised and how discussions around her ability to drive in intricate Indian formal attire were some of the questions she was asked during important leadership meetings. P22 further went on to highlight how attire mattered in gaining respect or vice versa. Such microaggressions illustrate that even those tasked with championing inclusion are not immune to gendered expectations.

In contrast, P3, an expatriate VP of HR who worked in India, described her organisation as a model for gender-inclusive leadership. Her narrative, marked by frequent affirmations of her employer's support for DEI initiatives and her own professional development, offered a rare yet powerful counterpoint. She credited her advancement to an organisational culture that valued competence and actively invested in women's leadership development.

Collectively, these findings underscore the pivotal influence of organisational culture in shaping women's leadership trajectories. While formal policies and academic qualifications serve as foundational enablers, they are insufficient in the absence of cultural and structural

congruence. The lived experiences of participants highlight that the most persistent barriers are not necessarily external but are embedded within organisational systems, manifesting both through formal structures and implicit norms. The findings from this study agree with a study conducted by Moslehpour *et al.* (2022), which posits that one of the components of Corporate Sustainability Practices (CSP) is organisational culture, which has a significant positive relationship with the sustainable performance of the automobile industry. Similarly, a study by Sriram, Drisy and Giridhar (2022) propose that organisational culture positively influences women's intention to remain in the workforce through initiatives such as flexible working hours, sick leave, annual leave, and maternity leave. While these interventions have been shown to play a crucial role in encouraging women to stay within the industry, they have not contributed meaningfully to their advancement into leadership roles. Participants P1, P2, and P3 exemplify how such measures have failed to support women in sustaining leadership positions. These recommendations were effective in facilitating women's entry into the industry, but did not ensure their progression into leadership.

Addressing such deeply rooted barriers necessitates a multi-layered approach that engages with individual, cultural, and structural dimensions of inclusion. A key contribution of this study lies in its focus on intrinsic organisational and cultural barriers, a dimension that remains significantly underexplored in existing literature, particularly in the context of women working within the Indian automotive industry. Prior research on women in India has predominantly concentrated on extrinsic challenges such as access to education, family responsibilities, or societal expectations, with limited attention to the internal dynamics of industry-specific organisational contexts.

This gap was explicitly acknowledged by participants themselves. Towards the conclusion of their interviews, all 25 women leaders expressed appreciation for the study's effort to

foreground their personal narratives and for engaging with the often-overlooked intrinsic and cultural obstacles they faced in their leadership journeys. The focus group discussions (FGDs) further reinforced the value of this dual-method approach, with participants acknowledging the importance of integrating their collective perspectives alongside individual leadership stories. Such feedback from participants not only validates the relevance of the research design but also underscores the importance of centring women's voices in academic inquiry on gender and leadership.

5.11 Theme 10: Gendered expectations

This theme revealed how women actively challenged gendered expectations within the workplace. It not only highlighted the obstacles women encountered but also illuminated the innovative solutions they offered, shaped by the bridges they had crossed. A central finding was the way in which women redefined traditional leadership styles through authenticity. For example, Participant 3 (P3) clearly articulated her desire to be recognised as a gentle leader rather than conforming to an aggressive leadership model. In contrast, Participant 23 (P23), who embraced her unique style of leadership, described a persistent sense of discomfort stemming from the lack of acceptance she experienced. Similarly, Participant 4 (P4) reflected on experiencing imposter syndrome, suggesting that adopting a leadership style that diverged from traditionally accepted norms presented significant psychological challenges.

Participant 5 (P5), who consistently expressed her authentic leadership style, found herself labelled as the "iron lady", a term that, while possibly intended as praise, reflects a gendered response to her assertiveness. These accounts highlight the recurring tension that women leaders face when asserting leadership styles that deviate from traditional masculine or agentic norms. Nevertheless, their resilience in maintaining authenticity remains evident throughout the findings.

These leadership challenges also influenced participants' broader perspectives on diversity. Participant 6 (P6) emphasised that genuine empowerment was more critical than increasing the number of women for the sake of a "tick in the box" exercise. Similarly, Participant 21 (P21) advocated for a leadership culture rooted in respect rather than one that pressures women to adopt masculine traits. Participant 9 (P9) added to this discourse by highlighting the need to reduce toxicity in organisational environments.

The first part of this theme, therefore, illustrated how women forged new leadership identities even when met with resistance. At the same time, it raised their expectations regarding diversity and inclusion. Central to their views was the importance of empowerment and respect over numerical diversity or forced assimilation into dominant leadership archetypes. This aligns with Gipson *et al.* (2017), who urged future leaders to research a more nuanced understanding of effective leadership, one that recognises the value of diverse approaches and discourages rigid adherence to traditional agentic leadership models.

Overall, Theme 10 revealed that women leaders sought the freedom to express their own leadership styles. They valued empowerment over superficial diversity measures and advocated for work cultures grounded in respect rather than toxicity. Importantly, they resisted the pressure to adopt agentic traits, instead preferring to lead in ways that reflected their authentic selves, an approach increasingly recognised as effective and sustainable in leadership research.

5.12 Theme 11: Navigating leadership in a male-dominated Industry

The final theme of the study examined how women navigated their professional journeys within the male-dominated Indian automobile industry. A central finding was the women's remarkable resistance to both structural barriers and deeply embedded organisational cultural expectations. These were not merely women who entered the field they were pioneers. Many

were the first women in their villages to pursue higher education, the first in their families to enter the workforce, the first in their engineering departments, and the first to assume leadership roles in their respective organisations. These “firsts” serve as compelling evidence of the societal and cultural hurdles they overcame to establish their professional presence. Having defied social conventions, these women are now contending with internal organisational challenges, indicative of how the locus of resistance has shifted from societal to institutional. Resilience, therefore, emerges as a defining trait. It was through resilience, reinforced by consistently delivering results, that they were able to carve out and sustain their leadership roles. This observation resonates with Chance’s (2022) assertion that adversity is a powerful force in shaping women into effective leaders.

The second aspect of this theme revealed how women leaders perceive and promote diversity and inclusion (D&I). Interestingly, their advocacy does not necessarily centre on increasing the number of women employees. Instead, D&I is seen as a developmental approach that supports leadership growth, encourages self-advocacy among women, and fosters a culture of mutual support. Participant 22, herself a Director of Diversity and Inclusion, underscored the importance of women sharing their success stories to inspire others. Similarly, Participant 24 noted the value of women supporting one another through informal networks and professional encouragement. Participant 2 added that the conversation around D&I is evolving beyond gender to include a diversity of skills and perspectives, noting that even suppliers have begun to adopt this broadened interpretation. These insights align with the work of Hoang, Suh and Sabharwal (2022), who argue that genuine diversity and inclusion extend beyond numerical representation to encompass structural and cultural change within organisations.

Finally, the theme highlighted how women are transforming traditionally male-dominated organisations through their distinctive leadership styles. Women leaders are actively shaping

inclusive cultures, not by conforming to existing norms, but by leading authentically. Their leadership is characterised by empathy, strong values, mutual respect, collaboration, sound decision-making, crisis management, adaptability, and confidence. These attributes not only distinguish their leadership approach but also exemplify the principles of authentic leadership. The findings align with those of Anwar, Abid and Waqas (2019), who identified that authentic leaders are typically resilient, self-aware, confident, and effective in decision-making. Through these qualities, women are not only challenging the status quo but are also contributing to the cultural transformation of their organisations.

5.13 Analysis of all the themes

This study builds on the proposals of Eagly (2005) and Gardiner (2024), who urge researchers to explore authenticity at the intersection of leadership and gender, and to recognise the courage required for individuals to speak and act truthfully within constraining environments. The findings demonstrate that such courage does not emerge solely from individual disposition, but from the interaction between individual agency, organisational systems, institutional structures, and dominant scholarly narratives. In examining how women leaders navigate leadership within a male-dominated automotive industry, the study reveals leadership as a relational and systemic phenomenon rather than an individual attribute.

Consistent with previous research identifying leadership as historically framed through a male-normative lens (Kapasi, Sang and Sitko, 2016), all 25 women leaders in this study reported having to continually prove their competence to be recognised as legitimate leaders. This experience reflects a contradiction between individual leadership capability and organisational evaluation systems, often mediated through HR practices that implicitly privilege masculine leadership norms (Eagly and Karau, 2002). While women demonstrated high levels of self-awareness and authenticity, these qualities were not always institutionally validated, revealing

a misalignment between individual leadership enactment and organisational recognition (Ibarra, Ely and Kolb, 2013).

The primary contribution of this study lies in its examination of gender and authenticity as interconnected and evolving constructs rather than discrete variables. Authentic leadership emerged as a key mechanism through which women leaders negotiated professional identity within organisational contexts where gender remained salient. However, authenticity functioned differently depending on institutional support. Where HR systems and leadership structures enabled autonomy, women were able to translate authenticity into influence. Where such systems were absent or contradictory, authenticity increased visibility without corresponding power, intensifying scrutiny rather than advancement.

Participants frequently acted as cultural disruptors, reshaping leadership norms through their lived experiences. For example, P17's role in influencing return-to-work policies and P21's contribution to inclusive hiring practices illustrate how individual authenticity can drive organisational change when coupled with institutional leverage, often facilitated through HR policy reform or leadership endorsement. This interaction supports Nicholson and Carroll's (2013) conceptualisation of authenticity as a social virtue enacted within relational and structural contexts, rather than a purely individual characteristic.

The findings further demonstrate how authentic leadership interacts with sponsorship systems, particularly those embedded within HR and informal organisational networks. Gendered authenticity facilitated trust and confidence, creating conditions for sponsorship to emerge organically. This extends Cho *et al.*'s (2019) theory of inclusive leadership cultures by illustrating how authenticity, when recognised institutionally, fosters collaborative networks essential for career progression. However, this relationship was frequently delayed, revealing

a contradiction: while authenticity promoted relational credibility, access to sponsorship remained contingent on prolonged performance and conformity to gendered expectations.

Although authentic leadership in relation to gender has been explored by scholars such as Gardiner (2015), Ely *et al.* (2011), and L.A. and Gibson (2018), its intersection with leadership structures in male-dominated industries remains underexplored. Drawing on intersectionality (Crenshaw, 2006; Mor Barak *et al.*, 2016; Bowleg, 2008), this study illustrates how women leaders navigate overlapping identities shaped by gender, organisational role, and institutional power. These identities are negotiated across multiple domains, including organisational systems, representative bodies, and broader societal expectations.

The debate between gender-neutral leadership perspectives (Powell, 1990; Braun, Peus and Frey, 2018) and gender-differentiated leadership approaches (Eagly, 2007; Inks *et al.*, 2020; Adams, 2023) is reflected in the findings. FGD participants, predominantly male, emphasised women's emotional intelligence, crisis responsiveness, and relational leadership strengths. These accounts contradict gender-neutral assumptions by demonstrating how gendered experiences shape leadership practice. However, HR systems and leadership frameworks often remain aligned with gender-neutral rhetoric, creating tension between lived leadership effectiveness and formal leadership evaluation.

Sponsorship emerged as a critical point of interaction between individual leadership, organisational systems, and representative structures. While all 25 women leaders had sponsors, sponsorship was often secured later in their careers, limiting its impact. Participants such as P20 and P22 highlighted how delayed sponsorship constrained leadership progression and contributed to persistent pay disparities, despite formal pay parity initiatives (Lewis, Pathak and Galloway, 2018). This contradiction reveals how organisational and HR systems may address surface-level equality while failing to disrupt deeper leadership inequities.

Representative bodies and professional networks provided partial support by offering visibility and advocacy beyond organisational boundaries. However, their influence was uneven and insufficient to compensate for structural barriers within organisations. Similarly, educational institutions played a foundational role in shaping leadership identity and confidence, yet were often disconnected from the realities of navigating male-dominated organisational cultures. This disconnect reinforces the need for stronger alignment between educational preparation, organisational practice, and leadership scholarship.

At the macro level, researchers and scholars shape the leadership ecosystem by legitimising particular leadership norms and practices. Dominant theories have historically reinforced male-centric models, influencing HR systems and organisational expectations. This study challenges those narratives by empirically demonstrating that leadership authenticity, gender, and sponsorship are interdependent and contextually situated. In doing so, it positions scholarship as both a contributor to and a potential disruptor of organisational inequality, as conceptualised in Figure 17.

Integrative Summary: In summary, the findings reveal women's leadership advancement as the outcome of interacting forces across individual, organisational, institutional, and scholarly domains. Intrapersonal leadership formation enables authentic leadership; HR systems determine whether authenticity is rewarded or penalised; sponsorship amplifies or constrains progression; representative bodies provide supplementary but limited support; educational institutions shape early leadership identity; and scholarly frameworks legitimise or challenge prevailing norms. Where these actors are aligned, leadership trajectories are reinforced. Where they contradict one another, even highly capable women leaders experience delayed progression and constrained influence. Addressing gender inequality in leadership therefore

requires coordinated, system-level interventions rather than isolated individual or organisational solutions.

Based on the findings, a Conceptual framework has been created as shown in Fig. 17.

Fig 17: Leadership, authenticity and gender A Conceptual Framework

5.14 Conclusion

This study presents a comprehensive and nuanced examination of the lived experiences of 25 women leaders in the Indian automotive industry, situating their journeys within the frameworks of authentic leadership, role congruity theory, and intersectionality. By employing a dual-method design that combined interpretative phenomenological analysis (IPA) of lead

interviews with focus group discussions (FGDs) conducted with participants' teams, the research generated fresh insights into the way authenticity operates not merely as a personal leadership style but as a strategic, gendered practice for navigating the layered realities of organisational life.

What emerges most clearly from these narratives is the duality of the leadership experience in male-dominated contexts. On the surface, many organisations champion inclusivity through formal policy and public rhetoric. Yet beneath this veneer, the women in this study consistently encountered subtle and systemic forms of exclusion in microcultures where belonging had to be repeatedly earned, feedback was filtered through gendered lenses, and sponsorship came only after long periods of performance and perseverance. These challenges were not solely structural but deeply psychological, giving rise to imposter syndrome, emotional labour, and the constant negotiation of self-worth in spaces that were not always welcoming.

And yet, these women did not merely endure; they redefined the very notion of leadership. By anchoring themselves in authenticity, they created space for genuine expression of values, emotional integrity, and relational trust. Their leadership was characterised not by the mimicry of dominant norms but by an intentional and adaptive integration of their identity and moral compass into their professional roles. Authenticity in this context did not mean static self-expression; it was dynamic, reflexive, and attuned to both organisational demands and personal convictions.

Importantly, the study also surfaces a quiet but compelling critique of some well-intentioned gender equality mechanisms. Quotas and targeted interventions, while helpful in improving representation, were at times perceived as amplifying feelings of otherness. Some participants reflected on how such measures could unintentionally overshadow their merit and reinforce the notion that they were present solely because of compliance, rather than competence. In

contrast, the processes that truly supported their advancement were those rooted in trust, sponsorship, and allyship initiatives that acknowledged and nurtured their potential through meaningful relationships and advocacy.

The conceptual framework that has emerged from this research offers both theoretical and practical contributions. It presents a more integrated view of leadership development, one that situates individual authenticity within broader cultural and structural contexts. Rather than viewing gender inclusion as a numerical goal to be achieved, the framework calls for a shift toward cultural transformation and relationship-driven change. It highlights the need for human resources practitioners, policymakers, educators, and industry bodies to move beyond surface-level interventions and cultivate ecosystems that allow authentic leadership to flourish.

Ultimately, this study highlights authenticity not just as a personal ideal but as a powerful driver of organisational and cultural change. In an industry long characterised by masculine norms and strict hierarchies, the women leaders at the centre of this research are not merely surviving; they are leading in new ways and, in doing so, redefining what leadership can be. Their stories demonstrate the resilience and innovation that can emerge when leaders are empowered to lead from a place of self-awareness, purpose, and relational integrity. This reimagined model of leadership, rooted in authenticity and inclusion, resonates well beyond the boundaries of the Indian automotive industry. It reflects the evolving global conversation on leadership, identity, and the urgent need for workplaces that value both competence and character.

CHAPTER SIX: CONCLUSION

6.1 Introduction

This study examined the role of authentic leadership in promoting and enhancing sponsorship for women in leadership positions within India's passenger car original equipment manufacturing (OEM) sector. It was motivated by the persistent underrepresentation of women in senior leadership, despite a significant increase in women graduating with engineering qualifications and entering the automotive industry. The main aim was to understand how women who have successfully taken on leadership roles in this traditionally male-dominated industry have achieved this, what internal and external challenges they faced, and how authenticity intersects with gender and leadership to affect access to sponsorship and career progression.

The conceptual framework underpinning this research was informed by both systematic and narrative literature reviews, addressing intrapersonal development and systemic constraints. It critically engaged with gendered leadership norms, organisational practices, and the limitations of existing leadership development frameworks for women. Adopting an interpretative phenomenological approach (IPA) and thematic analysis, the study sought to interpret the lived experiences of women leaders within the sociocultural and industrial context of Indian automotive manufacturing.

Data were collected through lead interviews with 25 women in leadership roles across five major automobile manufacturing firms located in southern and western India, encompassing both multinational and domestic corporations. These were complemented by five focus group discussions (FGDs) with mixed-gender participants reporting directly to these women leaders. This dual-method design provided a holistic view of leadership: the interviews offered introspective accounts of leadership identity, values, and personal evolution, while the FGDs

offered insight into how these leaders were perceived and how their leadership influenced team-level dynamics and workplace culture.

Together, these data sources enabled triangulation, reinforcing the study's credibility and depth. They facilitated a nuanced understanding of both the individual trajectories of women leaders and the broader relational and organisational landscapes they operate within. This chapter synthesises the key findings, aligning them with the study's objectives and research questions. It then offers interpretive insights, practical implications, theoretical contributions, limitations, and recommendations for future research. The chapter closes with a reflective commentary on the transformative potential of authentic leadership as a mechanism for advancing gender inclusion within the automotive industry and beyond.

The chapter proposes several key recommendations:

For Organisations: Introduce structured mentorship and sponsorship programmes, revise leadership pipelines to better include women, and roll out comprehensive unconscious bias training.

For Policymakers and Industry Bodies: Support initiatives that promote women in core manufacturing functions and adopt flexible work policies that reflect the diverse life stages of women employees.

For Academia: Pursue further research into intersectional experiences of leadership and undertake longitudinal studies to track the long-term impact of inclusive leadership practices in traditionally male-dominated industries.

In conclusion, this thesis advocates for a redefinition of leadership one that moves beyond numeric targets and hierarchical dominance to embrace authenticity, empathy, and inclusivity. These are not merely complementary to effective leadership; they are central to it. The women

leaders in this study exemplify a leadership model that is principled, collaborative, and profoundly human offering both a critique of the present and a blueprint for the future of automotive leadership in India and beyond.

6.2 Summary of Research findings in relation to Objectives

6.2.1 Research objective One

To identify the skills and traits that have contributed to women leaders' success, how these skills/ traits were developed and in what manner a fresh approach could be created in empowering women leaders in the future:

Findings: The research found that authenticity, emotional intelligence, resilience, empathy, and a strong ethical compass were defining attributes of the women leaders studied. These qualities were cultivated not through formal training but through lived experience, introspection, and aligning with values. Participants frequently reflected on how early life choices, such as the decision to pursue engineering, often in the face of resistance, became formative moments of self-definition and empowerment.

Rather than adhering to traditional, programme-based leadership pathways, participants described leadership development as an organic, experiential process. Key enablers included supportive families, a sense of personal purpose, and a consistent alignment between inner values and professional conduct. Authentic leadership emerged as a central, animating principle rooted in self-awareness, transparency, and moral clarity, enabling these women to lead with integrity and navigate institutional challenges effectively.

Crucially, the absence of structured development or institutional sponsorship meant that participants relied on self-directed learning and deliberate career planning. This form of resourcefulness was underpinned by a future-oriented mindset and a high degree of emotional resilience.

Findings highlight the urgent need for organisations to move beyond prescriptive training programmes and towards developmental ecosystems grounded in psychological safety, experiential learning, and structural inclusion. Three enabling factors were identified as critical: organisational cultural permission for authenticity, developmental rather than transactional learning opportunities, and the institutional embedding of equity and fairness beyond tokenistic diversity rhetoric.

6.2.2 Research objective Two

To investigate some of the challenges women face within the workplace and how these challenges could be reduced.

Findings: The lead interviews were designed to delve into the multifaceted challenges encountered by women throughout their professional journeys within the Indian automobile sector. The narratives that emerged were composed of distinct ‘pockets of experience’ some challenges were the result of being proactive or assertive in male-dominated environments, others were unforeseen or externally imposed, and still others were subtle and discreet in nature. Despite their varied origins, a consistent observation across these accounts was the profound impact these challenges had on the participants’ professional trajectories and personal confidence.

Among the most reported challenges were imposter syndrome and persistent self-doubt, often intertwined with internalised gender expectations. These were further exacerbated by the absence of visible female role models in leadership positions. Participants recounted encountering implicit and explicit biases, deeply entrenched gendered stereotypes, and widespread assumptions regarding their leadership capabilities, challenges that became particularly pronounced during key life stages, such as pregnancy and early motherhood. The organisational culture within many firms was described as exclusionary, characterised by

informal barriers to sponsorship, limited access to influential networks, and restricted participation in key decision-making processes.

A particularly striking insight was the critical role of family support in enabling career continuity. Fathers and spouses were frequently cited as important allies who provided both emotional and logistical support, thereby allowing women to persist in demanding roles that often required long hours, relocation, or travel. This support was not universal, but where present, it played a significant enabling role.

The examination of these experiences in granular detail revealed that a major point of transition and often the beginning of gendered barriers occurred at the educational stage, specifically when participants chose to pursue engineering disciplines such as mechanical, automotive, or electronics. This moment of divergence was marked by resistance from peers, educators, and sometimes extended family, revealing how gender bias is embedded early in the talent pipeline. As such, any comprehensive strategy aimed at addressing the systemic challenges faced by women in the automotive industry must begin not only within organisations, but also within educational institutions.

Several strategies were proposed by participants to address these barriers. First, there is a urgent need for implementing comprehensive bias-awareness training at all organisational levels, with particular focus on unconscious biases that affect hiring, promotions, and daily interactions. Second, participants called for the development of inclusive performance appraisal systems that recognise and reward a diverse array of leadership styles, beyond the traditionally masculine or authoritative models that prevail today. Third, maternity leave emerged as a common concern; many participants noted that it is often regarded within organisations as a ‘break’ or ‘holiday’ rather than a medical necessity or a vital aspect of workplace wellbeing. Therefore, there is a clear need to raise awareness about both maternity and paternity leave

entitlements, reframing them as essential elements of a forward-thinking and equitable workplace culture.

Overall, the findings underscore that addressing the challenges women face in the automotive sector requires a holistic, systemic approach, one that spans education, organisational policy, leadership development, and cultural transformation. Such change must be both structural and attitudinal, rooted in genuine commitment rather than tokenistic gestures.

6.2.3 Research objective Three

To obtain comparative insight into the ways in which authenticity, leadership and gender intersect in creating sponsorship.

Findings: The study demonstrates that authenticity, when practiced consistently and visibly, can serve as a powerful catalyst for sponsorship. Women who led with integrity, empathy, and ethical clarity were often informally championed by colleagues and subordinates. However, formal sponsorship defined as senior leaders actively advocating for women's progression remained inconsistent and largely circumstantial.

Mentorship emerged as a helpful, but insufficient, support mechanism. Sponsorship, by contrast, was identified as the true enabler of career progression, especially when it entailed senior-level advocacy. Women who strategically built peer alliances, secured informal mentorships, or cultivated relational capital were better positioned to overcome bias and secure visibility.

To foster more equitable sponsorship structures, organisations must shift from informal, ad-hoc models to intentional frameworks with accountability mechanisms. Encouraging senior leaders to act as sponsors and recognising authentic leadership as a driver of organisational trust can reshape the sponsorship landscape, enabling systemic rather than individual change.

6.3 Summary of research findings in relation to the research question

The findings of this study will be examined in relation to the research questions outlined in Chapter 1. Given the nature of the study, the two phases of data collection elicited participants' perceptions of authenticity, women in leadership, and the broader dynamics of leadership itself. It is essential to determine whether the research findings are sufficient to address each of the stated research questions.

6.3.1 Research question One

How have successful women leaders navigated and flourished in upholding their leadership fit within the automobile industry? The research found that authenticity formed the cornerstone of how women leaders defined, enacted, and sustained their leadership identities. Participants articulated a strong connection between personal values and professional practice, citing attributes such as emotional intelligence, ethical integrity, and reflective learning as essential tools in their leadership development. These were not merely aspirational traits but strategic enablers that helped them build trust, challenge gender bias, and guide teams effectively.

Despite working within masculine leadership cultures, the women interviewed maintained their integrity through what might be called "authentic adaptation" the ability to stay true to themselves while strategically navigating organisational expectations. Many drew on deeply rooted internal values shaped by upbringing, education, and early professional experiences. The alignment between personal values and organisational culture was often vital in sustaining engagement and job satisfaction.

Support networks, whether formal mentoring relationships or informal peer alliances, emerged as crucial. These systems provided both emotional and strategic scaffolding for women as they pursued visibility, credibility, and ultimately, sponsorship. FGDs confirmed these patterns,

highlighting women leaders' dedication, resilience, and relational leadership styles, all of which contributed significantly to their acceptance and respect within the organisation.

6.3.2 Research question Two

What were some of the internal challenges they had to overcome? The second key finding relates to the internal challenges women faced, including imposter syndrome, self-doubt, and emotional labour. Despite their education, competence, and accomplishments, many struggled with internalised societal messages that questioned their legitimacy as leaders. This was particularly evident in contexts where leadership was narrowly defined through masculine norms.

Nevertheless, these challenges were addressed through continuous self-reflection, emotional regulation, and a deliberate approach to learning. Mentorship, allyship, and peer support played crucial roles in strengthening confidence and alleviating feelings of isolation.

In addition to internal barriers, women leaders had to contend with systemic issues: gender stereotypes, unequal access to development opportunities, limited formal sponsorship, and discriminatory assumptions around motherhood, marital status, and emotional capability. Maternity and post-maternity stages, in particular, were sites of acute bias and marginalisation.

Despite this, women demonstrated significant agency. They created their own leadership pathways by proactively acquiring skills, building networks, and demonstrating their value through results. Formal leadership development programmes, when available, were often limited in scope and impact. Many participants described these initiatives as tokenistic and reactive, implemented only after they had already achieved leadership positions rather than developmental from early career stages.

A recurring theme in both interviews and FGDs was the "prove it again" bias. Professional titles did not suffice; credibility had to be earned repeatedly through outcomes. Recognition often came informally, through titles such as "iron lady" or "warrior princess," bestowed not by HR but by peers and teams. Women's emotional expression, while sometimes difficult to manage, was generally viewed positively when tied to transparency, empathy, and authenticity.

Ultimately, the study found that intrinsic challenges rooted in self-perception, societal narratives, and emotional labour were often harder to overcome than structural obstacles. Yet, women drew on strong family support, often being "firsts" in their families or communities to pursue engineering, work in manufacturing, or hold leadership roles. This foundational support, combined with personal resilience, helped them transcend deeply embedded social and organisational biases.

6.3.3 Research Question Three

How authenticity, leadership and gender could intersect in building a culture of sponsorships, advocating for women's career advancement? A major contribution of this research lies in demonstrating how the intersection of authenticity, leadership, and gender can cultivate cultures that support women's advancement through sponsorship. The findings suggest that when authenticity is embedded in leadership, it drives behaviours such as ethical decision-making, transparency, empathy, and crisis competence, all of which build credibility and trust.

Women who led authentically were more likely to attract informal sponsors, bosses, peers, and even direct reports who advocated for their progression. Sponsorship, in these cases, was earned through performance, integrity, and trust rather than formal organisational mechanisms. FGDs revealed that team members themselves often championed their women leaders, recognising their impact and leadership value.

Furthermore, women leaders were shown to actively seek feedback, not merely as a professional requirement, but as a reflective practice that facilitated continuous growth. Importantly, they exercised discernment in acting on feedback, choosing to adapt in ways that aligned with their core values.

This intersection of authenticity, leadership, and gender thus played a transformative role, challenging rigid leadership archetypes and creating inclusive ecosystems that enabled women's advancement. It also pointed to a broader organisational shift: when women lead authentically, they not only succeed individually but contribute to systemic change that benefits others.

6.4 Integrated Contributions of the Study:

This section interprets the broader contributions of the study's findings through Figure 17 (Conceptual Framework), which illustrates how different stakeholders including HR functions, individual leaders, representative industry bodies, educational institutions, and researchers may engage with the study's recommendations. It provides a high-level synthesis of the study's insights, linking the empirical findings to the more detailed theoretical and practical contributions articulated in the sections that follow. By examining women leaders' lived experiences within the masculinised environment of the Indian automotive sector, the section highlights how authenticity is enacted, negotiated, and constrained within organisational contexts.

At a broader level, the findings reveal that authenticity within masculinised industrial contexts cannot be understood as a fixed individual attribute. Rather, it emerges as a negotiated and relational process shaped by gendered norms and organisational power structures. This insight underscores the importance of industry-specific leadership analysis, particularly within capital-intensive manufacturing environments where gendered norms are deeply embedded.

The findings further illuminate the relational dimension of authenticity, demonstrating that leadership identity is co-constructed through interactions between leaders and followers. Insights from the focus group discussions reveal that authentic behaviours were not merely observed but actively validated, reinforcing authenticity as a socially negotiated process rather than an individual possession. By incorporating both women leaders' narratives and the perspectives of their teams, the study strengthens the conceptual understanding of authentic leadership as relational, contextually embedded, and dynamically enacted within masculinised organisational environments.

To provide structural clarity and align the study's contributions with the preceding discussion, Figure 18 presents an integrated framework that differentiates between theoretical and practical contributions. Although both dimensions emerge from a shared conceptual foundation of authentic leadership, gender, and organisational context, the framework differentiates their domains of influence. The upper tier illustrates the study's practical contributions for automobile organisations, whereas the lower tier highlights its theoretical contributions to research.

Figure 18: Integrated Framework of Theoretical Contributions and Practical Implications

6.4.1 Practical Contributions:

In sum, the practical implications outlined in this section emphasise the importance of coordinated organisational and policy-level action to foster inclusive leadership ecosystems. By embedding authenticity, sponsorship, and gender-responsive practices into leadership pipelines, automotive organisations and industry bodies can move beyond symbolic inclusion toward sustained cultural and structural transformation. For practitioners within automotive organisations, the findings translate into actionable strategies aimed at restructuring leadership development and organisational systems to better support women's progression. Together, these interventions demonstrate how inclusive leadership ecosystems can be operationalised within the Indian automotive context.

One of the key recommendations is the redesign of leadership development programmes to position authenticity as a core competency. Authenticity, as revealed in the study, is not just a

personal trait but a critical component of effective and sustainable leadership. Encouraging leaders to express their true selves within the organisational context enables them to lead with greater confidence and integrity. Integrating authenticity into leadership development reshapes how leadership potential is identified, assessed, and nurtured within organisational systems.

In tandem with this, organisations should establish formalised sponsorship frameworks. It is essential to recognise that women often demonstrate relational and purpose-driven leadership styles that may not always align with traditional, hierarchical norms but are equally impactful. Sponsorship plays a crucial role in career advancement, and creating structured systems where women receive consistent advocacy from senior leaders can bridge the gap between talent and opportunity. This may include formal sponsor–protégé pairing structures, visibility tracking mechanisms, and accountability measures embedded within leadership performance metrics.

Cultivating a psychologically safe environment is another vital intervention. Organisations need to create spaces where open dialogue, constructive feedback, and self-expression are not only encouraged but are also seen as integral to personal and professional growth. A culture of safety in which women can freely share their experiences, challenges, and aspirations without fear of repercussion is critical for fostering trust and transparency within leadership teams.

Moreover, introducing structured mentorship opportunities early in a woman’s career is key. These relationships can provide valuable guidance, affirmation, and a clear sense of direction, helping women navigate the complexities of career advancement. Well-defined learning and development trajectories should be established to ensure that women are equipped with the necessary capabilities to progress confidently into leadership roles. Such frameworks should encompass both technical and interpersonal skills, with a particular focus on preparing women for the leadership challenges inherent in male-dominated industries, such as the automotive sector.

Ultimately, these strategic interventions will help create a more inclusive and supportive environment. By institutionalising authenticity, structured sponsorship, and early mentorship, organisations can build sustainable leadership pipelines that support women’s long-term advancement within the automotive industry. From a practical standpoint, the framework provides actionable insights for organisations seeking to enhance their learning and development strategies, advance diversity and inclusion initiatives, and implement effective cultural interventions. It provides a structured approach to embedding gender-responsive practices into leadership pipelines, helping organisations to build more inclusive cultures that support women’s leadership at all stages of their careers. The framework encourages organisations to consider not just numerical gender representation but also the cultural transformation needed to make women’s leadership both possible and sustainable.

6.4.1.1 Human Resources Departments

Organisations should move beyond compliance-based diversity and inclusion initiatives and embrace culture-transforming allyship. HR departments should move beyond symbolic diversity initiatives and embed allyship recognition into formal performance and recognition systems. Furthermore, organisations should benchmark best practices from industries such as information technology, which have achieved higher representation of women, and examine the policies and cultural shifts that contributed to this progress. HR functions can embed authenticity into leadership assessment frameworks through structured behavioural indicators and leadership capability models. The various functions within HR could benefit from this study by incorporating the following strategies.

To operationalise these recommendations across key HR functions, Figure 19 outlines a structured framework linking talent acquisition, development, management, engagement, compliance, and communication processes to inclusive leadership practices.

Fig 19: HR Operational Framework for Embedding Inclusive Leadership Practices in the Indian Automotive Sector

6.4.1.2 Policy Makers: From a policy perspective, the findings of this study advocate for shifting focus from narrow recruitment metrics to a broader emphasis on sustainable career development. Policymakers are encouraged to view inclusivity through a long-term lens, ensuring that women's careers are supported not just at the entry level but throughout their professional journeys. Representation metrics must be complemented by structured retention, sponsorship, and leadership progression pathways.

To advance women's leadership, organisations should be incentivised to adopt sponsorship practices, recognising the power these practices hold in providing visibility, advocacy, and career progression. Sponsorship should be integrated into organisational policies, ensuring it becomes a systematic and formalised part of women's career development. This is not merely about having mentors but about creating a culture of active, purpose-driven sponsorship that champions women's leadership potential at crucial stages of their careers.

Moreover, embedding gender-responsive leadership frameworks into organisational policy is essential to bridging the aspiration–representation gap. While increasing women's representation in leadership is a critical goal, organisations must ensure that policies and practices support their advancement in a meaningful and sustained way. Such frameworks should not only focus on promoting women into leadership roles but also on creating inclusive environments where women can thrive and lead authentically. This focus on the broader leadership ecosystem ensures that gender equity is not a one-off achievement but a continuous process that requires structural support, policy commitment, and cultural transformation.

In essence, this study provides a comprehensive and multifaceted contribution to the discourse on women's leadership in male-dominated industries, offering both scholarly and practical tools that can drive lasting change.

Collectively, these interventions require coordinated HR systems, performance structures, and policy alignment to institutionalise inclusive leadership practices within automotive organisations. It is not enough to simply address structural inequities or to tackle cultural barriers in isolation. Both must be examined simultaneously to create a truly inclusive leadership ecosystem, particularly in male-dominated sectors like the Indian automotive industry. This approach requires a deep understanding of the interplay between organisational culture, leadership development, and gender dynamics.

6.4.1.3 Individual

This framework encourages both current and aspiring women leaders to take a proactive approach in constructing a well-defined career trajectory within their respective organisations. It highlights the importance of being strategic in leveraging available opportunities and resources to facilitate professional growth and advancement. Rather than viewing their male colleagues as barriers, women are encouraged to see them as key allies in their leadership development. This can be achieved by actively seeking mentorship, sponsorship, and constructive guidance, which are crucial elements for navigating career progression. It offers reflective pathways and strategic insights to help women navigate systemic challenges, develop authentic leadership capacities, and build influence within their organisations.

Self-branding and professional visibility are emphasised as critical components of leadership advancement. Women are advised to shift away from any perceptions of marginality or minority status and, instead, adopt a confident stance that highlights their capabilities and contributions. This shift in mindset can be empowering, encouraging women to confidently own their professional achievements and voice their leadership potential. Recognising the value of visibility in leadership is a key step towards breaking down barriers and building influence within organisations.

The framework also underscores the importance of fostering a culture of mutual support among women in the workplace. By sharing personal leadership narratives and professional experiences, women can create a strong, collective sense of empowerment. This sharing of stories and strategies not only fosters solidarity but also provides valuable insights into navigating common challenges. It reinforces the idea that leadership is not a solitary pursuit but a communal effort that can be enriched through collaboration and mutual encouragement.

At the heart of this framework lies the concept of authenticity in leadership. Women are encouraged to embrace and express their unique leadership styles, resisting the pressure to conform to traditionally masculine leadership paradigms. By doing so, they can challenge the normative assumptions that often underpin organisational leadership cultures. This approach not only promotes a more diverse and inclusive understanding of leadership but also encourages organisations to recognise the value of different leadership expressions. In doing so, women can contribute to reshaping organisational cultures that have long been dominated by masculine norms, fostering environments where diverse leadership styles are valued and celebrated.

In sum, the framework calls for a shift in both personal and organisational approaches to leadership. It empowers women to take charge of their career paths, build supportive networks, and assert their authentic leadership identities in a way that transforms both their individual careers and the organisations they work for. Through this approach, women can navigate the complexities of leadership in male-dominated environments, fostering a more inclusive and equitable future for all.

6.4.1.4 National bodies representing Indian automobile manufacturers

National industry bodies representing Indian automobile manufacturers hold a uniquely influential position in shaping the future of gender inclusivity within the sector. As guardians

of industry standards and collective voices of organisational leadership, these bodies are well-placed to drive cultural transformation across the automotive landscape. One of the most powerful contributions they can make lies in actively promoting and disseminating the leadership journeys of women who have broken through the barriers of a traditionally male-dominated industry. By bringing these stories to the fore, they not only enhance visibility but also contribute to the normalisation of female leadership, an essential step in changing perceptions and reshaping organisational mindsets.

Such storytelling is not merely symbolic. It sets a precedent. By publicly recognising and celebrating organisations that demonstrate a sustained and meaningful commitment to inclusion, national bodies can establish benchmarks for excellence. These benchmarks then serve as aspirational models for other companies, fostering a culture of accountability and continual improvement. When inclusion is positioned as a marker of institutional success, it becomes integrated into the industry's strategic priorities rather than relegated to the margins as a token effort.

However, creating a truly inclusive leadership culture cannot rest solely on the recognition of women's achievements. Equally important is the acknowledgement of male allies those leaders, mentors, and sponsors who have actively supported the career advancement of their women colleagues. Recognising these men not only validates their role in challenging gender norms but also expands the conversation to one of shared responsibility. It reframes gender inclusivity not as a women's issue but as a collective imperative, one that requires the engagement and commitment of all members of the organisation.

This more integrative approach promotes a collaborative vision of leadership development, where different perspectives and contributions are valued. It also helps dismantle the binary framing of gender equity efforts, making space for men and women to work together in building

inclusive cultures. In doing so, the industry moves closer to effecting meaningful, long-term cultural and structural change that benefits not just women, but the sector as a whole.

Ultimately, the leadership shown by national industry bodies in this area could prove transformational. By championing both exemplary women leaders and their supportive male counterparts, these institutions have the potential to shift narratives, influence policy, and embed inclusivity as a core value across the Indian automobile manufacturing sector. Additionally, the framework can inform the work of automotive gender representation bodies across India as they shape sustainable gender policies.

6.4.1.5 Educational Institutions: Educational institutions, particularly higher secondary schools and engineering colleges, play a vital and transformative role in reshaping society's view of disciplines such as mechanical and automotive engineering. These institutions are more than academic environments; they are early socialising agents where young people begin to form their professional identities and aspirations. As such, they play a critical role in fostering early allyship and challenging the longstanding gendered assumptions that continue to influence students' subject and career choices.

Strategic collaborations between educational institutions and industry stakeholders offer a powerful avenue for intervention. When thoughtfully designed, such partnerships can help dismantle the entrenched cultural narratives that present engineering, especially in the mechanical and automotive fields, as inherently male domains. These efforts, if initiated early, can help expand the pipeline of female talent entering the sector by making these disciplines more visible, accessible, and appealing to young women. Rather than waiting until tertiary education or employment to address gender disparities, such interventions work proactively at the root.

That said, while current efforts such as engine donations to laboratories or the provision of internships reflect a degree of industry-academia engagement, they are not sufficient on their own. These initiatives, though helpful, tend to focus on technical exposure without addressing the deeper, often invisible, cultural and perceptual barriers that deter young women from pursuing these fields. Real change requires a shift in narrative and in how the sector is presented to aspiring students.

To that end, it is crucial that the lived experiences and voices of women working in the automotive sector are amplified within educational settings. Inviting women professionals to engage directly with students through guest lectures, panel discussions, mentorship programmes, or storytelling initiatives can challenge stereotypes and help reframe the industry as not only viable but deeply rewarding for women. Such representation does not simply inform; it inspires. It signals to female students that they, too, belong in these spaces and that their perspectives are both needed and valued.

Moreover, integrating women's experiences into both curricular content and extracurricular activities offers a more holistic and humanised view of the profession. It shifts the focus from machines and mechanics alone to the broader societal impact of engineering and leadership. This, in turn, can foster a stronger sense of purpose and identity among young women considering careers in the automotive and mechanical sectors.

Ultimately, for genuine change to take root, educational institutions must go beyond technical training and engage actively in cultural transformation. By embedding inclusivity into the core of engineering education, they can play a vital role in shaping the future of the Indian automotive industry, making it more diverse, innovative, and equitable.

6.4.2 Theoretical contributions

This section articulates the study's theoretical contributions to authentic leadership scholarship, gender and leadership studies, and context-sensitive leadership theory. It delineates how the research advances existing scholarship on authentic leadership, gender and leadership studies, and context-sensitive leadership theory. By positioning women leaders' experiences in the Indian automotive industry at the centre of analysis, the study offers original insights that extend, refine, and in some cases, challenge prevailing theoretical assumptions within these bodies of literature.

The study reconceptualises authenticity within masculinised industrial contexts by situating it at the intersection of gender, organisational culture, and structural power. It challenges the prevailing conceptualisation of authenticity as a stable, individualised trait (Kernis, 2003; Bartsch, Zeugner-Roth and Katsikeas, 2022; Kapusta, 2025) and instead reconceptualises it as a dynamic, relational, and culturally contingent construct. By exploring how women leaders navigate and negotiate authenticity within the highly masculinised environment of the Indian automotive sector, the study extends the theoretical understanding of authenticity as an adaptive process shaped by organisational culture, gender norms, and structural power dynamics. Furthermore, the findings highlight the need for a shift in scholarly attention toward the intrinsic, less visible dimensions of organisational life that shape women's leadership trajectories.

The conceptual framework developed in this study advances leadership scholarship by offering a contextually grounded and theoretically integrative model that connects authentic leadership, gender, and organisational culture within a masculinised industrial environment. Rather than treating authenticity as an abstract or universal construct, the framework situates it within lived organisational realities shaped by hierarchy, power, and gendered expectations. In doing so, it

contributes to a more relational and structurally embedded understanding of leadership, encouraging scholars to move beyond decontextualised and Western-centric interpretations. The framework therefore provides a conceptual lens through which future research can examine how authenticity is enacted, negotiated, and legitimised within industry-specific and culturally situated contexts.

6.4.2.1 Researchers

The proposed framework lays a solid foundation for future research into gender perceptions within the automotive sector, particularly by emphasising the importance of early educational experiences. By adopting a lens that accounts for the complex interplay of sociocultural, psychological, and institutional influences, it becomes possible to unpack the ways in which students particularly young women develop perceptions about academic disciplines and professional possibilities. This is especially crucial in understanding why certain fields, such as mechanical and automotive engineering, remain male-dominated despite broader societal progress towards gender equity.

Future research on women's leadership should critically examine the intrinsic cultural and structural factors within organisations that either support or hinder the development of women leaders. It is essential to investigate leadership through an industry-specific lens, particularly given the insights from eight participants who transitioned from sectors such as IT and pharmaceuticals. These individuals highlighted that the leadership challenges within the automotive industry were unique and not readily transferable, emphasising the importance of a nuanced, sector-sensitive understanding of leadership.

Investigating these early influences often formed in school-level environments is not merely an academic exercise but a necessary step toward dismantling systemic barriers before they solidify. At this stage, young women are at a critical juncture in shaping their self-concept,

aspirations, and confidence. Research grounded in the framework can explore how gendered socialisation; the visibility (or invisibility) of role models, curriculum design, and teacher attitudes collectively influence educational choices that ripple into future career pathways. By doing so, such inquiry can help reimagine educational settings as fertile ground for nurturing inclusive aspirations, rather than as early gatekeepers of exclusion.

Beyond the educational context, there is also an urgent need for sustained and longitudinal research into the career trajectories of women within the automotive industry itself. While prior scholarship has commendably addressed external, structural impediments such as recruitment practices, policy gaps, and broader societal expectations, it has often overlooked the more subtle and persistent internal dynamics that shape women's professional experiences. This gap calls for a deeper inquiry into the organisational cultures of automotive firms, with a focus on how these environments either foster or inhibit women's career progression.

Organisational culture, after all, is not a neutral backdrop; it actively shapes leadership norms, career development opportunities, and everyday workplace interactions. Research must probe how implicit biases, unspoken norms, and entrenched leadership archetypes influence women's sense of belonging and legitimacy within the sector. For instance, are women's leadership styles validated and encouraged, or subtly undermined? Do organisational values truly reflect inclusivity, or are they performative in nature?

Such questions are crucial for developing robust and context-specific strategies that transcend surface-level diversity initiatives. By centring the lived experiences of women and tracing the nuances of their journeys over time, researchers can offer richer, more actionable insights that contribute not only to academic knowledge but also to transformative industry practices. In essence, this framework not only informs future research directions but also demands a more

layered, empathetic, and sustained engagement with the question of gender in the automotive sector, starting from school classrooms and extending deep into corporate boardrooms.

This study addresses that gap by applying authentic leadership as a conceptual lens within the automotive context. While previous research has explored authentic leadership in relation to gender (e.g. Eagly, 2005; Ely *et al.*, 2011), this study extends the conversation by examining the advancement of women into leadership roles through the lens of authenticity. It offers insight into how authenticity is experienced, negotiated, and challenged by women leaders in a male-dominated industrial setting, thereby situating authenticity within a broader gendered and socio-cultural framework.

In doing so, this study also addresses a noted lack of intersectionality in earlier authentic leadership research, specifically, the limited exploration of how gender and leadership intersect with authenticity (Gardner *et al.*, 2021). By foregrounding the lived experiences of women leaders in the Indian automobile industry, the research demonstrates that authenticity is not a neutral or universally accessible trait, but rather one that is shaped and contested within the constraints of industrial culture and gendered expectations.

Moreover, Alvesson and Einola (2019) have critiqued authentic leadership theory for its excessive positivity, urging future research to engage more critically with its contradictions and complexities. They argue that authenticity should be understood as a contested terrain a “cultural minefield” rather than a stable ideal. Responding to this call, the present study provides an account of the real-life struggles women face in navigating authenticity within a male-dominated and often exclusionary organisational environment. It thereby enriches the ongoing scholarly discourse by illustrating how authenticity is constructed and performed under pressure, demonstrating that it remains a core albeit complex element of leadership in practice.

While these remain vital areas of inquiry, this research adopts a different lens by highlighting the success stories of women who have attained leadership positions despite operating in male-dominated industrial environments. It moves beyond merely identifying inequality, instead exploring the practical strategies women have employed to overcome these challenges and assert their leadership identities.

Through rich empirical data gathered from focus group discussions (FGDs), the study captures how leadership is not only enacted by women but also perceived and reciprocated by their teams. This dual perspective on leadership emphasising both individual agency and team dynamics offers a more nuanced understanding of effective leadership practice. It underscores the relational and interactive dimensions of leadership, thereby enriching existing frameworks within gender and leadership studies.

Finally, this study contributes to the localisation of leadership theories by offering a South Asian perspective, thereby challenging the dominant Western-centric orientation of existing leadership literature (House *et al.*, 2004). The research is situated in India's passenger car manufacturing sector, a context often overlooked in gender-focused leadership research and introduces regional and industrial specificity into broader leadership discussions. In doing so, it deepens understanding of leadership practices within the socio-cultural and organisational dynamics unique to India.

This culturally grounded approach not only expands the empirical base of leadership studies but also contributes to the growing discourse on the importance of contextual sensitivity in leadership theory (Jackson, 2019). By acknowledging the complex interplay between gender, industry, and cultural context, the study reinforces the need for more inclusive and regionally attuned models of leadership. It thereby adds to the global conversation on leadership by amplifying voices and experiences from underrepresented contexts in the academic literature.

By foregrounding intrinsic and often invisible organisational dynamics, the study points to important avenues for future research, particularly those adopting sector-sensitive, relational, and methodologically plural approaches. These implications provide the conceptual foundation upon which the study's theoretical contributions and practical recommendations are articulated in the sections that follow.

6.5 Limitations and future research:

While this study provides rich insight into women's leadership experiences in the Indian automotive industry, three key limitations should be acknowledged. First, the study focuses exclusively on women who have already attained mid-to-senior leadership positions within passenger car original equipment manufacturers (OEMs). As a result, the experiences of early-career women such as apprentice, executives, as well as those working in supplier, R&D segments of the automotive value chain, are not captured. These groups may face distinct developmental challenges and structural barriers, which limits the breadth of perspectives represented in this finding.

Second, the relatively small and purposive sample, while appropriate for an in-depth qualitative design, limits the generalisability of the findings. The study prioritises depth over breadth, offering nuanced understanding rather than statistical representativeness. Consequently, the insights should be interpreted as contextually grounded rather than universally applicable across the automotive sector or other industries.

Third, the study adopts a cross-sectional qualitative design, capturing leadership experiences at a single point in time. This approach does not allow for examination of how authenticity, professional identity, and sponsorship evolve across different career stages or leadership transitions, which may shape women's leadership trajectories over time.

Future Research: This study focused primarily on senior women leaders within the Indian automotive sector. While this provided rich insights into leadership experiences at advanced career stages, it limits understanding of the earlier phases of women's professional trajectories. Future research should therefore incorporate women at multiple hierarchical levels to generate a more holistic understanding of leadership progression and to identify potential bottlenecks across career stages.

Additionally, although sponsorship emerged as a significant enabling factor in this study, the research did not include organisations where sponsorship operates as a formally institutionalised process. Future studies could examine firms with structured sponsorship frameworks and include sponsors themselves as participants, in order to better understand how sponsorship functions as a strategic organisational mechanism rather than an informal relational practice.

Finally, the study was confined to a capital-intensive manufacturing context. Comparative research between the automotive industry and service-based sectors may offer valuable insights into contextual differences in leadership development practices. Such comparative analysis could identify transferable strategies that may strengthen inclusion efforts within manufacturing environments.

6.6 Personal Reflection

When I embarked on this research exploring the experiences of women in leadership within India's automobile industry, my motivation stemmed from a deeply personal space, both from my own professional journey within the sector and a strong commitment to advocating for the advancement of women into leadership roles. What I had not fully anticipated, however, was the emotional intensity that would emerge through the course of the interviews. The narratives shared by the participants were rich in vulnerability, resilience, and profound emotional depth.

Their stories revealed not just professional challenges, but personal battles, conflicts, systemic biases, and moments of isolation that they had to confront in order to grow within their organisations.

As the interviews unfolded, emotional cues became increasingly evident. There was a clear sense of relief, and even joy, in finally having a space to share their stories that, in many cases, had remained unheard. It felt as though these women had been waiting for someone to listen, to bear witness to their journeys of determination and growth. Yet, there were also moments that were emotionally difficult for both the participants and for me as the researcher. Discussions around motherhood, maternity, and the intersection of personal life with professional ambition often brought a pause to the conversation, a silence that reflected unspoken grief or lingering pain. As a mother myself, I found those moments particularly challenging. I could relate deeply to the emotional toll of navigating motherhood alongside a demanding career, and there were instances where their pain mirrored my own.

Navigating these sensitive discussions required emotional maturity, empathy, and a conscious effort to strike a balance between remaining a compassionate listener and maintaining the focus of the interview. Returning to their triumphs and accomplishments helped ease the emotional weight, allowing us to end the conversations on an uplifting note. Although the interviews were scheduled to last approximately ninety minutes, many extended well beyond two hours. The women were eager to speak and interrupting them as they passionately described how they challenged biases and overcame obstacles felt both inappropriate and unkind. These extended conversations, while immensely rich in insight, were emotionally demanding. I often ended each session feeling drained, overwhelmed by the blend of emotion, strength, and perseverance that each story carried.

This experience brought to light an aspect of qualitative research I had not prepared for: the emotional labour of listening deeply and engaging empathetically with lived experiences. It required more than academic rigour; it demanded emotional presence. Yet, it is this very process that has left a lasting impact on me. Conducting this thesis has deepened my appreciation for the women in the Indian automobile industry who, often against formidable odds, have demonstrated remarkable resilience, adaptability, and the courage to lead.

On a more personal level, the research journey has enabled me to find my own voice as a scholar. It has strengthened my conviction in the importance of inclusive leadership, and just as importantly, taught me the value of truly listening without rushing to respond. This thesis has also taken me on a parallel journey of self-reflection, encouraging me to revisit and reinterpret my own experiences within the industry. It has ignited a renewed sense of purpose, gratitude, and responsibility to continue advocating for women in the automobile industry and beyond.

6.7 Concluding Reflection

This research offers an in-depth, empirically grounded account of how women in India's automotive sector navigate and reshape leadership cultures through authenticity. Far from merely adapting to prevailing norms, these women actively challenged and transformed them.

Their stories reveal that authenticity is not just a personal attribute but a strategic, value-driven leadership philosophy that has the potential to reshape industries. As India positions itself as a global manufacturing hub, embedding inclusive, authentic leadership is not merely aspirational; it is imperative.

The responsibility now lies with organisations, educators, policymakers, and industry leaders to build ecosystems that do not ask women to conform but empower them to lead on their own

terms. In doing so, we move closer to a leadership paradigm that is not only effective but also inclusive, equitable, and human-centred.

“Authentic leadership incorporates an internalisation of a leader’s personal credibility enhanced through integrity, to foster social virtues through expressions of a distinctive vision, a sense of passion driven by purpose and care for followers”

“I am not a woman in an automobile; I am a leader in the Automobile”

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APPENDICES

Appendices A- A-Information sheet and Interview Initial email invite

Participant Information sheet

Research Title: Gender equality and authenticity-women leading India's automobile industry

Researcher: Pearlana Bharath Kumar

Contact details: [REDACTED]

You have been nominated to take part in this research and I am delighted to have you part of this study. Please take time to read the following instructions carefully. If you have any questions or clarifications to be made do reach out to me and I would be delighted to furnish you with the required information.

About the Study: The purpose of this study is to examine how authentic leadership in women leaders within the automobile industry could elevate them into leadership roles. The focus would be primarily on authentic leadership as a trait when applied by women leaders could influence their colleagues to become sponsors to their growth from within. The main objective would be to understand how the application of authentic leadership be an influencer to a women's growth within the organisation.

What participation will Involve: Participants would be part of an in-depth interview which will last around 60 min at a location preferred by the participants. Interviews would be recorded for the purpose of transcription. The researcher will only access all the data that has been recorded. Post transcribing, the recordings would be destroyed. Participants would be anonymous. The data would not be shared with any other organisation or institution.

Dear

This is Pearlana, doctoral candidate from university of the west of Scotland, Glasgow, United Kingdom. You have been selected to participate in an interview on 'gender equality and authenticity within the automobile industry'. The purpose of this study would be to examine how authentic leadership in women within the automotive industry could progress into leadership roles. This study would take the perceptions of automotive leaders from senior manager and above. You are invited to participate in this study and share your experiences towards your growth into a leadership role. The interview would take place on at..... between 10:00 to 17:00. Do feel free to drop in within this time.

Your response would be completely anonymous, and information shared would be held confidentially. There will be no personal identifiable information collected. If you have any questions please contact Pearlana at [REDACTED] my primary supervisor [REDACTED]

Yours sincerely
Pearlana Bharathkumar

Appendices B- In-depth interview Questions-Women Leaders

1. I would like to hear more about your journey within the automotive industry.
2. How do you describe your experiences of authenticity or the lack of it in the automobile industry?
3. Could you describe your leadership journey by relating to a time where you were most comfortable leading and a time where you felt intimidated?
4. Could you share all the development opportunities that was provided to you during this journey?
5. Have you had a sponsor in your career? If so, how did it impact your growth?
6. How do you define authentic leadership and what qualities do you associate with it?
7. Who influenced your thinking about leadership and authenticity?
8. Can you describe how your understanding about leadership has changed over time?
9. In what way have your colleagues contributed to your growth?
10. What is important for an inclusive work culture?
11. How do you respond to feedback?
12. What advice would you give to aspiring women?
13. Anything else you would like to add.

Appendices C: Individual Consent Form

Title of Project: Gender equality and authenticity-women leading India's automobile Industry

Please initial box:

- 1 I confirm that I have read and understand the information sheet dated xxx for the above study with the relevant information and have had the opportunity to ask questions.
- 2 I understand that my participation is voluntary and that I am free to withdraw at any time, without giving any reason.
- 3 I understand that my responses will be anonymised (unless I state otherwise) and that confidentiality will be ensured.
- 4 I agree to take part in the above study.

Your signature will certify that you have voluntarily decided to take part in this research study having read and understood the information in the sheet for participants. It will also certify that you have had adequate opportunity to discuss the study with the researcher and that all questions have been answered to your satisfaction.

Name of Participant:

Signature:

Date:

Name of researcher:

Signature: Pearlena Rebecca Bharath Kumar

Contact information: XXXXXXXXXX

Date: 17/08/2024

1 copy for participant and 1 for researcher

Appendices D: Participant information sheet-IDI

Name of School: Business and Creative Industries

Name of Degree: Phd

Title of Project: Gender equality and authenticity-women leading India's automobile Industry

This is an invitation to participate in a research study. Before you make your decision, it's important to understand the purpose of this research and what it entails. Please read the information provided below carefully and don't hesitate to raise any doubts if any question is unclear or if you would like additional information. Take your time to decide whether you would like to participate in this study.

Thank you for reading this.

My Name is Pearlena Rebecca Bharath Kumar I am a PhD student at the University of the West of Scotland. My research topic is Gender equality and authenticity-women leading India's automobile Industry. The University of the West of Scotland School of Business and creative industries is supporting me to undertake this research.

Purpose of this investigation

Given the role the automobile industry plays in India, this study is significant as the industry is progressing towards an inclusive culture. This study addresses the relatively new trait which has seen a dramatic increase in scholarly study on authentic leadership. The study's inclusion of authentic leadership with gender and the automobile industry within the context of India provides an intersectional means of understanding and identifying ways in which women could progress from within into leadership roles. The main aim of the research proposal is to explore the lived experience of women leaders within the automobile industry and to examine the impact of authentic leadership towards creating sponsors to their growth. The proposed objectives and questions must be answered to facilitate the development of a competent proposal.

Research Objective

The study will address the following objectives:

Research Objective 1: to identify the skills and traits that have contributed to women leaders' success, how these skills/ traits were developed and in what manner a fresh approach could be created in empowering women leaders in the future

Research Objective 2: to investigate some of the challenges women face within the workplace and how these challenges could be reduced.

Research objective 3: to obtain comparative insight into the ways in which authenticity, leadership and gender intersect in creating sponsorship.

Do you have to take part?

Participation in this study is voluntary. I will describe the study and go through the information sheet, which will be given to you. I will then ask you to sign a consent form to show you agree to take part. At any time, you are free to withdraw without giving a reason. This will not affect the standard of care you receive.

What will you do in the project?

You will be required to attend an in-depth interview session which will cover topics including about yourself, your leadership journey, authentic leadership & sponsorship, development opportunities that were offered to you, your role, motivations and advice for future women leaders.

The interview will take place in your organisational setting between December 2024-January 2025 and each interview will last approximately 60 minutes. The interviews will be recorded on a Dictaphone and handwritten notes will be taken. In the review of guidelines by the Social Research Association (2003) principles have been taken to ensure respect for privacy, confidentiality and protection of data, honesty and integrity of information and preventing harm and risk to yourself and other participants taking part. However, if at any time during the process you feel uncomfortable answering a question you can decline to answer it.

Why have you been invited to take part?

You have been chosen to take part because you are or have been in a managerial position with more than five years' experience as a manager/supervisor/ team leader/head of section/head of department/general manager and vice president in the Automobile industry in India and thus have the expert knowledge required to answer my questions.

What are the potential risks to you in taking part?

During the research you will not be exposed to any physical, psychological or legal risk or harm.

Interview questions have been structured in such a way so that your privacy will be protected, and no pressure will be put on you to answer sensitive questions. All information pertaining to you as an individual and your organisation will be anonymised and kept confidential. The data you provide will not compromise your position in the organisation at any point in time.

What happens to the information in the project?

All information received will be stored securely in either locked or secure cabinets or password protected electronic files. All references to individuals and organisations will be removed or given pseudonyms of data is to be included within the submitted study, unless exclusive permission has been given. All data will be destroyed on submission and successful completion of my PhD.

The University of the West of Scotland is registered with the Information Commissioner's Office who implements the Data Protection Act 1998. All personal data on participants will be processed in accordance with the provisions of the Data Protection Act 1998.

Thank you for reading this information – please ask any questions if you are unsure about what is written here.

What happens next?

If you are happy to be involved in this project, please sign the consent form to confirm this. If you do not wish to be involved, thank you very much for your time.

If desired, a feedback report can be sent once the investigation is complete.

This investigation was granted ethical approval by the University of the West of Scotland, School of Business and Creative Industries ethics committee.

If you have any questions/concerns, during or after the investigation, or wish to contact an independent person to whom any questions may be directed or from whom further information may be sought please contact:

School Ethics Committee

School of Business and Creative Industries

Paisley Campus

University of the West of Scotland,

High Street,

Paisley

PA1 2BE

Researcher Details: Pearlana Rebecca Bharath kumar

Address: Hamilton International Technology Park, Stephenson PI, Blantyre, Glasgow G72 0LH

E-mail: [REDACTED]

Telephone: [REDACTED]

Supervisor Details: Dr Pravin Balaraman

Address: Hamilton International Technology Park, Stephenson PI, Blantyre, Glasgow G72 0LH

E-mail: [REDACTED]

Telephone: [REDACTED]

Appendices E: Focus Group Questions

1. Can you share any personal experiences where you have supported or been supported by female leaders in your organization?
2. Do you believe women bring a different perspective to leadership? If so, how?
3. How do you consider the current representation of women leaders in your organisation?
4. Have you observed any challenges women leaders face when they take on leadership roles?
5. How do you define authentic leadership and what qualities do you associate with it?
6. What specific behaviours or actions of women leaders do you find most compelling when considering sponsorship?
7. Have you had a sponsor in your career? If so, how did it impact your growth?
8. In your view how important is sponsorship compared to mentorship for career advancement for women leaders?
9. What is important for an inclusive work culture?
10. What can be done to better support women in using authentic leadership to secure sponsorship?

Appendices F- Participant Information Sheet-FGD

Name of School: Business and Creative Industries

Name of Degree: Phd

Title of Project: Gender equality and authenticity-women leading India's automobile Industry

I would like to invite you to take part in a research study. Before you decide you need to understand why the research is being done and what it involves. Please take time to read the following information carefully. Please feel free to ask questions if anything you read is not clear or would like more information. Take time to decide whether or not you want to take part.

Thank you for reading this.

My Name is Pearlena Rebecca Bharath Kumar I am a PhD student at the University of the West of Scotland. My research topic is Gender equality and authenticity-women leading India's automobile Industry. The University of the West of Scotland School of Business and creative industries is supporting me to undertake this research.

What is the purpose of this investigation?

Given the role the automobile industry plays in India, this study is significant as the industry is progressing towards an inclusive culture. This study addresses the relatively new trait which has seen a dramatic increase in scholarly study on authentic leadership. The study's inclusion of authentic leadership with gender and the automobile industry within the context of India provides an intersectional means of understanding and identifying ways in which women could progress from within into leadership roles. The main aim of the research proposal is to explore the lived experience of women leaders within the automobile industry and to examine the impact of authentic leadership towards creating sponsors to their growth. The proposed objectives and questions must be answered to facilitate the development of a competent proposal.

Research Objective

The study will address the following objectives:

Research Objective 1: to identify the skills and traits that have contributed to women leaders' success, how these skills/ traits were developed and in what manner a fresh approach could be created in empowering women leaders in the future

Research Objective 2: to investigate some of the challenges women face within the workplace and how these challenges could be reduced.

Research objective 3: to obtain comparative insight into the ways in which authenticity, leadership and gender intersect in creating sponsorship.

Do you have to take part?

Participation in this study is voluntary. I will describe the study and go through the information sheet, which will be given to you. I will then ask you to sign a consent form to show you agree to take part. At any time, you are free to withdraw without giving a reason. This will not affect the standard of care you receive.

What will you do in the project?

You will be required to attend a focus group discussion (FGD) session which will cover topics including about your personal experiences, perspective of women leaders, authentic leadership & sponsorship, sponsorship in your own career, your views on an inclusive workplace culture, and advice for future women leaders.

The FGD will take place in your organisational setting between December 2024-January 2025 and each FGD will last approximately for 1.5 hours. The discussions will be recorded on a Dictaphone and handwritten notes will be taken. In the review of guidelines by the Social Research Association (2003) principles have been taken to ensure respect for privacy, confidentiality and protection of data, honesty and integrity of information and preventing harm and risk to yourself and other participants taking part. However, if at any time during the process you feel uncomfortable answering a question you can decline to answer it.

Why have you been invited to take part?

You have been chosen to take part because you are or have been reporting into a women leader within the Automobile industry in India and thus have the experience required to answer my questions.

What are the potential risks to you in taking part?

During the research you will not be exposed to any physical, psychological or legal risk or harm.

FGD questions have been structured in such a way so that your privacy will be protected, and no pressure will be put on you to answer sensitive questions. All information pertaining to you as an individual and your organisation will be anonymised and kept confidential. The data you provide will not compromise your position in the organisation at any point in time.

What happens to the information in the project?

All information received will be stored securely in either locked or secure cabinets or password protected electronic files. All references to individuals and organisations will be removed or given pseudonyms of data is to be included within the submitted study, unless express permission has been given. All data will be destroyed on submission and successful completion of my PhD.

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If you have any questions/concerns, during or after the investigation, or wish to contact an independent person to whom any questions may be directed or from whom further information may be sought please contact:

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Address: Hamilton International Technology Park, Stephenson PI, Blantyre, Glasgow G72 0LH

E- [REDACTED]

Telephone: [REDACTED]

Appendices G-Timeline

Appendix H: Ethics approval letter

12/09/2024

Dear RESCHBU1 Pearlena Bharath kumar,

Your application 22861: Gender Equality and Authenticity- Women Leading India's Automobile Industry, submission 18004, has been approved by the Business and Creative Industries SAIEC. You may now proceed with your study. This approval is valid for the duration of the study. If you wish to make any significant changes to the study you must seek the committee's approval before actioning them.

Good luck with your research.

Dr John Quinn